

**Achieving Lean Success in the Petroleum Industry: Development of a
Conceptual Framework To Improve Lean Implementation in the
Upstream Sector**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that work is my original work dully approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland, and that no part of this thesis has been presented for an award in a different University. I further declare that all sources of literature used in this research have been dully acknowledged and cited. The conduct of this research was carried out in strict adherence to UWS research policies and guidelines with the requisite supervisory support.

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	MEANING
4ps	Problem solving, people, Process and Philosophy
AfCFTA	African Continental Free Trade Area
API	American Petroleum Institute
BCG	Boston Consulting Group
BoG	Bank of Ghana
BP	British Petroleum
BPR	Business Process Re-engineering
BPC	Business Process Change
CI	Continuous Improvement
CFA	Confirmatory Factor Analysis
CFF	Critical Failure Factors
CFI	Comparative Fit Index
CSFs	Critical success factors
CSFs	Critical Success Factors
DMAIC	Define, Measure, Analyse, Improve and Control
DPMO	Defects per million opportunities
EFA	Exploratory Factor Analysis
EFQM	European Foundation for Quality Management
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
FDPSO	Floating, Drilling, Production, Storage and Offloading
FPSO	Floating Production, Storage and Offloading
FPSO	Floating, Production, Storage and Offloading

GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GNPC	Ghana National Petroleum Corporation
GSS	Ghana Statistical Service
HRM	Human Resource Management
JHA	Job Hazard Analysis
I4.0	Industry 4.0
IEA	International Energy Administration
IOCs	Independent Oil Companies
IoT	Internet of Things
ITLOS	International Tribunal of the Laws of the Sea
JIT	Just-in-Time
KATH	Konfu-Anokye Teaching Hospital
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
LCP	Local Content Participation
LD	Leadership Direction
LEI	Lean Enterprise Institute
LI	Legislative Instrument
LM	Lean Manufacturing
LSS	Lean Six Sigma
MBNQA	Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award
MOFED	Ministry of Finance and Economic Development
NDT	Neural-based Decision Model
NFI	Normed Fit Index

NOCs	National Oil Companies
NPC	National Petroleum Council
OAPEC	Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries
OEE	Overall Engineering Effectiveness
OP	Organisational Performance
OPEC	Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries
PC	Petroleum Commission
PCA	Principal Components Analysis
PCB	Petroleum Commission Bill
PDCA	Plan-Do- Check-Act
PIAC	Public Integrity and Accountability Commission
PRMB	Petroleum Revenue Management Bill
QFD	Quality Function Deployment
QI	Quality Improvement
RMSEA	Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation
RNI	Relative Non-Centrality Index
SEM	Structural Equation Modelling
SLR	Systematic Literature review
SMED	Single Minute Exchange of Dies
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SPE	Society of Petroleum Engineers
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

SS	Six Sigma
TLP	Tension Leg Platforms
ToC	Theory of Constraints
TPM	Total Productive Maintenance
TQM	Total Quality Management
TTPs	Tools, Techniques and Practices
WE	Waste Elimination
WIP	Work – In-Progress

Abstract

Upstream petroleum companies in developing economies are riddled with production-related inefficiencies, technological transfer challenges and inadequate skills with its concomitant employee underperformance, and these have compelled management to explore strategies to enhance efficiency, improve productivity, profitability and customer satisfaction. Lean Manufacturing is both a philosophy and a management strategy used to eliminate waste, enhance operational efficiency, and has been widely accepted and applied across various sectors.

Adopting a mixed methods approach underpinned by an exploratory sequential research design, 15 interviewees composed of Senior Managers, Consultants, Petroleum Engineers and Lean experts in the upstream petroleum sector were interviewed, after which a thematic analysis was performed using Nvivo 12.0. In addition, survey questionnaires were administered to 503 shop floor employees within the upstream petroleum sector and a structural equation modelling (SEM) composed of exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were performed with SPSS 25 and AMOS version 21.

From the data and extensive review of 101 existing Lean frameworks, a Conceptual Framework was developed to improve lean adoption in the upstream petroleum sector. Some of the main gaps affecting lean implementation in the sector have been identified as: lack of awareness, lack of comprehensive approach to lean adoption, inadequate stakeholder engagement, corruption and political interference, misalignment between lean and strategic business priorities and lack of local expertise especially within the upstream regulatory body. In proffering solutions, this research affirms Lean as a critical managerial strategy and philosophy suitable for adoption within upstream petroleum operations in developing economies with particular emphasis on leadership and governance, project management, shop floor management, Lean awareness, alignment with business priorities, people management,

culture and change management, waste elimination, continuous improvement and safety, health and environmental sustainability issues. From the literature, lean waste was mapped to waste in the upstream petroleum sector.

This study addresses the paucity in Lean literature within the research context, highlights key factors for successful implementation and proposes a conceptual 3-tier lean implementation approach. The results also affirm not only the existence of a structural relationship among lean elements, but underscore a strong relationship between lean elements and competitive business priorities when Lean elements are aggregated and tested. The results showed the composite strength or effect of lean of 0.69 on Cost and 0.82 on Quality. However, some Lean elements failed to establish a relationship with competitive business priorities when tested individually. This research is contextually novel and explores uncharted territories and serves as a foundation for further studies with potentially significant benefits to operators and major stakeholders within the upstream petroleum sector.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background of the Study

The global oil and gas industry has come under significant pressure to prioritize sustainable operations without compromising on quality, cost, and efficiency. Researchers, practitioners, and consultants continue to explore novel strategies to enhance business operations. One of such strategies is Lean Manufacturing.

According to Seitz (2003), citing Todd Philips (2000), explain that ... “the first thing you learn about lean, ... is that it’s a journey you set out upon, towards a destination you’ll never quite reach”. Lean Manufacturing (LM), Six Sigma (SS), Theory of Constraints (ToC), and Total Quality Management (TQM) are perceived as some of the most innovative management approaches being adopted by businesses to address existing challenges including profitability, growth and market share(Dekier, 2012). However, of the approaches outlined, lean became the most preferred because of its effectiveness (Dekier, 2012). Furthermore, Womack and Jones (2003) proffer that while on a world trip to launch the book titled: *The Machine That Changed the World* in the fall of 1990, many readers expressed interest and indicated a willingness to give lean production a try, but questioned... “*How can we do it?*” (Womack and Jones, 2003 p.9). Thus, whilst lean acceptability has been souring from its inception, the process of its adoption has been of concern to key stakeholders.

From a philosophical viewpoint, Lean Manufacturing (LM) is about “doing more with less” or “achieving more with less” and this mantra strongly resonates and aligns with the strategic

objectives of organizations striving to attain world-class status, meet ever-changing and sophisticated customer requirements in a highly competitive global business landscape (van Dun, Hicks and Wilderom, 2017a, De et al., 2020).

It is worth noting that extensive research has been conducted on the subject of Lean Manufacturing and its application across various industries including the petroleum industry in general, and the upstream petroleum sector in particular. However, many researchers, within the upstream petroleum sector contend that though lean plays a key role in the transformation of several industries, its application within the upstream petroleum sector is still highly undeveloped (Taj and Morosan, 2011a, Tsiga, Emes and Smith, 2017a, Rachman and Ratnayake, 2019).

The upstream petroleum sector is aptly described as the heart of the petroleum industry value chain, and consists of major activities including but not limited to exploration, drilling, production, geological surveys, seismic studies, gravity and magnetic surveys (Devold, 2013, Özgür, 2016), and each of these operational activities within the upstream sector also consist of activities relevant to their individual operations. Persaud (2007), indicate that the upstream petroleum sector encapsulate exploratory activities aimed at development and production of crude oil, and hence, it excludes refining. For the purpose of research, the terminologies “oil and gas” and “upstream petroleum” will interchangeably be used to refer to the same sector.

Anchored to a pragmatists worldview (Creswell, 2015), this cross-sectional sequential-exploratory research explores the application of lean manufacturing in petroleum producing organizations within the upstream petroleum sector. These petroleum producing companies,

otherwise called service companies or operators, undertake the core activities of lifting crude oil from viable wells. Service companies provide the requisite equipment, technology, and man-power necessary in the petroleum exploration and production process (Bagheri and Di Minin, 2015). Notable service companies operating within the West African enclave and Ghana, in particular, including but not limited to Schlumberger, Halliburton, and Baker Hughes (Bagheri and Di Minin, 2015).

Additionally, prior research posit that there is a paucity of empirically rigorous literature on Lean application in the upstream petroleum sector especially, in emerging economies in Sub-Saharan Africa (Ayarkwa, Joshua, Agyekum, Kofi, Adinyira, Emmanuel, Osei-Asibey, 2012, Ehie and Muogboh, 2016, Belhadi et al., 2020). This creates a knowledge gap which does not adequately support theorization, strategy, policy formulation, and practice.

This research is borne out of a need to contribute to existing context-specific knowledge, and practice of Lean manufacturing with specific reference to the upstream petroleum sector in emerging economies in Sub-Saharan Africa in general, and Ghana in particular. The stark challenges of the Ghana upstream petroleum sector including but not limited to operational inefficiencies, inadequate technical and managerial skills, production shortfalls, environmental, safety and regulatory issues are explained in the next sections of this research and lays the foundation for the conduct of this research. Subsequent sections of the research provide a detailed introduction to the petroleum industry, Lean manufacturing, and further justify the need and rationale for this research.

1.1 Problem Statement

Though lean was initially developed for the Toyota company, it has over the years become widely accepted and embraced across various industries. Thus, the challenges confronting the upstream petroleum sector could achieve the desired results through lean implementation. Apart from the constant crude oil price volatilities (Siakwah, 2017, Fitz et al, 2018a), other challenges affecting the upstream petroleum sector include environmental, geopolitical, societal unrests and dissatisfaction, operational inefficiencies, regulatory issues, emerging alternative sources of energy and falling demand (Irhoma, Su and Higginson, 2016, Fitz et al, 2018b, 2018a, Olujobi, Oyewunmi and Oyewunmi, 2018). Furthermore, the challenges outlined in the upstream petroleum sector negatively impact employee morale and performance. For instance, a survey of 1500 respondents conducted within the upstream petroleum sector in 2017 indicates that 54 percent of respondents were considering leaving the industry (Newman, 2012, Fitz et al, 2018b).

According to Lynch (2005), citing Womack and Jones, (1996); Monden,(1993); and Hirano, (1995), lean manufacturing is one of the innovative and most efficient methodologies compared to traditional or process-based production systems. Also, Taj and Morosan (2011) surveyed 65 Chinese companies fully practicing Lean, and argued that the petroleum industry is well advanced in the application of LM practices. However, there seems to be a paucity of literature to support this reality. To buttress this assertion, Rachman and Ratnayake (2017) explored Lean application in the petroleum industry and concluded that based on the type of literature reviewed, the subject was still very much immature. Also, Hossain (2006); Briggs and Tolliver (2012), hold the view that suppliers, long transportation lead times and inadequate production capabilities are key challenges facing the petroleum industry.

Furthermore, to lay emphasis on LM popularity in all economic sectors globally, studies show that “40.2 percent of US process industries adopted lean as compared to 62 percent of discrete industries” (Panwar et al., 2015 p.12). Also, “21% of Canadian food industries adopted lean” (Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015a).

Business leaders, researchers, practitioners and consultants continue to promote lean manufacturing as one of the most effective management strategies which organisations desirous of attaining world class status ought to embrace. However, justification for Lean implementation is critical to its success. The conditions prevalent in developing economies largely inform and provide context for Lean implementation in companies operating within those economies (Yadav et al., 2020). According to the Ghana statistical service (GSS,2020), Ghana’s industrial sector recorded growth rates of 3.32% in 2017; 3.4% in 2018 and 3.42% in 2019. In addition, the World Bank report on Ghana indicated an overall growth domestic product (GDP) of 4.2%. in 2019. Thus, the poor performances seen in Ghana’s manufacturing sector is also reflected in the upstream petroleum sector (Siakwah, 2017).Therefore, according to Sharma and Kodali (2008), Anand and Kodali (2009) and Jasti and Kodali (2016), though Lean manufacturing is a popular manufacturing strategy, it is important to determine the extent to which LM is suitable to the upstream petroleum sector. To buttress this assertion, Okhovat, Khairol, et al., (2012), argue that Lean implementation must be based on industry-specific requirements in order to ensure operational excellence.

Justifiably, the teething inefficiencies and challenges confronting the upstream petroleum operations in Ghana require the adoption of innovative production strategies to effectively support manufacturing organisations. However, notwithstanding the widespread acceptance of LM, there is little or no correlation between LM popularity on one hand, and LM implementation success (Pay, 2008, Jadhav, Mantha and Rane, 2014).

The overwhelming statistics of lean implementation failures point to a fundamental problem which requires a pragmatic solution. Identifiably, many authors (Liker, 2004; Mostafa et al., 2013; Chay et al., 2015) advance several valid viewpoints that contribute to lean implementation failures. The lack of industry-specific framework to guide lean implementation has been identified as one of several setbacks to successful LM application (Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2013a, Jasti and Kodali, 2019, Yadav et al., 2020). Similarly, Sharma and Kodali (2008) argue that the lack of a practical and detailed framework/model is a major setback to companies working towards attaining world-class status. Furthermore, some authors argue that the development of country-specific frameworks can enhance Lean implementation success especially in developing economies (Yadav et al., 2020). Similarly, in their publication, *“If Japan can, why can’t Africa?”*, Douglas, (2016), posit that whilst companies are growing in line with Africa’s continuous growth, quality culture in companies appear to be low. Furthermore, Chay et al., (2015) argue that enhancing quality and efficiency through Lean implementation is critical, but though the development of a framework is not a guarantee for LM transformation success, it is nonetheless seen as a major setback to LM implementation success.

Though several frameworks have been developed to guide Lean implementation across different sectors/companies (Ahlström, 1998, Anand and Kodali, 2009a, Dombrowski and Zahn, 2011a,

Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2013a, Bhamu and Sangwan, 2016, Jasti and Kodali, 2016, 2019, Rachman and Ratnayake, 2019), none of these frameworks seeks to improve Lean implementation within the upstream petroleum sector in developing economies like Ghana.

1.2 Research Questions

Literature on lean implementation suggests that there is an on-going debate among experts on the need to ensure the development of industry-specific frameworks for lean application. This will improve the rate of lean implementation success among organisations. The countless lean implementation challenges across various sectors, coupled with the lack of research on lean application in the upstream petroleum sector within the geographical context of Ghana, underscore the rationale for the formulation of the following research questions to guide the conduct of this research:

1. To what extent is Lean Manufacturing suitable for implementation in upstream petroleum producing organisations in developing economies?
2. How can Lean be successfully implemented in upstream petroleum producing organisations?
3. How best can Lean waste be translated/ mapped to the upstream petroleum sector?
4. What factors support the development of a comprehensive framework for lean application in upstream petroleum sector in developing economies?
5. What is the relationship between lean principles and competitive business priorities?

1.3 Research Aims and Objectives

The overarching aim of this research is to explore ways by which Lean implementation can be improved in developing economies through the development of a conceptual framework for LM implementation in the upstream petroleum sector.

The following constitute the main objectives guiding this research:

1. Review existing frameworks and identify key dimensions to successful framework development
2. To identify and evaluate critical success factors (CSFs) suitable for lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector.
3. To translate/map lean waste for the upstream petroleum sector
4. To determine the relationship between competitive priorities and lean principles
5. Explore LM tools, techniques, and principles adaptable in the upstream petroleum sector.
6. To develop a conceptual LM framework for adoption in the upstream petroleum sector.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study is to improve Lean implementation success through greater lean awareness in Ghana, establish the impact of and/or the benefits of implementing lean management principles within the upstream petroleum industry and make critical regulatory recommendations for adoption within upstream petroleum sector, academia and interested industry players. The target audience in this research include various categories of employees in the upstream petroleum industry, the Petroleum Commission of Ghana (PC), Energy Commission, and Consultants in the petroleum industry, service organisations within the upstream sector, academic and professional institutions interested in lean management. The findings and recommendations of the research will

also be useful in helping business leaders effectively improve Lean implementation in order to achieve desired objectives.

The study has explored insights about LM principles among senior management and operational staff drawn from upstream petroleum companies, directors/managers from regulatory institutions, and lean and/or petroleum experts within the upstream petroleum industry. Though the purpose of this research focuses on developing a conceptual framework for application within the upstream petroleum industry, an important aspect of this research explored ways by which lean implementation can be improved especially in developing economies.

1.5 Theoretical Foundation

Theoretical principles and practices have always significantly informed management discourse over the centuries and have resulted in the desired transformation in business operations. Theorists and practitioners including Frederick Taylor, Fayol, Gantt, Cook, and Gilbreth have significantly and validly contributed to a paradigm shift in management and industrial engineering (Taneja et al., 2011). In this study, various theoretical concepts have been explored and examined. The business process change (BPC) theory adequately underpins this study. Extant literature posit that researchers identify appropriate theoretical foundations that guide the conduct of their studies. Likewise, based on an evaluation of some existing theories including Lewin's change theory (1947), the theory of Constraints (Goldratt, 1990), Institutional theory (Scott, 1987), the theory of Business Process Change (Kettinger and Grover, 1995) is perceived to appropriately underpin the rationale and context of this research.

According to Kettinger and Grover (1995, p.iv) ...“*a business process is a set of logically related tasks that use the resources of an organization to achieve a defined business outcome*”. Furthermore, “*Business Process Reengineering (BPR), Process Improvement, Business Transformation, Process Innovation and Business Process Redesign are terms frequently used interchangeably to represent the phenomenon of Business Process Change*” (Kettinger and Grover, 1995, p iv). Out of several competing definitions of the BPC, one that resonates with the researcher’s perspective states that BPC is “*the fundamental rethinking and radical redesign of business processes to achieve dramatic improvements in critical, contemporary measures of performance*” (Kettinger and Grover, 1995).

Researchers trace the evolution of the BPC from contextual realism. To enhance successful lean implementation, the overarching importance of changes in business structure, systems, processes, and employee behaviour cannot be overemphasized (Almanei, Salonitis, and Tsinopoulos, 2018). Some of the most compelling and core tenets of BPC that support its adoption to guide this research include the following: “*BPC is strategy-led and mostly adopts a top-down approach similar to lean implementation; BPC also adopts cross-functional core processes; BPC is customer driven with a view to ensure customer value and satisfaction; It also adopts adequate methodical approaches in its implementation; BPC ensures individual and team empowerment; BPC strongly requires expertise/consultant support to enhance success; Finally, BPC harnesses information technology as a critical lever for success*”(Kettinger and Grover, 1995 p. iv.). The adoption of an appropriate methodology which supports this research is critical. The next subsection expounds on the rationale for, and the adoption of a mixed-methods approach supported by an exploratory-sequential design.

1.5.1 Methodological Considerations

The choice of appropriate methodological approaches to support the business process change theory cannot be overemphasised. From the research union approach proposed by Saunders et al., (2012), coupled with a review of existing philosophies, pragmatism was deemed most appropriate philosophy for this research. The study also adopted a mixed methods approach (Creswell, 2015), and developed a conceptual framework for lean application in the upstream petroleum sector in developing economies. The researcher further investigated the relationship between competitive business priorities and lean principles which culminated in the establishment of structural relationships between identified elements and business priorities.

The suitability of a mixed methods approach coupled with exploratory sequential design and a pragmatists paradigm, provides a comprehensive solution to the research objectives (Pallinkas et al., 2011; Creswell, 2015), theory/theories that support the adoption of an improvement strategy(ies) should demonstrate an appreciable level of congruence. Benin (2017), citing Stone (2015) discussed a methodical approach to kaizen activities including the “*identification of waste, implementing solutions, measuring results, and standardizing work practices*” (Benin, 2017, p.7). Many large organizations are adopting aspects of BPC or BPR in their operations (Childe, Maull, and Bennett, 1994). The upstream petroleum sector plays a pivotal role in global economic development. The adoption of improvement processes that will create the required sustainable and efficient production system cannot be overemphasized. The methodological structure of this research is represented in Figure 4.2 which illustrates how the research is positioned. To achieve the objectives set out in this research comprehensively, the research union approach proposed by Saunders et al., (2012), was adopted. Thus, to anchor this research on the theory of BPC is not only fundamental but gives credence to the pragmatist worldview underpinning the conduct of this research.

1.6 Chapter Scheme

This research is structured in seven chapters as illustrated in Figure 1.1 below:

Figure 1. 1: Schematic Structure of Thesis

Source: Author's Construct (2020).

1.7 Chapter Conclusion

This research has adopted a mixed-methods approach and a sequential exploratory design to address the research questions and hypotheses. The overarching objective of this research is to address the knowledge gap and contribute to existing contextual literature on lean application within the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana.

The research also contributes to and develops local expertise in the field of lean manufacturing in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. The introductory chapter outlines the scope of the research which encapsulates thematic areas including the background and context of the research, the challenges of the petroleum industry, statement of the problem, the purpose of the research, the aims and objectives of the study as well as research questions guiding the conduct of the research. Another important aspect covered in the introductory chapter is the significance of the study.

The second chapter explored extant literature on lean implementation, overview of the petroleum industry, challenges facing the upstream petroleum sector, lean definitions, gaps in the literature, and justification for the study. Other critical aspects covered in chapter 2 include translating lean wastes for the upstream petroleum sector, review of existing frameworks, and identifying critical success factors for lean implementation in the petroleum sector.

Chapter three outlined the research context, whilst chapter four is devoted to the methodology adopted. The fifth chapter consists of the analysis, results and discussions, whereas chapter six focused mainly on the framework development and adjustment process. The final chapter focused on the conclusions, recommendations and proposed future research.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

Globally, there are fundamental business concerns related to the achievement of business priorities including but not limited to profit, quality, cost, safety, and flexible operations. Available literature shows a constant and sustained effort by all categories of businesses not only for survival but to remain profitable within a highly competitive business landscape. Nonetheless, business survival depends on continuous improvement and innovation. Thus, organizations aiming to achieve world-class status adopt innovative management strategies such as lean manufacturing.

Notwithstanding the paucity of literature on lean application in the upstream petroleum industry in general and the Ghanaian context in particular, coupled with a lack of lean awareness within the Ghanaian context, insights drawn from literature in allied industries could be synthesized and made contextually relevant for application in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana (Ayarkwa, Joshua, Agyekum, Kofi, Adinyira, Emmanuel, Osei-Asibey, 2012).

According to Murray (2011), there are different approaches to adopt in writing a literature review. Whereas some writers prefer to integrate literature review in all chapters of the research process, others opt to make the literature review stand alone as a separate unit. Thus, after exploring the various approaches in existence, this research adopts the latter. There are varied perspectives of the literature review which contextually underscore the rationale and significance of the research. The perspective/definition should ideally guide the researcher's approach. Murray (2011), citing Anderson et al. (1970, p.17), posits that a literature review can be defined as "*A task that continues throughout the thesis...shows how the problem under investigation relates to previous research*".

In line with this definition, the literature review conducted in this research provides literature related to the lean application in the upstream petroleum industry, outlines existing gaps, and underscores the rationale for carrying out this research. The scope of this chapter includes but not limited to the following thematic areas: Introduction and nature of the petroleum industry, Critical success and failure factors for LM implementation, Analysis and synthesis of LM frameworks, the upstream petroleum production and management process, challenges of the upstream sector and translating lean wastes for the upstream petroleum sector.

The chapter also explores deeper meaning and understanding about the concept of lean, its evolution, guiding principles, and application processes to draw insights that will form the basis for the development of a holistic conceptual framework for application in the upstream petroleum sector. An in-depth exposé of the process flow adopted in conducting the literature review section of this research provides an informed perspective on the formulation of the research hypotheses. Thus, drawing insights from the literature review process culminated in a better understanding of lean theories and concepts, and how these are applied within the upstream petroleum industry. This further enhanced the gap analysis process in the literature leading to the formulation of research hypotheses.

2.1 Literature Search Strategy

Extant research shows that a well-thought-out literature review plan does not only guide the researcher but enables the researcher to focus on the most critical aspects of the research (Spackman, 2015; Benin, 2018). In this research, the following schematic outline was adopted as a guide in the literature review process:

Identification of keywords and terminologies including Lean Manufacturing, Lean Production, Lean Six Sigma, Lean Framework, Lean implementation model, Lean implementation roadmap, Lean implementation guidelines, Lean implementation approaches, critical success factors, challenges of lean implementation, petroleum industry, Upstream petroleum sector, petroleum production process, lean in the petroleum industry. However, to obtain relevant literature, and knowing that the concept of “*Lean*” has been extensively researched, the literature search strategy excluded the use of “Lean” in the search criteria and instead opted to use “Lean manufacturing” and “Lean production”. This criterion enabled the researcher obtain literature that was relevant to the study.

Identification of databases and Journal sources including Google Scholar, Emerald Insight, UWS One Search portal, Ebsco databases, Sage Journals, Taylor and Francis, SpringerLink, EthOs, IEEE Xplore, Statista, Web of Science and Science Direct. To elicit the relevant literature for the study, the following keywords/terminologies were used in the literature search. These included: oil and gas, petroleum industry, critical success factors, lean enablers, lean guiding principles, lean culture, lean thinking, lean framework, lean models, roadmaps, lean implementation approaches, upstream petroleum sector, offshore petroleum production process, and petroleum supply chain. To expand the search, OR (Boolean operator) was used to link two keywords, and “AND” was used to join sets of words to one another. For example: “lean OR lean models OR lean implementation” AND “upstream petroleum sector” AND “benefits” OR “challenges”. The study adopted literature filtering procedure similar to the format used by Farias et al., (2019). Figure 2.1 illustrates the literature review strategy adopted in this research.

Figure 2. 1: Filtering procedure for Literature Review

Source: Farias et al., (2019)

2.2 Introduction to the Petroleum Industry

Petroleum is an extractive natural resource. Its formation dates back millions of years ago and involved the build-up of dead leaves, animals for millions of years without oxygen and transformed into dark liquid oil (Above and Bankole, 2018). The petroleum industry is the driving force of the global economy (Statistica, 2018). In the USA, the “petroleum industry supports more than 9.2 million jobs and accounts for 7.5 per cent of the GDP. According to the American Petroleum Institute (API), the petroleum industry has created about 2 million jobs from 2004-2007 (American Petroleum Institute, 2010). Future investments in the petroleum industry are also significant. The International Energy Administration (IEA) forecasts \$9.6 trillion investment in the petroleum industry (out of a total of \$22 trillion investment in the energy sector) from 2006-2030” (Mellat-Parast, 2013).

The evolution of the petroleum industry dates back to 1859 when Colonel Edwin L. Drake discovered oil in Titusville, Pennsylvania (Fagan, 1991). It is a definitive process-based industry (Fagan, 1991, Acha and Cusmano, 2007). The upstream petroleum operations constitute one of the world’s largest industries and covers a wide range of activities (Fagan, 1991, Bagheri and Di Minin, 2015, Jafarinejad, 2017). Research suggests that the trajectory of the petroleum industry in the 20th century encapsulated critical periods of expansion and disruptions followed by periods of equilibria (Mitchell and Mitchell, 2014). *“The market size of the global petroleum industry is estimated to be about \$3073.4 billion, with a total volume of 46792.5 million barrels’ equivalent, with a 4% increase projection by 2019”* (Tsigas, Emes and Smith, 2017b p.225). Furthermore, it is worth noting that *“at its core, however, the industry is ultimately based on the extraction and utilization of a depleting and finite petroleum resource base and requires enormous capital investment”* (Clews, 2016 p. 252). Processes include petroleum field operations, production,

refining and refinery operations, and refining technologies (Devold, 2006, 2013, Jafarinejad, 2017). The major products produced from petroleum refinery process include; “*liquefied petroleum gas, gasoline, diesel fuel, kerosene, fuel oil, lubricating oil, and paraffin wax*” (Speight and Wiley, 1949 p.1).

The industry is categorized into upstream, midstream, and downstream operations (Devold, 2006, 2013, Özgür, 2016, Jafarinejad, 2017). The value chain in the petroleum industry starts with the upstream which entails exploration, drilling, and production, to the transportation and refinery which is the midstream and ends with the downstream which is responsible for the marketing and distribution of petroleum (Maleki, Rosiello and Wield, 2018). “Although petroleum products were first used for heating and lighting, it was only with the development of diesel, petrol, and jet engines that demand for the industry’s products began to accelerate. The growth of the industry largely mirrors the growth in the automotive industry and increased rapidly as vehicle usage grew, particularly in the decades following the end of world war 2 (WWII). The development of turbine technology also increased demand for other petroleum products such as jet fuel for the airline industry and natural gas for power generation (Clews, 2016).”

The petroleum industry accounts for more than half of global energy requirements. Available data from the BP Statistical Review of World Energy (2014), indicate that the world’s demand for energy was projected to be around 12.7 billion tonnes of oil equivalent in 2013 of which oil and gas accounted for about 57%, while the remaining was catered for by coal, nuclear energy, hydropower, and renewable energy.

2.3 Nature of the Petroleum Industry

2.3.1 Crude Oil

Crude oil is a mixture of more than 200 compounds consisting of alkanes and smaller fractions of aromatics (Devold, 2013). Stated differently, crude oil is defined as a complex mixture of molecules, consisting of compounds formed from hydrogen and carbon atoms known as hydrocarbons, and typically categorized into light, heavy, sweet, or sour (Nguyen et al., 2014). Extant literature shows that light crude oil reserves have been declining over the years, and this has necessitated the need to explore options to upgrade available heavy crude oil (Meyer et al, 2007, Nassar, Hassan, and Pereira-almao, 2011).

Crude oil/petroleum is a major energy source without which the global economy will suffer dire consequences. There are variations in crude oil as measured by the American Institute of Petroleum (API). Crude oil is made up of *10-14wt% hydrogen and 83 -87wt% carbon* (Jafarinejad, 2017 p.2). Other elements that make up crude oil include *oxygen (0.05–1.5wt%), sulphur (0.05-6wt%), and nitrogen (0.1– 2wt%)*(Jafarinejad, 2017 p.2).

2.3.2 Petroleum Formation

The term “petroleum” originates from the Latin word meaning “rock oil” (Devold, 2013). Petroleum is formed from the accumulation of decomposed organic materials including plants and animals and constitutes one of nature’s most valuable resources within the extractive industry which supports the transportation and many other industries for maintenance and contributes significantly to global economic development (Jafarinejad, 2014; Jafarinejad, 2016). In other words, oil and gas together with the transport industries constitute the main drivers of the global economy (Briggs and Tolliver, 2012; Fitz et al., 2018).

A major objective of the petroleum industry is to ensure constant and uninterrupted provision of hydrocarbon fluids, oil and gas at a profit (Nashawi, Malallah and Al-bisharah, 2010). While studies project that world energy consumption including coal, fossil fuels, lignite oil, and natural gas, will increase from 81% in 2000 to 88% in 2030, with oil representing 34%, continuous pressure from environmentalists, pro-climate change advocates and lobbyists maintain the need to transition from non-renewable extractive resources to cleaner and environmentally friendly energy sources to enhance sustainability, protect the eco-system and avoid environmental pollution (European Economy, 2003, Sachs, and Ban, 2016, Aho and Bankole, 2017, 2018, Gulas et al., 2017). An outstanding affirmative action plan to reduce the over-dependence on non-renewable energy sources underpins the adoption of policy-directives for the introduction and stringent implementation of electric vehicles (Christophe Brognaux, Eric Boudier, 2017).

Ideally, it is expected that countries/economies enriched with crude oil resources should translate into development and strong economic performance. Paradoxically, countries with huge deposits of crude oil continue to suffer the consequences of underdevelopment compared to countries without crude oil (Ranis, 1991, Sachs and Warner, 1995, Lal and Myint, 1996, Auty, 2001). Notably, the per capita incomes of countries without natural resource deposits have tripled compared to countries with crude oil. Economic growth has constantly and rapidly widened since the 1970s (Donwa, Mbame, and Ekpulu, 2015). More than four billion metric tons of oil are delivered annually, of which about 33% is produced in the Middle East and Saudi Arabia. The United States follows with 13% whilst Russia accounts for 12% of the world's aggregate oil production volume (Statista, 2018). Evidence shows that between 1992 – 2013, the Middle East controlled 60% of the world's petroleum reserves (Jafarinejad, 2016).

Notwithstanding the observed economic impact of the petroleum industry, uncertainties in the global economic outlook, coupled with unpredictable price fluctuations within the oil and gas industry (Mohaddes and Pesaran, 2017, Yu et al., 2018), exert enormous pressures on petroleum organizations not only to establish production flexibility systems (Okhovat, Ahmadpour, et al., 2012, Dombrowski, Ebentreich and Krenkel, 2016) but also to ensure sustainability, increase efficiency, enhance quality, optimize production (Dombrowski and Zahn, 2011b); as well as eliminate waste and create customer value (Kazmi, 2008a).

The division of the petroleum industry and the functions of the three sectors are independently interrelated because the output of one sector serves as raw material for the next (Devold, 2009; Fitz et al., 2018). According to Jafarinejad (2017), the operational focus areas of the various subdivisions include:

- The upstream sector undertakes the exploration, development, and extraction/production of crude oil (Jafarinejad, 2017).
- The midstream sector focuses on activities such as transportation of crude oil (using pipelines, trucks, tanker ships, and rail), storage, and processing of crude oil.
- The downstream sector covers the refining and/or processing of hydrocarbons, marketing, and distribution.

2.3.3 Global Distribution of Petroleum Reserves

Crude oil is a naturally occurring depletable resource. This fact necessarily reinforces the need for strategic planning to diversify economic sectors capable of complementing and/or taking over economic sustainability when the natural resource is eventually depleted. However, crude oil reserves continue to be a major source of economic attraction for major actors. Available literature

suggests that between 1990 to 2011, global oil reserves increased from one billion(1bn) barrels in 1990 to a record of 1.7 billion barrels in 2011. Reserves on regional basis show a decline in reserves in the Middle East and North America, with Latin America reporting a fifth of world oil reserves (Statistica, 2020). Figure 2.2 and Table 2.3 illustrate the world oil reserves.

Figure 2. 2: World distribution of petroleum reserves, 1990 – 2000

Source: Jafarinjad, (2017)

Extant literature suggests a paradigm shift in global petroleum reserves. The data shown in Fig.2.2 above indicate that the Middle East recorded the highest reserves of petroleum in the world between 1990--2000. According to Jafarinejad (2017), the Middle East reported about 60% of total world petroleum reserves between 1992 to 2013. However, this is contrary to the evidence shown in Table 2.3 and figure 2.3 below which puts Latin America ahead of the Middle East.

Table 2. 3: Global crude oil reserves

Crude oil global reserves 1990-2019	
Volume of global oil reserves from 1990 to 2019 (in billion barrels)	
1990	1,027.5
1995	1,126.2
2004	1,366.2
2005	1,374.4
2006	1,383.7
2007	1,427.1
2008	1,490
2009	1,531.8
2010	1,636.6
2011	1,675.3
2012	1,697.9
2013	1,701
2014	1,700
2015	1,697.6
2016	1,697.1
2017	1,727.5
2018	1,735.9
2019	1,733.9

Source: Statistica,(2020)

Figure 2. 3: World distribution of petroleum reserves from 1990 -2019

Source: Statistica, (2020)

2.3.4 The Upstream Petroleum Sector

The production processes within the upstream petroleum sector consists of key stages of activities aimed at converting petroleum resources into useable end-products. It starts with the identification of suitable areas to conduct exploration (Bagheri et al., 2015). The upstream value chain consists of interrelated and interdependent projects which requires specialized skills to ensure effective execution. Figure 2.4 illustrates the four critical operational areas of the upstream petroleum sector. Typically, the talent pool required to execute upstream petroleum projects include: geoscientists, geologists, geophysicists, engineers, technicians and specialists (Alleyne and Alexander, 2018).

Figure 2. 4: The Value Chain of the Upstream Sector

Source: Alleyne and Alexander (2018)

The upstream petroleum activities are categorized into four entities as shown in Figure 2.5. Operating companies are involved in high-risk/high-reward aspects of exploration and production of crude oil, whilst the regulators are sector leaders tasked with the responsibility of monitoring, controlling and with overall management of the upstream operations. In the case of Ghana, the Petroleum Commission (PC) is the regular of the upstream sector. Also, oil field service companies provide services to upstream exploration and production companies whereas academia consists of institutions involved in research, education and the provision of scholarships to support talent development (Alleyne and Alexander, 2018, Benin, 2018).

Figure 2. 5: Petroleum Industry Entities

Source: Alleyne and Alexander (2018)

Typically, the upstream petroleum operations are a high capital investment venture which has long dominated capital expenditure market compared to conventional operations (Fitz et al., 2018). Studies show that large oil and gas companies spend more on upstream operations than the downstream operations. Thus, upstream spend in 2014, by major oil companies was estimated to be between 80 to 90 percent of overall capital expenditure (Clews, 2016). To buttress these research findings, a study by the Boston Consulting Group (BCG) established that between 2014 to 2017 show that upstream Capex budgets in 2016 were 60% lower than in 2014 albeit budgets went up between 7% - 9% in 2017 (Streubel and Ravishankar, 2017, Fitz et al, 2018a). Investments in the upstream petroleum industry continue to increase over the years as a reflection of the pivotal role the industry plays in the global economy. Figure 2.6 depicts the annual rate of investment in the upstream petroleum sector.

Figure 2. 6: World upstream oil and gas investment

Source: <http://energyfuse.org/oil-gas-industry-dealing-unprecedented-decline-investment>

As demand for energy continues to increase and shape business globally, the petroleum industry in response, is rapidly undergoing significant changes in two ways. “First, with much of the world’s “easy oil” already consumed, upstream petroleum companies will have to use increasingly sophisticated technologies to find and produce future hydrocarbons” (Perrons, 2014 p.301). To support this assertion, available literature projects that future exploration of natural resources such as oil will be extremely hard to find because continuous exploration and depletion of the resource will restrict future finds to highly inaccessible environments (Perrons, 2014). Secondly, notable disastrous incidents such as the “Piper Alpha incident in 1988 (Paté Cornell, 1993), the Exxon Valdez oil spill in 1989 (Coll, 2012; Plater, 2011), Shell’s Brent Spar incident in 1995 (Frynas, 2003; Shuyterman, 2010) and the recent Deepwater Horizon accident (Flournoy, 2011; Perrons, 2014) have brought about drastic changes in the expectations placed upon upstream petroleum companies with regards to environmental stewardship, safety and human welfare” (Perrons, 2014 p.301). Amidst the current challenges, the vital role of technology as a

determinant of the success or failure of tomorrow's firms in the upstream petroleum sector cannot be overemphasized (Mitchell et al., 2012). Furthermore, Perrons (2014), citing Perrons and Watts, (2008) and Sharma, (2005), posit that notwithstanding the focus on technology, the upstream petroleum industry is regarded as being slow to develop and adopt changing technology and innovations. Thus, some upstream petroleum operations make it extremely difficult for upstream operators to adopt and maintain proprietary information in relation to technology and innovations (Perrons, 2014). As a consequence, this erodes any competitive advantage that might accrue to an organization which prioritises and adopts innovation and technological improvements in its operations (Paul, 2007; Mitchell et al., 2012; Perrons, 2014). In addition, the highly sophisticated nature of upstream operations "*coupled with the extreme risks...and high cost of failure associated with being a first user of new technologies are such that upstream operators prefer to be fast followers*" (Perrons, 2014 p. 302). Consequently, the average timelines for innovation and technological advancement is estimated to take 16 years within which projects progress from the concept phase to widespread commercial adoption (Perrons, 2014).

The upstream petroleum sector is further categorised as "slow clock speed" (Perrons, 2014), "low and medium-tech" and "technologically timid" (Lashinsky, 2010). Major players within the sector have also been classified as "low R&D intensity" due to historically low investment of less than 1% of accrued net revenue in research and development. Research findings show that the upstream petroleum sector has undergone significant changes, nonetheless, several international oil companies (IOCs) point to technology as an increasingly important strategic priority (Chazan, 2013; Kulkarni, 2011; Parshall, 2011), and spending on innovation and R&D by both IOCs and national oil companies (NOCs) has increased significantly over the past few years (Thuriaux

Alemán et al., 2010). The forgone discourse underscore rational presumptions of sustained efforts to increase not only the amount but also the pace of innovation within the upstream petroleum sector”(Perrons, 2014).

2.3.5 Challenges facing Upstream Petroleum Operations

The petroleum industry has, and continues to face challenges such as operational/production issues, environmental, geopolitical, governance and regulatory issues, the threat of emerging alternative sources of energy, and price and demand fluctuations (Jafarinejad, 2017, Fitz et al, 2018b). The next subsections expand on each of the aforementioned challenges outlined and contextually justify the overarching significance of the research.

2.3.5.1 Operational/Production Challenges

The petroleum production process is one of the highly specialized operations. As a result, several factors can obstruct smooth operations. However, fundamentally, people constitute the most important factor in the production and/or operations process. The upstream petroleum sector lacks highly-skilled, well-trained, and highly-motivated local employees to effectively undertake production (Al-Mahroos and Zubari, 2009; Benin, 2018; Alleyne and Utt, 2018). Morel et al. (2010) argue that owing to remote and often highly inaccessible locations of many offshore production facilities, shipment and storage tend to become significantly expensive. The upstream sector is characterized by a lack of a conducive environment for quick decision-making and effective and efficient monitoring and evaluation systems (Al-Mahroos and Zubari, 2009). Hegazi and Andersson (2016) also asserted that the sector is continually troubled with the corrosion of processing equipment. These constitute a tip of the iceberg of challenges with a negative impact on production and/or operational activities.

2.3.5.2 Environmental Challenges

Atmospheric emissions, aquatic, terrestrial impacts, and potential emergencies are some environmental challenges caused by upstream petroleum operations (Bayagbon, 2011; Bukhari, 2013; Sonibare and Akeredolu, 2006). Specific environmental challenges within the upstream operations are described below:

- At the exploration and production stages in the upstream operation, adequate work procedures and technologies are strictly adhered to in order to minimize emissions. Some consequences of environmental degradation including oil and gas exploration, flaring, venting from diesel engines result in climate change, ozone layer depletion and greenhouse gases.
- Also, upstream activities include drilling, liquid and solid disposal, and spills/leakages impact negatively on aquatic life, the soil and the environment.

Olujobi and Oyewunmi (2018) emphasized that upstream petroleum operations affect the ecosystem, and interference with land use, brings about environmental pollution, safety problems, and poses significant health risks to lives. The upstream petroleum operational challenges need to be addressed to minimize environmental impact and create sustainability. Lean management and environmental management impact each other (Chiarini, 2014), and the need for proper and strategic integration to provide an eco-friendly and sustainable manufacturing operations cannot be overemphasized. Existing literature posit that the synergistic link between Lean and environmental management which has been strongly advocated and supported by major regulatory agencies in the US and Europe is not entirely new. The integration of these strategies is important for sustainable manufacturing (Vargas and Scott, 2017).

2.3.5.3 Geopolitical Challenges

Historically, the global oil and gas industry has experienced significant price-volatility attributable to two major periods of price shocks with associated geopolitical underpinnings. The first major price shock occurred between 1973 – 1986, whilst the second happened between 1998- present (Ediger and Berk, 2018). Economically, the impact of price-volatilities of petroleum on producing countries cannot be overemphasizing especially in developing economies. Closely linked to this is the fact that petroleum as a resource can be perceived as a double-edged sword because it is both a power tool in global geopolitics and in many instances a source of conflict and instability (Anifowose et al., 2012, Ediger and Berk, 2018). Thus, the geopolitical challenges of petroleum require effective management. Oil production in Nigeria is said to have deprived the country of the peace due to numerous oil-related conflicts (Olujobi and Oyewunmi, 2018).

Noguera-Santaella (2016) “mapped the relationship between conflicts and oil prices and found that geopolitical events caused oil prices to rise before 2000, but have had little if any, impact since 2000. Geopolitical factors were more consequential for oil prices during crisis periods, and conversely, oil crises had several implications for global geopolitics. It was a genuine chicken-and-egg situation: geopolitics have affected prices, and the resulting prices have changed geopolitics. It can be a vicious circle in which one problem causes another problem, which compounds the first problem (Ediger and Berk, 2018). Emerson (2015) explains this situation as the cyclic variation of geopolitics, energy security, crude export ban, and low prices. For instance, resource nationalism followed by the Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries’ (OAPEC) embargo in 1973/74 can be considered as one of the main reasons for oil crises.”

Economically powerful nations have capitalized on geopolitical competitiveness to entrench their presence in oil-rich or resource-rich countries, and their activities have and continue to create attention across the globe. For instance, the United States of America has positioned its forces across countries and continents for several reasons including the natural resource gains that it stands to benefit. Specifically, the US military is positioned in the Middle East, Africa, Europe and others (Ediger and Berk, 2018; Olujobi and Oyewunmi, 2018).

2.3.5.4 Leadership, Governance and Regulatory Challenges

Studies show that majority of the world's untapped oil reserves is found in developing countries without the requisite resources and technological know-how to exploit those resources. Therefore, governments within these developing countries endowed with oil resource resort to contract and/or partnerships with international oil companies (IOCs) with the resources and technical capabilities to carry out the exploration and production (Hunter, 2015; Ediger and Berk, 2018). The nature of contractual agreements between governments and IOCs tend to be long-term contracts which often expose governments to dire sovereign risks including but not limited to political interference. For instance, in the event of a regime change, corrupt practices may result in contract renegotiation, unilateral change in terms of contract by the host country, or the expropriation of property in oil reserves, and these constitute risks developing economies with oil reserves are exposed to (Hunter, 2015; Ediger and Berk, 2018; Olujobi and Oyewunmi, 2018).

Many species including marine mammals, birds, and fishes “are highly vulnerable to oil spill impacts due to the activities carried out in or near offshore petroleum drilling areas. It is important that the development of robust, internationally acceptable policies and technologies are certified

prior to renewal of exploration interests and related protocols are considered (Amos, 2011; Fidler and Noble, 2012).

Globally, several agreements and protocols are in place to cater for emergency response regulations and procedures for Arctic oil and gas activities (Monitoring, 2007). However, the ability of nations to respond to oil spills that could cross nautical boundaries is limited, but the Arctic Council, an inter-governmental forum composed of eight Arctic states, was created to address these challenges (Arctic Council, 2016). States that have recently conducted offshore oil and gas activity have established systems for emergency preparedness that follow Arctic Council guidelines developed specifically for the Arctic (Council, 2009; Knol and Arbo, 2014). However, increasing accessibility has raised concerns about international emergency preparedness and oil spill pollution prevention. Whereas the literature describes emergency preparedness for well-established and experienced operational regions/countries, the same cannot be said of developing economies whose operations are still described as being at an infant stage. Nonetheless, insights from experienced operations props up infrastructural support systems and emergency measures adopted in operations within developing economies.

The development of effective technologies, regulations, and policies to help mitigate potential negative impacts, particularly to protect fragile marine resources are required (Koivurova and Molenaar, 2009). Without effective emergency response systems, future exploration and production of oil and gas may be politically unacceptable. Arguably, there remain significant and unacceptable environmental risks, regardless of individual nation preparedness or strong regulatory frameworks” (WWF-Canada, 2011).

2.3.5.5 Price and Demand Fluctuations

The energy price and its volatility influence the overall layout of the energy sector and are considered to be the most powerful driving factors at present. The energy price level affects new oil and natural gas resource development prospects, technological development, infrastructure, etc. The volatility of the energy price creates additional instability and unpredictability in the energy markets (Blomkvist and Johansson, 2016). Additionally, these forces add to the price imbalance among regional energy markets and between the energy resources themselves. The price of natural gas in Europe, the U.S., and Japan differs significantly, whereas price volatility increases the gap (Blomkvist and Johansson, 2016).

“Until recently, global interest in petroleum exploration has been largely fuelled by relatively high global energy prices” (Gulas et al., 2017 p.53). Furthermore, studies show that *“offshore drilling activity has seen cycles of exploration and development, largely due to wide fluctuations in global energy prices”* (Gulas et al., 2017 p.53). significant interests in Arctic petroleum exploration cannot be overlooked, however, considerable logistical and technical challenges have affected interests (Gulas et al., 2017). Nonetheless, *“the cyclical nature of Arctic hydrocarbon exploration, a resurgence in oil and gas prices could spark renewed interest”* (Gulas et al., 2017 p.53).

2.3.5.6 Conflict and Instability

Communal unrest, terrorism, and wars are characteristic features of many petroleum-producing countries/communities. These unrests have generated concerns with the stability of energy supplies (Blomkvist and Johansson, 2016).

Drawing lessons from upstream operations in neighbouring Nigeria, available literature indicates that *“conflicts between oil companies and local communities have...revolved around land ownership and compensation for land appropriation as well as compensation for environmental damages due to oil operations, and also, there have been frequent disputes over the causes of oil spills and whether oil companies are eligible to pay compensation, and if so, to what extent”* (Oyefusi, 2007 p.7).

Conflicts resulting from distribution of oil revenues, infrastructure and social between ethnic and regional groups, and the failure of governments to take adequate measures to address and/or mitigate environmental effects of oil operations on local communities or to adequately compensate communities for such damages (Oyefusi, 2007). These conflicts can have far-reaching consequences on energy markets and petroleum prices (Blomkvist and Johansson, 2016). To buttress this assertion, Herbert-Burns (2012), assert that major petroleum producing countries/geographical locations are bedevilled with crisis. Figure 2.7 illustrates petroleum-rich locations in the world riling in various forms of crisis.

Statistics of oil and gas reserves show huge deposits along the Arab world including but not limited to: *“Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Qatar, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, the UAE and Uzbekistan”*(Herbert-Burns, 2012 p.38). Within the context of geographical context of this study, studies show that the major world producing country in West Africa is Nigeria which akin to factors prevalent in oil-rich Arabian countries, is characterized by perpetual ethnic conflicts and terrorists activities (Oyefusi, 2007, Atsegbua, 2012, Omojolaibi and Egwaikhide, 2013, Aabove and Bankole, 2017). Notwithstanding high risks of conflicts that

characterize oil-rich states globally, it still remains a key global economic driver which political actors and major global superpowers will continue to use to control and consolidate their powers. Ghana's oil reserves may appear insignificant in comparison with but its relatively peaceful political and geographical climate appear to be a point of attraction to some multinational operators who are keen to conduct deep-water explorations. However, unlike other jurisdictions, literature available indicate that in 2014 Ghana approached the International Tribunal and instituted a case against neighbouring Ivory Coast and demanded the International Tribunal for the law of the Sea (ITLOS) to interpret the equidistance principle for the maritime delimitation. Subsequently, in 2017, the International Tribunal presented its judgement which went in favour of Ghana (Garrido-Muñoz, 2018). Thus, whilst it is critical to adhere to international standards and regulations in petroleum production process, the reality of perpetual conflict across the world cannot be overlooked.

Figure 2. 7: Global petroleum-rich locations associated with various forms of crisis

Source: Herbert-Burns (2012) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

The challenges outlined above represent a tip of the iceberg of untold challenges within the upstream petroleum sector that require pragmatic and sustainable solutions considering the pivotal role the sector plays within the global economy. Lean Management(LM) is one of many problem-solving strategies/approaches/methods/philosophies available for management consideration. Thus, without recourse to other strategies, this study focuses on how LM can provide the much-needed sustainable and strategic solutions to the operations within the upstream petroleum sector.

2.3.5.7 Technological Challenges

Technology plays a crucial role in all sectors of the global economy. The highly specialized nature of the upstream petroleum operations makes the application of advanced technology more crucial. The global business landscape revolves around technological advancement. Thus, the evolution of the concept of industrialization and the subsequent inception of the fourth industrial revolution otherwise referred to as Industry 4.0 (I 4.0) underscore the overarching importance of information and communication technology (Buer, Strandhagen and Chan, 2018), in the operations of not only the upstream petroleum sector but the entire global business landscape.

The upstream petroleum sector is aptly described as risk-averse and slow to adopt innovation and technology (Mitchell et al., 2012) albeit technology is the bedrock of the success of upstream operations. However, notwithstanding the assertion that the upstream is a slow adopter to innovation, technology can be used to lower operational risks (Bret-Rouzaut et al., 2005). The commencement of seismic surveys, through exploration, drilling, and production relies heavily on highly advanced technology and engineering equipment/machines. Research further shows that technology and innovation continue to reshape the global upstream landscape (Alleyne and

Alexander, 2018). Within the upstream petroleum sector, exploration, drilling, and production activities are more pronounced in offshore territorial waters than it is onshore. Though the level of sophisticated operations remains relatively high, the technology required to operate offshore far advanced than it is for onshore exploration, drilling, and production of hydrocarbons.

Technological innovation is/can be described as the panacea and/or a critical success factor to upstream operational success (Persaud, 2007). However, suffice to surmise that it would be paradoxical to discuss technology without discussing the human resource capability to manage technology especially within the upstream sector in emerging markets akin to Ghana. Thus, in its emerging stages, the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana has a huge human resource-deficit. The required skill set to effectively manage technology within the sector is in scarce demand. The local content law (L.I 2204) provides in part, to upskill local expertise within the upstream sector (Alleyne and Alexander, 2018, Benin, 2018).

2.3.6 Characteristics of the Upstream Petroleum Sector

The upstream petroleum sector which constitutes the bedrock of the entire non-renewable oil and gas sector is laden with certain key features that either positively or negatively impact the operations of the sector. There is no doubt that it is first and foremost an intensive capital investment sector, especially with regards to offshore deep-sea exploration activities. Thus huge investments in technology, research, and development (R&D), seismic survey activities, drilling, equipment as well as required logistics. Researchers have categorized the characteristics of the upstream operations from different perspectives. For instance, Lashinsky (2010), indicates that the sector is technologically timid whereas, Aleman et al. (2010) hold the view that following the increasing participation of IOCs within the sector, with huge capital investment in R&D, it will

inure to the benefit of IOCs. Furthermore, von Tunzelmann and Acha (2006), intimate that characteristically, the sector is low and medium-tech.

From an operations management perspective, “the petroleum industry has several unique characteristics (Varma et al., 2007):

Suppliers: The number of suppliers in the petroleum industry is rather limited. From this aspect, it is a sellers’ market.

Raw material: While the price of raw material is pretty stable in other industries, the price of the crude oil fluctuates significantly.

Reverse production system: In most industries, several components/parts are assembled to develop a new product. In contrast, in the petroleum industry, the creation of new products starts from downstream, i.e. several products (e.g. gasoline and diesel) are created from crude oil.

High-transportation cost: Petroleum industry has a relatively high-transportation cost compared to other industries. It is estimated that the transportation cost would be about 20 percent of the production cost in the petroleum industry.

Production process: Petroleum industry uses continuous operations. Therefore, it enjoys relatively low-unit costs (due to the standardization of the processes and high rate of output). It uses rigid and standard operations; therefore, it is less flexible.

Another challenge is capacity planning and utilization. To get the lowest unit price, oil and gas companies need to operate constantly. There is little room to make any changes to the capacity. As a result of this, it would be difficult to make scheduling change (due to high set-up costs). Therefore, product postponement is not applicable in this situation.

Sources of profitability: Due to the lack of product variety, cost reduction, and efficiency are the major sources of competitiveness.

Information sharing: Despite some efforts to integrate business processes, there is not much emphasis on information sharing within the petroleum industry. As a result of this, visibility across the supply chain in the petroleum industry is low. The importance of operations, high level of standardization, and emphasis on efficiency make the petroleum industry a suitable industry to test a variety of operations and production management theories. Besides, due to the importance of the petroleum industry to the global economy, any improvement in operational processes and cost reduction has a significant effect on the regional, national, and global economy (Mellat-Parast, 2013).”

2.3.7 The Upstream Petroleum Production Process

Petroleum/oil and gas exploration and production are generally referred to as E&P, which is within the upstream petroleum sector (Jafarinejad, 2017). The term “Production” is described as a process of extracting crude oil from drilled wells and critically evaluated reservoirs, in which a mixture of fluids from the reservoir in the form of oil, gas, and water is lifted to the surface of production area for separation and further refinery (Devold, 2013, Jafarinejad, 2017).

Within the upstream petroleum sector, production is carried out either offshore or onshore, and in the offshore production process, the Floating, Production, Storage, and Offloading(FPSO) vessel is primarily deployed to perform the production function. Thus, appropriate strategic and critical analysis of FPSO selection is an important task in managing operational costs and improving efficiency (Maria et al., 2015, Allahyarzadeh-Bidgoli et al., 2018, Barbosa et al., 2019). According

to Devold (2013), the increasing depth of new offshore oil field development presents huge risks making the deployment of FPSOs inevitable in the production process.

FPSOs come in various capacities, complexities, and range optimal usages with its attendant cost implications. Some FPSOs perform drilling operations and are referred to as FDPSOs (Floating, Drilling, Production, Storage and Offloading) units. Figure 2.8 presents a typical FPSO in operation. FPSOs operate as a complete unit without additional infrastructure requirements and can be moved from one location to another to continue operation once a particular well is depleted. FPSOs are either converted from already existing tankers or made-to-do, especially with specific operational requirements by the operator. Notable variations in the design of FPSOs include but not limited to the Seven Marine design, Tension Leg Platform (TLP), Semi-submersible platforms and the SPAR (Alvarado et al., 2002, Devold, 2013). Notwithstanding the invaluable functionality of the FPSO, corrosion remains a major threat to the durability of the vessel (Suarez and Polomka, 2018).

Figure 2. 8: Floating, Production, Storage, and Offloading(FPSO) vessel

Source: BW Pioneer, (2020) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Petroleum or crude oil is generally used to describe the “black gold” which consists of a range of other elements including sulphur, nitrogen, and oxygen. Petroleum is a non-renewable naturally occurring mixture of hydrocarbons in liquid form (Devold, 2009; Peters et al., 2005).

The petroleum production consists of a complex process with shared similarities and significantly varied differences dependent on whether it is onshore or offshore production. Whilst onshore production is economically viable (Devold, 2009), offshore production is more sophisticated and capital intensive. After a successful analysis of seismic data (Baaziz and Quoniam, 2019), the next major activity is drilling which is carried out to establish the find. When drilling is completed, the drilled well is verified to determine if there are commercially viable quantities of crude oil. Once verified, viable wells are “completed” by the casing and evaluating for pressure and temperature

before production (Devold, 2013, Jafarinejad, 2017). Figure 2.8 captures the process flow of oil and gas production activities (Devold, 2013).

Figure 2. 9: Process flow of Oil and Gas Production

Source: Devold, (2013)

The core business of the upstream petroleum operation is the extraction of hydrocarbons from commercially viable drilled and verified oilfields/wells. Thematic terminologies and/or processes which require further description such as drilling, fracking, new well evaluation, well casing, production and emerging petroleum gateways are further elaborated (see Appendix M).

The significance of crude oil in the context of the global economy, and most importantly in the context of developing economies like Ghana, cannot be overemphasized. Thus, the exploration and production as well as its appropriate management has the capacity to propel economic

development. Thus, application of innovative management strategies like Lean manufacturing is vital to the overall operational success of the sector. The challenges outlined herein under subsection 2.3.5 require effective implementation of Lean manufacturing interventions in order to optimize operational success. the next section of literature review section explores Lean manufacturing and its implementation approaches.

2.4 Introduction to Lean Manufacturing (LM)

Lean also termed Lean Management, Lean Manufacturing, Lean Production, or Lean Enterprise has been adopted by several companies within the manufacturing, production and/or extractive industries (Liker and Morgan, 2006, Pedersen and Huniche, 2011, Kundu and Manohar, 2012, Parkes, 2015, Netland, 2016a, Roriz, Nunes and Sousa, 2017).

There are as many diverse perspectives to lean as there are experts in the field. Organizations adopt lean for various purposes including adding value to end-users, eliminating waste, continuous problem solving (Liker & Rother, 2010), improve quality and efficiency, reduce costs of operations, and reduction in lead time (Lodgaard et al., 2016). Other reasons for lean adoption include satisfy market needs, and gain a competitive edge (Bortolotti, Boscari and Danese, 2014). Anything that does not contribute to customer value but results in a cost to a company is called waste. Proponents of lean have identified eight wastes in Lean management including over-production, waiting, transportation, inventory, re-work movement, under-utilized talent, and defects (Ohno, 1988; Liker, 2004; Drew et al., 2014; Panwar et al., 2015).

This research sought to explore a deeper understanding of the concept of lean and its evolution, to draw on insights that will form the basis for the development of a holistic conceptual framework for lean application in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana.

Within the context of this research including the petroleum industry and geographical location, the level of awareness LM application can best be described as low or rudimentary (Ayarkwa et al., 2012, Rachman and Ratnayake, 2019). However, globally, a plethora of studies have been conducted on the history, evolution, and application of lean principles across various industries as well as challenges encountered thereof (Ohno, 1988; Womack and Jones, 2003; Liker, 2004; Todorut and Cirnu, 2011; Dekier, 2012).

Since its inception, LM has gained acceptance and popularity as one of the most innovative management practices adopted by organizations to eliminate waste and increase operational efficiency (Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2013b). With its origins emanating from the aftermath of Japan's defeat in World War II (Ohno,1988), LM was coined as the Toyota Production System (TPS). However, from its origins, LM has been applied across various industries including but not limited to Information Technology (Nashaat et al., 2019), Higher education(Balzer, Brodke and Thomas Kizhakethalackal, 2015, Cano, Moyes and Kobi, 2016) health (Zarbo, 2012) mining (Seifullina et al., 2018), aviation (Garre et al., 2017, Panagopoulos, Atkin and Sikora, 2017), textiles (Mohan Prasad et al., 2020), petroleum (Taj and Morosan, 2011a, Newman, 2012, Siakwah, 2017, Rachman and Ratnayake, 2019), and manufacturing (Sharma and Kodali, 2008, Ghosh, 2013, Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman, 2013a, Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015b) and construction (Paez et al., 2005, Ogunbiyi, 2014a, Salifu-Asubay and Mensah, 2015, Fuenzalida et al., 2016, Bajjou, Chafi and Ennadi, 2019, Meng, 2019).

Available studies support the assertion that effective application of lean principles within the upstream petroleum sector could yield desired results and address the challenges within the sector. Lean can address the challenges in the upstream in a multiplicity of ways. The next section of this study provides justifications on ways by which the application of lean can potentially address the challenges within the upstream petroleum sector.

2.4.1 Lean Definition(s)

Researchers and practitioners unanimously agree on key principles of lean such as elimination of waste, reducing operational costs, adding value, satisfying customer requirements (Ohno, 1988, Womack, Jones and Roos, 1991, Bhamu, 2013, Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015a, Netland, 2016a). Also, research findings show that countless quantitative and qualitative benefits of lean including, but not limited to: faster response time, reduction in lead time, reduced operational costs, reduced cycle time, reduced work-in-process (WIP), higher throughput, enhanced production flexibility, enhanced customer satisfaction, better customer service, enhanced communication, improved supplier relationship and enhanced problem-solving capabilities (Buus, 2011, Bhasin, 2012, Bhamu and Sangwan, 2016, Sangwa and Sangwan, 2018a). However, notwithstanding the innumerable benefits of lean, there is no universal definition of the term “lean”; instead, lean has assumed different perspectives depending on the approach and/or viewpoint of various authors and/or researchers. Bhamu and Sangwan (2014) citing Pettersen (2009) supported the assertion that there is no universal consensus on the definition of lean management. Thus, a particular definition of lean depends on the perspective of the author as illustrated in Table 2.1 below:

Table 2. 1: Researcher perspectives of Lean definitions

Authors' Name	Year of publication	Sector	Definition of Lean management
Liker	2004	Manufacturing	“Lean manufacturing is defined as a five-step process including defining customer value, defining the value stream mapping, pulling from the customer back, and striving for excellence.
Hayes and Pisano	1994	Manufacturing	Briefly, it is called lean as it uses less, or the minimum, of everything required to produce a product or perform a service
Womack and Jones	1996	Manufacturing	Lean refers to a system that utilizes significantly fewer resources(inputs) to create the same outputs comparable to a mass-production system with increased varieties for customers.
Bhasin	2012	Manufacturing	Lean is defined as a business model that delivers far superior performance for customers, employees, shareholders, and society at large.
Womack and Jones	2010	Lean Thinking	Defined lean thinking as a business approach which delivers better customer value through elimination of all non-value-adding processes”
Khaba and Bhar	2018	Lean production	“Defines lean production as a wide set of production practices for continuous improvement by eliminating waste or any other non-value-adding activities.
Mostafa, Drumrak, and Soltan	2013	Manufacturing	Lean Manufacturing is an integrated socio-technical system that comprises a package of management practices that can be applied to eliminate waste and reduce the variability of suppliers, customers, and internal resources and processes.
Pedersen and Huniche	2011	Public Sector	Lean is perceived as an improvement approach that consists in eliminating waste to improve the flow of value to customers
Ratnayake and Chaudry	2015	Oil and Gas	A ‘lean’ approach to administrative and office work offers a systematic approach enabling the entire industrial organization to focus on continuously improving quality, cost, delivery, and safety

			through eliminating waste, creating flow, and increasing the velocity of the system's ability to satisfy clients' requirements
Womack et al	1990		Lean is a dynamic process of change driven by a systematic set of principles and best practices aimed at continuous improvement. LM combines the best features of both mass and craft production.
Storch and Lim	1999	Shipbuilding	Lean production is an efficient way to satisfy customer needs while giving producers a competitive edge.
Shah and Ward	2003	Manufacturing	Lean manufacturing can be best defined as an approach to deliver the utmost value to the customer by eliminating waste through the process and human design elements. Lean manufacturing has become an integrated system composed of highly inter-related elements and a wide variety of management practices, including Just-in-Time (JIT), quality systems, work teams, cellular manufacturing, etc.”
Seth and Gupta	2005	Manufacturing	“Lean production refers to a manufacturing paradigm based on the fundamental goal of continuously minimizing waste to maximize flow
Crute et al	2003	Aerospace	Perceived as a guiding principle in the elimination of waste from the production cycle.
Shah and Ward	2007	Manufacturing	Lean is a management philosophy focused on identifying and eliminating waste throughout a product's entire value stream, extending not only within the organization but also along with its entire supply chain network.
Hallgren et al	2009	Manufacturing	Lean manufacturing is a program aimed mainly at increasing the efficiency of operations.
Taj and Morosan	2011	Manufacturing	A multi-dimensional approach that consists of production with minimum amount of waste (JIT), continuous and uninterrupted flow (Cellular Layout), well- maintained equipment (TPM), well-established quality system (TQM), and well- trained and empowered

			workforce (HRM) that has a positive impact on operations/competitive performance (quality, cost, fast response, and flexibility).
Dombrowski & Zahn	2011	Lean Design	It is an enterprise-specific compilation of rules, standards, methods, and tools as well as appropriate underlying philosophy and culture, for the comprehensive and sustainable design of the development.
Chay et al	2015	Manufacturing	Defined briefly as a people-oriented production system. Employee involvement is regarded as a critical component of the lean transformation process.
Marley and Ward	2013	Normal Accident Theory	They view lean as an approach that leads to both higher performance and continuous improvement. Alternatively, lean is perceived as the creation of a culture that encourages learning and continuous improvement.
Jones et al	1999	Lean Thinking	They define lean thinking as a body of practice with the primary aim to reduce waste and focus only on activities that add value for the customer”
Dekier	2012	Manufacturing	“Defines LM as a successor of TPS, and applies the tools, techniques in addition to the five principles including identify customer value, map the value stream, create the flow, establish the pull and seek perfection.
Panwar et al.	2015	Manufacturing	Lean eliminates unnecessary processes, increases productivity, enhances the quality and shortens lead times, and thus reduces overall operational costs.
Belekoukias et al.	2014	Manufacturing	Lean manufacturing is defined as a management approach to manufacturing to make companies more competitive by adopting a process of increasing efficiency, elimination of non-value-added processes.
Jasti and Kodali	2016	Lean Production	Defined as a way to achieve excellence in the organizational performance that starts with product development, supply chain, and manufacturing activities.

Parkes	2015	Lean Management	LM is defined as a concept of helping the organization to achieve a slim shape. Thus, a slimmed organization is without unnecessary loads.
Arlbjørn & Freytag	2013	Manufacturing	Lean focuses on waste and slimming and trimming down. Unnecessary fat must be removed in processes that are repeated within production within production and administrative processes
Holden	2010	Lean Thinking	Lean thinking is defined as “a bundle of concepts, methods, and tools derived from the Toyota Production System, the production philosophy of Toyota Corporation”
Bortolotti et al	2014	Lean Management	LM is regarded as a “powerful managerial approach widely recognized as improving the overall performance of a company”
Van Dun et al	2017	Manufacturing	Lean management is a managerial approach focused on enhancing customer value through the elimination of non-value-adding steps from work processes”
Khaba and Bhar	2018	Lean production	Defines lean production as a wide set of production practices for continuous improvement by eliminating waste or any other non-value-adding activities.
Alahyari, Gorschek, and Svensson	2019	Lean Product Development	Lean principles and practices focus on improving product development to increase speed and quality and deliver value to the customer”

The continuous evolution of lean underscores its widespread acceptance and adoption across various industries. Lean was initially developed for the automotive industry, however, over the years, there has been no consensus on lean definitions. Table 2 illustrates various perspectives of lean definitions based on industry and the researcher’s perspective. However, citing Jørgensen and Emmitt (2008), Rachman and Ratnayake (2019) outlined five common factors common in lean literature as follows:

- “emphasis on reduction and elimination of waste during the provision of goods and/or services to end customers;
- a focus on end customers and their needs as the reference to specify value and waste;
- an emphasis on the establishment of mechanisms to allow the creation of a continuous flow of products/services;
- the utilization of pull production as a means to meet customer demand and reduce inventory
- the application of a systematic approach to enable optimization of the entire system.”

2.4.2 Lean Manufacturing Evolution

The evolution of lean manufacturing predates the origins of the craft industry from the 1880s till 1915 when the production related problems became difficult to solve. Consequently, the era of mass production emerged as an antidote to crafts industry from the 1920s to around 1950s when mass production was characterised by insurmountable inefficiencies, and realisation of a new dawn was the proposition of lean management to tackle the challenges of mass production (Womack, Jones and Roos, 2007; Torodut and Cirnu,2011; Dekier, 2012).

Notwithstanding the assertion that the term “lean” was coined by John Krafcik (van Aartsengel & Kurtoglu, 2013), its origins can be traced to Toyota as the Toyota production system (TPS). Although the Lean concept continues to gain global acceptance, (Liker and Rother, 2010; Shah & Ward, 2007), research show that many organisations struggle to achieve lean success and sustainability (Bamber, Sharp and Hides, 1999; Pay, 2008; Ayarkwa et al., 2012; Lodgaard et al.,2016). It stands to reason that lean adoption from inception would have been characterised with implementation challenges due to inadequate awareness, skills and expert support during its implementation, but as concept evolves and gain acceptance, its implementation success rate

should reflect the high level of lean awareness and evolution. However, contrary studies show that the rate of lean implementation success remains relatively low across various industries. The level of scepticism of the lean concept also remains relatively high among industry practitioners (Coetzee, van Dyk and van der Merwe, 2016).

Furthermore, the evolution of lean is linked to the industrial revolution which continuous to experience improvements in processes resulting from technological advancements, enlightenment/education and changes in customer demands. This historical transformation aligns to the industrial revolution in which machines consisting of shorter through-put times substituted human activities. Continuous improvement in education, enlightenment, technology coupled with sophisticated customer requirements underpin the ever-changing competitive manufacturing and business landscape. Thus, businesses evolve to meet changing customer demands. Businesses that fail to adopt to changes become obsolete, non-competitive and phase-out of business. The fourth industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) presents a multidimensional perspective of the present as well as the future business landscape driven by technology. The next section of this research discusses Lean and Industry 4.0.

2.4.3 Lean Manufacturing Evolution and Industry 4.0

One important way manufacturing can meet the ever-changing sophisticated demands of customers is by adopting a new research in the field of Industry 4.0 (I4.0) (Saxby, Cano-Kourouklis and Viza, 2020). The overarching purpose of I4.0 is first and foremost to establish how manufacturing can conjoin digitation to produce maximum output while using minimal resources (Sony, Antony and Douglas, 2020). Also, I4.0 is based on cyber-physical systems (CPS) which organizes the value creation process by themselves. In addition, one significant feature of I4.0 is

its focus on the internet of things (IoT) which enhances a worldwide data communication in real time. Authors proffer that production paradigms, especially LM & I4.0, promise to solve future challenges in manufacturing (Mayr et al., 2018, Sony, 2018). The inception of I4.0 which focuses on the application of information technology, communication and advanced technologies, the continuous evolution of lean and machines within a highly sophisticated production environment has become even more critical. In response to the prospects of I4.0, researchers have positively responded to the challenges and are exploring ways to align the requirements of I4.0 with Quality Management (Sony, Antony and Douglas, 2020).

There has become an urgent need to explore best practices in which I4.0 and LM become the anchorage of manufacturing and production operational excellence (Hobbs, 2003; Wagner, Hermann and Thiede, 2017; Jens, 2016; Vaidya, Ambad and Bhosle, 2018). Being one of the most famous and advanced operational management practices, lean management is a blend of advanced procedures of operational management (Schonberger, 2007). Lean manufacturing sets forth the reduction of operational costs by forming a more adept business, which is flexible to customer requirements. This strategy focuses on reducing/eliminating all actions that do not enhance value in the production process, including blocking of stock, correcting defective products and unnecessary movement of individuals as well as products in the scope of the business (Voehl et al., 2013). The primary focus of Lean Manufacturing is to reduce time between customer requirements and the procedure of production through elimination of wastes (Liker, 2004; Womack, Jones and Roos, 2007; ArlbjØrn and Freytag, 2013).

One expert's view about lean is that it is a concept that helps organisations achieve a 'slim shape' (Parkes, 2015). The process of reducing unwanted or non-value added wastes results in the slimming of the organisation, thus improving operational flexibility and effectiveness (Parkes, 2015). The lean concept originated from Japan after the Second World War (Bhamu & Sangwa, 2014; Ohno, 1988). However, lean was preceded by Taylorism in the scientific management epoch. Between the early 1920s and 1945, production processes had been revolutionized (Ohno, 1988; Parkes, 2015), and with a successfully automated assembly line production scheme in place, Ford attained perfection in mass production processes (Hobbs, 2004). This resulted in waste reduction including resources, time and space in single unit production process.

Some manufacturers, who started applying Ford's ideas, rapidly concluded that rigidity of the system itself presented an issue. In the meantime, Toyota was founded at a time when American automobile companies including Ford and General Motors controlled the automobile market. Nevertheless, after the Second World War, Toyota encountered several challenges in which mass production was no longer a viable option partly due to changes in customer requirements. Undisposed inventory/stock reached its highest point in the company's history as a result of impact of the war (Ohno, 1988).

The Toyota Production System (TPS) is anchored on two main concepts namely, 'autonomation (automation with a human touch)' or Jidoka and Just-In-Time (JIT). The term autonomation means transferring human intelligence to machine (Ohno, 1988). It also refers to the process of automatically stopping a process when a defective product is detected (Perez, 2014). Stated differently, Jidoka/autonomation is akin to an error-prevention system in which an in-built

automatic quality improvement system triggers process stoppages in the event of any defective product. The lean concept is still evolving and its applicability is all encompassing (Sajan et al., 2016).

The application of LM in the extractive industry and by extension the upstream petroleum industry is of utmost importance. However, extreme precautionary measures need to be adopted due to the nature of the industry. The application of lean principles improves production processes and enhances efficiency (Dombrowski and Zahn, 2011b, Lodgaard, Ingvaldsen, Aschehoug, et al., 2016, Almanei, Salonitis and Xu, 2017a). However, lean application should not be oversimplified and reduced to the application of lean tools, techniques and practices because the introduction of lean culture and philosophy into an organisation is a complex task (Almanei, Salonitis and Xu, 2017a).

Extant literature posit that managers sometimes apply lean principles within their organisations based on assumptions of the lead manager without proper structure and standards to ensure success and sustainability (Lodgaard, Ingvaldsen, Aschehoug, et al., 2016). The overarching need for standardisation in LM application has been expressed by many researchers who unanimously propose the development of industry-specific frameworks based on cultural and philosophical variations between organisations (Kazmi, 2008a, van Dun, Hicks and Wilderom, 2017a).

Also, proponents of LM implementation hold the view that a critical aspect of successful LM implementation depends not only on the right lean tools, techniques and principles, but the culture of the organisation, and the extent to which it adapts to the lean culture and permeate organisational

structures, systems and operations (Bhasin, 2012, Niemi, 2018). Stated differently, lean implementation without cultural transformation remains a mirage (Pay, 2008).

The fundamental pillar of lean is to eliminate waste and add value to the customer (Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015b). The types of wastes include overproduction, inventory, waiting, motion, transportation, over processing, defects and under-utilised talent (Ohno, 1988, Sajan et al.,2016, Womack and Jones, 2003). However, notwithstanding the benefits of Lean espoused by practitioners and stakeholders, a conjoined LM and I4.0 will catapult manufacturing excellence beyond expectation and consequently lead to customer satisfaction.

Extant research buttress a Lean – I4.0 integration and further outlined critical factors that will enhance a smooth and effective integration of Lean and I4.0 including: continual improvement, engaging with Supply Chain, Pull Systems and having a Customer Focus(Saxby, Cano-Kourouklis and Viza, 2020).

The inception of I4.0 has triggered scholars to explore the idea of Lean 4.0 in order to propel manufacturing organisations adopt appropriate technological measures to meet customer requirements. The integration of LM and technology 4.0 offers greater prospects for manufacturing output. Consequently, LM tools which integrated with technology 4.0 also offer improved contribution to productivity. Some of the LM tools include; JIT 4.0, Kaizen 4.0, Kanban 4.0, Poke-Yoke 4.0, VSM 4.0, and TPM 4.0(Valamede and Akkari, 2020). Similarly, researchers have explored integration of Lean Six Sigma tools and I4.0 technologies in order to establish opportunities enhance manufacturing capabilities and optimize operational efficiency (Chiarini and Kumar, 2020). The application of Lean 4.0 and its tools in the upstream petroleum operations

especially within developing economies is critical to achieve overall operational efficiency in the sector.

2.4.4 Benefits of Lean Manufacturing

Notwithstanding its implementation challenges as evidently outlined by authors (Pay, 2008, Chong et al., 2012, Balzer, Brodke and Thomas Kizhakethalackal, 2015, Almani, Salonitis and Xu, 2017b, Effah-Kesse, 2017), available evidence suggest that benefits of lean manufacturing implementation continuous to motivate and challenge businesses across various economic sectors to adopt lean manufacturing. Organisations across various sectors report improvements including but not limited to: *improved quality, reduced cycle time, reduction in work in progress (WIP), improvement in on-time deliveries, improved net income, reduced operational cost, improved utilization of labour, improved employee satisfaction, reduced incident rate, inventory reduction, increased productivity, enhanced flexibility, reduced machine downtime and improved skills* (Pavnaskar, Gershenson and Jambekar, 2003, Achanga et al., 2006a, Buus, 2011, Logistics and Effah-kesse, 2017, Almani, Salonitis and Tsinopoulos, 2018, Yadav et al., 2020). More specifically, Pavnaskar et al.,(2003), citing CITEC 2000; Connstep, 2000; & Zimmer, 2000) presented a detailed outline of 14 measurable lean benefits attributed to lean implementation tools and practices including: [1] *“Defects reduced by 20% per year, with zero defects performance possible [2] Delivery lead times reduced by more than 75% [3] On time delivery improved to more than 99% [4] Productivity (sales per employee) increases of 15–35% per year [5] Inventory reductions of more than 75% [6] Return on assets improvement of more than 100% [7] Improvements of 10% or more on direct labour utilization [8]Improvements of up to 50% in indirect labour utilization [9] 50% or greater increases in capacity in current facilities [10] 80% reduction in floor space [11] 50% improvement in quality [12] 95% machine availability [13] 80–*

90% reduction in changeovers and [14] 60% reduction in cycle times” (Pavnaskar et al.,(2003 p.3076).

However, notwithstanding the numerous benefits of lean reported across various sectors, some practitioners and managers still express reservations and/or scepticism with regards to lean adoption (de Souza and Pidd, 2011, Pedersen and Huniche, 2011, Lodgaard, Ingvaldsen, Gamme, et al., 2016). To buttress this assertion, sceptical perspectives in extant literature indicate that lean is perceived as “an instrument of managerialism” though lean is potentially capable of solving problems created by managerialists actions/inactions by offering novel ways of working leading to cost reduction, improvement in operational efficiency(Cano, Murray and Kourouklis, 2020).

According to Belhadi et al., (2016), “this philosophy of production combines distinctive tools, practices and strategies that can be applied to identify immensely efficient and effective production system using fewer resources to create higher quality and generate more profits (Pettersen, 2009). In fact, many companies, mostly large ones, have widely strived for lean transformation in order to keep their competitiveness in global markets (Anand & Kodali, 2008). As a matter of fact, various authors have highlighted the enormous benefits of lean such as reduction in costs, times, defects and wastes along with improvement in quality, flexibility and overall equipment effectiveness” (Bhamu & Sangwan, 2014; Dennis, 2007). While the debate about the benefits of lean implementation continuous, it is important to emphasize that lean continuous to gain widespread acceptance and awareness and hence its survival amidst scepticisms from critics of lean strategy. Furthermore, though some authors argue that Lean manufacturing is not about a set of tools and techniques. However, as part of a systemic approach to lean implementation, the

identification and implementation of the most appropriate tools and techniques inevitably play pivotal roles in the implementation process (Russell and Taylor 1999).

2.4.5 The Role of LM in addressing Challenges facing Upstream Petroleum Operations

Globally, Lean implementation initiatives have recorded significant successes across various economic sectors, industries and geographical locations (Pay, 2009, Powell et al., 2013, Douglas, Antony and Douglas, 2015, Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015b, Garre et al., 2017, Solheim and Tveterås, 2017, Alleyne and Alexander, 2018, Sangwa and Sangwan, 2018a, Rachman and Ratnayake, 2019). Some of the key success indicators include but not limited to improvement in operational efficiency, improved quality, and reduction in operational costs (Ohno, 1988, Resta et al., 2015, Verrier, Rose and Caillaud, 2016).

Lean is a ubiquitous philosophy (Shah and Ward, 2003), and applicable to all sectors including the upstream petroleum industry (Tsigas, Emes and Smith, 2017a). This research explores challenges affecting the successful implementation of lean initiatives (Almanei, Salonitis, and Xu, 2017), and programs across various economic sectors, and adopts a practitioner-focused, novel and pragmatic framework to guide lean implementation within the upstream petroleum industry.

According to Rachman and Ratnayake (2019), the application of Lean within the upstream petroleum industry is still at an infant stage. Thus, the findings of Rachman and Ratnayake opens up a knowledge gap for further research on lean implementation within the petroleum industry, most especially the upstream petroleum sector within sub-Saharan Africa where lean awareness and adoption is appreciably low (Ayarkwa, Joshua, Agyekum, Kofi, Adinyira, Emmanuel, Osei-Asibey, 2012).

Fundamentally, Lean implementation success depends on the ability of the researcher to explore and/or identify the main linking rods, a suitable constellation of success and failure factors as well as appropriate implementation guidelines, systematically outlined in the simplest form to enhance practitioner comprehension and application. To this end, Nordin et al (2012 p.309) state that “*lean manufacturing should be implemented comprehensively and holistically in terms of scope and content*”. Many researchers argue “that the transition from a traditional to a lean environment is more of a cultural change within the organization, rather than a manufacturing or technical issue (Balle, 2005; Sawhney and Chason, 2005; Losonci et al., 2011)”.

2.4.6 Shortcomings of Lean Manufacturing

The concept of Lean Manufacturing has been widely accepted across various industries (Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2013c), and despite proven records of measured lean success checked across industries, several factors still inhibit successful lean implementation process (Scherrer-Rathje, Boyle and Deflorin, 2009, Noori, 2015, Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015a, Cano, Moyes and Kobi, 2016, Secchi and Camuffo, 2019). Scherrer-Rathje et al., opine that “being lean is not easy”. Thus, the lean implementation process should neither be taken for granted nor be over-simplified. This is because, despite its innumerable benefits to industry, sceptics shy away from adopting lean. In view of this, researchers, consultants, and industry practitioners outline key challenges affecting smooth lean implementation including but not limited to: uncertainties in demand, bottom-up approach to project implementation and lack of top management support (Scherrer-Rathje, Boyle and Deflorin, 2009, Chong et al., 2012, Noori, 2015).

Though several obstacles affect lean adoption, extant literature suggests the overarching determinants of lean implementation success are leadership, lack of expert unsupervised

implementation, and lack of clarity on the rationale for lean implementation (Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2013c, Balzer, Brodke and Thomas Kizhakethalackal, 2015). Notwithstanding the challenges affecting lean implementation success, the global acceptance of and adoption of lean initiatives are indicative of the fact that the challenges of lean implementation are not insurmountable. This research will among others advance justifiable reasons for the adoption of lean within the upstream petroleum sector especially within emerging economies like Ghana.

2.5 Rationale for Adopting Lean Manufacturing

The aforementioned shortcomings may seem to portray lean manufacturing as an inept management strategy not capable of delivering desired results as promised. However, this understanding of lean manufacturing is ill-informed because many researchers, industry practitioners, and consultants have chronicled series of successful lean implementation projects which have resulted in the transformation of several organizations across varied industries. Studies show the benefits that organizations derive from implementing lean

The rationale for lean adoption varies across companies but the underlying benefits of lean remain the same. The following is a summarised catalogue of justifiable reasons for the adoption of lean principles or lean strategy within the upstream petroleum sector:

2.5.1 Operational Efficiency and Cost of Production

One of the core benefits of lean is to enhance operational efficiency within the organization through waste elimination, reduction in turnaround time, and improved employee satisfaction. The attestation that manufacturing organizations are climbing the lean bandwagon in droves (Pay, 2008), cannot be overemphasized. The bedrock of every business venture is its ability to achieve world-class operational excellence and enhanced efficiency (Gao and Low, 2014, Davies and Van

Der Merwe, 2015, Garza-Reyes et al., 2018). The upstream petroleum sector is a specialized field of endeavour which requires the achievement of optimal efficiency to deliver a return on investment (ROI) to stakeholders. This is because it is a capital intensive industry and hence investor confidence is largely linked to production efficiency. This is a compelling reason why the upstream sector which regardless of geographical context should seek to, or implement lean management strategies in its operations.

Akin to the unpredictable nature of petroleum production (Gulas et al., 2017, Fitz et al, 2018b) (Chandler, 2017; Chari, 2018), Achanga et al. (2006) present a precarious situation of continuous decline in manufacturing companies in the United Kingdom as a result of high production costs which compelled many manufacturing companies to relocate to the Far East and elsewhere in pursuit of lower operational costs. The situation is further compounded with the involvement of State institutions (especially in developing world like Ghana) whose decisions have the potential to cause operational inefficiencies as evidenced in the Norwegian Continental Shelf (Kashani, 2005). Thus, the significance of innovative management and operational strategies in manufacturing and production operations cannot be overemphasized

2.5.2 Customer/Employee Satisfaction

Research suggests that organizations achieve superior performance and profitability based on employee satisfaction and performance (Bortolotti, Boscari, and Danese, 2015, Alefari, Salonitis, and Xu, 2017). Lean implementation is viewed as an interaction between soft and hard practices. Soft lean practices refer to people, culture and change management dimensions of lean, whereas the hard practices deal mainly with the technical, tools and techniques, equipment/machinery

dimensions of lean (Shah and Ward, 2007, Ahmad, 2013, Van der Merwe, Pieterse and Lourens, 2014, Bortolotti, Boscari and Danese, 2015a).

Extant research further demonstrates that soft lean practices are critical for achieving superior performance, and since the overarching aim of lean implementation is to achieve customer satisfaction, the adoption of lean will result in an enabling work environment in which employees are well trained, properly motivated, engaged and valued resulting in enhanced employee and organizational performance (Ahmad, 2013, Bortolotti, Boscari and Danese, 2015a).

2.5.3 Sustainable Operations

Sustainable operations have become a mantra for organizations determined to achieve world-class status, satisfy customer requirements, adhere to environmental regulations, and remain in perpetual operations. Sustainability has become the main driving force of twenty-first-century manufacturing, and its requirements are said to be ubiquitous. In response to calls for organizations to ensure environmentally friendly operations, many organizations jointly adopt lean and green production systems (Mostafa, Dumrak, and Soltan, 2013a, Reis et al., 2018, Franciosi et al., 2020, Reinhardt et al., 2020). To further buttress the need for sustainable operations in all sectors including the upstream petroleum sector, researchers propose the integration strategies such LM, Six Sigma and Sustainability, which will improve sustainable operations, improve productivity and preserve the environment (Cherrafi et al., 2016). Although oil production is an essential component to support human life through industrialization, it is worthy of note, that man's operations is potentially destructive to the ecosystem through human-induced environmental activities (Sachs and Warner, 1995, Hsu et al., 2013). The world has come to acknowledge the overarching impact of sustainable operations, and as a result, environmental protection

campaigners, activists, and key stakeholder groups continue to exert enormous pressures on manufacturing, production, and extractive organizations to adopt lean and green production systems.

Furthermore, researchers posit that cognisant of the impact of the resource curse syndrome (Panford, 2017), economies endowed with crude oil that has been properly extracted and effectively managed are among the most developed countries in the world (Jafarinejad, 2017). However, effective petroleum management is an uphill task resulting from uncertainties in the global economic outlook, unpredictable price fluctuations within the oil and gas industry (Mohaddes and Pesaran, 2017, Yu et al., 2018). This exerts enormous pressure on petroleum producing companies not only to establish production flexibility systems (Okhovat, Ahmadpour, et al., 2012, Dombrowski, Ebentreich and Krenkel, 2016) but also to ensure sustainability, increase efficiency, enhance quality, optimize production (Dombrowski and Zahn, 2011b). Furthermore, studies show that *“the petroleum industry was not sufficiently sustainable from its inception especially from waste elimination”* (Ratnayake and Chaudry, 2015). Hence, the rationale for lean adoption in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana is in line with operational and stakeholder requirements to adhere to environmental regulations.

2.5.4 Standardization

Contextually, Ghana has suffered many setbacks specifically regarding meeting international standards (Maxwell, 2014, Annor, Mensah-Bonsu and Jatoe, 2016). The global business landscape is highly competitive but highly sophisticated, hence, exerts enormous pressures on organizations to adhere to the highest international standards possible. More so, the upstream petroleum sector, which qualifies as the bedrock of the petroleum industry, is a highly specialized sector which requires operators to adhere to the highest industry standards. Operations within the sector demand

the highest skill-set and expertise because minor operational lapses could result in potentially catastrophic consequences to the environment in particular and life in general.

Research posit that though Ghana's upstream sector is still at its infant stage, coupled with the Country's record on meeting standards, a lot must be done to adhere to international standards within the upstream sector. Akin to challenges encountered by the upstream petroleum sector in Nigeria, spillages and other environmental disasters including pollution have already claimed precious aqua-culture within the catchment area (Anifowose et al., 2012, Panford, 2015, Baker and Glover, 2017). There is no gainsaying that the adoption of lean strategies will significantly enhance standardization within the sector and bolster stakeholder confidence and industry performance.

2.6 Lean Manufacturing Tools, Techniques and Practices (TTPs)

One of the first steps in the Lean manufacturing implementation process is the identification and mapping of waste within the organisation. Lean tools and techniques are designed to solve specific waste related problems. The extent to which managers, practitioners and/or consultants identify and use the most appropriate tools and techniques for particular waste issues, will determine the benefits that will accrue as a result.

It is worth a note, that because lean implementation is a systemic approach, proper classification of tools and techniques would therefore enhance lean implementation success. Effective implementation of tools and metrics may be affected due to the lack of a systematic classification of lean tools and techniques.

Misapplications of lean manufacturing tools and techniques have been reported by companies in their pursuit to become lean. These misapplications are of three type namely *“use of the wrong tools to solve a problem, use of a single tool to solve all of the problems and use of all tools (same set of tools) on each problem. The misapplication of a lean manufacturing tool may result in the additional wastage of resources such as time and money. It may also result in reduced employee confidence in the lean philosophy”* (Pavnaskar et al., 2003 p.3077). An example is cited of a case study where misapplication of LM tools has deprived the company of the benefits of lean. Thus, ... *“a small manufacturer struggling with on-time deliveries due to a bottleneck in a manual operation. It implemented 5S, a tool it had been implementing all over the plant, thinking this would help solve their problems. They focused on taping, labelling, signs and other visual controls. Instead of gaining improvements, the cells became even more erratic in their cycle times, resulting in scepticism about lean in the company (. The lean manufacturing classification scheme proposed in this research is intended to minimize the misapplication of tools and metrics”* (Pavnaskar et al., 2003 p.3077).

To enhance lean implementation success among organisations, it is helpful to outline broad framework of the process and the fundamental building blocks which underpin a smooth conceptualisation, planning, adoption and implementation of lean programmes. According to Bicheno and Holweg (2016), lean tools present an opportunity for implementing organisations to chip away everything/process that does not add value to the consumer. Thus, as a precursor to lean implementation, best practice requires that organisational strategy is in sync with lean methodology. Also, variations in organisational requirements fundamentally anchor the planning process before lean implementation. Inherent in the planning process of a lean implementation

process is an organisation's ability to map lean tools, techniques and practices (TTPs) suitable for the peculiar needs of the implementing organisation.

Though researchers, practitioners and consultants proffer the ubiquitous characteristics of TTPs, others opine that it is nonetheless critical to evaluate organisational requirements and objectives for lean adoption, and align appropriate TTPs to enhance lean implementation success and achieve desired results (Anand and Kodali, 2009b, Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman, 2013b, Bhamu and Sangwan, 2016, Lodgaard, Ingvaldsen, Gamme, et al., 2016, Lermen et al., 2018).

Though originally intended for the auto industry, the lean concept has gained widespread acceptance and has been applied across all economic sectors. Consequently, the wide acceptance of lean has resulted in divergent views, perspectives, scope and definitions of lean among scholars, practitioners and consultants. Some scholars have categorised lean into three levels notably the philosophy, principles and tools, and techniques as presented in Figure 2.10. Similarly, lean can be viewed from operational, tactical and strategic levels (Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015a).

The strategic level focuses on the philosophy of lean with the core objective of waste elimination, enhancing customer value and creating a continuous improvement culture. The tactical level focuses on the principles that underpin lean implementation whereas the operational level deals with the set of tools, techniques and practices. One main reason for lean implementation failures is when organisations fail to align lean initiatives to corporate strategic objectives. Therefore, the adoption of a lean initiative becomes something "nice to have" and/or treated as a "hobby" and not the execution of a task aligned to an organisation's strategic objectives.

Though it is undeniable to assert that the most suitable approach to lean implementation is top-down, employee involvement and buy-in constitute a significant step to lean success (Höök and Stehn, 2008, Sharma and Kodali, 2008, Services et al., 2010, Jagoda, Lonseth and Lonseth, 2013, Chay et al., 2015). However, other researchers identified the emergence of both bottom-up and top-down approaches and highlighted pros and cons of each of the methods (Cano, Moyes and Kobi, 2016). The application of the philosophy at the strategic level, the adoption of the underlining principles at the tactical/managerial level and the application of appropriate tools, techniques and practices at the operational level are fundamental for lean implementation success.

Figure 2. 10: Three levels of Lean

Source: Liker (2004)

From a different perspective, Liker (2004) emphasizes the adoption of the 4Ps approach to solve root cause problems and enhance organisational learning. The 4Ps include problem-solving, people, process and philosophy. Though the perspectives are different, themes and/or terminologies referenced in the 4Ps are similar to approaches adopted by other authors (Sharma and Kodali, 2008, Taj and Morosan, 2011b). An illustration of the 4Ps is captured in Figure 2.11. Detailed analysis of the breakdown of the 4Ps gives a comprehensive perspective of the philosophy, the processes, the techniques, tools and practices required to add value to the operations of an organisation.

Figure 2. 11: The 4Ps

Source: Liker (2004)

Though the 4Ps proposed by Liker, many researchers approach lean implementation by identifying and recommending appropriate lean tools, techniques and practices for adoption during lean implementation initiatives. However, since specific lean tools are considered based on the extent to which individual tools are relevant to the implementing organisation, the main purpose for adopting lean ought to be the guiding principle for selection of tools and techniques. Table 3 outlines some lean tools and the reason(s) for their application (Ohno,1988:Sakhardande, 2011; Agustiady & Cudney, 2018).

Table 2. 2: Lean Tools and Reasons for Application

Lean practice	Rationale for application
Kanban	Used for effective inventory control
5S	For proper housekeeping
Poke –Yoke (Mistake proofing)	To prevent procedural error
Total Productive Maintenance(TPM)	To reduce variance resulting from machine breakdowns
Kaizen/Continuous Improvement	To discover, prescribe and permanently implement lasting solutions
Cellular Manufacturing	To enhance material flow from one work station to another.
Single Minute Exchange of Die(SMED)	Essentially used to reduce set-up times.
Value Stream Mapping(VSM)	To identify, map out and eliminate waste from the operational process to enhance efficiency.

Levelled Production	Also known as Heijunka, production levelling is a Just-In-Time technique used to level/smoothing either variety/volume of production over a fixed time, with the ultimate goal of maintaining low inventories.
Standard Work	This method is used for performing repetitive actions by employing the same procedures each time.
Jidoka/Automation	Jidoka is also described as a set of tools that notify and prevent machine failure.

Source: Author's Construct (2020).

The lean practices outlined in Table 2.2 is not exhaustive. Researchers continuously explore lean practices and their applications based on specific organisational requirements and motivation for the adoption lean initiatives. This means the lists of lean practices or elements maybe inexhaustible. Buus (2011), assert that lean is complex system with many elements extensively explored by researchers who attempt to construct a comprehensive list of the most suitable set of elements. However, though many common elements exist, the lists appear inexhaustible from one researcher to another. Liker (2004), proposed the “TPS House of Lean” in which he constructed a list of lean elements required to ensure successful lean implementation, as presented in Figure 2.12. Although, the proposed lean elements do not appear exhaustive, it nonetheless, provides the basis for further research. Thus, a host of researchers including but not limited to (Anand and Kodali, 2009a, 2010, Buus, 2011, Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015b, Jasti and Kodali, 2016, 2019), have used Liker's TPS House of Lean and the proposed elements as basis for further research.

Figure 2. 12: The House of Lean

Source: Liker (2004)

Based on synthesis of available literature on lean application across different industries, it has been observed that certain elements appear common. An overview of these common elements include: Continuous Improvement/Kaizen (CI), Leadership, Standardisation, Safety, respect for people, Total Productive Maintenance (TPM), Waste Elimination (WE), and Just-In-Time (JIT).

2.7 Overview of Lean Wastes

The whole idea of lean is the elimination of waste and inefficiency. Thus, anything that does not contribute to customer value but results in costs to a company is regarded as waste. Proponents of lean have identified eight wastes associated with LM. Proponents of LM originally identified seven types of wastes including over-production, waiting, transportation, inventory, re-work, movement, and inappropriate processing (Ohno, 1988). These seven original wastes were later increased to eight with the addition of “underutilised people”. Thus the full list of all eight wastes

are identified in Figure 2.13 below (Ohno, 1988; Liker, 2004; Drew et al., 2014; Douglas et al, 2015; Cano et al., 2016; Jasti and Kodali, 2019).

Figure 2. 13: 8 Wastes

Source: Drew et al., (2014); Douglas et al., (2015)

An effective lean initiative does not only align with corporate strategic objectives, but is systemic and utilizes appropriate lean tools, techniques and practices to eliminate waste and inefficiency from organisation's operations. Although wasteful processes, activities, resources and other operational procedures may vary from one organization to another, a good deal of commonalities exist across different organisations. In view of this, an important requirement of translating lean waste to reflect the operations of the specific organization or industry plays a pivotal role in any successful lean implementation process. Extensive research into lean application in various sectors have been carried out by researchers. However, an identified gap in some of these studies show that researchers either do not specifically map out the lean waste within the industry/organization,

but rather provides generalized viewpoint of waste and how lean can be implemented. On the contrary, this research has identified the waste within the upstream petroleum industry and proposed how suitable lean can be implemented in the sector. The next section of this literature translates lean waste in line with the operations of the upstream petroleum sector.

2.7.1 Identification of Lean Waste in the Upstream Petroleum sector

The core activities of the upstream petroleum sector such as exploration, well drilling and completion, well stimulation, production and storage involve several processes with opportunities to identify and eliminate non-value adding processes. Lean wastes affects all aspects of the production process. However, for the purpose of this research, the scope of translating lean wastes for the sector will be limited to the production subsector of the upstream petroleum operations.

Many studies have attempted to translate the eight wastes for specific industrial sectors. Radnor et al (2006), translated lean wastes for Scottish Public Sector, whilst Kollberg et al (2007) also identified wastes for the healthcare sector. Furthermore, McCue (2012) translated wastes in public procurement. These notwithstanding, Sakar (2008) holds the view that lean waste can be universally applied across all industrial sectors. Adapting the approach by Douglas et al (2014), this section of the study seeks to identify lean waste associated with the upstream petroleum production sector.

The process to identify and map out waste within the activities of the upstream petroleum producing organisations, a first critical step is an unambiguous definition of what constitute value (Ohno, 1988; Womack and Jones, 2003; Liker, 2004). According to Melton (2005), *“an evaluation of most production operations suggests that only 5% of production activities add value whilst 35% of production activities are considered necessary non-value added activities. The rest of the 60%*

of production activities are non-value adding”. Thus, identifying value is at the heart of the lean thinking process. Lean practitioners and researchers agree that value is anything a customer is able and willing to pay for, and most importantly value represents the voice of the customer (Womack and Jones, 2003). Thus, any activity/process which does not add value to the product qualifies as waste for which a customer is unwilling to pay for. Extant literature on LM show that several studies have been carried out on lean implementation process. Whereas some researchers hold the view that lean waste are ubiquitous and hence are universally applicable (Sarkar, 2008), others hold contrary views. In light of this, Melton (2005) presents an analysis of lean waste associated with process industries whilst Douglas et al. (2014) identified lean waste associated with higher education institutions. There is however no known study which has mapped out lean waste associated with the upstream petroleum operations. To close this gap and to contribute to knowledge, this research outlined lean waste associated with the upstream petroleum operations. In Table 2.3 below, the conventional eight lean wastes (Duffy and Wong, 2013; Douglas et al., 2015), are translated to suit requirements of the upstream petroleum sector.

Table 2. 3: Identification of waste associated with the upstream petroleum sector

Lean waste	Description	Waste associated with Upstream petroleum operations
Underutilised talent	Not making full use of the skills, abilities and/or human capital available in the organisation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employees’ skills not fully utilized • Lack of motivation/commensurate remuneration for work allocated • Insufficient capacity building/training opportunities for employees • Inadequate employee recognition schemes/promotion to enhance employee retention • Petroleum price volatilities and employee job security • Lack of requisite skillset to execute projects.
Over processing	Activities/operations which add no value to the customer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extreme caution/precautionary measures in the production process due to the high-risk nature of offshore operations • Over-engineering a JHA or HAZOP • Adjusting a component after installation

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Running more well testing analyses than required • Double entry of PPEs and personnel at work stations or on-board FPSO
Overproduction	Associated with producing ahead of demand, or producing with no specific customer ready to purchase.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Either underproduction as measure to curb decline in international price or production glut regardless of demand • Producing excessively more bpls of oil as estimated by the Reservoir Engineer • Exceeding the life-time productivity of a reservoir • Providing more cash in excess of operating expenditure for well development
Waiting	Idle time or period of relatively no activity adds no value to the customer/end-product. Waiting/idle time by machinery or people leads to the same result.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contract negotiations and major service agreements involving major equipment usage. • Analysis and selection of drill ships and FPSOs • Project delays • Planning and forecasting
Inventory	Storage of all raw materials, resources and unused products resulting in accumulation of working capital which could otherwise be put to productive use.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procurement of large batches of raw materials for production stored in warehouse for long without being used. • The application of Just-In-Time approach in the upstream operations suitable?
Transportation	The movement of products from one place to another. The idle period in which the product is being moved maybe necessary, but adds no value to the product.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transporting crude oil from FPSOs to the refineries. • Excessive movement of equipment and stationery machinery during production • Movement of an increasing of crew more than specified in the JHA • Doubling and handling of explosives and chemicals through unnecessary movement at the working area on the FPSO
Defects	Errors that occur from operational processes and requires re-work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased operating costs • Increased overheads/overtime costs • Missed project timelines • Time and cost spent for accident investigations and corrective actions implementation
Motion	Unnecessary and excessive movement of machine operators on the shop floor as well as materials results in waste and/or unproductive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data capture in MRP • Movement of people from one place to another • Excessive operator movement

Source: Author's Construct (2020)

2.8 Lean Enterprise and LM principles

Lean is essentially a mind-set and a way of thinking, with a commitment to achieve a waste-free process that aim at creating the best customer value (Hogg, 2008). Lean enterprise is the practice that is focussed at value creation for the end user with minimum wastage in a number of processes. The processes include lean awareness, adopting and implementing various tools and techniques to attain the incremental improvement of the organisation. It is imperative to know that lean thinking is not just about the processes and the techniques. It involves all the employees of the organisation and includes a major change in their way of thinking and embedded attitudes that make the organisation (Joydeep, 2018). The thinking process that is applied to lean allows companies to set out value, group value forming actions in the appropriate sequence, perform tasks without interruption whenever needed, and carry them out adequately. These accomplishments are achievable with the help of six identified Lean Thinking principles including; value stream, value, flow, perfection, pull and respect for individuals (Womack and Jones, 1996, Shah and Ward, 2007, Oppenheim, Murman and Secor, 2011). However, there is still some level of vagueness about what constitutes lean and how it differs from conventional management philosophy.

Achieving the highest degree of customer value is the basis of identified Lean Principles. By so doing, the rationale is to attain zero defects, waste elimination, and generating only what is required at a particular moment. All of these goals must be achieved by focusing on continuous improvement and just-in-time. To optimize results, it is important to continuously interact with customers and personnel at all levels (Ishikawa, 1985, Imai, 1986, Bashin and Burcher, 2004, Sayer and Williams, 2012). On the whole, the lean approach can be categorised into five principles (Womack and Jones, 1996, Shah and Ward, 2007, Oppenheim, Murman and Secor, 2011). These principles constitute the foundation of any lean implementation process and these include: value

identification, mapping the value stream, create flow, establish the pull and seek perfection as captured in figure 2.14 below.

Figure 2. 14: Lean Principles

Source: Womack and Jones (1996)

Principle 1: Identify Value: Lean manufacturing starts by identifying value from customer's perspective and the customer's willingness to pay for a product or service (Abdi, Shavarini and Hoseini, 2006). Seddon (2005) observe that evaluating customer requirement is the significant starting point in the process of lean thinking. Organizations face a threat of optimizing processes and products that ignores the customers' perspective (customer voice) in the absence of a comprehensive definition of value. Thus, to infer that customer requirements or the voice of the customer should underpin any lean thinking initiative cannot be overemphasized.

Principle 2: Map the Value Stream: “The second lean principle describes the value stream, maps all the pertinent activities needed to deliver a product/service and identifies areas where waste (muda) can be eliminated (Womack and Jones, 1996). The concept of waste, called muda in Japanese, is considered to be any activity that does not contribute to the product’s value from the customer’s perspective (Ohno, 1988). In this regard, the customer’s perception is of great significance (Abdi, Shavarini and Hoseini, 2006). In the evaluation of value streams, activities are categorized in three as outlined below (Womack and Jones, 1996):

- **Value-Adding:** These activities add value and are necessary changes to the specific product/service. Therefore, these activities should be enhanced.
- **Value-enabling:** This is description of activities which are not value adding but are necessary and cannot be avoided. These are unavoidable administrative transactions that enable the process without adding value to the product or service.
- **Non-Value-Adding:** Activities that can generally be eliminated as waste.

Principle 3: Create Flow: The lean process eliminates all forms of waste and creates a continuous flow of work through planned and stream-lined value-adding steps or processes, by eliminating waiting, downtime or scrap time between steps. Flow is the systemic and uninterrupted movement of products or services from the input through to the customer or consumer. Based on customer requirements, value-adding activities flow to the customer. Hines (2009) acknowledges work in queue, batch processing and transportation as the primary blocks in creating a flow.”

Principle 4: Establish Pull: A pull system is established through the manufacturing process to provide solutions to the demands of customers. Before a customer request is made, Lean reduces

delivering value and strives to not produce more than required. Customer Pull involves delivering a product or service based on customer demand (Bicheno, 2008, Hines, 2009). It calls for the organization's understanding of the customer's demand. A pull system eliminates building of inventory and locking up working capital. A pull system also enforces just-in-time production.

Principle 5: Strive for Perfection: Lean advocates perfection through continuous improvement (Liker and Morgan, 2006). According to Womack and Jones (1996), perfection is the total removal of wastes (Muda), paving way for every activity that enhances value stream to add value. Naturally, striving for perfection is an ongoing process, since the value of every activity can be regularly evaluated, and enhanced (Abdi, Shavarini and Hoseini, 2006). This attempt is repetitive and ongoing, striving to eliminate non-value adding activities, enhance flow and comply with the customer needs (Womack and Jones, 2003). The process of waste reduction and continuous improvement is cyclical in nature. For instance, we can consider buffer space, lead time, mistakes, costs etc. Several layers of waste turn out visible as process improvement starts up and the process progresses towards the theoretical level of perfection.

Davies and Merwe (2015), further clarified, identified and expounded on the 5 lean principles with a detailed outline of the lean tools and techniques applicable under each of the 5 principles. Figure 2.15 is adopted from Davies and Merwe (2015) and illustrates the classification of lean tools and techniques under the 5 principles.

Figure 2. 15: Classification of lean tools and techniques under the 5 Lean Principles

Source: Adopted from Davies and Merwe (2015)

Extant literature shows the significance of the 5 lean principles. Lean practitioners and researchers have extensively applied these principles across various lean implementation processes as well as studies in different sectors (Bechino, 2008; Bechino and Howleg, 2016; Ohno, 1988; Liker, 2004; Anand and Kodali, 2009, 2010, 2016; Jasti and Kodali, 2019). These notwithstanding, the approach adopted by Davies and Merwe (2015), provides further insight on the application of the 5 lean principles in the lean implementation process. Suffice, therefore, to reiterate what scholars proffer that lean adoption, and/or development of a lean implementation model, guide, roadmap or framework is incomplete without the 5 principles.

2.9. Critical Success Factors of LM

Critical success factors constitute an integral part, and fundamentally underpin any lean implementation initiative. Success factors do not only anchor lean implementation process, but serve as a focal point of the specific requirements which will enhance lean success.

Extant literature posits, that though several definitions of the term “lean” exists, there is no consensus among experts on a generic definition of the term. Similarly, there is no agreed definition of the term ‘success’ as applicable in the context of the petroleum industry, nor is there any agreed set of factors upon which lean implementation success is guaranteed. This notwithstanding, various scholars have identified generic factors that can lead to lean implementation success.

A project is successful when its key stakeholders are satisfied with the project outcomes and when the project’s initial targets are achieved. Traditionally, business leaders measure project success based on time, cost and quality objectives. Various recent studies recommend that a new set of measures are required to measure project success (Wateridge, 1998, Atkinson, 1999). According to Müller and Jugdev (2012), effective criteria for measuring project success is both industry and project-specific because each project will differ in size, complexity and uniqueness. Therefore, it is difficult to identify the unique set of measures of success for all industries (Westerveld, 2003). Antony and Gupta (2019) conducted a study of Lean Six Sigma and proffer that, the success of a project(s) is dependent on stakeholders. Therefore, project success is thwarted by lack of effective communication. If there is no continuous dialogue among all key stakeholders, then successful implementation of a project is compromised. Moreover, when a project does not succeed, the

planned strategic aim of the organization will not be met; resources will be wasted, expectations of clients will not be fulfilled and, most importantly, organizational performance will be negatively affected (Bourne, 2005). To enhance project outcomes therefore, the identification of Critical Success Factors (CSFs), taking cognizance of their implications, is crucial. This process enhances the planning process, reduces time and ensures judicious resource utilization.

Cognisant of the fact that varied viewpoints exists in relation to how CSFs are defined; this research defines CSFs as the essential requirements that contribute to the attainment of desirable project outcomes. Some researchers perceive CSFs as “those key areas of activity in which favourable results are absolutely necessary for a manager to reach his/her goals”, or “those factors in a project that can lead to positive outcomes of all project stakeholder expectations and requirements”.(Rockart, 1982, Futerer, 2004). Similarly, CSFs are perceived as “those few things that must go well to ensure success for a manager or an organization, and, therefore, they represent those areas/aspects that must be given special and continual attention to bring about high performance”(Shank, Boynton and Zmud, 1985). However, notwithstanding variations in viewpoints about CSFs, a common underlying factor is anchored on the understanding that critical evaluation and selection of appropriate success factors constitute the cornerstone of every project implementation success.

There is sufficient evidence to attest to the fact that critical evaluation and selection of CSFs constitute a pivotal role in the implementation success of any project. Thus, studies conducted across varied industrial sectors including but not limited to construction (Berssaneti and Carvalho, 2015), information technology (Almajed and Mayhew, 2014), generic projects (Müller and

Jugdev, 2012) and petroleum projects (Tsigas, Emes and Smith, 2017a) and petroleum (Rachman and Ratnayake, 2019). In view of this, a number of specific-sets of CSFs relevant to the successful implementation of Lean have been identified: there are those that state that there should be generic CSFs that could be universally applied across different sectors (Ohno, 1988, Womack and Jones, 1996, Liker and Morgan, 2006), however there are others that different sectors / environments require different approaches (Hines, Francis and Found, 2006, Netland, 2016b, Knol et al., 2018). This fundamentally underpins Contingency theory on four main factors including the implementation of Lean (Netland, 2016a).

Though experts posit that the core principles of Lean are ubiquitous in nature and hence may have universal applicability (GODOLFIM, 2012), other researchers hold contrary views and suggest the need for industry-specific research to identify CSFs relevant to the culture and philosophy of specific industries (Kazmi, 2008b, van Dun, Hicks and Wilderom, 2017b). Furthermore, a study by Achanga et al. (2006) established that leadership and management, finance, skills and expertise as well as organisational culture are critical success factors for lean implementation. Similarly, (Marodin and Saurin, 2013), also argued that, management commitment is a critical factor responsible for lean implementation success. Also, success in any lean initiative depends on key support programmes such as, training and education, the availability of a long-term plan, provision of resources for implementation and the application of appropriate lean tools and techniques (Netland, 2016a). Some researchers identified leadership, management and policies as critical factors that should be prioritized in lean implementation (Belhadi, Touriki and El Fezazi, 2016), while Abu et al.,(2019), propose that 5S and employee training constitute CSFs for Lean implementation in the wood and furniture industry (Abu et al., 2019).

Also, according to Alhuraish, Robledo and Kobi, (2017), top management commitment, culture change, education and training, communication, employee involvement and establishing a link between Lean methods and strategies of businesses were the topmost CSFs for the implementation of Lean in the manufacturing sector.

Extant literature shows that 'Project Management' is the most frequently adopted CSF followed by 'leadership commitment', 'work environment' and 'team work'. Table 2.4 presents a compilation of success factors based on the literature across various industries. Admittedly, majority of Lean initiatives assume a top-down approach (Jadhav et al., 2014; Berroir et al., 2015; Chay et al., 2015). Thus, management commitment and support and leadership play a pivotal role in providing focus and direction for Lean projects. Undoubtedly, and admittedly so, the importance of employees with the requisite knowledge and skills to execute Lean initiatives cannot be overemphasized. This approach has been adopted from a similar survey-based approach in which 76 empirically validated TQM factors were analysed (Sila and Ebrahimpour, 2003).

Table 2. 4: Classification of CSFs

Name of author(s)	Year of Publication	Industry/sector	CSFs identified
The Standish Group	1994; 2006		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Team project effort, ▪ Proper project planning, ▪ Skilled working teams, ▪ Well-defined requirements, ▪ Top management involvement and ▪ Frequent checkpoint controls.
Tan and Ghazali	2011		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Site management and supervision, ▪ overall managerial actions, ▪ capacity to make and carry out decisions, ▪ cash flow and experience of contractor, ▪ Decision making effectiveness, ▪ Project team experience, ▪ Project delivery system, ▪ Project team monitoring and ▪ Project manager's experience.
Godolfim	2012	IT Support Services sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management leadership ▪ Management support ▪ Top management commitment ▪ Organizational culture ▪ Communication ▪ Training and skills building ▪ Financial Capability ▪ Measurement Framework.
Omran et al.	2012		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Physical environment, ▪ Regulatory/legal environment, ▪ Social environment, ▪ Economic environment, and ▪ Political environment are the important critical success factors.
Gudienė et al.	2014		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Good decision-making abilities ▪ Realistic and clear project goals ▪ Relevant prior experience of the project management team ▪ Precise goals/objectives of the client ▪ Experience of the project manager ▪ Project planning skills ▪ Competence project manager project management team, ▪ Uniqueness and complexity of the project
Lodgaard et al.	2016		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management commitment ▪ Leadership ▪ Financial capabilities ▪ Training/Knowledge

Tsiga, Emes and Smith	2017	Petroleum Projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Project Manager Competence</i> ▪ <i>Project Organization</i> ▪ <i>Project Risk Management</i> ▪ <i>Requirements Management</i> ▪ <i>Top Management Support</i> ▪ <i>Contractual Aspects</i> ▪ <i>Project Characteristics</i> ▪ <i>Institutional Factors</i> ▪ <i>Client Knowledge and Experience</i> ▪ <i>External Challenge</i>
Laureani and Antony	“2018	Lean Six Sigma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Project management</i> ▪ <i>Leadership</i> ▪ <i>Selection of talented employees</i> ▪ <i>Financial accountability</i>
Achanga et al.	2006	SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Finance</i> ▪ <i>Leadership</i> ▪ <i>Organizational Culture</i> ▪ <i>Skills and Expertise</i>
Boynton and Zmud	1984	MIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Present losses through risk management</i> ▪ <i>Increase diversification of the customer base</i> ▪ <i>Increase professional staff productivity</i> ▪ <i>Enhance the corporate image with firm’s market and public</i>
Rachman and Ratnayake	2018	Petroleum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Leadership and commitment from management</i> ▪ <i>Employee involvement</i> ▪ <i>Cooperation and trust with contractors/suppliers</i> ▪ <i>Lean project management</i>
Netland	2015	Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Commit to, lead and take active part in the lean programme</i> ▪ <i>Provide and attend training and education</i> ▪ <i>Have a long-term plan and follow it up on a day-to-day basis</i> ▪ <i>Allocate resources and share the gains</i> ▪ <i>Apply lean tools and techniques”</i>

Source: Author’s Construct (2020).

The upstream petroleum operations are predominantly linked with project planning and execution, and available literature indicate critical success factors necessary for success of the petroleum production processes. According to Tsiga, Emes and Smith (2017), the importance of critical success factors for the execution of petroleum projects cannot be overemphasized. Table 2.5 consists of a compilation of critical success factors suitable for the petroleum projects (Tsiga et al., 2017).

Table 2. 5: Critical Success factors for the petroleum projects

Author(s)	Year	Identified success factors	Category
<i>“Gudiene et al., Omran et al., Tan and Ghazali</i>	2014 2012 2011	<i>Economic environment, social environment, political environment, physical environment and regulatory/legal environment.</i>	<i>External Challenge</i>
<i>Gudiene et al., Omran et al., The Standish Group</i>	2014 2012 2013	<i>Nature of finance, experience, organization size, emphasis on cost, quality and time, ability to brief, decision making, roles and contribution, expectations and commitment, involvement and influence.</i>	<i>Client knowledge and expertise</i>
<i>Almajed and Mayhew Ram and Corkindale Varajao et al.,</i>	2014 2014 2014	<i>Support given to project head, support to critical activities, understanding of project difficulty and stakeholder influence.</i>	<i>Top Management support</i>
<i>Gudiene et al.,</i>	2014	<i>Standards and permits.</i>	<i>Institutional factors</i>
<i>Omran et al., Yong and Mustafa</i>	2012 2013	<i>Project type, size, nature, complexity, design, resources allocation time and level of technology</i>	<i>Project Characteristics</i>
<i>Toor and Ogunlana Mala-Pines Barclays and Osei- Bryson</i>	2009 2009 2009	<i>Planning and control effort, team structure and integration, safety and quality program, schedule and work definition, budgeting and control of subcontractors</i>	<i>Project Manager Competence</i>
<i>Berssaneti and Carvalho Gudiene et al., Varajao et al.,</i>	2015 2014 2014	<i>Contract type, tendering (procedures or steps for the selection of that service) and procurement (company selection to provide services) process.</i>	<i>Contractual aspects</i>
<i>Almajed and Mayhew Gudiene et al., Ram and Corkindale Varajao et al.,</i>	2014 2014 2014 2014	<i>Team experience, technical skills, planning and organizing skills, commitment and involvement, teams’ adaptability to changing requirements, working relationships, educational level, training availability and decision making effectiveness”</i>	<i>Project team competence</i>

<p><i>Almajed and Mayhew</i> <i>Rebechini Junior and De Carvalho</i> <i>Didraga</i></p>	<p>2014 2013 2013</p>	<p>Hard aspects; <i>Initiation, identification, assessment, response planning, response implementation</i></p> <p>soft aspects: <i>Risk communication and attitude, monitoring and review.</i></p>	<p><i>Project risk management</i></p>
<p><i>Didraga</i> <i>Mirza et al.,</i></p>	<p>2013 2013</p>	<p><i>“Elicitation technique, identification, analysis and negotiation, modelling, validation and scope management”</i></p>	<p><i>Requirements management</i></p>

Source: Tsiga et al., (2017)

The content of Table 2.5 justifies the significance of project management competency in the execution of petroleum production projects. Suffice to reiterate that the upstream petroleum sector counts among sectors with the highest project tasks.

The high risk management impacts of the upstream petroleum operations, coupled with high standards and regulatory requirements exert enormous pressures on operators/companies within the upstream sector to ensure the identification of success factors that will support and/or enhance performance. Even though the critical success factors compiled in Table 2.5 (Tsiga et al., 2017) may not be exhaustive, nevertheless, it provides a foundation for further research from different perspectives. In support of this assertion, Rachmand and Ratnayake (2018) identified Lean Project management, leadership and management commitment, employee involvement and corporation and trust with contractors and suppliers as critical success factors to enhance performance in petroleum projects. Further, Claudiu et al., (2012), emphasized the risk management role and its involvement to the success of the projects in the previous literature. The study revealed that a

significant component in the project management process is the risk management which is anticipated indirectly to work in favour of project success. Within the context of upstream petroleum operations, an in-depth analysis, identification of appropriate success factors plays a pivotal role in the lean implementation process. Lean cannot be implemented in a vacuum. The context under which Lean is implemented will determine to some extent, the success or failure of the initiatives. Thus, cultural context coupled with change management processes underpin any successful Lean programs. The next section of the literature review discusses the culture and change management within the context of Lean implementation.

2.10 The Role of Culture and Change Management in Lean Implementation

Lean implementation should not be oversimplified to the extent that it loses its rigor. National and organisational culture as well as change management constitute pivotal pre-requisites for any successful lean implementation initiative. This section of the literature review explores the role of culture and change management in improving lean implementation success.

2.10.1 National Culture

Culture underpins societal and/or organisational existence and *modus operandi*. It anchors societal/organizational cohesion. In the context of this study, culture is the bedrock of lean implementation. Notwithstanding the extent of an organisation's preparedness for lean implementation including the types of tools, technics and practices deployed, if the organization fails to adopt a more systemic approach anchored by cultural values and philosophical tenets of lean manufacturing, then chances of success may be slimmer than anticipated.

Zarbo (2012), defines culture as the way people get incentives to behave, think, talk, and act, every day. National cultures have a direct impact on organizational culture. Some researchers opine (implicitly or explicitly) that the Japanese culture is a quality culture wherein they thrive to add value to their peoples' lives by making the continuous improvement as daily attitude and lifetime process (Bernstein, 2005, Merwe, Pieterse and Lourens, 2014, Bortolotti, Boscari and Danese, 2015b, Alhuraish, Robledo and Kobi, 2017).

However, Spear and Bowen (1999) presented a counter view saying that if Japanese culture in itself was to promote lean, then other automotive companies in Japan, such as Nissan, should have been equally competitive as TPS. They further posit that Toyota has managed to achieve the same efficiency levels in all its manufacturing units around the world, despite different national cultures. Thus concluding that even if national culture has an impact on lean implementation, it can be overcome by other factors, such as organizational culture.

Dierickx (2016) did a comparison of LM in Japanese and Belgian manufacturing SMEs wherein one of the hypotheses was National culture has an impact on lean implementation through behaviour and thinking patterns of employees and cultural beliefs. He found that since the Japanese and Belgian cultures were very similar, it explained the minor differences regarding the leanest in both countries. However, some of the cultural differences were evident on the shop floor during interviews with regards to employee behaviour and attitude.

In a recent study, Kull et al. (2014), a large scale research was conducted in which data was collected from 1400 companies across 24 countries. This research found that LM was easier to

implement in countries which had cultural characteristics such as; Low assertiveness, High uncertainty avoidance, Low performance orientation and Low future orientation.

Also, Wong (2007) pointed out that it wasn't only an organization's internal culture that affects the implementation of LM but the national culture as well was observed with particular reference to LM implementation in Taiwanese enterprises. It was noted that Taiwanese companies had effectively managed cultural resistance to bring about the prerequisites for lean success.

2.10.2 Organizational Culture

Lean manufacturing has been adopted globally across different industries to improve the efficiency and profitability of the company through elimination of waste and focus on value-add activities. Yet, there is a concern regarding the successful implementation of lean in an organization. A prime concern that has been under study is the culture aspect of the organization and its people. Research has proven that an organization should have a culture that supports education, training, involvement and teamwork and for any company to remain competitive, it has to adopt a culture of continuous improvement. Daft (2001) capitulates the concept of a company's culture "*is the set of values, guiding beliefs, understandings and ways of thinking shared by members of the organization and taught to new members*".

Lean management as explained by its pioneers is a way of thinking, and culture of doing things continuously which could be replicated anywhere and anytime. Hence, in order to achieve success in implementing the lean management or transforming to lean management, the basic thinking of each and every stakeholder needs to be changed right from shop floor employees to senior management.

Lean manufacturing is deeply rooted in Japanese culture so as to make it imperative for the others to change their organizational culture to imbibe lean thinking (Ahmad, 2013). Bernstein (2005) stipulates that change and innovation depends on the ability of an organization to entrench a culture of routine and consistent ways of carrying out activities.

Liker and Hoseus (2008) stated that developing and sustaining lean is 20% technical and 80% cultural. This was further reinforced by Saha et al., (2014) whose research in lean manufacturing, suggested that change in the employees' mindset and company's willingness to embrace lean transformation contributes 80% of lean's success in the company (Saha et al., 2014). Organizations have little probability of successfully implementing LM if little or no attention is directed towards institutionalizing the right culture and the right conditions as basis for adoption of the required changes (Lacksonen et al., 2010). Figure 2.16 illustrates lean cultural framework developed by Merwe et al. (2014).

Figure 2. 16: Lean organizational culture change framework

Source: Adopted From Merwe et al. (2014)

Many researches have established the critical role of leadership in transforming lean culture. The researchers formulated a list of casual activities that need to be addressed and one of the important factors is the flow of communication. The failure of lean is because of the fact that most organizations fail to identify the specific actions that could bring about the cultural change. However, this framework needs to be validated. Ahmad (2013) proposed a theoretical framework on the role of culture in LM. The framework is based on an extensive qualitative literature review on the importance of culture in lean manufacturing. This is shown in Figure 2.17 below.

Figure 2. 17: Lean Culture Framework

Source: Ahmad (2013)

2.11 Change Management

The Lean implementation process is nothing more than changes in work processes, work attitudes, changes in thinking as well as behavioural changes. Stated differently, Lean implementation is about changes in organizational culture. This explains why culture and change are pre-requisites for any successful Lean implementation initiative.

The concept and theory of change management is at the heart of the life cycle of every organization. The scope of change management spans from individual, team and organizational change management processes (Cameron and Green, 2009). Group dynamics is fundamental in the change management process. Hossan et al., (2013), proffer that group dynamics reflects internal forces within a group that shape the actions/behaviours of its members, and which is pivotal in change management process. Change management can assume one of two typologies

notably either planned or emergent change (McGarry, Cashin, and Fowler, 2012). The highly competitive and technologically fast-changing business landscape, coupled with changing customer requirements continuous to exert enormous pressure on managers to adopt novel change management approaches in the management of their organisations. To survive within a highly competitive business landscape, manufacturing organisations must adapt to reality (Bamford and Forestter, 2003). The theory of change management is defined as the “process, tools and techniques to manage the people-side of business change to achieve the required business outcome, and to realize that business change effectively within the social infrastructure of the workplace” (Hiatt and Creasey, 2011). Leadership play a pivotal role in organizational change management process, and core leadership attributes critical for change management success constitute essential prerequisites. Cameron and Green (2009, p.4), citing Evans (2000), outlined 11 paradoxes of leadership attributes that are fundamental for change management success. These include: “

“To be able to build a close relationship with one’s staff, and to keep a suitable distance; to be able to lead, and to hold oneself in the background; to trust one’s staff, and to keep an eye on what is happening; to be tolerant, and to know how you want things to function; to keep the goals of one’s department in mind, and at the same time to be loyal to the whole firm; to do a good job of planning your own time, and to be flexible with your schedule; to freely express your view, and to be diplomatic; to be a visionary, and to keep one’s feet on the ground; to try to win consensus, and to be able to cut through; to be dynamic, and to be reflective; to be sure of yourself, and to be humble”(Cameron and Green, 2009 p.4).”

Several change management models exist notable among them are Kotter’s 8 step change model and Lewin’s 3 steps change model (Chappell et al., 2016; Benin, 2017). Whilst available literature indicate that Kotter’s 8 steps change model is among one of most widely used, there is still some

disagreement on the most appropriate approach to adopt when implementing change in an organization (Bamford and Forrester, 2003). From both practitioner and researcher perspectives, Kotter's model of leading planned change emerged from his observations of organizations that had not been successful in implementing change. An outline of Kotter's eight steps for successful change include: "*establish a sense of urgency; create the guiding coalition; develop a vision and strategy; communicate the change vision; empower employees for broad-based action; generate short-term wins; consolidate gains and produce more change, and anchor new approaches in the culture*" (Gupta, 2011 p.1-2).

In contrast, whilst Kotter's model assumes that "*successful change of any magnitude goes through all eight steps, usually in sequence*", Chappell et al., (2016) applied Kotter's change model on workplace initiatives and found that not all the 8 steps were necessarily applied. Akin to the approach by Chappell et al., (2016), some researchers and practitioners are of the view that lean elements are ubiquitous and with universal applicability, whilst others believe that industry-specific or company-specific requirements are necessary to ensure lean implementation success. This provides adequate basis for Kotter's change model to be deemed suitable for lean application. Nonetheless, lean adoption can also be suitably aligned to Lewin's change model which assert that change occurs through a process of unfreezing, freezing and refreezing (Cardwell and Boff. 2019; Benin, 2017). Change models can be applied differently based on researcher worldview and research objectives and/or perspectives. Cardwell and Boff (2019) adopted Kotter's 8 step change model for library management whilst Benin (2017) applied Lewin's theory of change in the local content requirements within the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. Lewin's change model asserts that prior to any successful behavioural changes, the old behaviour ought to be cast-off. This allows the new behaviour to be fully embraced (Bamford and Forrester, 2003; Benin, 2017).

Notwithstanding the change management model adopted, it is critical that managers recognize challenges with regards to change management implementation. It is not easy to effect change because it permeates every aspect of an organisation's operations. Particularly, change impacts on people, culture and organizational values and philosophy. To buttress this assertion, Cardwell and Boff (2019), outline critical barriers to change such as anxiety, staff morale, buy-in, burnout, frustration, and reluctance. Managers must anticipate these barriers and put in place appropriate measures to mitigate their negative impact in the change management implementation process.

2.11.1 A synopsis of Lean and Change management in the Upstream petroleum sector

The concept of Lean manufacturing evolved in the 80s and has since been widely accepted and applied across various industries. However, suffice to revisit the assertion that popularity of the lean concept does not correlate with implementation success. Available literature suggest that scepticism and reservation from organisations in adopting lean "system has been a major setback for lean application worldwide(Achanga et al., 2006b).Also, the low success rate of lean transformations in many countries has given a cause for concern. Much of the literature had pointed out that the main reason is due to the failure in managing the change process during a lean manufacturing transformation, and hence the need to further explore change management in the context of lean application in the upstream petroleum sector.

Lean implementation is fundamentally a change management and/or a cultural change strategy (Stehn and Hook, 2008; Syed and Syed, 2013; Nordin, 2012). Contextually, lean manufacturing implementation and organizational change management are intertwined and/or interrelated. A successful lean management intervention consequently leads to change within an organization. For

the purpose of this research, lean manufacturing implementation in the upstream petroleum sector has socio-economic, technical, environmental and regulatory requirements.

Application of lean in the upstream petroleum sector composed of highly complex operations cannot be overemphasized.

2.12 Lean Suitability for Adoption in the Upstream Petroleum Sector

Hobbs (2004), posit that manufacturers continue to search for the Holy Grail, and to discover which methodology is the magic bullet. However, notwithstanding the fact that the proponents of lean manufacturing originally focused on the manufacturing sector (Ohno, 1998; Womack and Jones, 2003), the concept has gained widespread acceptance and become a catchphrase/buzzword and has been implemented across different industrial sectors (Hobbs, 2004; Garza-Reyes et al., 2012; Bicheno and Howleg, 2016; Jasti and Kodali, 2019). In support of widespread acceptance of lean across all economic sectors, extant literature indicates that to compete globally on critical competitive priorities including quality, cost, safety, reliability, and flexibility, business operations need to adopt and practice advanced manufacturing philosophies such as lean (Sharma and Kodali, 2008; Jasti and Kodali, 2019).

The entire petroleum industry with specific focus on the upstream subsector plays a critical and pivotal role in the global economy. Stated differently, the upstream petroleum sector is the bedrock of many economic sectors including the production, manufacturing, transportation and allied services sectors. It is undeniable that these sectors heavily depend on energy as a major source of their operations. Thus, the priorities of the upstream petroleum sector have a ripple effect on its entire supply chain.

According to Taj and Morosan (2011), data analysed from a study of 65 manufacturing plants across different industries in China to determine performance of lean practices found that the petroleum and high-tech plants performed relatively better compared to other sectors. Furthermore, the study explored the potential of lean implementation in the petroleum industry and established that *“the lean concept has been used to improve operational and technical aspects, contractor/supplier relationships, team organization and project management practice in the petroleum industry”* (Rachman and Ratnayake, 2018, p. 2).

Literature is laden with lean applications in the petroleum industry in general, and the upstream petroleum sector in particular. assessment of 65 companies in China, found that the petroleum industry is by far the most advanced sector in the application of lean principles. The question whether lean is a suitable methodology for adoption in the upstream sector does not arise because literature presented several instances of lean application within the upstream petroleum sector(Fulks and Cook, 2002, Taj and Morosan, 2011a, Rachman and Ratnayake, 2016, 2019). Ghany (2010), explored the application of 5S as an improvement tool in the upstream sector whilst Fulks and Cook (2002), examined how BP applied lean drilling as an approach in its supplier selection of the drilling and completion of its project dubbed Mad Dog. The authors further examined the lean drilling process from supplier perspective with particular focus on technology transfer. In summary therefore, the forgone discourse on lean adoption in the upstream petroleum sector is grounded in literature and adequately justified as an innovative methodology that is not an end in itself, but which further lays the foundation for the implementation of Six Sigma.

2.13 Review of Existing LM Frameworks

2.13.1 Introduction

Researchers have made several attempts to develop frameworks for lean implementation (Buus, 2011), but there seem not to be a corresponding success ratio in lean implementation. According to Anand and Kodali (2010), citing Yusuf and Aspinwall (2000), a framework is a “*prescriptive set of things to do*”. Similarly, Hakes (1991), posit that a framework “*helps to translates theory into practice*”.

Hobbs (2004), suggest that a framework serves as a guide on “how to” systematically and procedurally accomplish a task. Similarly, Jasti and Kodali (2016), citing Aalbrektse (1991) postulate that a framework is a strategic management tool used to showcase overall business objectives. Whilst expert opinions and definitions of frameworks may vary; the overarching rationale for any framework is to provide guidance.

LM scholars and practitioners recommend industry-specific frameworks to guide LM application processes. In view of this, Smeds, (1994) “proposed a generic framework in managing change towards lean enterprises. Similarly, Motwani (2003) developed a theoretical framework based on business process change, whereas Anand and Kodali (2010) devised a conceptual framework with 65 lean elements, the internal stakeholders and decision levels.

According to Karim and Arif-Uz-Zaman (2013) citing Powell et al. (2013), another innovative lean implementation process combines the methodologies for lean manufacturing and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP). In discussing further some frameworks, it is worth noting the five lean principles (Figure 2) fundamentally underpin most of LM frameworks.”

Literature is laden with several frameworks/models developed for lean implementation in different enterprises (Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2013b). Dombrowski and Zahn (2011) developed a lean framework for application which was validated in the automotive industry. Sangwa and Sangwan (2018) also proposed an integrated measurement framework for lean organizations. Ahlstrom (1998) proposed a descriptive framework and laid down sequential steps for lean implementation. The framework prescribed a simple structure based on the lean theory which outlines the sequences of the manufacturing improvement initiatives which elude managers incapable of prioritizing improvement processes. According to Ahlstrom, management should take care of some fundamental tasks including:

- Establish a foundation for subsequent improvements by delayering the organization and establish a system to attain zero defect.
- Working with the core principles including elimination of waste by means of manufacturing cells operated by multifunctional teams, which function through a pull production.

2.13.2 Framework Analysis

As a precursor to this research, insights drawn from previous studies found that an extensive analysis of existing frameworks with particular focus on the lean elements used in the framework development provides a solid basis for the conduct of this research. Thus, a total of 101 frameworks published between 1998 - 2020 were identified and analysed. One area of interest in the process involved the identification of lean elements and other considerations in the process of developing existing frameworks. A total of 123 elements were identified from the analysis of 101 frameworks

which were considered in this research. Figure 2.18 is a word cloud which gives a pictorial view of the most dominants lean elements that emerged from the review of the 101 lean frameworks.

The following process was adopted in the framework analysis process:

Source: Author’s Construct (2020)

Figure 2. 18: Word cloud of Lean Elements from SLR

Source: Author’s Construct (2020)

2.13.3 Lean Manufacturing Frequency Distribution Table

Table 2.6 below presents a detailed illustration of the 123 elements identified in the literature.

From the word cloud presented in Figure 2.18 above, it can be observed that in no particular order, some of the dominant/frequently occurring elements include but not limited to Continuous Improvement (CI), Waste Elimination (WE), Leadership Direction (LD) Standardisation(S) and Human Resource Management(HRM). A simple word frequency test performed using Nvivo is presented in Table 2.6 below:

Table 2. 6: Frequency Distribution of Lean Elements from SLR

Lean Elements	Publications	Freq.
3Ps	[53]	1
5 Whys	[13]; [73]; [93]	3
5s/Workplace Housekeeping	[2]; [3]; [7]; [8]; [11]; [13]; [15]; [25]; [32]; [33]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [48]; [51]; [52]; [57]; [64]; [65]; [69]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [78]; [82]; [83]; [84]; [93]; [97]; [100]	31
6Rs	[33]; [42]; [55]; [64]; [72]	5
8 Wastes	[2]; [3]; [18]; [30]; [32]; [37]; [39]; [42]; [57]; [64]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [92]; [94]; [97]; [100]	18
Accountability	[21]; [48]; [56]; [72]	4
Adoption of Lean Paradigm/Lean thinking	[1]; [5]; [12]; [15]; [36]; [40]; [41]; [42]; [46]; [56]; [65]; [67]; [66]; [74]; [79]; [83]; [86]	17
Agile manufacturing strategies/Agile assessment systems	[22]; [87]	2
Autonomation	[47]; [52]; [60]; [64]; [67]; [72]; [83]; [84]	8
Basic and operational stability	[18]; [19]; [23]; [25]; [42]; [47]	6
Building Lean Expert Team	[1]; [2]; [4]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [11]; [13]; [14]; [15]; [17]; [18]; [19]; [20]; [25]; [32]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [47]; [48]; [49]; [50]; [55]; [56]; [59]; [61]; [67]; [68]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [82]; [83]; [84]; [85]; [87]; [94]; [97]; [100]	40
Business Process Improvement	[3]; [8]; [12]; [27]; [29]; [35]; [37]; [41]; [48]; [52]; [57]; [63]; [65]; [71]; [72]	15
Cause and effect diagrams	[13]; [73]	2
Cellular Manufacturing	[5]; [11]; [24]; [33]; [42]; [48]; [52]; [64]; [82]; [87]; [94]; [100]	12
Coaching leadership	[1]; [11]; [36]; [49]; [79]; [83]	6

Communication and feedback	[2]; [6]; [7]; [8]; [10]; [13]; [13]; [18]; [19]; [23]; [24]; [32]; [36]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [43]; [49]; [52]; [56]; [57]; [59]; [62]; [71]; [72]; [79]; [80]; [83]; [91]; [94]; [100]	31
Competitive benchmarking	[87]; [96]	2
Competitiveness	[65]; [71]	2
Concurrent Engineering	[37]; [57]; [81]; [94]	4
Conformance to Quality	[18]; [42]; [54]; [69]; [74]; [94]	6
Consistency	[56]	1
Continuous Improvement	[2]; [3]; [4]; [6]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [11]; [12]; [13]; [13]; [15]; [16]; [17]; [18]; [19]; [21]; [24]; [25]; [27]; [29]; [32]; [34]; [36]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [43]; [46]; [44]; [47]; [48]; [50]; [52]; [54]; [55]; [57]; [61]; [64]; [65]; [69]; [71]; [72]; [73]; [74]; [76]; [79]; [81]; [82]; [83]; [84]; [85]; [86]; [87]; [88]; [91]; [93]; [94]; [95]; [97]; [100]; [101]	63
Control Charts	[13]; [73]	2
Cost Reduction	[3]; [5]; [12]; [17]; [29]; [33]; [35]; [42]; [48]; [54]; [68]; [73]; [76]; [91]; [94]; [97]	16
Creative thinking and innovation	[3]; [42]; [57]; [67]; [66]; [72]; [74]; [76]	8
Culture and change management	[1]; [2]; [6]; [8]; [10]; [13]; [16]; [17]; [18]; [19]; [23]; [24]; [32]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [47]; [49]; [50]; [57]; [58]; [60]; [62]; [68]; [71]; [72]; [79]; [83]; [85]; [88]; [95]; [98]; [99]	33
Current state evaluation	[41]; [60]	2
Customer Relationship Management/ Customer Focus	[1]; [2]; [3]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [13]; [13]; [18]; [20]; [21]; [26]; [29]; [35]; [36]; [37]; [38]; [39]; [42]; [46]; [44]; [45]; [47]; [54]; [57]; [61]; [65]; [68]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [76]; [77]; [79]; [80]; [83]; [88]; [91]; [94]; [95]; [96]; [98]; [100]; [101]	45
Cycle time reduction	[3]; [17]; [21]; [25]; [34]; [52]; [54]; [69]; [73]; [87]; [94]; [97]; [100]	13
Define lean assessment metrics	[12]; [15]; [18]; [19]; [25]; [36]; [41]; [42]; [50]; [55]; [59]	11
DMAIC	[25]; [64]; [78]; [79]	4
Drivers for lean success	[3]; [7]; [8]; [29]; [30]; [41]; [63]; [71]; [74]; [76]	10
Elimination of waste	[1]; [2]; [3]; [4]; [5]; [10]; [11]; [12]; [13]; [13]; [15]; [17]; [18]; [19]; [24]; [25]; [27]; [29]; [32]; [33]; [35]; [37]; [39]; [40]; [42]; [46]; [44]; [45]; [47]; [50]; [53]; [54]; [55]; [57]; [59]; [61]; [64]; [65]; [67]; [68]; [69]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [73]; [74]; [79]; [83]; [85]; [88]; [89]; [91]; [92]; [94]; [97]; [100]	56
Employee involvement and participation	[2]; [3]; [7]; [8]; [10]; [12]; [13]; [13]; [15]; [18]; [19]; [27]; [29]; [31]; [36]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [48]; [49]; [50]; [52]; [54];	36

	[62]; [68]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [75]; [79]; [80]; [83]; [84]; [94]; [101]	
Empowerment	[1]; [2]; [8]; [15]; [27]; [29]; [30]; [36]; [42]; [48]; [49]; [50]; [52]; [54]; [62]; [70]; [72]; [79]; [81]; [83]; [94]; [97]; [100]	23
Engagement	[3]; [7]; [8]; [29]; [49]; [50]; [54]; [56]; [88]; [94]; [100]	11
Equipment Utilisation	[94]	1
Equipment work processes	[2]; [10]; [12]; [13]; [17]; [18]; [19]; [20]; [21]; [26]; [35]; [36]; [37]; [42]; [47]; [57]; [58]; [62]; [69]; [71]; [74]; [79]; [83]; [84]; [94]; [96]; [98]	27
Fast and reliable delivery	[42]	1
FMEA	[2]; [10]; [53]; [57]; [64]; [72]	6
Focus on Lean Structure and Behaviours	[5]; [6]; [7]; [8]; [17]; [18]; [22]; [41]; [43]; [48]; [52]; [56]; [58]; [74]; [80]; [86]; [89]	17
Focus on Value Stream Mapping	[2]; [10]; [13]; [15]; [18]; [19]; [24]; [25]; [28]; [30]; [32]; [33]; [39]; [40]; [41]; [42]; [47]; [48]; [54]; [55]; [57]; [64]; [67]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [78]; [79]; [83]; [84]; [85]; [86]; [94]; [100]	35
Focused Factory and Production System	[2]; [36]; [37]; [42]; [71]; [73]; [82]; [87]; [88]	9
Frontloading	[10]; [31]; [47]	3
Genchi Genbutsu	[32]; [36]	2
Goals and objectives/Strategic initiatives	[3]; [5]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [13]; [16]; [18]; [25]; [30]; [31]; [32]; [35]; [37]; [41]; [49]; [50]; [60]; [61]; [65]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [83]; [90]; [99]	27
Group Technology	[21]; [22]; [36]; [42]; [48]; [71]	6
Human Resource Management/Respect for humanity/People management	[2]; [3]; [4]; [6]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [13]; [13]; [15]; [18]; [19]; [20]; [21]; [22]; [25]; [27]; [28]; [29]; [32]; [36]; [37]; [39]; [42]; [46]; [44]; [45]; [48]; [54]; [55]; [57]; [62]; [63]; [64]; [65]; [68]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [76]; [77]; [79]; [81]; [83]; [84]; [87]; [88]; [89]; [90]; [94]; [95]; [97]; [100]	55
Information Technology Systems	[2]; [10]; [17]; [22]; [26]; [29]; [36]; [37]; [46]; [44]; [48]; [50]; [58]; [60]; [61]; [68]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [76]; [77]; [81]; [90]; [94]; [96]; [97]; [99]; [100]	28
Inventory Reduction	[3]; [11]; [29]; [42]; [48]; [54]; [57]; [69]; [71]; [74]; [91]; [94]; [97]; [100]; [101]	15
Jidoka	[11]; [15]; [28]; [36]; [42]; [60]; [64]; [72]; [85]; [93]	10
Just in Time/Continuous Flow Production	[1]; [2]; [3]; [10]; [13]; [13]; [15]; [19]; [20]; [21]; [23]; [24]; [25]; [28]; [32]; [33]; [36]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [46]; [44]; [47]; [48]; [57]; [64]; [67]; [66]; [71]; [72]; [81]; [83]; [85]; [87]; [93]; [97]	36
Justification	[10]; [56]	2
Kaizen	[2]; [10]; [13]; [15]; [18]; [24]; [25]; [31]; [32]; [33]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [47]; [52]; [64]; [65]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [79]; [82]; [83]; [93]; [94]; [97]	26

Kanban	[2]; [8]; [11]; [13]; [15]; [21]; [25]; [30]; [33]; [36]; [41]; [42]; [48]; [52]; [53]; [60]; [64]; [67]; [66]; [71]; [72]; [73]; [82]; [83]; [93]; [94]	26
Labour Relations/Engage Labour Unions	[3]; [8]; [29]; [35]; [42]; [48]; [69]; [79]; [91]; [94]; [97]	11
Leadership and Direction	[1]; [2]; [4]; [5]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [12]; [13]; [13]; [15]; [16]; [18]; [19]; [21]; [23]; [26]; [27]; [31]; [32]; [36]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [43]; [46]; [44]; [48]; [49]; [51]; [52]; [57]; [58]; [62]; [63]; [64]; [67]; [66]; [69]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [75]; [77]; [78]; [79]; [80]; [83]; [84]; [86]; [88]; [89]; [93]; [95]; [96]; [98]; [100]; [101]	58
Lean Accounting	[35]; [48]; [72]; [83]	4
Lean awareness training and education	[2]; [3]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [11]; [13]; [13]; [18]; [19]; [21]; [27]; [29]; [35]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [47]; [48]; [49]; [50]; [52]; [54]; [55]; [56]; [59]; [60]; [61]; [62]; [68]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [79]; [80]; [82]; [83]; [84]; [88]; [94]; [97]; [100]; [101]	44
Lean Culture	[39]; [54]; [95]	3
Lean Enterprise transformation management	[3]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [18]; [29]; [41]; [48]; [50]; [56]; [71]; [72]	12
Lean Performance Metrics	[3]; [8]; [12]; [17]; [18]; [21]; [22]; [35]; [41]; [43]; [48]; [50]; [52]; [54]; [56]; [71]; [77]; [80]; [84]; [87]; [88]; [89]; [94]; [100]	24
Lean Philosophy	[18]; [83]	2
Lean Project Management	[2]; [7]; [8]; [10]; [11]; [13]; [15]; [17]; [22]; [26]; [32]; [35]; [36]; [37]; [42]; [47]; [53]; [57]; [71]; [72]; [75]; [81]; [83]	23
Lean sustainability	[8]; [25]; [29]; [35]; [41]; [54]; [71]; [74]; [76]; [97]	10
Lean Tools, Principles and practices	[22]; [29]; [40]; [41]; [49]; [52]; [54]; [60]; [63]; [65]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [89]; [97]	15
Learning organisation	[1]; [8]; [13]; [18]; [41]; [50]; [63]; [71]; [72]; [83]	10
Market Share	[3]; [94]	2
Mistake Proofing	[51]; [64]; [94]	3
Multifunctional employees	[2]; [3]; [4]; [8]; [11]; [13]; [18]; [36]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [54]; [64]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [82]; [84]; [87]; [94]; [97]	21
Network relationships	[10]; [60]; [74]	3
One piece flow	[10]; [25]; [28]; [36]; [39]; [42]; [47]; [52]; [60]; [83]; [84]	11
Order-based production	[1]; [4]; [13]; [13]; [18]; [42]; [47]; [77]; [78]; [83]; [91]	11
Organisational culture	[54]; [95]	2
Pareto analysis	[13]; [73]	2
PDCA	[12]; [41]; [52]; [53]; [64]; [72]; [79]; [93]	8
Planning and scheduling strategies	[2]; [4]; [10]; [13]; [17]; [18]; [19]; [22]; [35]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [47]; [54]; [57]; [58]; [72]; [73]; [77]; [79]; [83]; [86]; [87]; [91]; [94]; [96]; [98]; [100]	28
Poka Yoke	[5]; [42]; [64]; [73]	4

Policy and strategy deployment	[8]; [29]; [30]; [36]; [63]; [71]	6
Problem-solving techniques	[25]; [36]; [38]; [41]; [52]; [54]; [57]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [93]	11
Process control systems	[9]; [12]; [17]; [18]; [19]; [25]; [39]; [41]; [42]; [47]; [48]; [49]; [50]; [52]; [54]; [62]; [69]; [74]; [79]; [83]; [89]; [94]; [100]	23
Process mapping practices	[3]; [8]; [9]; [11]; [12]; [13]; [18]; [29]; [30]; [37]; [39]; [40]; [41]; [42]; [44]; [48]; [50]; [52]; [54]; [57]; [60]; [63]; [64]; [69]; [71]; [72]; [73]; [74]; [94]; [97]; [100]	31
Process simplification	[3]; [5]; [9]; [12]; [17]; [41]; [71]; [99]	8
Process variability	[7]; [18]; [30]; [53]; [79]	5
Production and Production Logistics	[24]; [26]; [34]; [35]; [42]; [64]; [74]; [77]; [87]; [90]; [94]	11
Production leveling	[24]; [36]; [42]; [64]; [67]; [66]; [72]; [73]; [87]; [93]; [94]	11
Pull System linked to customer	[2]; [4]; [10]; [15]; [18]; [19]; [23]; [25]; [28]; [30]; [36]; [37]; [38]; [39]; [42]; [47]; [54]; [67]; [66]; [70]; [72]; [79]; [80]; [81]; [83]; [84]; [87]; [93]; [94]	29
QFD	[40]; [53]; [57]; [64]; [74]	5
Quality Circles	[42]; [64]; [74]; [78]; [82]; [83]	6
Readiness for change	[8]; [9]; [10]; [17]; [18]; [19]; [36]; [41]; [42]; [49]; [50]; [54]; [58]; [60]; [62]; [69]; [71]; [74]; [83]; [94]	20
Reduction in Lead time	[11]; [54]; [93]; [94]	4
Reengineered production processes	[2]; [5]; [15]; [19]; [20]; [28]; [36]; [42]; [46]; [47]; [57]; [67]; [78]; [83]; [87]; [94]; [98]	17
Resources, Needs and Requirements	[8]; [22]; [26]; [29]; [35]; [40]; [49]; [50]; [52]; [53]; [54]; [61]; [76]; [91]; [100]	15
Review potential wastes and lean practices	[5]; [10]; [13]; [35]; [37]; [41]; [48]; [55]; [56]; [59]; [62]; [74]; [79]; [82]; [83]; [92]; [97]	17
Reward Schemes	[94]	1
Safety improvement programs	[2]; [12]; [13]; [18]; [19]; [20]; [29]; [35]; [37]; [42]; [50]; [68]; [72]; [79]; [83]; [87]; [91]; [93]; [94]; [97]; [98]; [100]	22
Sense of urgency	[7]; [8]	2
Set up Reduction time	[54]; [82]; [91]; [93]; [94]	5
Six Sigma	[24]; [42]; [64]; [71]; [79]	5
Small lot size	[42]; [52]; [64]; [70]; [82]; [87]; [94]	7
SMED	[2]; [5]; [13]; [25]; [33]; [42]; [52]; [57]; [64]; [67]; [66]; [69]; [71]; [72]; [73]	15
SPC	[2]; [10]; [21]; [36]; [37]; [38]; [52]; [53]; [64]; [70]; [72]; [74]	12
Stakeholder involvement	[7]; [8]; [29]; [32]; [35]; [36]; [37]; [54]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [94]; [100]	13
Standadisation	[1]; [2]; [10]; [13]; [15]; [16]; [18]; [23]; [25]; [28]; [29]; [30]; [31]; [32]; [33]; [36]; [37]; [39]; [40]; [41]; [42]; [46]; [44]; [45]; [48]; [49]; [52]; [54]; [57]; [60]; [64]; [69]; [70];	50

	[71]; [72]; [74]; [78]; [79]; [81]; [82]; [83]; [84]; [85]; [86]; [93]; [94]; [97]; [98]; [99]; [100]	
Strategic Alignment	[3]; [7]; [8]; [11]; [29]; [37]; [39]; [41]; [48]; [65]; [71]; [87]; [88]; [89]; [90]; [100]	16
Supplier Relationship Management	[1]; [2]; [3]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [13]; [13]; [18]; [20]; [21]; [23]; [26]; [29]; [30]; [35]; [36]; [38]; [42]; [46]; [44]; [45]; [57]; [67]; [66]; [68]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [75]; [76]; [77]; [82]; [83]; [88]; [94]; [96]; [98]; [100]; [101]	42
SWOT analysis for lean application	[36]; [59]	2
Testing and Validation	[25]; [30]; [53]; [57]; [71]; [79]; [92]	7
Top Management Commitment	[2]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [11]; [12]; [13]; [16]; [18]; [21]; [23]; [29]; [32]; [36]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [46]; [44]; [45]; [49]; [50]; [51]; [52]; [54]; [61]; [62]; [64]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [75]; [78]; [83]; [94]; [101]	37
Total Quality management/Quality Improvement Systems	[2]; [6]; [10]; [13]; [18]; [24]; [25]; [29]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [46]; [44]; [45]; [48]; [50]; [52]; [54]; [64]; [65]; [69]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [78]; [81]; [82]; [83]; [87]; [88]; [93]; [94]; [100]; [101]	35
TPM	[1]; [2]; [10]; [11]; [13]; [15]; [17]; [21]; [25]; [26]; [29]; [32]; [33]; [37]; [38]; [39]; [41]; [42]; [48]; [51]; [52]; [64]; [67]; [66]; [70]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [82]; [83]; [84]; [85]; [87]; [93]; [94]; [97]; [100]	37
Transparency	[5]; [8]; [18]; [29]; [49]	5
Understanding Lean Concept System	[50]; [53]	2
Value Engineering/Value Identification	[5]; [39]; [50]; [53]; [57]; [67]; [66]; [81]; [87]; [91]; [94]	11
Value Stream	[5]; [29]; [39]; [50]; [54]; [68]; [76]	7
Vendor Development	[8]; [36]; [42]; [74]; [94]; [100]	6
Vision, Mission and Values(VMV)	[6]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10]; [13]; [32]; [36]; [49]; [56]; [64]; [65]; [71]; [72]; [79]; [90]	16
Visual Control Systems	[2]; [3]; [48]; [49]; [52]; [54]; [73]; [82]; [93]; [94]; [100]	11
Volume flexibility	[42]; [69]; [87]; [88]; [94]	5
Waste analysis/Identification of wastes	[2]; [3]; [10]; [12]; [13]; [13]; [17]; [18]; [32]; [35]; [36]; [37]; [41]; [42]; [50]; [55]; [57]; [59]; [61]; [64]; [68]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [79]; [83]; [85]; [92]; [94]; [97]; [100]	31
Waste elimination guidelines	[3]; [5]; [8]; [12]; [33]; [35]; [41]; [50]; [65]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [92]; [94]; [97]	15
Zero-Defects	[2]; [4]; [10]; [12]; [13]; [13]; [19]; [23]; [24]; [30]; [31]; [47]; [54]; [67]; [66]; [71]; [72]; [74]; [79]; [83]; [94]”	21

Source: Author’s Construct (2020); refer to Appendix C for reference citations.

From the word frequency distribution table above, the lean elements identified in the literature were subsequently reduced from 123 to 10 elements and ranked based on the frequency of occurrence. This is highlighted in Table 2.7. In furtherance of this research, the 10 most frequently occurring lean elements will play a vital role in the construct development as well as the hypotheses testing processes of the research.

Table 2. 7: Top 10 Ranking of Prevalent Lean Elements Gleaned from Literature Survey

Element	Rank
Continuous Improvement	1
Leadership and Direction	2
Elimination of waste	3
HRM/Respect for humanity/People management	4
Standardisation	5
Customer Relationship Management/ Customer Focus	6
Lean awareness training and education	7
Supplier Relationship Management	8
Building Lean Expert Team	9
Top Management Commitment	10

Source: Author's Construct (2020)

The ranking of the Lean Elements formed the basis for the development of constructs for the independent variable in this research.

Based on the review of the 101 frameworks which constitute a major part of this study, the following observations were made:

- None of the identified frameworks was developed entirely to suit the operational requirements of the upstream petroleum sector.

- Secondly, no known framework has been developed specifically for upstream petroleum producing organisations in Ghana.
- Inadequate industry specific analysis resulting in wrong selection of lean tools for effective problem solving (Idayu, Ali and Kasim, 2020).
- Extant literature also shows a paucity in research on LM in the Ghanaian context and most especially the upstream petroleum sector.

Therefore, this research attempts to close this gap in the upstream petroleum sector and contribute to knowledge, theory and practice by developing an industry-specific framework for Lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector. Consequently, though conceptual, the development of a framework if validated and implemented, will guide companies towards operational excellence and improve quality in a developing economy like Ghana (Perez, 2014, Douglas, 2016, Yadav et al., 2020).

2.14 Conceptual Framework for LM Application

2.14.1 Introduction

Many authors have explored different approaches adopted in the development of Lean frameworks various purposes. To enhance Lean practices across various companies and industries, the impact of guidelines/roadmap or framework cannot be overemphasized. Notwithstanding the typologies of frameworks in existence, this research draws insights from the development process of a conceptual Lean framework. A multiplicity of factors account for the choice of conceptual framework including but not limited to time and resource constraints to test and/or validate the framework. In this research, 101 case studies or frameworks have been examined purposely to identify the elements considered in developing the frameworks. However, detailed study of specific conceptual frameworks provides adequate basis on which to draw insights relevant

application in the upstream petroleum sector. Sharma and Kodali (2008), developed a Lean framework for providing guidance and direction to Indian manufacturing companies. Similarly, prolific authors in the area of Lean frameworks notably Anand and Kodali (2009; 2010a;2010b), Nordin, Deros and Wahab (2012) Mostafa, Drumrak and Soltan (2013), Sangwa and Sangwa (2018) and Jasti and Kodali (2014;2016 and 2019). However, the development of the Lean framework in this research was anchored by a combination of insights drawn from Lean frameworks developed by Jasti and Kodali (2016) and Yadav et al., (2020). The analysis and justification for the selection of these two frameworks are presented in the next section of the literature review.

2.14.2 Analysis of Frameworks underpinning the research

After an extensive review of available literature, two frameworks were identified based on a proposed criteria set out by the author as follows:

1. The proposed framework should be relevant within the context of the research
2. Identified Lean implementation drivers should reflect the key characteristics of organisations within the environment
3. It must be simple to adopt by practitioners
4. There has to be an established relationship between Lean implementation elements and/or drivers
5. The framework consists of inputs from all stakeholders

Based on the above criteria, Lean frameworks developed by Jasti and Kodali (2016), and Yadav et al., (2020) were identified as providing multidimensional perspectives as well a solid anchor to this research. Jasti and Kodali (2016), adopted an integrated approach to develop a Lean Production (LP) framework for adoption in Indian manufacturing sector. The authors conducted a

critical analysis in which collected 131 system-related frameworks and sampled 39 frameworks for analysis which culminated in the development of an integrated LP framework which consisted of 11 pillars and 89 elements. In contrast, Yadav et al., (2020), developed a Lean framework to improve Lean implementation in developing economies. They opine that whilst Lean manufacturing implementation has yielded significant success in developed economies, same cannot be said of Lean implementation in developing economies. The main objectives the authors set out to achieve include but not limited to the following “*To identify and assess the intensity of key lean manufacturing drivers that assist LMs adoption in manufacturing companies in developing economies; To develop a LM implementation framework and to analyse the inter-relationships among the drivers*”(Yadav et al.,2020 p.2).They compare, contrast and synthesize factors and/or Lean elements suitable to organizational/corporate environments that positively impact successful Lean implementation. Though the overarching aim of the authors was to identify drivers for improving Lean implementation, the underpinning significance of this framework hinges on its context which is relevant to this research. A major finding of this research show that frameworks have been developed without participation of practitioners and consultants. This finding has been corroborated by Mostafa et al., (2013). Yadav et al., developed a 3 Level framework. Level 1 sets out the objectives of the framework. Level 2 presents the major Lean improvement drivers (pillars). They identified 6 major group drivers including: Shop floor Management (SFM), Manufacturing Strategy(MS), Quality Management (QM), Manufacturing Process(MP), Supplier and Customer Management (SCM) and Workforce Management (WM). The main pillars that anchor the development of the framework fundamentally focuses on creating a culture of shop floor operations and people management. Benefits of Lean implementation which

focuses directly on the shop floor motivates employees, enhances a sense of ownership and pride of accomplishment and finally improves visual management.

Suffice, therefore, to suggest that insights generated from a combination of frameworks by Jasti and Kodali (2016) and Yadav et al., (2020), provide adequate foundation upon which this research is conducted.

2.15 Gaps in Literature

The general search, analysis and synthesis of contextually relevant literature on Lean application in the upstream petroleum industry in developing economies show a paucity of literature on the overall context of the research. Whilst pockets of available literature have fuelled the assumption that trade secrets and patent rights within a highly competitive upstream petroleum business landscape has compelled upstream operators to repulsively respond to requests for data. Consequently, a paucity in literature on Lean application in the upstream petroleum sector remains a critical reference point for future studies.

First and foremost, there is no consensus regarding the critical requirements of a framework as well as the process involved in developing an acceptable framework. This implies that Lean framework development is left to the discretion of the author. Also, notwithstanding the fact that countless Lean frameworks have developed for lean implementation across several industries, only Rachman and Ratnayake (2018), developed a framework for lean application in petroleum projects within the petroleum industry. Thus, in the analysis of 101 frameworks, one framework was

applicable in the context of the petroleum industry in general, but no framework has been developed for the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana.

Furthermore, the scope and extent of stakeholder engagement in the framework development process. Notwithstanding the established fact that frameworks are developed for different purposes, the central and/or core function of any framework is to serve as a guide and also for information (Ahlström, 1998, Anand and Kodali, 2009b, Gurumurthy and Kodali, 2010, Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2013c). Studies reveal that a comprehensive Lean framework comprises inputs from stakeholders including shop floor employees, middle managers, senior leadership, consultants/experts and academia (Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2013a).

Evidence of existing lean frameworks suggests majority of Lean frameworks are developed with less emphasis on context, size of company, and most especially individual and combined suitability for lean elements adapted in the framework development process. Less emphasis on the importance of the suitability and/or interrelationships of lean elements in the overall Lean implementation process should be a factor considered in of the framework (Jadhav, Mantha and Rane, 2014).

In the literature review process, it became evident that some researchers place less emphasis on the systemic approach to development of lean frameworks, and Lean implementation (Dombrowski, Ebentreich and Krenkel, 2016). Whereas some authors highlight the implementation process as part of the framework development process (Ogunbiyi, 2014b), others

tend to not place priority on the framework without recourse to proposed implementation methods (Jasti and Kodali, 2016).

It was also observed that the complexity of the petroleum extraction/production process especially within the context of developing economies underscore a need for more robust, rigorous and high-precision management approaches including Lean Six Sigma methodologies. Lean lays the foundation for effective implementation of Six Sigma methodology. Thus, a coherent integration of lean, Six Sigma and sustainability is by no means an invaluable contribution to sustainable petroleum operations (Chiarini, 2014, Pampanelli, Found and Bernardes, 2014, Cherrafi et al., 2016).

Framework reliability and validity measurement constitute a significant part of framework evaluation, and whilst some authors appear to gloss over these critical aspects of the usefulness of framework, others pay keen attention in the methodology adopted and thus ensure reliability and validity assessments in the framework development process (Sharma and Kodali, 2008, Jasti and Kodali, 2016).

Last but not least, the overall literature review ought to provide an overview of relevant literature upon which to situate this study, and rightly so, however, the context of the study points to a paucity of relevant literature in this research. Nonetheless, the paucity of literature among other factors informed the research design and the adoption of an exploratory sequential approach.

2.16 Chapter Conclusion

This chapter explored literature on LM and its application in different industries. Lean experts, practitioners, consultants and business leaders continuously uphold the concept as a fundamental strategy to business competitiveness. Though originally developed for the automotive and/or manufacturing sector, Lean has become a buzz word across the entire spectrum of the global business landscape of which the upstream petroleum sector plays a vital role.

The literature review process was characterized by a paucity of literature on lean application in the petroleum industry within the geographical context of the study. However, pockets of research on lean application within the mining industry, the construction industry, health, education, the hospitality and real estate were identified as relevant and provided the required relatable context. Suffice therefore, to assume without admission that if studies on lean application in the petroleum industry exist, then it would be logical to conclude that such studies may have been patented and kept away from public eye due to trade secrets and confidentiality.

Another observation relates to the paucity of literature on lean application in the upstream sector. After exploring a total of over 4975 publications from various databases, and finally selecting 101 Lean frameworks from the literature, less than 1% of authors researched on lean application within the upstream petroleum sector. Rachman and Ratnayake (2017) developed a framework for lean application in petroleum projects.

In addition, a review of 101 frameworks were reviewed spanning the last three decades. The scope of literature review reflects the inception of LM dates back about three decades ago, and the era of oil exploration and production dates back to 1859 (Fagan, 1991, Acha and Cusmano, 2007). After

analysis of the 101 frameworks, a total of 123 elements were identified as non-repetitive elements. These were further categorized based on frequency of application or frequency of occurrence.

The literature reviews also explored answers to key research questions including establishing linkages between lean management and petroleum production process, relevance of lean tools and techniques in the operations of the upstream petroleum sector. The chapter also explored lean suitability for adoption in the upstream petroleum sector and most importantly, identifying lean waste associated with the upstream petroleum operations. Last but not least, the literature review identified critical success factors relevant to the upstream sector.

CHAPTER THREE

CONTEXT OF THE STUDY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter focuses on contextual issues related to the research. The chapter starts with profiling Ghana which constitutes the case study of this research, provides information on lean practices that are conducted in Ghana based on published studies, an overview of the global petroleum industry as well as the Ghanaian petroleum industry.

3.1 Profile of Ghana

Ghana is located on the West African coast of the Gulf of Guinea in Africa, south of the Sahara Desert and sharing a border to the west with Cote d'Ivoire, to the east with Togo and to the north with Burkina Faso. Ghana gained its independence from British rule on 6th March, 1957 and became a democratic republic. Ghana is a tropical country with favourable weather and sunshine throughout the year and with peaceful socio-political climate which makes it a favourable travel destination (GTA, 2019).

Ghana's current population stands at 30.42 million (GSS, 2019), spread across a land area of 238,538 km, made up of sixteen (16) regions and 216 districts. Although English is the official language, there are over 100 dialects spoken in Ghana with the common ones being Akan, Ga, Ewe (in the southern part) and Dagbane and Hausa (in the northern part). About 65% of Ghana's population lives in the rural areas and despite the upgrade in 2011 to a lower middle-income economy status (KPMG, 2012), poverty is still a huge phenomenon in rural Ghana and even in the peri-urban centres. More so, in recent times, urban poverty is on the increase due to a general growth in population, coupled with rural-urban migration (Ewusi, 2013).

In addition, there is a disparity in the distribution of Ghana’s population, income, and mineral resources, which are largely concentrated in the southern half of the country (Foster and Pushak, 2011) and even more so in the urban locations of the southern half. A ray of hope, though, for Ghana now is its recent oil discovery, for which reason the nation is expected to raise additional public funding from increased tax receipts.

Figure 3. 1: The Map of Ghana

Source: Ghana Statistical Service, 2020

3.2 Lean Practices in Ghana

Although there is a paucity of lean literature in Ghana, a number of relevant studies in the field of Lean Manufacturing have been carried in different sectors in Ghana. Carter (2012) conducted a study to identify the “application of Lean manufacturing techniques to improve clinical operations at Komfo Anokye Teaching Hospital (KATH). Similarly, Osumanu et al (2018), investigated the relationship between lean adoption and housing finance in Ghana. The study was conducted to provide a description of the factors that affect house financing within the context of Ghana and provide lean strategies for reducing construction cost. The findings of the study support the hypothesis that lean adoption leads to performance efficiency, cost control and waste elimination. Lean construction within the Ghanaian construction industry leads to waste elimination and improvement in productivity. The study assessed perceptions of Ghanaian construction practitioners of lean construction and identified the level of knowledge in the construction industry (Ayarkwa et al., 2012).

Furthermore, Boateng-Okrah and Fening (2012) conducted a study to ascertain the level at which total quality management (TQM) practices have been implemented in a mining company in Ghana. Statistical analyses were conducted to calculate percentage distributions and to determine the level of TQM implementation. The paper reveals that the company passed through the introductory stage of the TQM training of top and middle level management and is now at the point of transferring knowledge to the rest of the employees in the company.” Also, Ofori-Kuragu et al. (2016) explored “the development of a set of critical success factors (CSFs) for Ghanaian contractors. Eight (8) CSFs were identified for Ghanaian contractors. These were; quality and zero defects culture, organizational design, work culture and work environment, client satisfaction, strategy, leadership, measurement, analysis of information and knowledge management and

implementation of lean principles (Ofori-Kuragu et al., 2016). Abor (2013) examined the healthcare waste management practices of selected hospitals in Ghana. The study adopted a multiple case approach, using two public and two private hospitals. Findings indicated that both public hospitals and one private hospital have waste management policies. Public and private hospitals have waste management plans and waste management teams. Public hospitals were found to generate more waste than the private hospitals. Graham et al. (2014) examined the role management plays in the implementation of TQM programme in Ghanaian printing firms. The study established that organizational performance (OP) is not significantly influenced by the level of commitment of top management in a printing organization. Rather OP is greatly influenced and determined by leadership styles of management and the quality policy which guides printing operations” (Graham et al., 2014).

Mensah et al., (2012) identified critical success factors and challenges of total quality management (TQM) implementation and proposed a model for successful implementation in Ghana. Top management commitment, empowerment and involvement of employees, resource availability, competition and increased customer awareness were found to be critical factors for successful TQM implementation.

Srofenyoh et al., (2016) investigated the performance of a continuous quality improvement collaborations at the Ridge Regional Hospital, Accra, Ghana. This study focused on reducing maternal and neonatal deaths (Srofenyoh et al., 2016). Furthermore, Alhassan et. al (2013) researched on “indicators of health worker motivation, quality care and patient safety in Ghana. The study identified interventions at the health worker level that contributed to quality

improvement in healthcare facilities in Ghana. One of the main findings in this research was that majority of health facilities lacked evidence of quality and safety. However, employee motivation appeared low in public health facilities compared to private facilities. Last but not least, Fening (2008) conducted a research into the relationship between quality management practices and SME performance in Ghana. It found that quality management practices improve organizational performance in both large and small businesses in any part of the world. The foregone discourse presents a summary of lean research in the Ghanaian context. It is evident from the summary that some research across industries including health, mining, SMEs, construction and printing. However, no known research has been conducted on lean application in the petroleum industry in Ghana and this further reinforces the rationale for this research.

3.3 An Overview of Ghana's Petroleum Industry

Located within the West Coast of Africa, Ghana has a population of approximately of 30 million people, and bordered “to the West, North, and East by Cote d'Ivoire, Burkina Faso, and Togo, and to the South by the Gulf of Guinea (Aratuo, 2012). It spans a region of 238,500 square kilometres and endowed with natural resources including, for example, gold, diamond, timber, bauxite and manganese” (Kusi-Sarpong et al., 2016). Ghana has become a politically stable democracy with some level of peace, and making great strides in its quest to become the economic hub of the West African sub-region.

Also, Ghana is seen as a successful democracy in the African context (Gyimah-Boadi and Kwasi Prempeh, 2012; Gyampo, 2011) “with a long history of mineral extraction and petroleum exploration. Large-scale gold mining dates back to the last quarter of the 19th century (Hilson, 2002), while oil exploration dates back to 1896 (Chitor, 2012), albeit on a limited scale. Oil and

gas exploration was largely hampered by the limited technology available at the time (Donyinah, 2016; McCaskie, 2008). The country's First Oil was drilled in 2010 from the Jubilee Phase I field, three years after commercial quantities of crude was discovered. A number of other discoveries were made after this (Asafu Adjaye, 2012; Obeng-Odoom, 2014). Several laws regulate oil and gas activities in Ghana, including those aimed at ensuring transparency, accountability, environmental sustainability and trickle-down of rents" (Ablo, 2015).

Figure 3. 2: The Voltaian Basin

Source: GNPC (2020) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

Notably, PNDC Law 84 (The Petroleum Exploration and Production Law) "sets out the policy framework and outlines the role of the Ministry of Energy. The Ghana National Petroleum Corporation Law (GNPC) or PNDC Law 64 empowers the national oil company, GNPC, to carry out petroleum exploration and production, and to enter into joint ventures and production-sharing

agreements on behalf of the government (Ablo, 2015). In 2011, the Petroleum Commission (PC) of Ghana was established following implementation of the Petroleum Commission Act, 821. It regulates the upstream oil and gas industry, processes applications and grants permits for petroleum related activities. It also set up a Local Content Committee to promote local participation. The Petroleum Revenue Management Act (Act 815), 2011, provides a framework for mobilizing, allocating and managing petroleum revenues. The focus of this article, however, is on the Petroleum (Local Content and Local Participation) Regulations (L.I.2204), 2013, which set out the guidelines for local participation” (Ablo, 2015).

Figure 3. 3: List of Right holders and Partners of Ghana's Oilfields

No.	Contract Area	Current Partners	Effective Date	Exploration Term	Current Period (Phase) /Activity	Development & Production End date
1	West Cape Three Points	Kosmos Energy Ghana HC Anadarko WCTP Company Tullow Ghana Ltd Ghana National Petroleum Corporation Sabre Oil & Gas Holdings Ltd (PetroSA)	13-Jul-2004	7yrs	Production (Jubilee) PoD Submitted (Greater Jubilee)	12-Jul-2034
2	Saltpond Oil and Gas Field	Saltpond Offshore Producing Co. Ltd Ghana National Petroleum Corporation	30-Jul-2004	N/A	Processes underway for Decommissioning	29-Jul-2024
3	Offshore Cape Three Points	ENI Ghana Exploration and Production Ltd. Vitol Upstream Ghana Ltd Ghana National Petroleum Corporation	15-Mar-2006	7yrs	Development	14-Mar-2036
4	Deepwater Tano	Tullow Ghana Ltd Anadarko WCTP Company Kosmos Energy Ghana HC Ghana National Petroleum Corporation Sabre Oil & Gas Holdings	19-Jul-2006	7yrs	Production (Jubilee) Development (TEN)	18-Jul-2036
5	Deepwater Tano-Cape Three Points	HESS Exploration Ghana Ltd Ghana National Petroleum Corporation	19-Jul-2006	7yrs	Appraisal Phase	18-Jul-2036
6	East Cape Three Points	Cola Natural Resources Limited Medea Development Ltd holds Ghana National Petroleum Corporation	12-Apr-2013	7yrs	Initial Exploration Phase (Seismic Data Processing and Interpretation)	11-Apr-2043
7	South Deepwater Tano	AGM Petroleum Ghana Limited GNPC Exploration & Production	12-Apr-2013	7yrs	Exploration (Seismic data	11-Apr-2038

		Company Ghana National Petroleum Corporation Ltd			acquisition, processing and interpretation)	
8	Expanded Shallow Water Tano Block	ERIN (Formerly CAMAC) Base Energy GNPC Exploration and Production Company GNPC	27-Mar-2014	6.5yrs	Initial Exploration (G&G Studies)	26-Mar-2039
9	Central Tano Block	AMNI International Development Company GNPC	27-Mar-2014	6yrs	Initial Exploration (G&G Studies)	26-Mar-2039
10	South West Saltpond Block	BRITANNIA-U Ghana Limited Hills Oil GNPC	17-Jul-2014	7yrs	Initial Exploration	16-Jul-2039
11	South-West Tano Block	Heritage Blue Star GNPC Exploration and Production Company GNPC	17-Jul-2014	6yrs	Initial Exploration	16-Jul-2039
12	East Keta Block	Heritage Blue Star GNPC Exploration and Production Company GNPC	17-Jul-2014	7yrs	Exploration	16-Jul-2039
13	South-West Cape Three Points Block	A-Z Petroleum Products Ghana Limited ECO Atlantic Oil & Gas Limited GNPC Exploration and Production Co. Ltd PG GNPC	18-Jul-2014	6.5yrs	Initial Exploration (G&G Studies)	17-Jul-2039
14	Offshore Cape Three Points South Block	UB Resources Limited Houston Drilling Management And Royalgate Ghana Limited Ghana National Petroleum Corporation	18-Jul-2014	7yrs	Initial Exploration	17-Jul-2039
15	Shallow Water Cape Three Points Block	Sahara Energy Fields Sapholda Ghana National Petroleum Corporation	18-Jul-2014	7yrs	Initial Exploration	17-Jul-2039

Source: GNPC (2020)

3.4 Governance Structure of the Upstream Petroleum Sector in Ghana

Information from the GNPC indicates that the number of sedimentary basins bearing oil and gas is four (4) in Ghana; made up of the Accra-Keta, Saltpond, Tano and Voltaian Basins with the Tano Basin noted to include the Cape Three Points Sub-basin (GNPC, 2014). The Accra-Keta, Saltpond and Tano are offshore basins while the Voltaian is an onshore basin (Figure 3.4 below).

Figure 3. 4: Sedimentary Basins of Ghana

Source: GNPC (2014) Content redacted due to copyright restrictions.

As depicted in Figures 2 and 3, “these four basins are located both offshore and inland. The offshore basins cover approximately 60,000 square kilometres, while the Voltaian Basin, which is the only inland basin, 103,600 square kilometres, constituting the biggest oil and gas sedimentary basin in Ghana (GNPC, 2014). Foreign petroleum companies operating within these offshore and onshore sedimentary basins have been allocated quotas to explore, develop, and produce oil and gas. These sedimentary basins have been subdivided into blocks that have been allocated to multinational petroleum companies for producing oil and gas (GNPC, 2014). While offshore sedimentary basins have been assigned to operators, the onshore Voltaian Basin is yet to be assigned to operators.

The emergence of Ghana's upstream petroleum sector dates back to 1896 when hydrocarbon exploration began in the western region of Ghana following the discovery by explorers of inland petroleum seepages. Between 1896 and 1957, shallow exploration wildcat drilling was conducted in 21 unproven areas. Of these areas, most of the shallow wells contained hydrocarbons (GNPC, 2014). Within the offshore environment, Ghana's first commercial well was drilled at Saltpond Basin in 1970. This well subsequently yielded commercial quantities of oil and gas, peaking at 4,800 barrels of oil per day (bopd) in 1978 (GNPC, 2014). From 1978 up to 2007, when significant quantities of oil and gas were discovered, Ghana's upstream petroleum sector was quiescent. In 2007, the discovery of substantial deposits of oil and gas at the Jubilee field led to oil production that reached a significant scale in November 2010 (GNPC, 2014). The successful launching of oil extraction in the Jubilee field, which produces an average of 110,000 bopd, attracted other multinational petroleum companies to Ghana, resulting in a vibrant upstream oil and gas industry. To increase local participation in the upstream petroleum industry, L.I. 2204 was ratified in 2013."

3.5 The Ghana Upstream Regulatory Framework

In 2007, Ghana discovered oil in commercial quantities (Overa, 2016), in addition to existing natural resources, which constitute an essential component of national development. As global product in demand, petroleum industry is undoubtedly the cash cow of every vibrant economy with huge potential to generate revenue for national development if proper management measures are put in place. However, prior studies posit that effective management, corruption and lack of vision constitute the bane of African leadership (Phillips, Hailwood and Brooks, 2016; Siakwah, 2017; Kojo Stephens, 2019). Ghana like all other sub-Saharan African countries, "celebrated the discovery of oil from the Jubilee Field in 2007 (Banda, 2019). While many rejoiced at the

discovery with euphoria, others expressed scepticism and advised against plodding the way of immediate neighbours, Nigeria (Phillips et al, 2016).

Cocoa has been a significant backbone of the economic Gross Domestic Product (GDP) through farming that records for 37 percent of GDP (Aratuo, 2012). The Ghana National Petroleum Corporation Act, 1983 (PNDCL.64), The Petroleum (Exploration and Production) Act, 1984 (PNDCL.84), and The Petroleum Income Tax, 1987 (PNDCL.188). The Ghana National Petroleum Corporation (GNPC) has been and continuous to assume crucial leadership in the oil industry. It was set up (GNPC Act, 1983) to advance research and development of the oil resource. For now, the GNPC does not have adequate expertise and resources to manage petroleum sector. Consequently it has entered into joint venture-ship with other petroleum companies including, Kosmos, Tullow, Anadarko, and ENI (Aratuo, 2012). The two different laws with significant impact on the oil and gas industry are the Environmental Protection Agency Act, 1994 (Act 490), and the Ghana Maritime Authority Act, 2002 (Act 630).

The Petroleum Revenue Management Bill (PRMB) and the Petroleum Commission Bill (PCB) have been passed by Parliament and assented by the President into the Petroleum Revenue Management Act (PRMA), 2011, Act 815 and Petroleum Commission Act (PCA), 2011, Act 821 respectively (Aratuo, 2012). In addition, the Petroleum Exploration and Production Bill (2010) and the Local Content and Local Participation Bill together contribute to local participation.

The Petroleum Exploration and Production Bill (2010) isn't completely new, since it is partly a revised version of the Petroleum Exploration and Production Law, (PNDCL 84). In 1984, the

National Oil and Gas Policy was passed as a Legislative Instrument to the Petroleum Exploration and Production Act.

Ghana National Petroleum Corporation undertakes due diligence on every single organization, assess funding, specialized capacity and reputation, proposed work program and spending plan. A comprehensive report with proposals is then submitted to the Minister of Energy.

A Standing Petroleum Agreement Negotiations Team, consisting of representations from the Ministry of Energy, GNPC, the Attorney-General's Department and Internal Revenue Service assesses all petroleum agreements. Draft Petroleum Agreements submitted to the Minister and sent to Cabinet for approval” (Aratuo, 2012).

3.5.1 Overview of the Petroleum Regulations 2013 (L.I. 2204)

The Local content and local participation law (L.I.2204) sets out operational requirements for engaging in upstream petroleum operations in Ghana with specific emphasis on local involvement of both talent development and deployment as well as local business involvement. The specific objectives outlined in L.I. 2204 include: *“Promote and maximize value addition and job creation through the use of local expertise; goods and services, businesses and financing in the petroleum industry; develop local capacities in the petroleum industry value chain through education, skills transfer and expertise development, transfer of technology and know-how and active research and development programmes; achieve the minimum local employment level and in-country spend for the provision of the goods and services in the petroleum industry value chain; increase the capability and international competitiveness of domestic businesses; create petroleum and related supportive industries that will sustain economic development; achieve and maintain a degree of*

control for Ghanaians over development initiatives for local stakeholders; provide for a robust and transparent monitoring and reporting system to ensure delivery of local content policy objectives” (L.I 2204, 2013, p.4).

The local content law calls for prioritizing “the use of Ghanaian-produced goods and services (Regulation 9a). It also calls for the sector to use Ghanaian services companies (Regulation 11 and Regulation 12), and affords them protection in the bidding process: no company can be disqualified, following evaluations, solely on the grounds of it not being the lowest financial bidder. A contract, rather, can be awarded to a qualified Ghanaian company if its value does not exceed 10% of the value of the lowest bid (Regulation 12 (3))” (Ablo, 2015).

CHAPTER FOUR

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.0 Introduction

This chapter sets out the strategies adopted in the data collection process, and discusses how data collected has been analysed and interpreted. As a precursor to the methodology anchored by the research onion proposed by Sanders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), different research philosophies have been discussed relative to their suitability for adoption in this research. Some of these philosophies include; positivism, realism, interpretivism, objectivism...and pragmatism (Plowright, 2011; Sanders et al., 2012; Creswell, 2015). Whilst acknowledging the significance of each research philosophy highlighted herein, it is important to state that a pragmatists paradigm is deemed to be most appropriate in this research. Justification for the choice of pragmatism as the most appropriate research paradigm is presented later in this chapter.

Cooper and Schindler (2006) define research as any organised inquiry carried out to identify a problem, and provide information for solving that problem. Hanke (2009) buttressed this point and further identified two components of a good research including “*good ideas and good research design*” (Hanke, 2009 p.10).

For some researchers, the core issue as far as methodologies are concerned is that the choice of the most appropriate research design (Hanke, 2009; Creswell, 2015), and the selection of a methodology is based on the research problem and stated research questions (Yin, 2015; Saunders et al., 2012). “Methodology is the general framework that guides the conduct of any research, and in the absence of sound methodology, research loses its focus and its credibility” (Hanke, 2009;

Creswell, 2015). It encompasses the guiding philosophy upon which the research is anchored. Research methodology has a crucial role in any kind of management research as long as the research purports to establish some level of credence. Thus, a particular methodology can only be more or less useful (Silverman, 2001) on the basis of the research being carried out. To this end, Nachamias and Frankfort-Nachamias (1996) argue “for instance that, methodologies are considered to be systems of explicit rules upon which research is based, and against which claims for knowledge are evaluated. Therefore, conducting any type of research should be governed by a well-defined research methodology based on scientific principles.” The chapter further outlines the strategies adopted on the field through which primary data was collected and discusses how the data collected was analysed and interpreted. Also, the methodology chapter explains the approaches chosen and how it would impact on the anticipated outcome (Creswell, 2014). Saunders et al. (2012) proposed the research onion approach as a methodological process researcher can adopt to achieve desired research objectives. Thus, this research adapted the research onion approach put forward by Sanders et al. as captured in Figure 4.1 below:

Figure 4. 1: The Research Onion

Source: Saunders et al. (2012)

4.1 Research Position

The ontological perspective considered in positioning this research draws on a combination of objectivism and subjectivism, whilst an epistemology of pragmatism emerged as the most appropriate philosophy underpinning all other subthemes. The research approach combines both the deductive and inductive approaches with phenomenology as the research strategy, and mixed methods which has become increasingly popular (Doyle, Brady and Byrne, 2016). Advocates of mixed methods propose pragmatism as a preferred research paradigm for social research, and rightly so, pragmatism does not only disrupt the assumptions of older approaches, but emphasizes practicality rather than philosophical assumptions (Morgan, 2014, Kaushik and Walsh, 2019), hence, its suitability for this research which explores Lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector. The time horizon is cross-sectional with data collection using semi-structured interviews and questionnaires. Finally, the data reduction and analysis involved thematic analysis

as well as structural equation modelling (Figure 4.2 below). The ensuing sections present in detail, the various alternatives available and the justification for the research position.

Figure 4. 2: Research Position

Source: Cano *et al.*, (2016)

4.2 Research Philosophy and Paradigm

Research is “underpinned by key philosophical perspectives which seek to regulate and explain how a researcher perceives the world and reality” (Saunders et al., 2012; Gray, 2013; Saunders and Bezzina, 2015). Paradigms are a “*set of basic and taken-for-granted assumptions which underwrite the frame of reference, mode of theorizing, and ways of working in which a group operates*” (Saunders et al., 2012 p.132). The chosen philosophical position influenced by the researcher’s worldview constitute the guidepost which enables the researcher to define the ‘why’ and the ‘how’ of the research (Holden and Lynch, 2004). Situated in the context of management research (Saunders et al., 2012), this research draws from the epistemological perspectives that “*True theories and knowledge are those that enable successful action*” (Saunders et al., 2012 p.137), and with a practical knowledge perspective of “*problem solving and informed future practice as contribution*” (Saunders et al., 2012 p.137). Based on multi-factorial analysis of the nature of this research, aims and objectives, and theoretical underpinning, and influenced by researcher worldview, pragmatism as a research paradigm emerged as the most appropriate as it focuses on enhancing organizational practice (Saunders et al., 2012; Creswell, 2015). Nonetheless, to illuminate perspectives and provide further justification for choice of philosophy, brief descriptive discourse on other philosophies including ontological, epistemological, methodological and axiological concepts (Hancke, 2009).

4.2.1 Ontology

Ontology examines the nature and structure of reality (Guarino, Oberle and Staab, 2009). It is a philosophical assumption concerned with reality, and which influences the perspectives of researchers’ worldview (Saunders et al., 2012). As a philosophy, ontology is concerned with the study of the nature of social being and reality (Schwandt, 2007; Saunders et al., 2012). It explores

questions such as what existence is and what it means to say that an object exists. Ontology focuses on understanding how a given social reality came to being (Given, 2008). It therefore seeks to inquire about the nature of what it is that the researcher seeks to learn. It is about the assumptions researchers hold about the way the social world operates (Creswell, 2015).”

4.2.2 Epistemology

Epistemology is perceived as “the theory of the nature of knowledge, its components, sources, limits and justification (Dawson, 2009). Akin to other research philosophies, the epistemological stance seeks to explore the centrality of the nature and origins of scientific knowledge(Wicks and Freeman, 1998, Dinsmore, 2017, Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). The epistemological debate around worldviews including but not limited to positivism, relativism, constructivism and realism fundamentally paved the way for researchers who focused on pragmatic studies to consider the relevance of organisational research by *avoiding entrenched epistemological distinctions that marginalize ethics and make research less useful*(Wicks and Freeman, 1998). Thus, the epistemological considerations in this research is particularly concerned with what kind of knowledge is possible and applicable, how can we establish knowledge of these things – and what criteria exists for deciding when knowledge is both adequate and legitimate(Kaushik and Walsh, 2019), when ontological assumptions are concerned with the nature of social reality. These assumptions make claims about what kinds of social phenomena do or can exist, the condition for their existence, and the ways in which they are related (Blaikie, 2010).

Methodology seeks to define the process adopted to conduct research, within the context of a particular paradigm (Wahyuni, 2012). According to Creswell (2015), methodology outlines the research process, the origin, the philosophy, interpretation and dissemination of results. The latter

can be contrasted from a research method which refers to a set of specific tools and techniques used to gather and analyse data specified by the research methodology (Sarantakos, 2012; Blaikie, 2010). In view of existing philosophies many researchers commonly refer to, or dominant paradigms that reflect major theoretical directions, positivism, and pragmatism constitute are key. “Saunders et al., (2012) argue that research is anchored on a specific view of reality espoused by the researcher. These views influence the research strategy and methods chosen to investigate a phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2012). This view of reality is referred to as the “Worldview”, which simply refers to the belief systems that guide one’s action (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Creswell, 20014). Some of the commonly accepted worldviews in literature include Positivism, Interpretivism, Social Constructivism and Pragmatism. These are further discussed in subsequent sections within the context of this research.

4.2.3 The Positivist Worldview

The positivist approach is primarily aligned with quantitative research approach, while relativism which is the direct opposite of positivism is heavily focused on qualitative research approach (Saunders et al., 2012; Creswell, 2015). Positivism postulate “that social entities usually exist in reality external to social actors, whilst the subjectivism postulates that social phenomena are the results of interactions between social actors and their existence” (Saunders et al., 2012).

Denscombe (2008), perceived positivism as an “approach to social science research that seeks to apply the natural science model of research to investigations of social phenomena and explanations of the social world. Positivist researchers view the world with a one-way mirror ‘, and the researcher is an undeniable character (Anderson, 1986; Healy and Perry, 2000). Accordingly,

positivists separate themselves from the world they study; while researchers in constructivism and critical theory paradigms believe they have to participate in the real world to better understand the investigations” (Healy and Perry, 2000). The primary data collection methods in the context of research which adopts positivists approach are resigned to experiments and surveys (Christie, 2000). Available literature indicate that three paradigms appear “*more suitable for exploring complex social phenomena that require working with people and real-life experiences*” (Christie, 2000). “*In contrast, Healy and Perry (2000) argue that positivism is not suitable when the research involves humans and their real-life experiences*”. Thus, cognisant of the research objectives guiding the conduct of this research, coupled with the above explanation implies that pure positivism alone is not suitable for this research.

Extant literature posit that Auguste Comte founded positivism in his work ‘*Course of Positive Philosophy*’ (Remenyi et al., 1998). “*This school of thought believes that a positivist researcher is completely objective, impartial observer of a tangible social reality*”. The positivist paradigm is based on the following assumptions that first, the world is external and objective, with the observer being independent; and secondly, a positivist research approach is associated with specificity and hypotheses testing using appropriate numerical approaches and supported with large data/samples in order to establish objectivity (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2012). These assumptions underscore the claim that positivists generally believe reality is objectively established and can be described by measurable properties which are independent of the researcher and his/her instruments. Generally, positivists research aim at testing theory, in an attempt to increase the chances of extrapolating results about a phenomena being studied (Myers, 2013). According to Remenyi et al., (1998), the basic principle of positivists research is the supposition that “*the*

researcher is independent of and neither affects nor is affected by the subject of the research". In addition, Gill and Johnson (2010), argue that "the positivist research emphasizes on highly structured methodology to facilitate replication and quantifiable observations which leads to statistical analysis". This scientific view of reality restricts knowledge to what can be observed and measured, and therefore ignores facts such as human thoughts and emotions that could not be scientifically measured (Bhattacharjee, 2012). Quantitative research methods are therefore associated with positivism (Styles and Seymour, 2006). The positivism allows for the testing of hypotheses and presents an objective perspective of the research.

4.2.4 The Interpretivist Worldview

Interpretivism describes "an ontology in which social reality is construed as the process through which social actors create and explain phenomenon (Blaikie, 1993). Denzen and Lincoln (2003) asserted that interpretivism is essentially a research paradigm that consists of the search for an explanation of the existence of multiple realities. Interpretivism thus entails the mind-set that phenomenon cannot be viewed as a single reality, and that social actors have a role to play in giving meaning to reality. Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2009) in trying to expand on the meaning of interpretivism stated that interpretivists argue that there are differences between subject matters in the natural and social sciences, and as a result, situations are interpreted differently by individuals and groups. People tend to interpret situations based on their expectations, experiences and memories. Qualitative researchers often tend to adopt this paradigm" (Gray, 2013). The main focus of an interpretivist worldview in research is not about generalisability, because life is ever so dynamic (Saunders et al., 2012), and how people interpret life issues depends on their perspective. When researchers continuously strive to interpret what they see, hear, and understand,

(Creswell, 2014), they are embarking on a process of theory formulation through adoption of interpretive methods (Bhattacharjee, 2012).

4.2.5 Constructivism

Constructivism as a research paradigm assumes “relativist ontology, a subjectivist epistemology, and a naturalistic set of methodological procedures, as stated by Denzin and Lincoln (2003). Constructivism suggests that —truth is a particular belief system held in a particular context, and it is interested in the values which underpin the findings (Healy and Perry, 2000). Therefore, it is an inductive process. Data collection under the constructivist paradigm depends mainly on the interaction between the researcher and interviewee so that the researcher has to be a passionate participant ‘during the field work or data collection process (Guba and Lincoln, 1994).’”

4.2.6 Realism

In exploring research philosophies or paradigms that can shape a particular study, realism as a research paradigm cannot be overlooked. Studies indicate that realism combines aspects from both positivism and constructivism (Healy and Perry, 2000; Dummet, 1982). Realism tend to suggest that “*what you see is what you get; what we experience through our senses portrays the world accurately*” (Saunders et al., 2012 p.138). Stated differently, realism opines that an actual social phenomenon can be determined with its imperfection (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Godfrey and Hill, 1995). Realism is also known as post-positivism (Denzin and Lincoln, 1994) or neo-post positivism (Miles and Huberman, 1994). Saunders et al., (2012) argue that the position of realists that the social world is constantly changing is *in tandem* with the purpose of management research. “In the context of this research, a combination of philosophical perspectives provides a holistic approach to address the research problem identified.

4.2.7 The Pragmatist Worldview

According to Saunders et al., (2012), proponents and supporters of pragmatism opine that concepts are described as relevant only when they support action(s). A comprehensive appreciation of the aforementioned philosophies fundamentally underpins the choice of an appropriate research paradigm.

Extant Literature indicate that advocates of mixed methods propose pragmatism as a preferred paradigm (Morgan, 2014). Though not entirely new, pragmatism has been linked to mixed methods research which has increased awareness. Upon critical evaluation of various paradigms discussed earlier, the epistemology of pragmatism as a paradigm was deemed most appropriate for this research for practical reasons (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). The overarching rationale to adopt pragmatism in this research is in three-fold; first, pragmatism focuses on the practical relevance of the research. Secondly, the nature of the research objectives consisting of both qualitative and quantitative attributes fundamentally informed the decision adopt a mixed methods approach, and thirdly, pragmatism and mixed methods research function *in tandem*. Notwithstanding the purpose of this research to develop a conceptual framework, results, findings and recommendations emerging from this process should reflect pragmatists views.

Gray (2013) averred that the nature of a research question can “*determine the kind of philosophical assumptions that may be selected to underpin a research work*”. And whilst Saunders et al (2012) submit that pragmatists hold the view that there are different ways to conduct research in terms of epistemology, ontology and axiology, Morgan (2014) argue that pragmatism is not only a paradigm which indicates practicality, but can serve as a philosophy regardless of whether a research adopts a qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods approach. “Pragmatism as an

alternative paradigm, sidestep issues of truth and reality, but accepts philosophically, that there are singular and multiple realities that are open to empirical inquiry and orients itself toward solving practical problems in the real world (Morgan, 2007;2014; Creswell and Clark, 2017; Kaushik, 2019). In that sense, pragmatism allows the researcher to be free of constraints imposed by the forced choice dichotomy between post positivism and constructivism (Creswell and Clark, 2017) and researchers do not have to be the prisoner of a particular [research] method or technique” (Robson, 1993; Morgan, 2014).

Based on critical evaluation of the research problem, the objectives and research questions that underpin the conduct of this research, there was adequate justification to adopt pragmatism as the most appropriate paradigm guiding the conduct of this research. The overarching reason for this choice is not only the fact that pragmatism strives to reconcile objective and subjective elements, but the emphasis of seeking practical and/or actionable knowledge (Saunders et al., 2012), It is important to reiterate that pragmatism is the choice of the study because it did not limit the researcher in conducting the study based on a particular technique; qualitative, quantitative or mixed methods (Morgan, 2007; 2014). This philosophy allows the researcher to conduct the study from both objective and subjective perspectives because the study combines both quantitative and qualitative objectives, which are deeply rooted and embraced by the pragmatist approach. In addition, pragmatism as a research paradigm places emphasis on the concept of applicability (Morgan, 2007; Scott and Briggs, 2009; Morgan, 2014; Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). The adoption of a mixed methods approach underpinned by a pragmatist worldview enables this research to comprehensively explore phenomena including the extent to which Lean concept is applicable or can be improved in the upstream petroleum sector (Morgan, 2007; Scott and Briggs, 2009;

Morgan, 2014). Probably, the best way to justifiably summarise the rationale for adopting a pragmatist paradigm is aptly articulated by Saunders et al. who stated that ... "*pragmatist research starts with a problem, and aims to contribute practical solutions that inform future practice*" (Saunders et al., 2012 p.143).

4.3 Research Approach (Deductive and Inductive)

In knowledge inquiry, researchers adopt inductive, deductive or a combination of both inquiry approaches. Inductive inquiry involves moving from specifics to generalization and vice versa is true for deductive inquiry in which case the researcher moves from generalisations to specifics (Hyde, 2000). This research employs a combination of both deductive and inductive approaches *in tandem* with pragmatism and mixed methods approaches. Further discussions on the two approaches to assess their suitability in different studies, and justification for a specific choice for this study.

4.3.1 Inductive Approach

Inductive reasoning starts from a point where a researcher observes specific instances, leading to generalisations about a phenomenon under investigation. This process perceived as a theory building process (Hyde, 2000). It is sometimes called a "bottom up" approach (Saunders et al.,2012). Data collected is analysed and becomes the basis for informed theory development. Though inductive inquiry seem most appropriate for qualitative research, it is however not exclusive as qualitative research can assume both inductive and deductive approaches (Theophilus, 2018). In this research, the formulation of the research objectives, the research questions partly could be addressed by inductive approach but not sufficient to comprehensively address research objectives and hence the need to adopt an alternative and integrated approach.

4.3.2 Deductive Approach

Cooper and Schindler (2006) argue that deductive approach focuses on testing a formulated research hypotheses supported by an appropriate research strategy. In a “deductive research, a theory and hypothesis are developed and a research strategy designed to test the hypothesis” (Saunders et al., 2012). The purist hypothetical-deductive perspective ... “*emphasizes universal laws of cause and effect on an explanatory framework which assumes a realist ontology; that is, that reality consists of a world of objectively defined facts*” (Henwood et al., 1993). In line with the deductivist approach, ... “with an abstract, logical relationship among concepts then move towards concrete empirical evidence” (Neuman, 1997). “Thus in deductivist research there is a well-established role for existing theory since it informs the development of hypotheses, the choice of variables, and the resultant measures which researchers intend to use. Within this approach the researcher formulates a particular theoretical framework and then sets about testing it. Deductive reasoning is narrower in nature and is concerned with testing or confirming hypotheses” (Saunders et al., 2012). Based on the foregone discourse on deductive reasoning, a combination of inductive and deductive approaches will effectively address both the research problem and the objectives of this research.

4.4 Research Methods

Quantitative, “qualitative and mixed methods research have been discussed as the most popular research approaches in management research (Kent, 2007; Malhotra, 2008; Saunders et al., 2012; Creswell, 2015; Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). These three research approaches have their respective qualities and are addressed within the context of this research which explores the phenomenon of Lean application in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana.

4.4.1 Quantitative Research

Quantitative research is typically viewed as the research approach that concerns itself with the use of formal and predetermined responses in a bid to understand social reality (Hair, Anderson, Babin and Black, 2010; Creswell, 2015). Quantitative researchers prefer structured questionnaires and believe that measuring constructs and applying them in a research framework offers a greater opportunity for generalisation (Davis, 2000). The quantitative approach is rooted in the philosophy of rationalism and follows a rigid, structured and pre-determined set of procedures to explore and aims to quantify the extent of variation in a phenomenon; emphasises the measurement of variables and the objectivity of the processes, believes in substantiation on the basis of large sample size” (Kumar, 2019).

4.4.2 Qualitative Research

Qualitative research approach on the other hand “concerns itself with the interpretation of a phenomenon through narratives. According to Hair et al., (2010) qualitative research is perceived as “the collection of data in the form of text or images using open-ended questions, observations or ‘found’ data. Qualitative research is used by researchers to explain social phenomena, enabling researchers to understand the world around them and how things work” (Hancock, 1998). Flick (2007) “explains that the qualitative research approach is a distinctive way to describe an alternative to the ‘quantitative research’ and was coined against the background of a critique of the latter and especially the development it had taken in the 1960s and 1970s. However, qualitative research has a long history in many disciplines, where social science research in general began with approaches that would now be summarized under qualitative research. Today, the label ‘qualitative research’ is used as an umbrella term for a series of approaches to research in the social

sciences.” According to Myers (2013, p.8), “the qualitative research approach was developed in the social sciences to enable researchers study social and cultural phenomena. Some of the known qualitative approaches are: action research, case study research, grounded theory, and ethnography. Qualitative data sources include observation and participant observation (fieldwork), interviews and questionnaires, documents and texts, and the researcher’s impressions and reactions. Generally, qualitative research methodology is designed to help researchers to understand people and the social and cultural contexts within which they live (Blaikie, 2010). The kinds of data generated are mostly a record of what people have said. In qualitative research, methods of in-depth interviews or focus groups are usually used and strive to explore attitudes, behaviour and experiences of respondents. Though sample size for qualitative research tend to be relatively smaller compared to quantitative, research, the time spent with one participant tend to be longer than in quantitative data collection process (Creswell, 2014). Qualitative research normally emphasizes on the relationship between contextualized elements in relation to a relatively few cases. In qualitative research, emphasis is on understanding the social reality on the basis of how the participants interprets reality in a particular environment. The ordinary flow of the steps in the qualitative research approach is more of theorising than a test of theory that is specified before the data gathering begins. It is confirmed that theories that are specified in the beginning can be tested with qualitative data.”

4.4.3 Mixed Method Research

Mixed methods research can be defined as a combination of qualitative and quantitative research approaches (Saunders et al., 2012; Morgan, 2014; Creswell, 2015; Doyle et al., 2016). “In mixed methods research, both the narrative and the statistical approach are used to offer a better perspective of reality and the phenomenon under study. The use of mixed methods involves the

collection, analysis and integration of quantitative and qualitative datasets in a single study or a series of studies” (Creswell and Clark, 2007; Creswell, 2015; Doyle et al., 2016).

Thus, mixed methods research is more than simply collecting and analysing different types of datasets; it “involves the use of both approaches together so that the overall research outcome is greater than any one type of research” (Creswell, 2014; 2015). Mixed methods research is categorized in different ways including; triangulation, embedded, explanatory and exploratory (Creswell, 2015). To this end, scholars contend that mixed methods research constitute a third methodological movement and should be seen as a normal, and perhaps, necessary part of knowledge generation rather than as a special type (Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007; Blaikie, 2010).

The rationale for the choice of mixed methods approach is based on the research problem identified, the objectives and research questions that underpin the conduct of this research. The multi-faceted research problem resulted in formulation of a combination of qualitative and quantitative objectives, and effectively address the research problem and achieve the stated objectives, the adoption of mixed methods approach was deemed most appropriate. The qualitative approach enables the researcher draw insights on Lean practices in the upstream petroleum sector, whilst the quantitative approach investigates the relationship between Lean principles and competitive priorities. The quantitative approach determines the relationship between variables whereas the qualitative provides the story lines by exploring views, opinions and perceptions about the nature of a phenomenon (Kumar, 2019).

In the quantitative study, the research seeks to establish the relationship between lean elements/principles and competitive business priorities, whereas the qualitative study explored insights from senior management and lean consultants about current lean practices in the upstream petroleum sector. Extant literature shows the value of mixed methods in various studies on lean manufacturing including Goa and Low (2014), Bijl et al., (2019), Holden et al., (2015) and van Dun et al., (2017). Though the aforementioned authors did not specifically adopt mixed methods approach in developing lean frameworks, Ogunbiyi (2014), adopted a mixed methods approach in which he developed a conceptual Lean framework for the construction industry.

4.5 Research Design

According to Saunders et al., (2012), research design outlines the plan adopted by the researcher to answer the research question(s). The overarching consideration in the research design stage is how well the research question(s) is/are defined (Creswell, 2015; Saunders et al., 2012). Extant literature indicate various research designs can be explored to achieve and/or address the research objectives (Kent, 2007). Research could adopt any of the following designs; exploratory, descriptive and explanatory (Malhotra, 2008; Gray, 2013). The subsequent sections provide brief descriptions of each of the aforementioned research designs.

4.5.1 Exploratory Research Design

An exploratory study seeks to gain insight into a new phenomenon in order to clarify an existing concept (Kent, 2007). This type of research design enables the researcher to dig deep for information relating to the subject under study. Also, it allows researchers to take early steps in understanding a concept or explore deeper insights to illumine an existing phenomenon.

Exploratory studies enable researchers to ask the right questions and probe the right places in a quest to elicit facts and unbiased responses that could influence existing or novel findings.

Exploratory studies aim at “investigating phenomena that are not well understood (Marshall and Rossman, 1999) or deal with a new, little understood, problem/issue/topic in order to facilitate the development and formulation of a research idea (Phillips and Pugh, 2000). In such cases, the research commonly begins with an exploratory phase to assess what the study should be about and then, depending on the aim of the study, evolves into a descriptive or explanatory phase (Eriksson and Wiedersheim-Paul, 1997). Exploratory research design is characterised by a flexible and evolving approach to understand a phenomenon that is inherently difficult to measure.

Yin (2003) indicates that exploratory research is used to identify important categories of meaning used in generating hypotheses for further research. Exploratory studies are useful for finding out what is happening; to seek new insights; to ask questions and to assess phenomenon in a new light (Robson, 2002). In addition, exploratory research could be used to identify important categories of meaning or to generate hypotheses for further research (Marshall and Rossman, 1999; Yin, 2003). It is particularly useful when researchers seek to clarify their understanding of a problem, such that they will present the precise nature of a problem (Saunders et al., 2012). According to Adams and Schvaneveldt (1991) exploratory research is very flexible and adaptable to change.”

4.5.2 Descriptive Research Design

A descriptive research design is employed by researchers in an attempt to profile the research phenomenon and obtain a descriptive insight into it (Burns and Bush, 2000; Saunders et al., 2012).

Descriptive research facilitates deep investigations into subjects of interest to the researcher. It

describes the research concept of study by collecting data about the nature of the phenomenon. This helps the researcher to put together findings about the phenomenon that lead to a better description of what the phenomenon is” (Kent, 2007; Malhotra, 2008).

Principally, descriptive research primarily seeks to describe how reality is. Descriptive research does not focus on testing a hypothesis, nor does it focus on developing or validating a theory (Harris, 1991). Rather, it seeks to objectively provide a description of the functions of a phenomenon (Malhotra and Birks, 2007). In its purest form however, descriptive research does not seek to explain or evaluate a phenomenon. It is the reader’s responsibility (Harris, 1991).

Descriptive research in management and business research has a very clear place and should be considered as a means to an end rather than an end in itself.

4.5.3 Explanatory (Causal) Research Design

The term explanatory research design refers to “research designs that facilitate the examination of the causal relationships amongst a number of variables (Malhotra, 2008). Explanatory research design allows researchers to determine the impact a variable has on other variables within a research framework (Gray, 2013). These type of research designs are often employed in studies that require a quantitative and statistical analysis of research phenomenon” (Hair et al., 2008).

Explanatory research—focuses on studying a situation or problem in order to explain the relationships between variables (Saunders et al., 2012). The data collected in explanatory research is usually subjected to statistical tests like correlations and regression analysis to explain or understand the link between the various variables.

The research problem in this research requires a combination of both exploratory and explanatory/causal research designs. The rationale for an exploratory research design is informed by the fact that the phenomenon to explore is new and the research focus is to obtain insights into Lean practices within the upstream industry in Ghana.

Given that this study sought to test the relationships between Lean elements and competitive priorities, a causal research design was also chosen. The causal research design allows researchers to assess the causal relationships between variables in a framework. In this study, Lean principles constitute the independent variables, and competitive priorities considered the dependent variables.

4.6 Research Strategy

A research strategy refers to a plan adopted by the research on how to answer the research question (Saunders et al., 2012). Various research strategies are available for selection by the researcher. However, the selection of a particular strategy depends on a number of considerations.

Researchers have outlined five major research strategies commonly used in the field of social science research including: experiments, surveys, archival analysis, histories, and case studies (Creswell, 2015; Rahi, 2017; Yin, 2017). However, Saunders et al. (2012) identified seven research strategies including; “*experiments, surveys, case study, action research, grounded theory, ethnography, and archival research*”. It must be noted that each of the strategies identified can be adopted in either explanatory, descriptive or exploratory research designs. These strategies are categorised as either inductive or deductive. However, the classification is not to say that one is better than the other. Rather, the emphasis should be on the one that enables the researcher to

achieve the objectives of the research. These strategies should be viewed as functioning complementarily, as opposed to being mutually exclusive. This is because depending on the nature of the research, two or more of these strategies can be combined to enable the researcher achieve the desired objective (Saunders et al., 2012). “However, all strategies are associated with advantages and disadvantages and the boundaries between them are often unclear and blurred. When selecting an appropriate research strategy, the decision should be based on the type of research question posed, the extent of control a researcher has over actual behavioural events and the degree of focus on contemporary events (Marshall and Rossman, 1999). Saunders et al. (2012) further posit that research strategies are essentially frameworks used by researchers in the quest to answer research questions and meet research objectives.”

Survey is one of the commonly-used strategies usually for quantitative studies, and case studies and ethnographies usually for qualitative studies (Saunders et al., 2012). However, these strategies are not mutually exclusive, in that there have been instances where case studies have been used alongside surveys. The choice of strategy is usually determined by the research questions and objectives, and how the researcher deems fit to have them answered. The choice can also be influenced by the philosophical basis of the study as well as the availability (or the lack) of the knowledge on the subject, time and resources available to the researcher (Saunders et al., 2012). Although the list below is not exhaustive, it presents some widely used research strategies that the researcher considered before a final choice was made.

Research strategies including narrative research, ethnography, case studies, archival research and grounded theory propounded by scholars have been reviewed within the context of this research, and whilst the suitability of each of these strategies have been duly examined, the researcher opted

for phenomenology as a preferred strategy. As elaborated in the next sub-section, the epistemological assumptions of phenomenology as a strategy posit that human truths are accessible through inner subjectivity (Flood, 2010). Scholars phenomenology as central to the interpretive paradigm (Wojnar and Swanson, 2007), thus, the adoption of phenomenology is aligned with the researcher's objective to interpreting the lived experiences of participants with specific reference to Lean practices in developing economies like Ghana.

4.6.1 Phenomenology

Fundamentally, phenomenology seeks to explore an understanding of how people make meaning of their lived experiences (Starks, 2010, Lewis, 2015). Phenomenological inquiry allows the researcher to ask questions without specific reference to existing literature (Creswell, 2014), thus making room for the use of intuition during the interviewing process. The principal source of data collection in a phenomenological research is obtained from the views of participants about their lived experiences. The assumption is that the participant's view is taken as "fact". In addition, the selection of participants is predicated on their lived experiences which is deemed as relevant for the concept under study. The most appropriate sampling technique in a phenomenological research is purposive sampling since it allows the researcher to apply discretionary ability in selecting participants with the relevant lived experiences capable to adequately responding to interview questions (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003; Saunders et al., 2012; Creswell, 2015). The researcher's qualitative analysis in this phenomenological study adopted Braun and Clarke's six-phase thematic approach in which key descriptors of the phenomenon under study are coded, and grouped into and finally to themes informed description of the essence and structure of participant lived experiences (Starks, 2010, Lewis, 2015). Based on the foregone explanation of the various philosophies and paradigms, and cognizant of the research problem, objectives and research

questions defined in the study, phenomenology was deemed to be the most appropriate strategy. Thus, the adoption of phenomenology underpinned the data collection method from senior managers, consultants, supervisors and employees who are experienced in the implementation of Lean practices.

4.7 Time Horizon

Time is an important consideration in any research project. The nature, scope, resource availability and overall purpose of a research project underpin the type research to adopt. However, available research findings indicate that majority of research projects carried out for academic purposes are time-bound, hence the choice between longitudinal and cross-sectional studies has become a critical consideration in research (Rindfleisch et al., 2008).

One important factor in any research project is the time-scale the researcher wants to adopt; be it a snapshot taken at a particular time or more of a —diary which will depict happenings over a given period (Gray, 2014; Saunders, 2012). Suffice to reiterate that there are two types of studies based on time perspectives. These include cross-sectional and longitudinal studies.

4.7.1 Longitudinal Studies

Longitudinal research refers to a study in which an individual or a group is observed over a long period of time (Rindfleisch et al., 2008). This approach is ideal “for researchers seeking to study change and evolution of a research phenomenon over a period of time. An advantage longitudinal research is its ability to make long observations over a period of time, thus enabling the researcher to exercise a measure of control over the variables being studied (Rindfleisch et al., 2008) Longitudinal studies equip researchers with the ability to identify explanatory factors and study

how they impact on other dependent variables (Gray, 2014). This research however is constrained with regards to time and hence longitudinal approach is not suitable.

4.7.2 Cross-Sectional Studies

Cross-sectional studies are studies that seek to take a snapshot of a research phenomenon at a particular point in time. In cross sectional studies, data is collected at a given point in time and the main emphasis lies on capturing the phenomenon at a specified moment in time (Gray, 2014). Cross-sectional studies have been noted to employ survey strategies in an attempt to describe and adequately explain an incidence at a given point in time” (Robson, 2002; Rindfleisch et al., 2008). Cross-sectional studies therefore allow a group/groups of individual institutions or persons to be composed into one large sample and studied at only a single point in time. This study adopts a cross-sectional study not only because of resource and time constraints, but also because the purpose of the research was to develop a conceptual framework and therefore a cross-sectional approach is deemed most appropriate.

4.8 Population of the Study

In the context of a research project, the term “research population” is defined as a set of elements identified for inquiry based on the objectives of a research (Hair, Anderson, Babin and Black, 2010). Existing literature suggests that it is impracticable for researchers to collect and analyse all data from an entire population due to time, access and resources constraints, therefore the need to sample (Saunders et al., 2012; Creswell, 2015). Also, suffice to emphasize, that undertaking a census investigation is no guarantee of obtaining more useful results compared to a well- planned sample survey. Granted that a sample is representative, generalizations about the underlying population can still be drawn (Churchill and Iacobucci 2009; Zikmund 1994). In this research, the

population covers upstream petroleum companies in Ghana. A projected population of about 5000 employees from ten companies in the upstream petroleum sector based on insights and data from the industry regulatory agency. These companies include operators, service companies and regulatory organisations.

4.9 Sampling techniques and procedures

The choice of an appropriate sampling technique for data collection in the conduct of the research constitute a critical part of ensuring credibility in a research. Many researchers have defined sampling simply as a process of choosing a subset of a target population from which data is collected for a study (Creswell, 2014). Therefore, a sample can be described as individual elements of a subset of an identified study population (Saunders et al., 2012; Creswell, 2015). It is practically impossible for a researcher to collect data from an entire study population and hence the need for a sample. This implies that a sample is smaller than a study population (Taherdoost, 2016). The sample size is determined by the researcher based on critical analysis of factors relevant to the research including the research questions and objectives of the research. Practically, the researcher ensures that the sample determined can be handled within the limit of resources and time. In addition, the sample size depends on a number of factors including whether the research adopts a qualitative or quantitative approach. Quantitative research requires larger samples termed representative samples (Punch, 2000; Bartlett et al., 2001; Payne and Payne, 2004; Creswell, 2015). *“A representative sample is a subset of the population that is large enough to account for findings that would have been produced if the entire population were surveyed. It is also defined as a sample that is sufficiently large to represent the entire population”* (Banerjee and Chaudhury, 2010).

One major advantage of a representative sample is that they offer a high chance of producing estimates or findings that approximate population parameters.

Since the basic goal associated with representative samples is to maximize external validity and generalize findings to the population (Bartlett et al., 2001), quantitative researchers are required to adopt representative sampling. The determination of a representative sample is done by applying an appropriate sampling procedure.

The two main sampling techniques are probability sampling and non-probability sampling techniques, and each of the two techniques also have various types (Etikan and Bala, 2017). Probability sampling which is also called '*random sampling this is a sampling which permits every single item from the universe to have an equal chance of presence in the sample*' (Etikan and Bala, 2017). These sampling methods are applicable if the researcher wants to achieve a representative sample. In this research, the researcher adopts a mixed methods approach and hence obtained representative sample from upstream petroleum organisations in Ghana. Some notable types of probability sampling include: simple random sampling, stratified sampling, systematic sampling, cluster sampling, and multi-stage sampling (Etikan and Bala, 2017).

Non-probability sampling techniques on the other hand do not offer every member of the population with an equal chance of being selected. Hence it is often referred to as a biased means of sampling. Non-probability sampling techniques often pertain to the researcher's discretion in identifying respondents that are best suited to the needs of the research" (Burns and Bush, 2006).

Purposive sampling which is a non-probability sampling technique was used in order to obtain the sample with the required expertise. Purposive sampling rather than random sampling is often used

because respondents selected are “information rich” are able to generate useful data and are likely to be representative of the larger population (Patton, 2002). Snow balling technique was also employed for the qualitative data collection because respondents were identified through referrals by members of the upstream petroleum sector. Respondents were purposively sampled in Ghana.

The study employed the mixed method approach. The decision to select a mixed-method approach stems from the fact that the research objectives are drawn from both qualitative and quantitative backgrounds; hence the combined value of both qualitative and quantitative methods will provide a better understanding of the research problem (Creswell, 2015).

The sample size for the qualitative research of 15 senior managers, consultants and practitioners within the upstream sector is consistent with research findings. Creswell, (2003) asserted that the ideal sample size for a qualitative study should be between five (5) to twenty-five (25) respondents. The respondents were senior managers and Lean consultants, and their selection based on their participation in the implementation of lean programmes. By selecting respondents who have gone through the lean implementation programme, suggests that, they understand the system and can provide better responses to interview questions (Ainul Azyan, Pulakanam and Pons, 2017). A quantitative study was also conducted on a sample size of 150 and 503 respondents for exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis respectively with the use of structural equation modelling. Respondents are categorized as floor/operational employees and supervisors within the upstream operations in Ghana. This will provide statistical data that will aid in the generalisation of results. The choice of a sample size of 150 and 503 is consistent with Hair et al. (2010) who asserted that a sample size of 250 respondents for a quantitative study is representative.

The ideal method for determining a saturation or information redundancy in the data collection process (Trotter, 2012; Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007). Contrary to the focus of quantitative studies which seek to extrapolate the results of the research, hence, the need to ensure that sample size is representative of the population, qualitative studies aim at obtaining insights into specific educational, social and familial processes and practices (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007). Thus, the importance of a sample size is insignificant in qualitative research. The chosen sample size in a qualitative study should not be too small to attain saturation, and suitable sample size in qualitative research is dependent on the researcher attaining a point of data saturation, theoretically not be too large to analyse (Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007), and this leaves determination of sample size to the discretion of the researcher. Interviews were conducted using a combination of purposive and snowballing sampling techniques.

4.10 Key Informant Selection

To aid with sampling, the recommendation on participant selection by Miles and Huberman (1994) was the standard used. The four main criteria used were the actors, events, process and setting and they are further explained below.

4.10.1 Actors

The actors refer to the person(s) being observed or interviewed. The key informants for this study were managers, consultants, supervisors and employees. By gathering data from different sources and reporting multiple perspectives, the researcher seeks to render a holistic account in order to build robustness into the study (Creswell, 2014).

4.10.2 Events

The events refer to what the actors do while being observed or interviewed. Using a phenomenological research methodology, this study identified a sample that have experiences in Lean practices in the upstream petroleum sector and/or relevant sectors within the context of the study.

4.10.3 Processes

The process refers to the nature in which the events unfold within the setting. Particular attention was paid to the various Lean practices that were relevant to the Upstream Petroleum Sector.

4.10.4 Setting

The setting refers to where the research takes place. Questionnaires were administered at the shop floor of the respondents. Meetings were held in the offices of the respondents to ensure minimum disruption to their routines. Interviews lasted between 45 minutes and 60 minutes, and were digitally recorded for transcription and analysis. Considerations were made also for dates and times that were convenient for each respondent, including meeting after office hours where required including follow up sessions for clarification.

4.11 Sources of Data Collection

Kent (2007) reveals that “data is an essential part of research; researchers need it to clarify their thoughts and propositions. There are two main forms of data standout in literature namely primary and secondary data (Burns and Bush, 2006). Primary data has been explained to refer to data that is collected for the purpose of satisfying a new research need. Secondary data on the other hand

refers to already existing data that has been collected by other researchers, and that is available for use and reference by other researchers (Kent, 2007; Gray, 2013).

Some scholars advise that before researchers set out to collect primary data, they should consider secondary data to learn what has already been found, and what gaps exist in the literature” (Malhotra, 2008). Wiedersheim-Paul and Eriksson (1997), posit that secondary data is data that has already been collected and analysed for a different purpose. On the other hand, primary data is collected by the researcher from sample population for the purpose outlined in the research. For the purpose of this study the researcher relied on primary source of data in answering research questions as well as address the research objectives (Saunders et al., 2012). Primary sources of data are “collected and analysed specifically for the research problem at hand, whereas secondary sources contain data gathered at a previous time for other purposes than the current research problem (Hair et al., 2006; Tull and Hawkins 1993). The advantage of secondary data is that it can usually be collected at a lower cost and more rapidly than primary data. On the other hand, since it was usually collected for a different purpose, its content might correlate poorly with the researchers’ current needs (Hair et al., 2006). This is why primary data source was utilised in this study as the major source of data. Moreover, considering the relative complexity and depth of the information required by the current study, limited available secondary sources was appropriate. The main data source of the study was the primary data since it was relevant to get information directly from the respondents.”

4.12 Basic Mixed Methods Designs

According to Creswell (2015), there are three types of basic research designs that underpin mixed methods studies. These include “convergent design, explanatory sequential design and exploratory sequential design” (Creswell, 2015 p.6). These are further explained below:

4.12.1 The Convergent Design

Creswell (2015) asserts that, this method requires the merging of both quantitative and qualitative results that have been separately analysed in order for the researcher to obtain varied insights and different perspectives of the results of the study. While the qualitative data seek to provide in-depth understanding of a phenomenon, quantitative data presents statistical data that highlights trends based on a problem under study.

Convergent research requires that the researcher collects and analyses both qualitative and quantitative data separately. The next step combines both qualitative and quantitative results (Creswell, 2015). The quantitative data is presented first, followed by the qualitative data. A discussion and comparison of results of both qualitative and quantitative provides a better understanding of the results. The discussion leads to confirmation or otherwise of results and an explanation of any differences observed (Creswell, 2015). The major issue associated with this design is the use of same measures for both qualitative and quantitative research approaches.

4.12.2 The Explanatory Sequential Design

This method requires the analysis of the quantitative results in order to design a qualitative study. The quantitative results present statistical information that does not explain why the results are obtained. Due to this, a qualitative study is conducted to explain the results that have been obtained because of the quantitative study (Creswell, 2015). The process entails, first, the collection and

analysis of quantitative data. When results are obtained from the quantitative data analysis, a qualitative data collection and analysis is conducted in order explain the quantitative results. The final stage consists of drawing inferences in order to aid in the explanation of the quantitative results (Creswell, 2015). The advantage of this design is that, the researcher presents two unique phases that build and rely on each order in an easy way. A challenge of this method is that, it is time-consuming. It is also difficult to determine which quantitative results will require more explanation (Creswell, 2015).

4.12.3 The Exploratory Sequential Design

This method requires the researcher to undertake a qualitative study first through the collection and analysis of data and based on the results obtained, develop a quantitative research instrument which is used to collect and analyse data. The process in this design starts with collecting and analysing of qualitative data. The next phase entails the design of quantitative research instrument such as a questionnaire based on results obtained from the qualitative study, for instance, themes. The third step is to test the data collection instrument in order to ascertain validity and reliability. The final step is to 'report how the new component improves upon the existing set of variables'. The processes involved is to conduct of qualitative study, followed by a quantitative study (Creswell, 2015).

In this research, the exploratory sequential design was adopted using a combination of qualitative (interviews), and questionnaires using the structural equation modelling (SEM) approach. When themes are identified from qualitative study, the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is carried out in which reliability of scales are determined, followed by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA)

which establishes the structural relationship between lean elements and competitive priorities. Exploratory Sequential Design provides rigour and is ideal for this study.

4.13 Ethical Issues

Malhotra and Birks (2007), postulate that in research, a significant issue that must not be ignored is the consideration of ethics. Ethics forms part of the basic foundations of organizational studies (Wicks and Freeman, 1998). Ethics establishes whether or not a research activity can be justified (Wicks and Freeman, 1998). It can be perceived as *the appropriateness of the researcher's behaviour in relation to the rights of those who become the subject of the research* (Saunders et al., 2012). In addition, ethics seeks to ensure that research design is both methodologically sound and morally justifiable without posing any harm to subjects involved in the research. Furthermore, ethics is anchored on researcher transparency, honesty, appropriateness and confidentiality with respondents and, ... *“how researcher formulates and clarifies research topic, designs research and gains access, collects data, processes and stores data, analyse data and write up research findings in a moral and responsible way”* (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Malhotra and Birks, 2007).

Kent (2007) averred that a fundamental aspect of research, often ignored, is the ethical considerations in conducting research. Observing relevant ethics is considered by Creswell (2003) as an obligation of research and is necessary to gain the approval of relevant stakeholders, acknowledge participant's rights and welfare and reach acceptable results. In his study, Allwood (2012) noted that the conduct of any research must adhere to strict ethical standards if the research and its result should be accepted legally and technically. For these reasons, adequate ethical considerations were taken into account in this research. This research obtained the required ethical approval prior to the data collection process.

In this research, “the ethical principles of confidentiality, disclosure of intent and transparency were embraced (Malhotra, 2008). The researcher made sure that permission was sought and the purpose of the study made known to respondents in an introductory letter. An appointment was booked with interviewees, and on the agreed date the researcher went to collect the data. In all dealings with respondents, the researcher assured them of confidentiality, whilst explaining the nature of the research and its relevance to their operations. Participants were not forced but rather encouraged to voluntarily participate and the researcher further made sure that information were kept confidential.” Participants signed Consent Forms before the data was collected. The respondents were informed that notes will be prepared during informal discussions when data relevant to the study are identified. The researcher took steps not to interfere in the business activities of respondents. As a result, each participant was asked to indicate and choose a convenient time to collect data.

4.14 Data collection Instruments and Techniques

The data collection instruments for this study were an interview guide and questionnaire. The interview guide was used to collect qualitative data while a questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data.

4.14.1 Interview Technique

The interview aided the researcher to obtain views, insights, opinions, perceptions and feelings of respondents. Some frequently used examples include the standardised open ended interview, informal conversational interview, the general interview guide approach and close, fixed response interview (Patton, 2002). This study employed the semi-structured open ended in-depth interviews.

This allowed the researcher grasp an insight into the phenomenon as understood by the respondents. Where necessary, the researcher made efforts to ask follow-up questions in a bid to clarify and interpret participants' thoughts (Baxter and Jack, 2008). The interviews were recorded and appropriate notes taken. The data was later transcribed, coded and analysed.

4.14.2 The Questionnaire Technique

The researcher incorporated the “use of questionnaires in the data collection process. According to Oppenheim (2008), a questionnaire is an instrument for data collection and measurement. A questionnaire was used to collect quantitative data from shop floor/ operational employees and supervisors in the upstream petroleum producing organisations in Ghana. The design of the questionnaire was based on an extensive review of existing lean practices and existing frameworks. The 5 most dominant lean principles were identified and constructs developed for each. The constructs identified in designing the questionnaire include waste elimination, continuous improvement, standardization, Leadership and Just-in-Time. In addition, two competitive priorities were adopted from literature namely quality and cost (Jasti and Kodali, 2016).

Three factors identified by Creswell (2003), constituted the criteria upon which this questionnaire was formulated. These factors include: (a) first, suitability for collecting data using validated and Likert scales; (b) second, suitable tool for collecting primary data for quantitative studies; and (c) questionnaires can be completed by participants in the absence of the researcher. The questionnaire was structured in main sections. The first section introduces the researcher and study to the respondent. The second section presents the demographic profile of the research. The third section measures the main variables of Lean principles and competitive priorities.

4.15 Pre-testing of Data Collection Instruments

The researcher employed structured questionnaires and semi-structured interview guide for the study. “After designing the questionnaire there was the need to ascertain the suitability and applicability of the questionnaire before proceeding with the main data collection” (Hair et al., 2006;2010). The purpose of piloting a data collection instrument is to enable the researcher refine the questionnaire to enhance ease of understanding and elicit the right responses from participants (Saunders et. al., 2012). The importance of pre-testing cannot be overemphasized as it offers an opportunity to clarify ambiguous items so as to avoid or minimize incomplete responses.

However, when using self-administered questionnaires, it is incumbent upon the researcher to critically examine the layout of the questionnaire as well as the content. In other words, the layout ought to be "user-friendly" to enhance ease of response. An easy to use questionnaire can ostensibly reduce measurement error and also reduce the likelihood of non-response error by providing a relatively pleasant task for the respondent. Pre-testing enables the researcher to obtain assessment of the questions' validity and the likely reliability of the data that will be collected (Saunders et al., 2012).

In order to assess instrument validity, a number of options are available to researcher's dependant on the research approach adopted. For instance, researchers may observe how respondents fill out a questionnaire and can infer likely problems in the instrument. This approach can be likened to behaviour coding in face-to-face or telephone interviews but is considered a less than optimal means by which the researcher can identify weaknesses in the questionnaire. A more effective way by which a pre-test can use self-administered questionnaires is to conduct personal interviews with respondents drawn from the target population (Zikmund, 1994). The pre-test phase of this research required respondents to fill-out questionnaires as though it were the actual data collection part of

the study. After completing the questionnaires, participants were asked about their general impression about the questionnaires and more specifically, the clarity of instructions, the layout of and structure of questionnaires as well as terminologies used. Participants were also asked about interpretation of questions, ease of understanding the questions and ease or difficulty in responding to questions (Nunnally and Bernstein 1994; Zikmund, 1994).

In this research, the researcher piloted the questionnaires first with participants drawn from the Scottish Development International (SDI) oil and gas trade mission to Ghana. Participants were made of employees of oil and gas companies from Scotland and Ghana. A second pre-test was conducted with students at the University of the West of Scotland. The results of the pre-test proved to be satisfactory, since all the respondents found the questions understandable. Nevertheless, some minor wording mistakes were found on a few questions which were corrected before actual data collection. Also, a pilot test of the semi-structured interview guide was done by using students of the University of the West of Scotland prior to actual data collection. The interview guide was then modified to help achieve the aims and objectives of the research.

4.16 Data Analysis Process

In analysing qualitative data, “the methodical sequence in organizing data from transcripts, reducing the data into themes through a process of coding, and finally data presentation through analysis and discussions” (Creswell, 2012). Data was “explored without any prior assumptions in order to identify themes that will emerge from the data. Data was then analysed in accordance with these themes in order to generate meaning (Robson, 2002). The thematic analysis technique was chosen as the analytical method for this study due to its ability to make reasonable inferences in interpreting data” (Vaismoradi, Turunen and Bondas, 2013).

According to Braun and Clarke (2006), “thematic analysis is a strategy for analysing qualitative data. Thematic analysis is a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data”(Braun and Clarke, 2006:79). “The data analysis in this study was undertaken through the use of thematic analysis (TA) due to the advantages inherent in its use. Thematic analysis enables researchers to unearth patterns as well as identify emerging themes to enable the establishment of a chain of evidence to build arguments (Braun and Clarke, 2006). It also allows the organisation and description of the research findings in detail. It is flexible, relatively easy and quick to learn and do and notably very accessible to beginners in research (Braun and Clarke, 2006:79). However, some researchers argue that the strategy is poorly defined and overlaps with many other approaches such as grounded theory in its search for themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The inherent advantages of a well-structured thematic analysis fundamentally underscored the adoption of the six steps approach proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006). After the transcription, the data was coded with the research questions and the theoretical framework in mind (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Braun and Clark, 2006; Saunders et al., 2007). The codes based on code names/code labels to construct a thematic map. The researcher employed Boyatzis (1998) criteria for a good code which refers to a code that reveals the qualitative value of the phenomenon under study. The process unearthed themes within the data that became the categories for the analysis.”

In order to begin the analysis, “the semi-structured interviews from each of the 15 cases were transcribed from the audio recorded interviews (Boyatzis, 1998; Marshall and Rossman, 1999). The interviewees comprised of senior managers and Lean consultants within the upstream

petroleum sector. Each transcription was saved under a filename that identified the interviewees while maintaining confidentiality and preserving anonymity (Saunders et al., 2007). The transcripts were checked for accuracy and cleaned of typographical errors. The data was then analysed qualitatively to extract insights related to core Lean elements used for implementing Lean in the upstream petroleum industry. The method used was analysing exploratory comments from respondents to identify emerging themes (Ainul Azyan, Pulakanam and Pons, 2017).”

Thematic analysis was conducted using QRS NVIVO software. The “themes that emerged from interviews and observations were then summarised and the relationships between themes identified. The summaries were also related to the contexts of the interviews and the observations (Saunders et al., 2012). This approach enabled the researcher to have an in-depth overview of the interview transcripts. The goal of the data analysis was not only to describe the data but to interpret, explain and understand the meanings given to the research phenomenon (Flick, 2002). The combination of QRS NVIVO and SPSS complimentarily provided a comprehensive understanding to the research problem. The researcher also used IBM Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20 for structural equation modelling analysis by conducting EFA and CFA with AMOS version 21.”

4.16.1 Factor Analysis

Primary data obtained from this research was subjected to factor analysis. The factor analysis technique is used by researchers to develop and evaluate tests and scales(Norris, 2011). Literature presents two main approaches to factor analysis – exploratory and confirmatory(Norris, 2011). EFA is a methodology used to reduce a variable set and to establish key dimensions of interest and

to illustrate or show quality of potential indicators(Norris, 2011). However, EFA is employed at the early stages of the research, CFA builds on the final data obtained from the EFA stage. CFA is a more complex and sophisticated set of techniques used later in the research process to test (confirm) specific hypotheses or theories concerning the structure underlying a set of variables as well as establish structural relationships among variables (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Pallant, 2011; Norris, 2011).

According to Hair et al., (2010), EFA can be used for “examining the underlying patterns or relationships for a large number of variables and to reduce/ condense or summarize data into smaller set of factors or components(Norris, 2011). Drawing on Pallant (2011), three main steps are followed in carrying out EFA; (1) Assessment of the suitability of data for factor analysis, (2) Factor extraction and (3) Factor rotation and interpretation. It must be mentioned that, there were two sets of data responses used for the EFA and CFA; 150 responses were used for the EFA while 503 was used for the CFA. Thus, the analysis of two major phases in SEM were performed”.

4.16.2 Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

Structural equation modelling refers to a collection of statistical techniques which allow a set of relationships to be established/examined between one or more independent variables or one or more dependent variables. These variables could either be continuous or discrete(Norris, 2011). Stated differently, SEM could also be used to examine and explain relationships among multiple variables, examine the structure of interrelationships expressed in a series of equations (Hair et al., 2010).

SEM as an analytical technique, integrates a number of standard multivariate analytical methods including factor analysis, analysis of variance, and regression analysis (Hair et al., 2010). Also,

SEM perceived as “*a comprehensive statistical approach to testing hypotheses about relations among observed and latent variables*” (Hoyle,1995 p.1). Furthermore, Byrne (1994) averred that SEM has gained popularity due to its demonstrable hypothesis-testing rigorous prowess, otherwise known as confirmatory approach. SEM has been used by researchers due to its ability to conduct simultaneous robust analytical processes together, while ensuring rigour and integrity of results obtained (MacLean and Gray, 1998). This research sought to establish the relationship between Lean principles and competitive business priorities. Therefore, SEM was chosen for this research based on its ability to simultaneously assess the relationships between Lean principles and competitive priorities. Compared to regression analysis, SEM offered a better opportunity to conduct a series of analysis (Ullman, 2006). In analysing data with SEM, the researcher adopted a covariance-based approach. Notwithstanding the fact that a number of SEM analytical approaches exists, this research adopted the covariance-based SEM approach due to its level of rigor which allows for comprehensive data analysis to be conducted on the data obtained (Hair et al., 2010).

SEM as an analytical technique has demonstrated significant benefits dependent on the nature of the research and how suitable the technique has been justifiably selected. An important benefit is its ability to address critical error types confounding first-generation procedures (Edwards and Bagozzi, 2000). SEM provides an important opportunity to establish a link between philosophy and theoretical and empirical research (Schumacker and Lomax, 2004). Drawing on the benefits espoused by several statistical authors, Bagozzi and Yi (2012) summarize the advantages of adopting SEM as follows:

- “SEM offers an integrative function under a single umbrella”.

- “It offers researchers help with adequate precision when specifying hypotheses and operationalization of research constructs”.
- “SEM takes cognisance of reliability of measures in testing hypotheses in ways going beyond the averaging of multi-measures of constructs”.
- “SEM guides exploratory and confirmatory research in a manner combining self-insight and modelling skills with theory. Highly recommended for philosophies of discovery and confirmation”.
- “SEM often suggests novel hypotheses originally not considered and opens up new avenues for research”.
- “It is useful in experimental or survey research, cross-sectional or longitudinal studies, measurement or hypothesis testing endeavours, within or across groups and institutional or cultural contexts.”

SEM is the appropriate technique where inherent errors reflecting the “imperfect nature” of the constructs are fully taken into consideration within the specification of the technique. It must be noted however, that SEM does not assess or “prove” causality (Bagozzi and Yi, 2012). Yet the technique evaluates and tests the influences which one construct has on another within a fully specified model (Byrne, 2013). This is because while model fitness of a data may provide measurement and predictive validity, it does not in itself express information about the ability of the underlying theory (Cronbach, 1951).

Werts et al. (1974), cautions researchers to take full account of several sources of misapplication of SEM by hinting that, “it is relatively easy to find a structural model which fits the data quite

closely...it is extremely difficult to demonstrate (a) that a model simulates reality, (b) that it provided better simulation than another model, (c) that the constructs defined in the model gave greater explanatory power from the observed variables from which they are derived, and (d) that these constructs are in any sense useful for promoting better research. Nevertheless, a full consideration has been given to these issues and cautions raised by scholars in designing, applying and reporting the SEM analysis presented in this research. More specifically, the author followed those guidelines enumerated by Jöreskog and Sörbom (1996) as well as Byrne (2013) in carrying out the various aspects of this analysis.

SEM was applied in examining the structural paths among the constructs (i.e. to test the various hypotheses proposed in this research). There are two widely used approaches in performing SEM: one-stage and two-stage. The one-stage approach purpose is to process the analysis of both the measurement and structural models simultaneously (Kline, 2005; Schumacher and Lomax, 2004). In the two-stage approach, the measurement model and structural model estimation are separated (Hair et al., 2010). Compared to the one-stage approach, the two-stage approach avoids interaction that is unnecessary between constructs during testing of the structural model (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988). In this research, the two-stage approach is used to test the research model; the first stage was carried out in the exploratory phase while the second stage used in the confirmatory phase. Kline (2005) maintains that a test of measurement model needs to be conducted because all the correlations between constructs must be estimated before testing the structural model. In addition, the measurement model can assess whether the constructs meet the requirements of validity and reliability (Byrne, 2013). The measurement model for this study was tested through

confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), where all constructs involved were assumed to covary with each other (Kline, 2005).”

4.16.2.1 Testing Model Fitness

Assessing model fit involves “the interpretation of how well the conceptualized model fits the empirical research. The process is comparative in nature because it involves choosing between numerous fit indices that subjectively indicate whether the data fit the theoretically postulated model (Schumacher and Lomax, 2004; Hair et al., 2010; Bagozzi and Yi, 2012). A number of fit indices have been proposed by scholars. However, there are at least two main conventions for the assessment of model fit that are apparent in literature; the assessment of the absolute fit of the model and the assessment of the comparative fit. Model fit criteria commonly used in absolute fit are chi-square (χ^2), goodness-of-fit index (GFI), adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI), root-mean-square residual (RMR) and Root-Mean-Square-Error of Approximation (RMSEA). These criteria are based on differences between the observed and model-implied correlation or covariance matrix (Hair et al., 2014). Comparative fit deals with whether the model being considered is better than a competing model in accounting for observed data. Comparative fit assessment is based on the examination of a baseline model in comparison with theoretically derived models (Kelloway, 1998). Some criteria in this category include normed fit index (NFI), comparative fit index (CFI) and the relative non-centrality index (RNI).”

The following “fit indexes were used to evaluate how well the measurement model fit the data collected, with each one having conventionally acceptable values: Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation ($RMSEA \leq 0.08$), Goodness of Fit Index ($GFI \geq 0.90$), Normed Fit Index ($NFI \geq 0.90$) and Comparative Fit Index ($CFI \geq 0.90$) (Bagozzi and Yi, 2012; Hair et al., 2014). The sufficiency of the theorized model’s creation of a covariance matrix is evaluated by the χ^2

goodness-of-fit value; it also estimates coefficients compared with the observed covariance matrix. However, since the value of χ^2 is affected by the sample size, a large number of participants can cause χ^2 to be inflated when assessing model fit (Hu and Bentler, 1999). Many researchers have applied the method that divides the value of χ^2 by degrees of freedom instead of relying only on the overall χ^2 and its associated test of significance. It is typically suggested that a χ^2/df ratio (Normed Chi square) of less than 3 is favourable for a large sample. These fit indices were employed to assess the strength and acceptability of the construct measurements. The selection of these fit indices was based on the classification proposed by Kline (2005) and Byrne (2013) as being the most commonly accepted criteria in social science.”

4.17 Data Reliability and Validity

Reliability is “an important element of instrument design. The reliability of a scale simply refers to its exclusion of random error (Pallant, 2016). It explains the level of confidence a researcher can have with regards to how reliable the data collection instrument is. In assessing or testing for scale reliability in a quantitative study, one of the preferred methods is the use of the Cronbach alpha (Cronbach, 1951). The Cronbach Alpha can be calculated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The threshold for assessing reliability using the Cronbach Alpha varies according to literature. Some scholars explain that in order to accept a scale as being reliable, the value of the Alpha should not fall below the 0.70 threshold (Pallant, 2016). Hair et al. (2016) however assert that Alpha values of 0.50 are also acceptable.

Another important measure in testing the suitability and acceptability of a scale is validity. Validity can be defined as the ability of a scale to accurately measure what it has been designated to measure without deviating from it to measure other variables (Zikmund, 2003). Some scholars believe that

there are instances where a measure may be consistent and reliable, but not accurate or better still valid (Holmes-Smith et al., 2006). It is therefore recommended that as part of quantitative studies, validity tests be carried out. Kent (2007) explains that the critical variations of validity that need to be examined are content, criterion and construct validity. Content validity can be described as the adequacy with which a scale has sampled from the specified content. Criterion validity on the other hand pertains to the relationship between specified measurable indicators. Construct validity involves testing a scale not against a single criterion but in terms of an underlying hypotheses governing the variable under examination. This study tested for all three validities and found them to be satisfactory and within required ranges.”

To ensure data reliability and validity of the interview guide, “all respondents were contacted to verify or confirm their views after data transcription. All the sampled respondents approved the transcripts as a reflection of their thoughts. This proved that the data collected did not lose its meaning after transcription. Also, to increase the reliability and validity of this study, the research followed appropriate research procedures such as the philosophical underpinnings and the research methodology.” Nonetheless, the themes by which data were analysed emerged from the data and not from the researcher’s own constructs.

CHAPTER FIVE

ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.0 Introduction

The purpose of this mixed method, cross-sectional research was to develop an industry-specific conceptual LM framework to improve lean implementation within upstream petroleum sector in developing economies. To achieve the overall purpose of this research, five research questions informed by extensive review of literature were formulated to guide the conduct of the research [see section 1.2]. To buttress the researcher's view, extant literature posits that achieving the objectives of a research depends on how the research questions are formulated and answered (Creswell,2015).

The analysis of data collected, the results and findings of the research is presented in this chapter along with discussions of results of the analysis. This is a mixed method research which combines both inductive and deductive approaches or qualitative and quantitative approaches. Thus, the chapter presents result and findings from both the qualitative [thematic analysis] and the quantitative [Structural Equation Modelling]. The qualitative thematic analysis is presented first in the next section followed by the quantitative structural equation modelling in the subsequent section.

5.1 Organisational Profiling for Data Collection

The upstream petroleum sector in Ghana consists of organisations aimed at prospecting, discovery, drilling and production of crude oil. Other important service organisations within the value-chain provide critical services to support the exploration and production of oil. Cognisant of the fact that this research focused mainly on production sub-sector within the upstream petroleum value-chain,

data collection was carried out within operators and service organisations mainly functioning within the production domain. In all, 10 organisations were identified. However, due to confidentiality and competition within the sector, these organisations were coded alphabetically in order to ensure confidentiality and also align with UWS research ethics requirements to ensure confidentiality. The table below provides a profile of the organisations from which participants were drawn for data collection;

Table 5. 1: Organisational Profiles

Name of organization[coded]	Main activity	Estimated Headcount
A	Regulatory	330
B	Operator/Production	1400
C	Operator/Production	850
D	Operator/Exploration	150
E	Engineering services	136
F	Operator/production	654
G	Operator/Production	600
H	Engineering services	250
I	Operator/Exploration	480
J	Operator/Exploration	550

Source; Author's Construct, (2021)

The estimated total population for the upstream sector is about 5000 with an estimated daily turnover of 126,000 barrels of oil per day. The activities within the sector are benchmarked against

international standards. Thus, data collection and analysis from the target population provides adequate insights on Lean practices within the upstream petroleum sector.

5.2 Thematic Analysis

Every research is underpinned by researcher's ontological and epistemological perspectives which permeates the entire research process including the research design and methods (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). Researchers adopt various methods of analysing qualitative data such as content analysis in which both content and context are analysed, and themes identified. Proponents of content analysis include Belrelson (1952) and Robson (2002). Ritchie and Lewis, (2003), highlighted other qualitative analytical approaches including grounded theory, discourse analysis, narrative analysis among other methods. However, this study adopted thematic analysis as its preferred approach to identify patterns and themes which would form the basis for construct development for the quantitative analysis. Braun and Clarke (2006), citing Boyatzis (1998) discussed Thematic analysis (TA) as a qualitative data analysis without a coherent developmental history.

Thematic analysis (TA) is defined as *“a method of systematically identifying, organizing and offering insight into patterns of meaning(themes) across a data set”* (Braun and Clarke, 2012 p.57).

The thematic analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase approach. In Phase 1 of Braun and Clarke's approach, the researcher familiarizes himself/herself with the data or the responses from interviewees. This entails listening to the recordings or reading the transcripts a couple of times to gain mastery of the content. Phase 2 involves initial coding process whilst phase 3 consists of the initial generation of themes from the codes. Phase 4 consist of reviewing the themes previously generated. Definition and naming of themes constitute phase 5 and a write up that maps

the themes generated to the most prevalent themes from the structured literature review is presented in phase six. Thematic analysis can assume different forms depending on the researcher's perspective. According to Braun and Clarke (2012,p58), thematic analysis can assume one of the following approaches: "*inductive versus deductive (theory-driven data coding and analysis; an experiential versus critical orientation to data; and essentialist versus constructionist theoretical perspective*" This research is situated within the inductive versus deductive approach because an inductive approach adopts a bottom-up approach, in which the data set dictates the analysis process. With an inductive approach, codes and themes are generated from the data set. On the other hand, a deductive approach ensures that analysis is top-down in which case the researcher leads the data set with predetermined concepts, ideas, and/or topics which guides the coding and theme generation process. Thus, the coding theme generation process are closely linked to the concepts, ideas and topics introduced by the researcher, rather than semantically-related to the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006;2012). In summary, Braun and Clarke opine that coding and analysis often adopts a combined approach. Thus, akin to the line of thought advanced by Braun and Clarke, this research adopted a combination of inductive and deductive analysis approach. Themes that emerged from an extensive literature review process, and which anchored the data collection instrument underpinned the coding and analysis process of qualitative research. Justifiably, the choice of a combined approach of inductive and deductive analysis aligns with the entire pragmatist worldview which also underpins the choice of mixed methods approach to this research. The overarching perspective is to provide an overall holistic and comprehensive view to the research.

5.2.1 Analysis Process

The semi-structured interviews were conducted face-to-face and over the phone. These semi-structured interviews [see Appendix B] were recorded and transcribed orthographically in which the entire speech, words, sounds and hesitations and false starts, interviewer's guggles were captured (Braun and Clarke, 2012). Whereas it would have been ideal to clean the data prior to the actual transcription, for the purpose of performing a thematic analysis, it is recommended not "cleaning up the transcript" (Braun and Clarke, 2012 p.60). Also, as a precursor to the actual transcription process, and coupled with data and ethical approval requirements, participants' biodata was profiled as seen in Table 5.1. Transcription options available include: listening to audio recording and typing in words, outsourcing the transcription process, use of transcription software such as Nvivo and last but not least, use of Dragon speak dictation (Davidson, 2009). The application of thematic analysis requires a researcher to indicate the overarching purpose of data transcription. This provides focus for the transcription process. For the purpose of this research, the objective of the carrying out data transcription was to identify relevant aspects of the data set that would help answer the research questions (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2012), and to achieve the objective of the data transcription, the researcher adopted the six-phase approach transcription approach proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006). These six-phases are discussed in detail in the subsequent sections of this research.

5.2.2 Familiarisation with Data

The semi-structured interviews [Appendix B] were recorded and transcribed. To enhance data familiarization, the transcripts from the interviews were read a number of times. The profile of the interviewees is presented in Table 5.1.

It is observed from Table 5.1 that all interviewees sampled for this study were either consultants or senior management personnel involved in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. Being senior managers and consultants, it must be the case that their responses provided adequate basis to answer the research questions by virtue of their level of exposure and interaction within the upstream petroleum sector of Ghana.

Table 5. 2: Profile of Interviewees

Interviewee	Background	Experience in Ghana's Petroleum Sector
#1	Sales Manager – BSc Chemical Engineer	7 years
#2	Consultant for Petroleum Commission – PhD Petroleum Engineering	7 years
#3	Consultant – PhD Mechanical Engineering	4 years
#4	Senior Manager – PhD	5 years
#5	Senior Manager – BSc Petroleum Engineering	10 years
#6	Senior Manager – MSc Organizational Innovation and Entrepreneurship	2 years
#7	Senior Manager	4 years
#8	Senior Manager - MBA Accounting and Finance	3 years
#9	Senior Manager – MSc Petroleum Economics and Finance	5 years 2 years
#10	Senior Manager – MSc Engineering and Management	5 years

#11	Senior Manager – MSc Health and Safety Management	8 years
#12	Senior Manager - BSc Chemical Engineering	5 years
#13	Senior Manager – MSc Supply Chain Management	6 years
#14	Senior Manager -	7 years
#15	Senior Manager -	4 years

Source: Author's Construct (2020)

5.2.3 Coding

An important aspect of the qualitative research process is the analysis of interviews in which the researcher examined how consciously interviewees used words and phrases that highlighted issues of importance or interest to the research. These observations were noted by the researcher and described in short phrases and/or theoretical constructs (Kendall, 1999). As the analysis process continuous, the same issue might be mentioned and/or described again by the interviewee and noted by the researcher. This process of observing, examining and noted key issues emerging from the data is what is termed coding (Moghaddam, 2006). According to Moghaddam(2006), the coding process should be carried out without any predetermined ideas and with an open mind. In contrast, Braun and Clarke (2006) argue that a deductive form of coding is where the researcher brings concepts, ideas or topics to the data set, and as indicated earlier, this research adopts the latter. Coding breaks down the data into analytical portions which can afterward be categorised and themes generated therein. In light of

this, Moghaddam (2006), citing (Goulding, 1999) posit that critical queries worth considering during the data coding process include: “*What is happening in the data? What is the basic socio-psychological problem? What accounts for it? And What patterns are occurring here?*” (Moghaddam, 2006 p.52-56).

The coding process involves “*generating succinct labels (codes) that identify important features of the data that might be relevant to answering the research question and it involves coding the entire dataset, and after that, collating all the codes and all relevant data extracts, together for later stages of analysis*” (Braun and Clarke,2006). According to Kendall (1999), citing Glaser (1978), coding is categorized into two types including substantive or open coding, and theoretical coding processes. However, Strauss and Corbin identified three coding types namely: open, axial, and selective coding. Substantive or open coding is a process in which codes are generated or emerge from the data set which fit and are relevant for integrating into a theory. Also, open coding is referred to as “the process of breaking down, examining, comparing, conceptualizing, and categorizing data” (Kendall, 1999 p.746). Axial coding seeks to create concepts and reduce the number of codes in subsequent stages in order to draw insights and relationships among or between codes. Furthermore, Moghaddam (2006), cited Babchuk (1997), Straus and Corbin, (1990), and posit that selective coding describes the stage where codes combine to become categories which now form the basis of theory formulation. Whilst theory formulation aligns with grounded theory advanced by Straus and Corbin (1990), this research adopts a phenomenological approach. The coding process was carried out with a combination of inductive and deductive approaches. An inductive coding approach ensures that codes and themes are generated from the data set. Though differences in approaches to use in the coding process may arise, nonetheless, these may be based on philosophical or pedagogical differences (Moghaddam, 2006).

The application of inductive coding was done during the initial coding phase of the analysis using the software Nvivo 12 to auto code the interview transcripts. The auto coding process yielded 38 parent codes and 456 child codes (Appendix D). This is an inductive process where the content of the data is given free rein to come up with initial themes. Figure 5.1 presents the hierarchy chart of the initial coding. The parent code aggregates commonalities of the child codes and can be seen as inductive themes generated by the software.

Figure 5. 1: Hierarchy Chart of Initial Codes

5.2.4 Initial Theme Generation and Review

To further develop themes from the initial open coding, axial coding was employed to capture the emerging relationships into condensed categories. This phase involved an examination of the initial codes in detail in order to identify broader patterns of meanings.

The theme review phase involved the collation of data cognizant of research questions and ideas of interest in order to assess viability of the themes. The themes that had support in the data (interview responses) were kept while those that could not be readily supported with data were discarded. This aligned with deductive coding approach (Braun and Clarke,2006). These two phases of the thematic analysis yielded the following sixteen (16) initial themes:

- Industry or Sector Categorisation
- Petroleum Production
- Lean Implementation Strategies
- People Management
- Continuous Improvement
- Business Priorities
- Petroleum Policy and Strategy
- Leadership
- Standardization and Regulation
- Vested Interests / Resource Ownership
- Operational Efficiency
- Safety, Health and Environment and Sustainability
- Waste Elimination

- Organisational Culture and Work Environment
- Shop Floor Management
- Project Management

Table 5.3 below presents the themes accepted at this stage and some of the supporting data (transcripts) for the themes.

Table 5. 3: Initial Themes from Interviews with Sampled Supporting Data

Transcript	Theme from Interviews
<p>Quote 1: <i>In fact, in Ghana we have the upstream industry and then the downstream industry as well and when it comes to the upstream industry basically from my observation I can see that we do more of exploration in the upstream industry and then also we do production (Interviewee #13).</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>And so talking about the upstream industry it is a bit young and comparing it to other areas like the North Sea, the US and other areas (Interviewee #15).</i></p>	<p>Industrial or Sector Categorisation</p>
<p>Quote 1: <i>So Petroleum Commission has the laws on the Ghanaian participation in the oil and gas industry in Ghana, and they always looking at making sure that Ghanaians are benefiting from the services they are offering to the oil and gas industry (Interviewee #3).</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>I think that it is estimated that in Ghana we produce about more than a little over 12000 of barrels of oil per day (Interviewee #13).</i></p> <p>Quote 3: <i>Our production currently is around 145, 000 barrels a day from the two FPSO that we have. Now, we are young in the industry, so when it comes to technology and a lot of challenges (Interviewee #2).</i></p> <p>Quote 4: <i>The spread rate for the rig, as I have mentioned, even if you have the rate for the rig for 600,000 Cedi, even if 1000 Dollars a day, the spread cost means that at every point in time, there are associated cost of the rig. You might have a supply vessel that you are paying for. You may have four or five companies that have their equipment on the rig that you are paying for daily. So when we say a spread rig, it is the rig’s daily rate plus all these people’s daily rate and their equipment daily rates for that day. So when the rig is a loan, nothing on top of that rig, may be 600,000 Dollars, when you have Schlumberger pumping unit on your rig, they are also charging you every day, and their personnel. Everybody is being paid every day. Their cooking and your cooking staff. So that is the spread cost. It goes into millions. So imagine just in time(JIT), you miss two days, that is may be three million Dollars, and the equipment you’ve been provided is about ten thousand or fifty thousand Dollars. It is not a model that is really fits</i></p>	<p>Petroleum Production</p>

<p><i>them. So the equipment should already be available before they even start to think of drilling. And even when they start, because you don't know when they are going to start because of their finances, and how they are going to have their finances approved, you going to make sure you are ready before them. So that you can go and sell your idea to them. So that is why I have an issue with the JIT model fitting the upstream as I know it (Interviewee #9).</i></p> <p>Quote 5: <i>With the advent of technology, you know technology permeates in all sectors of businesses and so with the advent of technology in making production exploratory much easier and so it is very key if petroleum industry wants to be very competitive firms in that sector need high grade of technology (Interviewee #13).</i></p> <p>Quote 6: <i>People have to be checking the integrity of the wells to make sure this well is not leaking so that we may have a huge oil leak coming but a small sip.(Interviewee #10)</i></p>	
<p>Quote 1: <i>Ok! So what I was trying to emphasise was, you know JIT is usually synonymous to Toyota kind of model, on the upstream. Especially in Ghana as a case study. There is much more to it than just in time. Just in time works very well with manufacturing. Because of all these uncertainties around it, it's not a fit for purpose module for the upstream industry. (Interviewee #7).</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>All we need to do, especially in the upstream industry, is to be able to show to management or decision makers that if you do XYZ, this will be the results and then they will follow XYZ. (Interviewee #12).</i></p> <p>Quote 3: <i>So the LEAN system shouldn't be based on all the nice findings with values and focus on money and profit and loss which is a typical corporate system, without taking into consideration some of the benefit being political benefits. ((Interviewee #2)</i></p> <p>Quote 4:</p>	<p>Lean Implementation Strategies</p>

<p><i>getting the human resource that is required to support the industry and here I am talking about locally and then also how to make sure that the local companies that will get involved are able to deliver to the best of ability that is required to enhance the industry because what happens is that sometimes you get a local company involved and then the expectation that we require normally doesn't come. (Interviewee #12)</i></p>	
<p>Quote 1: <i>So local content is also one of the main focus of the government to ensure that Ghanaians are also given the opportunity to participate in the upstream industry. The local content law actually seeks the opportunity into the upstream industry to actually seek opportunity for Ghanaians to participate in the upstream industry. (Interviewee #11).</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>The quota system to restrict importation of expatriates' services into the country has really made relatively dutiful for local content participation. ((Interviewee #8)</i></p> <p>Quote 3: <i>You know we started this petroleum stuff not too long ago and we don't really have more home grown individuals that have the capacity to you know do much of the work there and so Ghana now is kind of relying more on expatriates to do the work ((Interviewee #13)</i></p>	<p>People Management</p>
<p>Quote 1: <i>So I think process improvement and the continuous process improvement in learning how to do these new things that the industry has provided for us will help the local companies in their quest to participate in the industry ((Interviewee #14)</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>And then I think that we must think technology because the petroleum sector needs that in order to ensure that really we achieve the lean objectives as we want to do. ((Interviewee #13)</i></p> <p>Quote 3: <i>Again we need very experienced people in the oil and gas because you know it is a venture that is very expensive; it is a venture that is very risky; it is a venture that is serious business (Interviewee #12).</i></p> <p>Quote 4:</p>	<p>Continuous Improvement</p>

<p><i>So talking about leadership from the government side we can see a lot of improvement I can say we are not there yet and I see that only from the Petroleum Commission because we can see that the Petroleum Commission is getting more serious in trying to make sure the local content is enhanced.(Interviewee #12)</i></p>	
<p>Quote 1: <i>So are to ensure that petroleum activities are conducted in a cost efficient manner so that monetary benefit can come it to the development of Ghana. (Interviewee #3).</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>When it comes to the oil and gas industry, we probably want to achieve, we want to get more money, efficiency, safety and, so that is our focus. (Interviewee #5).</i></p> <p>Quote 3: <i>Your hear companies say cost cutting, cost cutting is a form of LEAN (Interviewee #11)</i></p>	<p>Business Priorities</p>
<p>Quote 1: <i>So in the upstream industry many jurisdictions have abandonment policy where you can some of them you put money, every barrel of oil you produce in an account so that by 25 years 30 years down the line when everything is depleted you can fall on that money to go and clean up the mess that was caused by the industry. (Interviewee #13).</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>That is in charge of policy direction, we have the regulator, which is the Petroleum Commission, which ensures efficiency in the conduct of petroleum activities. (Interviewee #4).</i></p>	<p>Corporate Policy and Strategy Formulation</p>
<p>Quote 1: <i>Because, at the end of the day it is the president of the day that appoints the CEO of GNPC so it's difficult to remove that interference. As independence that they might seem, the CEO is appointed by the president of the government of the day, and the CEO is the head of the entity that holds a portion of the block and the decisions that are made, every decision that are made are made with GNPC, every decision that are made on any block are made with GMPC. GMPC is government, and governments is every four years either changes or extended. That part is always going to be there, and it's something that in future we can have another look, and made GMPC autonomous, semi-autonomous and run like an autonomous entity void of any political interference (Interviewee #5).</i></p> <p>Quote 2:</p>	<p>Leadership</p>

As I said earlier on leaders would want to have profits; they would want to have sustainable production, they would want to have quality of products that you know they send to consumers and so these are the things that I think management expect are leaders expect from you know the you know the implementation of the lean (Interviewee #1)

Quote 3:

I have always wondered... I have a feeling that when it comes to leadership politically, although there are regulators, they don't really act or depend on government. That is my personal opinion or take on that and so for me I think that there are some contracts that I feel honestly that is my feeling. I feel that these contracts are awarded to people who are not really qualified. And this is usually based on you know the kind of association or the kind of relationship that has been created by the political elites with this business and I have a funny feeling that there might be underhand dealings in that regard. And so for me I think that the government needs to play a less active role so that we can have an independent regulator who will oversee issues of emm...this nature so that when it comes recruitment, contract issues, bidding we should have...because the Minister of Energy has a say in issues of who wins what contract and all that. And for me I think that we must leave the regulators alone so that they will have their independent opinions and work as such. And so I have a funny feeling that there is the issue of underhand dealings which could be eliminated from the whole process. ((Interviewee #13)

Quote 4:

So as for corruption there is...I have that feeling that there might be some corrupt activities just to favour businesses to engage in you know the exploration or production of petroleum products in that regard (Interviewee #13).

Quote 5:

Because in Ghana for example, we know that institutions have been set up to manage the revenues coming from the oils specifically, but once again either perceptions or even reports coming from the same institutions that have been charged to monitor the effectiveness of these resources have shown that the resources has been misapplied, has been siphoned, for example, we know of the public accountability regime if you like, and then also there was a fund set up called the heritage fund that as it were some percentage will be set aside but these issues have become a topic of too much controversy from government to government. In Ghana here, we are talking about from NDC to NPP regimes, the two of them coming in and out at the same time and everybody accusing each other of corruption and siphoning the resources and now that it is quite horrible really, that the managers of this have come clearly in the public to say, well, this government officials or institution collect so much money and say they are putting up so much edifice. At the end of the day, following the change of government, they come and say, well, the edifice is not standing there, but the money has been siphoned and that is the end of the story. No, what do you call persecution, nothing, and that

<p><i>is the bane of Africa. That is the bane of the African people ((Interviewee #3)</i></p> <p>Quote 6: <i>I think leadership is one other challenge in the implementation of lean processes ...(Interviewee #8).</i></p>	
<p>Quote 1: <i>PC does well to organise seminar and invites service companies and operators to attend so that it expands on its vision for the oil and gas industry in Ghana, so that everybody is aligned, everybody knows what to do to abide by the laws. (Interviewee # 3)</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>But talking about regulation, our regulator is the petroleum commission. (Interviewee #15).</i></p> <p>Quote 3: <i>So the government of Ghana took it upon itself to ensure that we put some systems in place to run at par with the international industry, because the oil and gas industry is an international industry. (Interviewee #15).</i></p> <p>Quote 4: <i>So it is a big challenge for the upstream petroleum sector because you know there are regulatory bodies like the Environmental Protection Agency that have standards that we must meet.(Interviewee #13)</i></p>	<p>Standardization and Regulation</p>
<p>Quote 1: <i>so there may be other blocks that are yet to go out there but the initial data and the initial research that would take place with the preparation of the initial exploration activities that would take place would be done by the GNPC. So they lead the exploration, development, production and disposal of petroleum resources in Ghana by leveraging the right means of domestic and foreign investments in partnership with the people of Ghana. (Interviewee #14).</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>That seems quite promising but even with that sort of promise we are not looking at anything happening significantly till 2021-2022 new development phase because there is the last check, the POD which is their plan on development is still up for consideration with the parliament and the regulator which is petroleum commission (GNPC) (Interviewee #5)</i></p>	<p>Vested Interests / Resource Ownership</p>

<p>Quote 3: <i>Each country is operating with Silos, so unlike when you go to the North Sea there is a hub at Aberdeen and there is hub in Norway, we don't have the hub system. ((Interviewee #9)</i></p>	
<p>Quote 1: <i>That is law Act 821 which gives us the mandate to ensure cost efficiency, exploitation and witty allegations of petroleum resources (Interviewee # 2)</i></p>	Operational Efficiency
<p>Quote 1: <i>But the safety system failed the well which led to oil spilling in the Gulf of Mexico, affecting lives, a lot of people dying on the rigs (Interviewee #1).</i></p> <p>Quote 2: <i>The upstream industry has a lot of impact on the environment. (Interviewee #12).</i></p> <p>Quote 3: <i>What I mean by sustainable resource is they produce having in mind that it would last longer than it should and so we have reservoir management team members put there (Interviewee #9).</i></p>	Safety, Health and Environment and Sustainability
<p>Quote 1: <i>You talked about human capacity development as one of the key aspects of the... and we are looking at waste within the upstream system so having the right people at the right place creating a living entity and everything. ((Interviewee #5)</i></p>	Waste Elimination
<p>Quote 1: <i>I think a lot of it comes down to people's personalities. If you will go get us steamy heads or person that considers anything as an obstacle, then you will want things to happen and expect people to just to do what they need to do but the people don't have the tools, the techniques, the will or thought to do what. Somebody else thinks the need to do to implement a new process. Then this program is not going to be entirely successful. ((Interviewee #7)</i></p>	Organisational Culture and Work Environment
<p>Quote 1: <i>I think the challenges are mainly two, as I sit here and I see. The first one is training and capacity building. In fact, that is the biggest problem we have in Ghana. In the oil industry, what pertains it that we deal with certification, and if you do not have the requisite certification you would not be allowed to work in the oil industry. It is an international</i></p>	Shop Floor Management

valve; they look into it. They look into risks involved in there and therefore they are specific certification requirements that if one of us working in the industry does not have, and because Ghana does not have that, we are actually challenged as to how to get our local people trained to have the requisite certification to be able to work in the oil industry (Interviewee #3).

Quote 2:

All we need to do, especially in the upstream industry, is to be able to show to management or decision makers that if you do XYZ, this will be the results and then they will follow XYZ. And XYZ as I said is profit making, efficiency, safety, value addition and whatever the result is and quantify it to the LEAN system you want us to do that is for, we go for it ((Interviewee #3)

Quote 3:

We are trying to build the capacity to make sure that in 30 years' time, if there is no oil in Ghana, we can boast of other relevant skills that can be transferred to the manufacturing sector of Ghana, and we might have also trained competent people to lead. Like the oil and gas benefitted from the qualified accountants and safety engineers that the mining companies have trained. So that is how we strategically develop and think about the future ((Interviewee #4).

Source: Author's Construct (2020)

Figure 5. 2: Concept Map

5.2.5 Defining and Naming Themes and Write-up

The fifth phase of the Braun and Clarke (2006) thematic analysis procedure involves defining and naming themes by developing detailed analysis of the themes generated from the previous phase.

This provides the scope and focus of each themes supported by relevant literature.

Therefore, to further develop themes from the initial themes generated and reviewed, axial coding was further employed to capture the emerging relationships into more condensed categories consistent with extant literature (Strauss & Corbin, 1990; Mey & Mruck, 2011; Vollstedt & Rezat, 2019). Thus, the process of defining and naming themes that emerged from the qualitative research yielded ten (10) themes:

Table 5. 4: Emerging Themes

1. Continuous Improvement
2. Petroleum Policy and Strategy
3. HRM, Culture and Change Management
4. Leadership and Governance
5. Engineering Project Management
6. Safety, Health and Environment and Sustainability
7. Stakeholder Engagement
8. Standardization and Regulation
9. Waste Elimination
10. Shop Floor Management

According to Braun and Clarke (2006), the write-up phase concludes the six-phase thematic analysis procedure and in the case of this research the write-up phase involved critical discussion on the themes generation process which culminated the emergence of ten (10) themes. Furthermore, based on the exploratory sequential design approach adopted in this research (Creswell, 2015), the ten themes from the qualitative research are mapped to the ten most frequently occurring Lean elements from literature (Table 2.6). Table 5.4 illustrates the mapping of Lean elements from literature to themes from qualitative research with the aim of developing constructs for the quantitative aspect of the research.

5.2.6 Qualitative analysis in the context of Research Position

This research has been positioned based on insights drawn from research objectives which further informed the decision to adopt the research union approach (Saunders et al., 2012; Creswell, 2015). The thematic analysis adopted in the qualitative research explored the experiences of Lean practices in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. According to Saunders et al., (2012), phenomenology as a research strategy explores how people make meaning from lived experiences. In the structure of this research, phenomenology was adopted as the most appropriate strategy based on the research union approach (Saunders et al., 2012). Furthermore, the analysis and results of the qualitative research formed the basis for quantitative research and hence the adoption of the exploratory sequential research design approach (Creswell, 2015). The research strategy[phenomenology] anchored the qualitative aspect of the research, and creates a link which transitioned the qualitative aspect of research to the quantitative aspect the research, and consequently provided a holistic approach and solution to the research objectives which fundamentally underpinned the study. However, notwithstanding the choice of phenomenology as

the preferred strategy for this research and which has been extensively discussed under section 4.5.10, other qualitative methods including case studies, ethnography, narrative research, archival research and grounded theory (Straus and Cobin, 1998; Bryman, 2001; Hjorth and Steyaert, 2004; Yin, 2014; Creswell, 2014; 2015).

Table 5. 5: Mapping of Themes from Interviews to Lean Elements from Literature

Themes from Interviews	Elements from SLR
Continuous Improvement	Continuous Improvement
Petroleum Policy and Strategy	Leadership and Direction
HRM, Culture and Change Management	Elimination of waste
Leadership and Governance	HRM/Respect for humanity/People management
Engineering Project Management	Standardisation
Safety, Health and Environment and Sustainability	Customer Relationship Management/ Customer Focus
Stakeholder Engagement	Lean awareness training and education
Standardization and Regulation	Supplier Relationship Management
Waste Elimination	Building Lean Expert Team
Shop Floor Management	Top Management Commitment

Source: Author's Construct (2020).

5.3 Constructs Development Process

The quantitative approach in this study seeks to test the relationship between Lean Elements and organization's competitive priorities. Constructs for the independent variables (Lean Elements) and the dependent variables (competitive priorities) were derived both from literature and the qualitative analysis. Selection of constructs for the independent variables were based on a review of 101 existing lean frameworks. At the end of the review, out of the 123 Lean Elements identified (Table 2.6), the 10 most dominant were identified and constructs developed for each (Table 2.7). Womack and Jones (1996) contend that lean doubles labour productivity, reduces lead times by 90%, reduces inventories by 90%, and reduces both quality defects and job related injuries by 50%. Mackelprang and Nair (2010) recently confirmed that lean leads to increased performance in an empirical study that showed a positive association between lean and aggregate performance - a construct comprised of quality, cost, inventory, cycle time, flexibility and delivery performance.

Based on the mapping in Table 5.4, between the two sets of data from literature and from the qualitative analysis, five common elements were identified and selected as constructs for the quantitative research. The five constructs include;

1. Continuous Improvement
2. HRM, Culture and Change Management
3. Leadership and Governance
4. Standardization and Regulation
5. Waste Elimination

These five (5) constructs were therefore selected for further quantitative analysis in order to validate the themes from the qualitative research and also to test the relationships between lean elements and competitive business priorities. Detailed explanations of each of the elements is presented below:

5.3.1 Lean Elements

Based on literature reviewed, 5 of the most frequently occurring Lean elements include waste elimination, leadership direction, continuous improvement, standardisation and human resource management. These elements are discussed below:

- *Waste Elimination*

Waste elimination is one of the principal lean elements. Effective waste elimination must commence with waste recognition/identification. Once waste is recognized, its causes must be understood (Seddon, O'Donovan and Zokaei, 2011), and addressed in order to achieve successful waste elimination process. Proponents of lean manufacturing originally identified eight wastes which are already captured in the literature review section of this research (Ohno, 1988; Liker, 2004). These universal lean wastes provide a framework for the identification and classification of wastes associated with specific sectors. The overarching importance of this process cannot be overemphasized as it provides the basis for any effective lean implementation initiatives. Extant literature show how lean waste has been translated to suite different sectors. A few examples of mapping lean wastes to specific sectors are presented below:

According to Radnor et al., (2006), the eight wastes for services include; delay, duplication, unnecessary movement, unclear communication, incorrect inventory, opportunity lost, errors and people. However, Sarkar (2008) argue that the eight wastes are universally applicable and therefore did not require sector specific identification. In identifying waste in the public sector, Waterman and McCue (2012) identified the “excessive amounts of guidance, elongated timescales, serial processing, inefficient supplier engagement, input based specifications and risk aversion waste in public procurement.

Similarly, Radnor et al (2006), identified wastes associated with public sector including: rework, preparing unnecessary reports, working with badly designed IT systems, firefighting, working from unreliable information, checking other people's work, too many meetings/working groups, progress chasing, doing things others have already done, obtaining authorisation, work not fit for purpose and dealing with failure demand. Drawing from the foregone discourse, this study translated lean waste associated with the upstream petroleum sector (Table 2.3).

- *Leadership Direction*

Leadership is the most important critical success factor in the lean implementation process (Achanga et al., 2006b, Taner, 2013, Nordin and Deros, 2017, Thi, Nguyen and Chinh, 2017). Lean implementation is conventionally a top-down approach (Jagoda, Lonseth and Lonseth, 2013). The quality of leadership mirrors the strategic focus/direction of the organization and its concomitant superior performance. Mann (2009) indicates that 80% of lean implementation initiative is spent on changing leaders' practices and behaviours, and ultimately their mindset. The pivotal role leaders play right from initiating lean programs and providing the requisite support by creating an enabling culture that supports lean implementation efforts cannot be overemphasized. Lean leadership epitomizes the role of leadership in lean implementation process by ensuring lean efforts are sustained (Alefari, Salonitis and Xu, 2017b). Leaders create organizational mission, vision and values that support continuous improvement initiatives (Futerer, 2004, Wong, 2010, Ogunbiyi, 2014a). Furthermore, Mackenzie and Hall (2014) posit that leadership commitment and creation of a Lean-focused vision is pivotal to "stakeholders' understanding of the benefits of Lean for themselves or for the organization as a whole. Different levels of organisational leadership hierarchy assume complimentary, yet overlapping, roles in the implementation of Lean (Mann, 2009). Literature is laden with critical

analysis on the role of leadership in lean implementation success. The selection of leadership as one core element in this study attest not only to it being a critical success factor, but also as one of the most frequently used elements in the development of lean frameworks (Anand and Kodali, 2009a, 2010, Netland, 2016c, Jasti and Kodali, 2019).

- *Continuous Improvement*

Continuous Improvement (CI) is the bedrock of lean manufacturing and seeks to create and sustain a culture of change and a consistently progressive work environment. It is one of the key pillars of lean manufacturing, and it is at the heart of every business to create efficiency through continuous improvement (Khan et al., 2019). It is also perceived as a managerial approach to achieve organizational competitive advantage through gradual and sustained improvements (Alvarado-Ramírez et al., 2018) In a highly competitive business landscape, continuous improvement plays a pivotal role in business sustainability (Khan et al., 2019). Furthermore, proponents of lean manufacturing underscore the significance of kaizen or continuous improvement in manufacturing efficiency and overall operational performance (Ohno, 1988; Liker, 2004). To buttress this assertion, Jha et al. (1996) state that a better understanding of how Continuous Improvement contributes to an organization's mission and strategy will increase its chances of success. However, while admitting the overall importance of continuous improvement in business competitiveness and performance, implementation challenges still exist. Nonetheless, continuous improvement as a lean element, and a manufacturing improvement technique remains a critical business improvement requirement (Carnerud, Jaca and Bäckström, 2018, Chaurasia et al., 2019). Insights drawn from critical analysis of 101 existing frameworks for lean implementation across different sectors show that continuous improvement is one key pillar in the lean implementation process. Thus,

whether continuous improvement is critical in the upstream petroleum sector is examined in this research.

- *Standardisation*

Standard work is a foundational lean tool for shop floor operations and involves specifying standards for process operation. Thus, it is important to note that without standards, there cannot be improvement (Bragança and Costa, 2015). Standard work ensures that work processes are completed in a consistent, timely and repeatable manner which helps eliminate variations and improve throughput (Lu and Yang, 2015). Standard work consists of a set of work procedures and/or routines which establishes the most appropriate sequence for each process and for each worker (Bragança and Costa, 2015). Stated differently, standard work aims at eliminating variations and inconsistency of results by educating workers to undertake manufacturing activities with strict adherence to laid down procedures. This is achieved by clear definition of operational work procedures with little or no room for personal discretion. Therefore, the operations are often referred as an inflexible work standard. These standards are used as auxiliary training tools (Womack and Jones, 2003). When standard work is effectively implemented, employee discretion is limited and hence strict adherence to laid down regulations lead to desired results and improvement opportunities. Standard work/standardization is therefore an essential tool for continuous improvement, because it facilitates change to improved standards, making it easier, faster and more efficient (Oliveira et al., 2017).

- *Human Resources Management*

One salient pillar in lean manufacturing implementation is the “people aspect” of the implementation process without which success remains an illusion. Human resources

management or people management consist of the process of talent acquisition, development, deployment and monitoring. It involves putting in place a “system” to manage the employee life cycle within the organization to ensure mutual benefit is achieved for both employee and organization. According to Arthur and Boyles (2007), HR systems identified in the ‘90s refers to “*a set of distinctive, but interrelated activities, functions and processes that are directed at attracting, developing and maintaining (or disposing of) the firm’s human resources*” (Lado and Wilson, 1994, p. 701). A relatively recent definition indicate that HR systems represents clusters of work practices and employment ones, oriented to a certain group of employees (Boxall and Mackey, 2009). Another definition is that “*HR systems are clusters of work and employment practices that have evolved to manage major hierarchical or occupational groups in the firm*” (Boxall and Purcell, 2011, p. 228-229). Effective HR practices constitute an essential prerequisite for successful lean implementation initiatives. Therefore, human resources management as an element of lean manufacturing is an anchor of the entire lean success effort.

“A number of recent studies state that not substantial research has been conducted into the human resource aspects associated with lean implementation (Angelis et al., 2011; Bonavía and Marín-García, 2011). Despite Lean involving significant changes in Human Resource practices and policies (Biazzo and Panizzolo, 2000), there is no consensus in the literature on the way that Lean might affect people (Conti et al., 2006; de Treville and Antonakis, 2006), or the role of Human Resource policies and practices during the Lean implementation process (Liker and Hoseus, 2010; Bonavía and Marín-García, 2011). There are various lines of research in the literature that links Lean and Human Resource Management that focus on describing the HR policies and practices associated with Lean (Forza,1996; Niepce and Molleman, 1996; Pil and MacDuffie, 1996; Biazzo and Panizzolo, 2000; Olivella et al., 2008), the impact that Lean

implementation has on people (Forrester, 1995; Niepce and Molleman, 1996; Conti et al., 2006; de Treville and Antonakis, 2006) and the influence that Lean-associated HR practices have on performance (Shah and Ward, 2003; Bonavía and Marín-García, 2011). However, despite the importance of managing Human Resource for Lean Production, significant emphasis observed in the literature appear to be on the technical aspects of the implementation process than on the people and cultural change aspects of the lean transition process (Martínez-Jurado, 2014). Thus, while a range of studies have analysed the general success factors in Lean adoption and implementation (Worley and Doolen, 2006; Turesky and Connell, 2010; Pedersen and Huniche, 2011), there are few that analyse the success factors of Human Resource Management in detail. There is no consensus on what the main success factors are in these studies, although different authors suggest different factors based on peculiar perspectives. Olivella et al. (2008), for example, identify Lean-oriented work organisation strategies, including standardisation, ongoing training, teamwork, participation and empowerment, versatility, commitment to company values, and contingent rewards. Meanwhile, Bonavía and Marín-García (2011) point to Lean-oriented companies promoting flexibility and versatility, investing in training and committing to variable compensation. The literature on advanced human resource practices (Huselid, 1995; MacDuffie, 1995; Pil and MacDuffie, 1996) identifies Human Resource factors that have a good fit with Lean, including teamwork, job rotation, ongoing training, contingent rewards, job security, versatility and participation” (Martínez-Jurado, 2014).

5.3.2 Competitive Priorities

The researcher adopted the constructs for the dependent variables, or competitive priorities from literature - Dangayach and Deshmukh (2000), Sharma and Kodali (2008), Anand and Kodali (2009), Jasti and Kodali (2017), Rachman and Ratnayake (2018) and Jasti and Kodali (2019) who developed various frameworks for Lean manufacturing across varied industries. Specifically, the survey questionnaire for this research is adapted from Jasti and Kodali (2019).

- *Quality*

Quality is defined as “conformance to requirements”(Hoyer, 2001). Quality is perceived as a major factor in the global business quality evolution , and it has proved to be the most powerful creators of sales, and revenue growth (Ribbins and Whale, 1991). The works of quality gurus such as Deming, Crosby and Juran fundamentally establish quality as a management science. According to Crosby, quality is defined as “Conformance to requirements” and must focus on measurable actions based on tangible targets rather than on experience or opinions (Crosby, 1979). Juran opined that quality is achieved through the quality trilogy (Juran, 1986), including quality planning, quality control and quality improvement. Deming suggested that quality cannot be achieved in an organisation without educating leadership on importance of quality – obligations, principles and methods (Krishnaiah and Rao, 1988). The research on quality excellence has been building over the theories of these three masters” (Sunder, 2016).

Quality is achieved through the implementation of lean and other improvement methodologies. The link between quality and the application of lean production principles (methods), for example, presented by Roriz, Nunes and Sousa (2017). They show how improvements based on the 5S technique and visual management achieved an average reduction of 47% setup time in a carton company. Lee and Peccei (2008) analysed determinants of employee quality commitment from low and high lean plant samples. They found that employee quality commitment differs in relative importance at different stages of lean production implementation.

- *Cost Reduction*

One of the four goals of lean management is through reducing costs. Lean management introduces “approaches and methods aimed at reducing all kinds of costs and increasing

production productivity (Ostaev et al., 2019). Savings on basic materials, auxiliary materials, energy, and other costs are taken into account when calculating the savings from cost reduction as a result of the introduction of the basic tools of lean manufacturing and improving the operation of the applied equipment and technology (Selezneva, Selezneva, 2017). Changing the entire production system in the complex, according to the proposed principles of lean production management, will reduce not only costs but also internal losses, while additionally we get free labour and other resources (Ostaev et al., 2018a; Ostaev et al., 2018b). Efforts of lean production management are based in the form of business processes that do not increase the cost of products from the point of view of the consumer and, accordingly, do not increase the added value for the enterprise of the consumer cooperation system (Ostaev et al., 2019).

Efforts of lean production management are based in the form of business processes that do not increase the cost of products from the point of view of the consumer and, accordingly, do not increase the added value for the enterprise of the consumer cooperation system” (Ostaev et al., 2019). When quality is improved through the application of appropriate tools, techniques and practices, a corresponding reduction in rate of defective products, elimination of waste and reduction in operational cost accrue as benefits to the organization. Also, a reduction in lead time enhances efficiency and reduction in facility cost. Overall, cost reduction is achieved through the effective implementation of lean. Senior managers view operational cost as the most important factor which must be on check at all times since higher operational cost will affect overall price per unit and which will have a rippled effect on sales and profitability.

5.3.3 Hypotheses Development

In order to develop Lean framework, the researcher developed the hypotheses between Lean Elements and Competitive Priorities which is consistent with Anand and Kodali (2009). The

research hypotheses are based on a comprehensive literature review of 101 frameworks, and competitive business priorities are stated below:

5.3.4 Composite hypotheses

- 1. There is a positive relationship between Lean Elements and Quality*
- 2. There is a positive relationship between Lean Elements and Cost*

5.3.5 Individual hypotheses

- 1a. There is a positive relationship between Waste Elimination and Quality*
- 1b. There is a positive relationship between Leadership Direction and Quality*
- 1c. There is a positive relationship between Continuous Improvement and Quality*
- 1d. There is a positive relationship between Standardization and Quality*
- 1e. There is a positive relationship between Human Resources Management and Quality*
- 2a. There is a positive relationship between Waste Elimination and Cost Reduction*
- 2b. There is a positive relationship between Leadership Direction and Cost Reduction*
- 2c. There is a positive relationship between Continuous Improvement Cost Reduction*
- 2d. There is a positive relationship between Standardization and Cost Reduction*
- 2e. There is a positive relationship between Human Resources Management and Cost Reduction*

5.4 Introduction to SEM

This section presents the various approaches used to analyse data collected from respondents in order to address the hypotheses formulated earlier in this research. The analysis was conducted in two sections; the first part of the analysis employed the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and the second part of the analysis focused on confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The

CFA was conducted using structural equation modelling (SEM) and the analytical tools used for the exercise was AMOS 21. Subsequent sections would comprehensively describe the stages involved in the data analysis process.

5.5 Data Preparation and Purification

Literature has indicated that data analysis requires a host of activities and as a result issues pertaining to cleaning of the data, correct coding and efficient data entry strategy is required before proper data analysis begins (Saunders et al., 2009). The essence of data purification and preparation exercise is to ensure error free data which could compromise the findings of the study. Baumgartner and Homburg (1996) supported the assertion of cleaning the data and ensuring suitability of the data by postulating that such exercise ensures coding error and missing values are eliminated in order to have effective and efficient data analysis results.

Responses were obtained from questionnaire administered (see Appendix A) to five hundred and fifteen (515) shop floor employees within the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. After carefully cleaning and exporting data from excel to SPSS spreadsheet, a review of the data indicates that twelve (12) responses were found to be below the 75% completion rate as suggested by Sekaran (2000). Therefore, the final sample size remained for the analysis was five hundred and three (503) collected within the upstream petroleum sector.

5.6 Demographic Profile of Respondents

The demographic information of the respondents obtained were analysed in this section. The essence of this exercise was to ascertain the respondent's knowledge on the chosen research topic. The section considered the age, gender, educational status, employment status, position held and the core activities of the company in which the respondent work with. The table below provides accurate information on the demographic profile of the respondents.

Table 5. 6: Respondents Profile

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	285	56.7
Female	218	43.3
Age		
18-27	57	11.3
28-37	165	32.8
38-47	150	29.8
48-57	83	16.5
58+	48	9.5
Educational Status		
SHS	206	41
Diploma	42	8.3
Degree	12	2.4
Post-graduate	46	9.1
Others	197	39.2
Employment Status		
Casual worker	425	84.5
Permanent Staff	78	15.5
Designation		
Factory supervisor	193	38.4
Factory worker	247	49.1
factory manager	63	12.5
Core Activities		
Exploration	265	52.7
Production	205	40.8
Well Development	33	6.6
Total	503	100

Source: Author's Construct (2020)

From table 5.6, it could be deduced that males dominated the study and they constituted about 57% of the total respondents. With respect to educational status of the respondents, all the respondents answered affirmatively that they have had some level of formal education with majority in the SHS bracket (n=206). The status of the respondents with regards to their employment was also examined and the outcome of the analysis stipulated that most of the respondents were casual workers (n=425) in the upstream petroleum sector. The roles of the

respondents were further studied and the outcome of the analysis implies that factory workers (n=247) dominated in this study and factory supervisors were second on the list in this column. The last element examined under the demographic profile of the respondents was the core activities pursued by the firms in the upstream petroleum sector. From the results generated, exploration was found to be the most dominated activity in the upstream petroleum sector.

5.7 Descriptive Statistics

The issue of descriptive analysis of measurement scales adopted for a study has become popular as research mostly involves human participant (Pallant, 2011). To comprehend the essence of descriptive statistics to determine the normality of the measurement scales, Kline (2005) emphasized the importance of such exercise. The rationale behind the descriptive analysis is to ascertain the distribution of the variables using mean, mode, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis in determining the normality of the itemized scale. Pallant (2011) further argued that, descriptive analysis is required before any further analysis. Against this background, the 47 total item scales were subjected to descriptive analysis in order to measure the respondents' level of agreement or disagreement to the statement used in the questionnaire. The table below presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. From the table, the highest mean was 4.26 (Reduction in labour cost through job enlargement) whilst the lowest mean was 3.83 (Elimination of all forms of wastes and non-value adding activities).

Table 5. 7: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics	Code	Mean	Std. Deviation
Elimination of all forms of wastes and non-value adding activities	WE1	3.83	1.236
Reduction in Storage Space	WE2	3.88	0.95
Reduction in changeover/start-up times	WE3	4.08	0.801
Supports the adoption of flat organisational structures	WE4	4.03	0.962
Enhances production levelling to eliminate waste	WE5	4	0.996
Leadership support my company's lean implementation initiatives	LD1	4	0.899
Leadership is fully committed to lean implementation initiatives	LD2	4.21	0.794
Leadership inspires long term and sustainable business thinking	LD3	4.06	0.919
Leadership develop and communicate the company's values	LD4	4.08	0.887
Leadership creates and enhances a learning culture	LD5	4.02	0.859
Horizontal and Vertical Information System	LD6	3.98	0.895
Use of Problem-Solving Tools	CI1	4.08	0.883
Zero defects by total training for operators	CI2	3.98	0.994
Compliance to safety Improvement Programmes	CI3	4.01	0.974
Elimination of Buffers	CI4	3.83	1.206
Total Productive Maintenance	CI5	4.14	0.873
Multifunctional Training	CI6	4.13	0.898
New Process or Equipment Technologies	CI7	4.02	0.925
Process simplification	CI8	4.05	0.886
Use of flat hierarchy to enhance innovation	CI9	3.93	1.08
Regular Performance reviews and progress to towards targets	CI10	4.07	0.856
Compliance to standard operating procedures	ST1	4.07	0.976
Standardised work processes	ST2	4.05	0.956
Clarification of roles and responsibilities	ST3	4.17	0.856
Standardised Tools and Equipment	ST4	4.19	0.821
Standardised Tools and Equipment	ST5	4.11	0.816
Automation	ST6	4.11	0.884
Long-Term Employment opportunities	HRM1	3.62	1.297
strategic direction of the company motivates all employees	HRM2	4.17	0.902
Employee Empowerment	HRM3	4.19	0.825
Employee involvement and Participation	HRM4	4.17	0.837
Rewards and Recognition initiatives	HRM5	4.17	0.817
Cross-Functional Teamwork	HRM6	4.18	0.835
Suggestion Schemes	HRM7	4.08	0.795
Job Enrichment	HRM8	4.13	0.82
Communication Between Employees	HRM9	4.11	0.831
Have Lean Problem Solving Skills	HRM10	4.04	0.858
Employees have knowledge and awareness about lean methodology	HRM11	4.05	0.852
Reduction in scrap/rework and rejects	Q1	4.02	0.857

Strong process control systems enhance overall quality	Q2	4.02	0.889
Lean principles improve the quality of production process	Q3	3.92	1.038
Regular supplier audits to receive high quality raw materials and equipment	Q4	4.17	0.896
Reduction in labour cost through job enlargement	C1	4.26	0.871
Reduction in cost production costs through implementation JIT.	C2	3.96	1.036
Enhance employee commitment and motivation to reduce cost	C3	4.22	0.912
Lean Principles minimises the cost of petroleum products produced	C4	3.97	0.979
Market volatility and price fluctuation adversely affect production cost	C5	4.15	0.932

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

5.8 Exploratory Factor Analysis

Prior to execute the structural relationships among the constructs earmarked for the study, the entire research variables were subjected to exploratory factor analysis to determine the reliability of the items used for the study. Therefore, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity were used for the exercise. Furthermore, the Cronbach alpha for the measurement scales were also examined. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value was .960, exceeding the recommended value of 0.6 (Kaiser 1970) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Bartlett 1954) reached statistical significance (Approx.: Chi-square=14012.797, df. 1081, sig. 0.000), supporting the factorability of the correlation matrix. Table 5.8 below displays the results of the KMO and Bartlett's Test which was ran for the data obtained from the respondents.

Table 5. 8: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.960
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	14012.797
	df	1081
	Sig.	.000

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

The Cronbach alpha which represents the reliability of constructs was also assessed to determine suitability of the elements with regards to the minimum threshold of 0.70 as suggested by scholars (Hair et al., 2010). As presented in table 5.9 below the Cronbach alpha of the total 47 items were subjected to reliability test and the outcome of the analysis revealed that 5 items were deleted (WE1, WE5, CI4, HRM1 and ST6) and 42 items remained for further analysis to assess the hypotheses formulated for the study.

Table 5. 9: Reliability Assessment

ITEMS	CODES	Cronb Alpha	No. Of Items	Item-Total Correlation	Alpha If Item is deleted
Factor1	WE2	0.781	3	0.582	0.746
	WE3			0.677	0.656
	WE4			0.612	0.713
Factor2	LD1	0.873	6	0.666	0.853
	LD2			0.542	0.872
	LD3			0.709	0.845
	LD4			0.729	0.841
	LD5			0.718	0.844
	LD6			0.681	0.85
Factor3	CI1	0.892	9	0.619	0.882
	CI2			0.714	0.874
	CI3			0.616	0.883
	CI5			0.697	0.877
	CI6			0.653	0.88
	CI7			0.673	0.878
	CI8			0.715	0.875
	CI9			0.571	0.888
	CI10			0.615	0.883
	Factor4			ST1	0.865
ST2		0.686	0.838		
ST3		0.672	0.84		
ST4		0.674	0.84		
ST5		0.697	0.837		
Factor5	HRM2	0.912	10	0.587	0.909
	HRM3			0.657	0.904
	HRM4			0.741	0.899
	HRM5			0.711	0.901
	HRM6			0.702	0.902
	HRM7			0.732	0.9
	HRM8			0.728	0.9
	HRM9			0.679	0.903
	HRM10			0.641	0.905

	HRM11			0.618	0.907
Factor6	Q1	0.78	4	0.619	0.711
	Q2			0.597	0.72
	Q3			0.562	0.744
	Q4			0.573	0.732
Factor7	C1	0.8	5	0.488	0.79
	C2			0.608	0.755
	C3			0.651	0.741
	C4			0.578	0.764
	C5			0.595	0.758

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

5.9 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

CFA has been suggested by scholars as an effective analytical method to support exploratory factor analysis (CFA) as the latter does not offer the opportunity to determine dimensionality. Based on this, structural equation modelling (SEM), AMOS 21 was employed to ascertain the robustness of the constructs adopted for the study (Bowen & Guo 2011). Hair et al (2010) therefore argued that a number of measured criteria are available to serve as a guide for the researcher to determine the fitness of the constructs. Notable measures suggested by the scholars include parsimony, overall and comparative fit. However, Bollen (1989) posited that the choice of any assessment rest on the researcher.

5.9.1 Measurement Model

The usability of structural equation modelling hinges on the constructs measuring common purpose (Jöreskog & Sörbom, 1996; Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). Failure to achieve such exercise requires model modification to meet the goodness-of-fit suggested in the literature (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). Therefore, the final 42 items used were subjected to modifications which resulted in several items dropped in order to meet the threshold specified by scholars (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012).

Figure 5. 3: Initial CFA Model

Source: Author's Construct (2021).

The processes involved in achieving the model fit for the study is specified in the table below. The final items remained with it corresponding fit indices are presented in the figure below signifying the suitability of the remained items under the constructs to determine structural relationships.

Table 5. 10:Model Fit Improvement

Stages	Modification	χ^2	GFI	NFI	CFI	RMSEA	TLI
		df					
1	Initial Assessment	3.144	0.799	0.812	0.863	0.065	0.852
2	Deletion (CI9, C1, LD2, Q3, HRM2)	3.320	0.816	0.829	0.873	0.068	0.861
3	Deletion (CI1, CI2, CI3, WE4, LD1, LD4, ST1, ST4, HRM5, HRM6, HRM7, HRM8, C3, Q1)	3.037	0.890	0.885	0.919	0.064	0.905
4	Deletion (LD5, CI7, CI8, CI10, ST2, HRM10, HRM11, Q1, C3)	2.765	0.947	0.934	0.956	0.059	0.937
5	Deletion (C5, HRM9)	2.390	0.964	0.954	0.973	0.053	0.956

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

Table 5.10 depicts the modification process as opined by scholars towards improving model fit of SEM (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012). The process resulted in deletion of several items in stages as expressed in the table. Therefore, the final elements remained with better model fit indices and no validity concerns as denoted in stage 5 of the deletion process is fourteen (14) which were suitable for SEM analysis in this study. Figure 5.4 therefore indicates the final measurement model for the study.

Figure 5. 4: Measurement Model

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

Table 5. 11: Model Fit Measures

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	132.083	--	--
DF	56	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.350	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.973	>0.95	Excellent
SRMR	0.028	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.053	<0.06	Excellent
PClose	0.369	>0.05	Excellent

Source: Hu and Bentler (1999) – Cut off Criteria for Fit Indexes

5.9.2 Validity Assessment

Table 5.12 below signifies the validity and reliability assessment of the final measurement model earmarked for the structural model assessment. The values obtained for the measurement of reliability as opined by scholars exceeded the minimum threshold (Fornell and Larcker, 1981) Thus, Cronbach’s alphas > .70, Average Variance Extracted > .50, composite reliability > .70). Therefore, the validity and reliability for the final items is presented in the table which signifies no issues concerning validity.

Table 5. 12: Validity Assessment

	CR	AVE	quality	waste	leader	continuous	standard	human	cost
quality	0.703	0.544	0.741						
waste	0.723	0.567	0.542	0.753					
leader	0.738	0.586	0.677	0.690	0.766				
continuous	0.775	0.633	0.647	0.736	0.733	0.796			
standard	0.784	0.645	0.648	0.618	0.672	0.601	0.803		
human	0.781	0.641	0.737	0.593	0.691	0.720	0.740	0.801	
cost	0.704	0.547	0.677	0.543	0.680	0.527	0.636	0.619	0.740

Source: Author’s Construct (2021). Note: *Variances extracted (VE) are on the diagonal; squared correlations are off-diagonal. The VEs for each construct are far greater than the corresponding inter-construct square correlations, thereby supporting discriminant validity.*

5.10 Structural Relationship

Relationship testing regarding research work could be assessed with dependence method such as regression analysis or structural equation modelling (SEM) techniques (Hair et al., 2014). SEM technique was deemed suitable for the study due to the complexity of the model and the robustness of the method in analysis involving interrelationships between latent constructs. Scholars have maintained that assessing structural relationships is the key purpose of SEM analysis. However, the execution of the structural models in SEM hinges on validation and

satisfying minimum thresholds opined in the literature (Anderson and Gerbing,1988; Kline, 2005). Byrne (2013) also indicated that structural models is used to determine whether latent constructs directly or indirectly influence the values of other latent constructs in the model. Therefore, the structural model conducted in this study was intended to test some hypothetical propositions based on the conceptual framework for this research. The outcomes of the structural relationships are presented in the figures and the table below.

5.10.1 Composite Assessment

The first major relationship examination was to determine the strength of relationship between lean management on cost and quality. Figure 5.5 and table 5.12 provides information relating to the composite analysis of Lean Management assessment on competitive priorities of firms in the upstream petroleum sector. From figure 5.5, it is deduced that Lean Management has significant effect on Cost and the relationship is explained by 0.69 (***). Lean Management was also found to have effect on Quality and the relationship had strength of 0.82 (***)

Figure 5. 5: Structural Relationship

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

Table 5. 13 : Model Fit for Composite Assessment

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	210.492	--	--
DF	71	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.965	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.952	>0.95	Excellent
SRMR	0.045	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.063	<0.06	Acceptable
PClose	0.017	>0.05	Acceptable

Source: Author’s Construct (2021)

5.10.2 Individual Hypothesis Assessment

The next major activity performed in this study was to determine the hypothetical relationships among the various elements of Lean Management (Waste Elimination, Human Resource Management, Continuous Improvement, Standardization and Leadership) on Cost and Quality representing Competitive Priorities in this study. The figure and the table below established the hypotheses assessment.

Figure 5. 6: Hypotheses Assessment

Source: Author’s Construct (2021)

Table 5. 14: Model Fit for Individual Assessment

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	164.542	--	--
DF	58	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.837	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.963	>0.95	Excellent
SRMR	0.034	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.060	<0.06	Acceptable
PClose	0.054	>0.05	Excellent

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

Table 5. 15: Hypotheses Assessment

Hypotheses	Relationships	β Estimates	T Values	P values	Outcome
H1a	Waste Elimination→ Quality	0.475	3.437	***	Supported
H1b	Leadership Direction→ Quality	0.289	2.228	0.026	Supported
H1c	Continuous Improvement→ Quality	0.597	3.403	***	Supported
H1d	Standardization→ Quality	0.089	0.862	0.477	Not supported
H1e	Human Resource→ Quality	0.811	4.915	***	Supported
H2a	Waste Elimination→ Cost	0.490	3.436	***	Supported
H2b	Leadership Direction→ Cost	0.357	2.604	0.009	Supported
H2c	Continuous Improvement→ Cost	0.674	3.697	***	supported
H2d	Standardization→ Cost	0.111	0.862	0.389	Not Supported
H2e	Human Resource→ Cost	0.683	4.291	***	Supported

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

From table 5.15, it could be deduced that eight (8) out of the ten (10) hypothesized relationships exhibited significant relationship. Thus, Lean Management (Waste Elimination, Continuous Improvement, Human Resource Management and Leadership) elements conceptualized in this

study were found to affect competitive priorities (Cost and Quality) of firms in the upstream petroleum sector. However, the analysis as proven in the table implies that Human Resource Management is the most highly significant element of Lean Management to drive competitive priorities of the firms in the upstream petroleum sector.

5.11 Summary of Results

The first part of chapter five focused on the results and findings of this research. The analysis of qualitative and quantitative data in line with research questions and hypotheses mirrored the process adopted in the development of the proposed conceptual lean framework for the upstream petroleum sector. In line with its pragmatist paradigm, the qualitative aspect of the mixed methods approach employed semi-structured interviews to collect data. These interviews were transcribed orthographically and analysed using a combination of inductive and deductive approaches. The researcher adopted the six-phase approach to conduct thematic analysis proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006). Codes were inductively generated from the data.

An application of deductive approach was used to generate initial themes which were subsequently reviewed leading to the emergence of final themes. The quantitative aspect of the research used structural equation modelling (SEM) to test the relationships between constructs or themes that emerged from the qualitative analysis. The exploratory factor analysis(EFA) was performed to determine the reliability of the items. After the EFA, a confirmatory factor analysis(CFA) was performed to test the relationship between the constructs. Finally, the hypotheses were tested to determine constructs that were significant and hence formed the basis for the development of the proposed conceptual lean framework. Detailed discussions of results and findings of this research is carried out in the next section of this chapter.

5.12 Discussion of Results

5.12.1 Introduction to Discussion

This section of the research discusses results and findings of the research and supports findings with literature. The overarching aim of this research was to develop a conceptual framework for lean application in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. Lean manufacturing as an innovative management strategy has been widely accepted and applied across sectors (Buus, 2011, Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015b, Netland, 2016c, Ankomah, Ayarkwa and Agyekum, 2017). This section of the research discusses the results and findings in relation to the literature review with specific focus on research questions and hypotheses with a view to finding best approach to achieve the objectives of the research.

According to Creswell (2015), the research question(s), provides answers to the research objectives and the problem statement of the research. Table 5.16 summarises the research questions, research objectives and the overarching problem statement guiding the conduct of this research.

Table 5. 16: Summary of research questions, objectives and problem statement

Research Questions	Research Objectives	Problem Statement
1.To what extent is LM suitable for implementation in upstream petroleum organisations in developing economies?	1.Explore LM tools, techniques and principles adaptable for the upstream petroleum sector.	The overarching problem statement guiding the conduct of this research is that though several Lean frameworks have so far been developed, none seeks to address the challenges facing Lean implementation within the upstream petroleum sector in developing economies.
2.How can LM be successfully implemented in upstream petroleum organisations?	1.To develop a conceptual LM framework for adoption in the upstream petroleum sector	
3.How best can Lean waste be translated/mapped to the upstream petroleum sector	1.To translate/map lean waste for the upstream petroleum sector.	
4.What factors support the development of a comprehensive framework ?	1.Review existing frameworks and identify key dimensions to successful framework development 2.To identify and evaluate critical success factors (CSFs) suitable for Lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector.	

5.What is the relationship between Lean principles and competitive business priorities?	1.To determine the relationships between Lean principles and competitive business priorities.	
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Source; Author’s Construct (2021)

The choice of pragmatism as a paradigm and anchor to this research, also informed the choice of mixed method approach which aligns with pragmatism in providing a comprehensive solution to the research objectives. The data integration approach adopted in this research was exploratory sequential design approach which requires the researcher to adopt a qualitative method, and the findings feed into the design of a quantitative method (Creswell, 2015). In this research, an exploratory sequential design was adopted not only because the population is perceived to be understudied, but also that it is misunderstood (Creswell, 2015).

5.12.2 Discussion of findings from qualitative analysis

In this study, the researcher adopted the six-phase thematic analysis approach proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006). The results of this process showed that ten themes emerged from a combination of inductive and deductive analytical processes. The themes that emerged from the qualitative analysis (see Table 5.3), are supported by literature (Sharma and Kodali, 2008, Anand and Kodali, 2010, Gurumurthy and Kodali, 2010, Karim and Arif-Uz-Zaman, 2013b, Jasti and Kodali, 2016, 2019). The results of the qualitative analysis addressed the fourth research question which is: “What factors support the development of a comprehensive framework for lean application in upstream petroleum-producing organizations?” The findings from the qualitative research identified the following themes which form the pillars for lean framework development. These findings which are consistent with literature include but not limited to: Continuous Improvement, Petroleum Policy and Strategy, HRM, Culture and Change Management, Leadership and Governance, Petroleum Production Process and Engineering Project Management, Safety, Health, Environment and Sustainability, Stakeholder

Engagement, Standardization and Regulation, Shop Floor Management and Waste Elimination. (Sharma and Kodali, 2008, Gurusurthy and Kodali, 2010, Jasti and Kodali, 2016, 2019, Ranchman and Ratnayake, 2019). Although, the findings of the qualitative research may appear ubiquitous (Shah and Ward, 2003, Anand and Kodali, 2009b, Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman, 2013b, Bhamu and Sangwan, 2016, Lodgaard, Ingvaldsen, Gamme, et al., 2016, Lermen et al., 2018), there are industry-specific themes that are critical to the upstream petroleum sector. Some of these include but not limited to; Petroleum Policy and Strategy, Safety, Health and Environment, Engineering Project Management and the operations of Regulatory agencies. These fundamentally anchor the smooth operations of the upstream sector. Despite the paucity of literature on lean application in the upstream petroleum sector, Ranchman and Ratnayake (2019) identified four key findings relevant for development of lean framework for petroleum projects including; leadership and management commitment, employee involvement, cooperation and trust with contractors/suppliers and lean project management.

Of equal importance, is the fact that factors that support a successful lean implementation include critical success factors for lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector. Thus, results of a pilot study in this research underscored the significance of identifying appropriate success factors that will support any successful lean implementation initiative. The findings of the pilot study supported by extant literature identified the following success factors suitable for application in the upstream petroleum sector including :Management Commitment, Active Leadership, Management Support, Communication, Organizational Culture, Sustainable Production , Training and Skills Development, Shared Vision, Financial Capability, Work Environment, Continuous Improvement, Measurement Framework, Supplier benchmarking, and Lean Readiness (Atkinson, 2013, Panwar, Jain and Rathore, 2015a, Netland, 2016c).

The findings of this research which is largely consistent with literature reflects the widespread acceptance of lean manufacturing as an efficient management philosophy. However, aspects of the findings underscore a need to not only give prominence to the soft aspects of lean including human resources, culture and change management, but to ensure adequate lean awareness to permeate the entire organization as a precursor to lean implementation. This will enhance lean implementation success.

The results show that leadership and governance constitute the most significant theme and factor when it comes to lean framework development. However, leadership and corruption appear to be the bane of unsuccessful implementation at various levels of the petroleum production process. These findings are consistent with extant literature (Hamzeh et al., 2010, Ayarkwa, Joshua, Agyekum, Kofi, Adinyira, Emmanuel, Osei-Asibey, 2012). For instance, one interviewee's opinion on leadership and corruption was captured as follows *"So as for corruption there is...I have that feeling that there might be some corrupt activities just to favour businesses to engage in you know the exploration or production of petroleum products in that regard"* (Interviewee #13). Similarly, a second interviewee had this to say regarding the impact of corruption on leadership and lean implementation within the upstream petroleum sector: *"Because in Ghana for example, we know that institutions have been set up to manage the revenues coming from the oils specifically, but once again either perceptions or even reports coming from the same institutions that have been charged to monitor the effectiveness of these resources have shown that the resources has been misapplied, has been siphoned, for example, we know of the public accountability regime if you like, and then also there was a fund set up called the heritage fund that as it were some percentage will be set aside but these issues have become a topic of too much controversy from government to government... and everybody accusing each other of corruption and siphoning the resources... and that is the bane of Africa.*

That is the bane of the African people” (Interviewee #3). Last but not least, another interviewee intimated on leadership as follow *“I think leadership is one other challenge in the implementation of lean processes”* (Interviewee #8). The issue about leadership and corruption which adversely affects productivity and profitability continuous to creep into all economic sectors especially with regards to natural resource extraction (Ayarkwa, Joshua, Agyekum, Kofi, Adinyira, Emmanuel, Osei-Asibey, 2012). Consequently, some stakeholders proposed that political leadership should be decoupled from operational or organizational management of the petroleum production process. However, constitutionally, all natural resources are vested in the state thereby making it impossible to decouple political leadership from operational and/or regulatory management of the petroleum production process. Thus, it is highly recommended that some political benefits should be proposed in any lean implementation effort. This will provide mutual platform for effective engagement on the best approaches to lean implementation.

Suffice to reiterate the importance of giving prominence to the soft aspects of lean implementation within the upstream petroleum sector. Therefore, the development of lean framework may be of immense value if prominence is giving to technology, and the soft aspects of lean. According to a consultant at the regulatory agency in the upstream sector in Ghana, the following were three critical upstream sector priorities *“So the first thing we did was to get the legal framework in place when we found the oil, which is basically what define the legal playgrounds for the oil and gas industry in Ghana. Then the focus, after we had put the framework, the focus moved to the technology. Because we are young and we did not have the expertise, we had to invite a lot of expertise from outside. And that is how come we have a lot of foreigners in this industry. So technology is the focus of the government, how we would be to get the appropriate technology and import them to Ghana and learn them and ensure that*

in the near future Technology also becomes available. Then the biggest one is the human resource development of our people, and that is why the local content law was promulgated. The local content law actually seeks the opportunity into the upstream industry to actually seek opportunity for Ghanaians to participate in the upstream industry. So local content is also one of the main focus of the government to ensure that Ghanaians are also given the opportunity to participate in the upstream industry. It ensures that Ghanaians are trained, job opportunities are given to them and they also have the opportunity to work in the oil industry. So these are the three main focus: the local content, training, and the technology. These are the three main focus areas of the government” (Interviewee #2).

5.12.3 Lean practices in the upstream petroleum sector

According to Taj and Morrison (2011), the petroleum industry is far advanced in the application of lean practices. However, Ranchman and Ratnayake (2019) posit that the application of lean in the upstream sector is at an infant stage. Similarly, the findings of this research show that the application of a structured process of lean manufacturing within the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana is either non-existent or at its infant stages. This finding is consistent with views expressed by interviewees during the data collection stage. An interviewee is quoted to have said “If I understand well, in every industry you want to add value. It is not only in the upstream industry, and for that the whole oil and gas industry. Every setup or system may probably need to add value. So anything or any process in the engineering industry we say iteration has to be done to give an incremental value addition to the system, I will call it LEAN. And obviously, we may have been practising LEAN without knowing we are practising LEAN because any opportunity we get we try to explore that and see how we can add value and make it more efficient, whether it is technology base or human resource processes. I think we’ve been doing that in the broader sense. With specific technical things that have to be recommended by LEAN specialists, I don’t think we have delved into that so much, especially with the

knowledge in specific areas that we have to develop in order to achieve the type of efficiency that we are looking for and all that. I wouldn't think that we are there yet. So we would still need your expertise or somebody who has this knowledge to be able to give to the commission... to increase the efficiency of the Commission. There is a very low lean awareness among employees within the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. For instance, nine (9) out of fifteen senior managers within the sector interviewed had very basic knowledge about "Lean", two others believe lean is a "technical thing" and one interviewee said Lean is a human resources activity to downsize an organization. This apparent lack of awareness by senior managers reflects the level of lean awareness across organisations and this is a major setback to any Lean implementation initiative.

5.12.4 Discussion of findings from quantitative analysis

In the previous section of this research, a thematic analysis was performed in which ten themes emerged from the data. The analysis process followed the six-phase approach proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006). Subsequently, these themes were mapped to the ten lean elements from literature. Consequently, five elements which were common were selected as constructs including: Continuous Improvement(CI), Waste Elimination(WE), Standardisation(S), Leadership Direction(LD) and Human Resource Management(HRM). These 5 elements hereafter referred to the independent constructs or lean elements were subjected to the rigor of statistical analysis not only to validate the themes that emerged from the qualitative analysis, but most importantly to establish the relationships between the elements. These 5 independent variables(herein referred), were tested against 2 selected dependent variables adopted from literature including Quality and Cost (Jasti and Kodali, 2016, 2019). The application of the structural equation modelling was aimed at answering the question "what is the relationship between lean principles and competitive business priorities?" The process of answering the

aforementioned research question consequently resulted in the achievement of the objective which was “to determine the relationship between competitive priorities and lean principles” The CFA analysis established that there is a relationship between all the Lean elements identified and hence the achievement of a structural relationship presented in Figure 5.5.

Lean elements have been identified as essential to firm competitive business operations (Nicholas, 2018; Raut et al., 2020). According to Caldera, Dehsa and Dawes (2019), the implementation of lean elements within organisations acts as a catalyst for firms and helps them to align competitive business priorities. This means firms that identify and implement the lean elements identified in this study, namely: continuous improvement, waste elimination, standardisation, leadership direction and human resource management are more likely to achieve business competitive priorities (Costa et al., 2020). This in turn will ensure that the firm maximises resources to deliver on the competitive business priorities (Ghezzi, 2019). In a globally competitive business environment, it is imperative for firms to understand the nature of the business environment, and set priorities and targets accordingly. Abreu-Ledón et al., (2018) in their study noted that the implementation of lean process geared towards aligning firm strategy and operations enables firms to perform better by following through on key business priorities. For some firms, the focus or priorities may be on process innovation which has been identified as being key to competitive advantage (Cherrafi et al., 2018).

Extant literature on lean management supports the notion and the results in this chapter which point to the fact that firms that implement lean elements are more likely to have a focused competitive business outlook (Bocken & Snihur, 2019; Costa et al., 2020). In this study, the analysis of quantitative data revealed that lean elements such as continuous improvement help firms to make business priorities that ensure that the performance of the firm is on a continuous

trajectory. This result is supported by the works of scholars such as Alves and Alves (2015) who found that lean elements resulted in continuous improvement which eventually resulted in organisational transformation. Other studies offer similar perspectives as follows: Zhan, Tan, Li and Tseng (2018) posit that the implementation of lean elements such as continuous improvement ensures that an organisation maintains a strong competitive position in the marketplace. It has further been mooted that lean elements such as waste elimination and standardisation result in greater efficiency in organisational practices (Lyons & Ma'aram, 2014; Zhou, 2016; Barth & Melin, 2018). In addition to these, the lean elements of leadership direction and human resource management also contribute to the competitive business priorities of the organisation and ensure that an organisation focuses on harnessing the talents of human resource personnel to achieve superior organisational performance in the marketplace. Emiliani (2006) concludes that there is overwhelming evidence which suggests that lean elements have a positive and significant impact on the competitive business priorities of an organisation.

5.12.5 Upstream petroleum sector and Lean implementation challenges

As has been stated in earlier chapters of this study, the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana is one that is riddled with many challenges which hinder the successful implementation of lean management systems and processes. From the data collected from respondents, one of the challenges faced is the challenge of bad leadership and corruption. The data points to the fact that some respondents from the qualitative study hold the view that some officials occupying important positions in the upstream petroleum industry in Ghana put personal interests first before the organisational wellbeing thus resulting in various levels of employee apathy. This finding hints at leadership being one of the major challenges that impact the implementation of lean manufacturing in the upstream sector.

From the literature, leadership orientation is one of the recognised challenges that impacts on the implementation of lean philosophy (Rymaszewska, 2014). Cheah, Wong and Deng (2012) also affirmed that some of the challenges that affect lean implementation emanate from within the organisation. Internal issues such as leadership, management, inter-functional coordination amongst others have been found to be influential in affecting the quality and scope of lean implementation. Panford (2014) maintained that most of the challenges pertaining to lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector were issues on human resource and strategic management. This study shares the same perspective. For the successful implementation of lean processes in the upstream petroleum industry in Ghana, leadership and human resource issues need to be addressed, whilst the necessary frameworks for lean implementation need to be adopted and implemented. The adoption of relevant lean frameworks can go a long way to mitigate the challenges faced during lean implementation in the upstream petroleum industry (Hunter, 2009; Charasia, Garg & Agarwal, 2016; Millad, 2013).

The actions of political leadership pose a grave threat to the survival and sustainable production of Ghana's upstream petroleum sector if steps are not taken to ensure proper accountability and non-interference in the operations of the industry. Leadership coordination between political leadership and regulatory as well as sector leadership requires a re-think with specific regards to how political leadership either interferes and/or usurps industry functions thereby depriving sector leadership the required independence to effectively manage organisations. The political leadership dictates including staffing and recruitment of personnel and this poses a risk for effective management since some personnel may lack the requisite skills but due to political affiliation, they may find themselves in positions with more complex requirements. A recent publication alluded to the fact that Ghana stands to lose its petroleum production capacity and revenue if political actors continue to interfere into the operations of industry

operators. Some authors have also established similar findings(Ayarkwa, Joshua, Agyekum, Kofi, Adinyira, Emmanuel, Osei-Asibey, 2012)

5.12.6 The role of Framework in LM implementation

Scholars have argued that the need for a framework in lean implementation is essential and cannot be overlooked (Tiwari, Sadeghi & Eseonu, 2020; Prasad et al., 2020). The framework developed in this research seeks to buttress the above assertion and further underscore the need for firms to be guided by a defined and instructional framework in lean implementation. Sadiq et al. (2020) claim that frameworks help to provide firms with more structured and directed approach to lean implementation. Additionally, they argued that frameworks are mostly preceded by extensive research, data collection and analysis which are rigorous in order to churn out fairly reliable results and output (Sadiq et al., 2020). Other scholars such as Seifullina et al. (2018) also reiterated the view that frameworks are needed in lean implementation. This opinion holds merit considering the fact that the lean sigma concept is one that seeks to achieve waste reduction and maximisation of firm performance through collaborative effort (Laureani & Antony, 2012; Knapp, 2015; Antony, Rodgers & Gijo, 2016). As a result, the adoption of frameworks for lean implementation is not only meritorious, but has considerable benefits for organisations. Furthermore, an understanding of how frameworks work, and their impact on the lean implementation process ensures that organisations are able to achieve the desired results.

Mellado and Lou (2020) further argue that through a framework, organisations can model lean systems to achieve desired outcomes. The framework thus becomes an important tool for the organisation. This view is supported by AlManei, Salonitis and Tsinopolous (2018) who asserted that lean implementation guided by frameworks tend to be more effective in helping firms achieve their objectives. The argument in support of the use of frameworks in lean

implementation was further buttressed by Cadden et al. (2020) who stated that due to diversity in organisational culture, it was imperative for firms to have a well-defined framework to guide lean implementation. The framework presents a more didactic and unbiased assessment of the organisation's needs and resources in order to effectively implement lean systems (Hofer et al., 2012; Yadav et al., 2020). Other studies also validate and underscore the significance of frameworks in lean implementation with majority of scholars acquiescing with the view that lean implementation is more effective if organisations are guided by a defined and practical framework (Anand & Kodali, 2010; Chay et al., 2015; Chaurasia et al., 2016; AlManei et al., 2017).

5.12.7 Institutional Commitment to Efficient Operations

Throughout the lean management literature, many scholars have expressed varied opinions on the need for management to be committed to efficient operations (Parast, 2011; Wen et al., 2020; Mellado & Lou, 2020). For lean process and management systems to be effective, management of organisations need to ensure that there is an institutional buy-in to the concept of lean management which in turn results in efficient operations (Fournier, Chênevert & Jobin, 2020). It goes without saying that the need for efficient operations has been made evident since the emergence of COVID-19 (Mahajan & Tomar, 2021). Organisations that have been lethargic about operational efficiency have found themselves suffering considerable loss of revenue and supplies due to the disruptions in supply chain and demand and supply during the global pandemic caused by the novel coronavirus (Akintokunbo & Adim, 2020). In addition, the current pandemic seems to have created a sense of urgency in respect of the realization of information technology and IoT as critical elements of I4.0 in enhancing operational excellence.

The results of this study seem to suggest that when institutional commitment is prevalent in organisations, firms are likely to be operationally efficient, and vice versa. This underscores a need for organisations to adopt efficiency methodologies akin to the lean process, and to trust that when lean practices/elements are implemented in organisations, it results in greater efficiency. A plethora of studies affirm this assertion; Aguado, Alvarez and Domingo (2013) note that firms which embrace lean process and are committed to its implementation are able to develop efficient models and systems which ensure that the firm achieves its goals and objectives. This ties in with an earlier argument which posited that the adoption and implementation of lean systems result in better competitive business priorities. Similarly, when firms and leadership commitment to lean practices results in organizational efficiency. Moyano-Fuentes et al. (2020) avers that firms need to achieve institutional commitment to efficient operations as a pre-requisite for improved organizational performance. Thus, without institutional commitment to efficient operations, firms in the upstream petroleum sector cannot achieve the desired benefits that lean management offers. The analysis of results also confirmed that with institutional commitment, firms can achieve better operational efficiency.

5.12.8 Summary of Discussions

This chapter analysed both qualitative and quantitative data in an attempt to achieve the objectives of the study and explain how lean operations can positively impact the upstream petroleum industry in Ghana. The analysis of the qualitative data yielded a number of interesting findings. It was found that in the context of the upstream petroleum industry in Ghana, five (5) lean elements emerged as being most relevant to the industry. These elements are: Continuous Improvement (CI), Waste Elimination (WE), Standardisation (S), Leadership Direction (LD) and Human Resource Management (HRM). The quantitative study confirmed that these five elements of lean were significant and positively related towards cost and quality, with the output of that study indicating organisations effectively implement and practice lean

such organisations will be able to minimize operational cost and improve quality. Overall, these discussions point to an irrefutable premise as far as this study is concerned; that lean management and lean elements identified in this study profoundly impact on cost and quality. To that end, in a subsequent chapter, some recommendations will be made based on these results and discussions. Furthermore, a summary of research questions outlined in the research, and the way each was answered is presented in the table below;

Table 5. 17: Summary of Research Questions and methods adopted

SL	Research Question	Method/s adopted to answer RQ
1	To what extent is Lean Manufacturing suitable for implementation in upstream petroleum producing organisations in developing economies?	SLR and output from thematic analysis
2	How can LM be successfully implemented in upstream petroleum producing organisations?	SLR and thematic analysis
3	How best can Lean waste be translated/ mapped to the upstream petroleum sector?	SLR and expert validated
4	What factors support the development of a comprehensive framework for lean application in upstream petroleum sector in developing economies?	SLR and Thematic analysis
5	What is the relationship between lean principles and competitive business priorities	Structural equation modelling (SEM)

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

CHAPTER SIX

FRAMEWORK DEVELOPMENT AND ADJUSTMENT

6.0 Introduction

This chapter is devoted to the framework development and adjustment process. Studies show that researchers develop frameworks for different purposes and are categorized as roadmap, Conceptual/implementation framework, assessment checklist initiatives (Mostafa, Dumrak and Soltan, 2015). Some frameworks are developed for academic purposes only and hence can be classified as conceptual, others are developed with a view to being implemented and/or validated. The proposed conceptual framework is underpinned by a pragmatist's worldview and provides a 3-tier approach which makes it simple enough to be adapted and implemented by practitioners and Lean managers. The 3-tier approach consists of: a framework development procedure, the proposed conceptual framework itself, and a proposed Lean implementation plan.

The context of this research is vital to the framework development process. Some authors argue that generic frameworks do not cater for the unique contextual requirements needed to ensure successful utilization of frameworks. For instance, a *“company only produces for local consumers, the situation may be different from global market companies with stricter expectations in products and services and in worker health and safety. Hence, it is necessary to develop country economy - specific frameworks rather than proposing generalised frameworks reported in the reviewed, LM literature”*(Yadav et al., 2020 p.6).

The proposed conceptual framework is based on an extensive review of 101 frameworks across various industries. Analysis of these frameworks resulted in the identification of 123 non-repetitive Lean elements which were ranked in order of frequency of researcher utilization.

Based on the ranking, the top 10 Lean elements were selected for further qualitative and quantitative tests to establish the relationships between the elements, and also to establish whether these elements were suitable for adoption in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. Notwithstanding the fact that Lean aims at simplifying work processes, it nonetheless advocates and calls for rigor as a way to reduce risk and oversimplification of Lean processes (Rishi et al., 2018). The Hierarchical Transformation Framework is one such simplistic approach but a bad idea to Lean framework development (Scherrer-Rathje, Boyle and Deflorin, 2009, Bicheno and Holweg, 2010).

6.1 Conceptual Framework and Research Questions

This section draws on the theoretical and conceptual frameworks to answer the research questions of the study. The main objective of this study is to understand the role of a lean framework in enhancing Lean implementation success in the upstream petroleum sector in developing economies. Hence the main research question is: How can Lean be successfully implemented in Upstream Petroleum Producing Organisations? Lean manufacturing has gained popularity as one of the most innovative philosophies organisations adopt in modern history. Lean can be implemented using either top-down or bottom-up (Arayici et al., 2011). However, akin to many other studies, this research adopted a top-down approach in line with Kettinger's Business Process Change theory. Lean implementation is a strategic corporate plan and devolves from senior management down to shop floor. This research adopted Kettinger's theory of Business Process Change which provides a rational basis for successful implementation. The theory of BPC fundamentally underscores the top-down approach for successful Lean implementation.

The fundamental conditions which makes BPC a suitable theory for this research include the fact that BPC is strategy-led and mostly adopts a top-down approach similar to lean

implementation. Also, BPC adopts cross-functional work processes which is also a key pillar in lean management. Furthermore, BPC is customer driven with a view to ensure customer value and satisfaction. The overall objective of lean is to ensure customer satisfaction. BPC also adopts adequate methodical approaches in its implementation which is akin to lean implementation process. In addition, BPC ensures individual and team empowerment, strong expertise/consultant support to enhance success and finally BPC harnesses information technology as a critical lever for success. The features outlined underscore the suitability of adopting the business process change theory in this research. Akin to Jasti and Kodali (2016;2019), Anand and Kodali (2009;2010), Sharma and Kodali (2008) and Yadav et al., (2020), this research adopts a conceptual framework approach in which emphasis is placed on top-down implementation approach. Lean application in developing economies similar to Ghana requires emphasis on shop floor practices with a possibility to achieve quick wins which will be properly and regularly communicated to all in order to motivate shop floor employees to take ownership and drive the process (Yadav et al., 2020).

Lean success depends on application of a systemic approach (Abdallah and Abdulsattar Al-Ali, 2016, Lermen et al., 2018). Lean is not the same as application of tools and techniques. The success of Lean adoption in the upstream petroleum sector focuses on soft aspects of lean manufacturing, technology transfer and the local content requirements of the industry.

6.2 Rationale for Framework in the Ghanaian Context

As revealed from the study, it can be observed that lean operations lead to operational excellence in the petroleum industry which provides competitive advantage across the globe. The framework for the implementation in the upstream petroleum sector provides direction and guidance to upstream operators in their quest to reduce cost, increase profits and achieve operational excellence (Sharma and Kodali, 2008). Considering the current crude oil market

globally, there is a need for a framework which will provide strategic direction in the effective way to implement lean in the upstream sector to reduce cost, improve quality, enhance customer satisfaction and improve operational efficiency. Currently there is no framework for Lean implementation in the upstream operations in Ghana, hence lack of direction and guidelines in lean implementation. Additionally, there is a significant difference between frameworks, as some frameworks do not consider the existing cultural and geographical differences peculiar to Ghana. Hence the proposed framework addresses the contextual operational challenges.

Reliability and validity assessments of the framework in the context of operational excellence in petroleum production operations is pivotal. In the context of this study, there is no evidence of a framework with a concise, comprehensive and sequential description of lean implementation process in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. Though frameworks are developed for specific purposes, and may consist of elements relevant to the specific requirements, some existing frameworks have considered lean elements like shareholder engagement, waste elimination, value stream mapping and corporate policy and strategy formulation. However, “petroleum production process” is a unique theme/factor in developing a framework for the upstream petroleum sector. Though there are some existing contextual frameworks within the oil and gas sector, authors considered critical factors based on their worldview and research perspectives. The significance of, and need for proper guidelines and directions in promoting the development of technological and managerial capabilities, to ensure best practices in lean implementation cannot be overemphasized. These guidelines or directions are addressed in the conceptual framework. Finally, to achieve world-class operational excellence, there is a need to benchmark industry best practices in the upstream

sector and adapt to suite the Ghanaian context cognizant of competitive priorities relevant for desired results in developing economies.

6.3 Development of the proposed Conceptual Lean Framework

The proposed conceptual framework is underpinned by insights drawn from Jasti and Kodal (2016) and validated by Yadav et al., (2020). A 6-point set of guidelines support the framework.

These include:

- The proposed conceptual framework is designed with Ghanaian upstream petroleum sector as a developing economy.
- The Lean implementation drivers reflect the key characteristics of organisations within the Ghanaian upstream petroleum sector.
- The framework incorporates the principle of frontloading but clear and simple enough to be adopted by Lean managers and practitioners.
- There has to be an established relationship between Lean implementation elements and/or drivers
- The conceptual framework ensures total stakeholder participation.
- Finally, the framework adopts the “Lean House” model by Liker (2004)

Though several tools, techniques, and practices (technical tools) have been recommended and in some instances implemented in certain sectors of the manufacturing industry such as Toyota, a cross-section of researchers argue that the mere adoption of prescribed lean tools, techniques and practices may not necessarily guarantee overall Lean implementation success (Liker and Hoseus, 2010, Osborne, Radnor and Nasi, 2013). They argued that Toyota implemented particular tools targeted at rectifying identified problems within its production lines, but applying the same tools in other sectors such as the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana may

not necessarily achieve the desired results. However, a misunderstanding of the Toyota approach to Lean as a philosophy and a long term paradigm shift in organisational culture underpins Toyota's lean implementation success, as opposed to "mechanistic short-term" perspectives to lean adoption by other organisations (Liker and Hoseus, 2010, Osborne, Radnor and Nasi, 2013). Furthermore, notwithstanding the fact that a multiplicity of factors underpins lean adoption success, many scholars affirm the ubiquitous nature of lean tools, techniques and practices. However, these ought to be reviewed to determine their suitability for adoption based on unique organizational requirements (Bicheno and Holweg, 2010; Piercy and Rich, 2015). Based on an extensive review of the literature and relevant practices, tools and techniques, and gaps identified thereafter, Cano et al. (2016) indicated that there is a need to resolve identified gaps in the literature concerning lean implementation to facilitate effective implementation of lean while ensuring removal of wastes and fast-tracking the rate of flow within the manufacturing process.

Lean implementation within the upstream petroleum sector in a developing country like Ghana requires pragmatic guiding principles which are contextually suited for an emerging economy.

6.3.1 Elements of the Proposed Framework

Lean implementation is a process and not an event. It seeks to ensure continuous improvement and a paradigm cultural shift. According to Liker (2004), the symbolic choice of a house diagram is the fact that a house is a structural system, consisting of key building blocks. The strength of the entire house depends on its roof, pillars, and foundation.

The overarching importance of the foundation cannot be overemphasized because the entire structure depends on it. Hence, based on the review, the fundamental components/foundational elements which form the crux of the upstream petroleum sector in the Ghanaian context include

6 foundational elements namely: Lean principles (LP), Information Technology (IT), Human Resource Management (HRM), Culture (C), Change Management(CM) and Shop Floor Management (SFM).

The objective was to establish that this framework was designed based on “soft lean principles” or the “people aspect” of Lean framework. Rationally, an organization with the right people, well trained, highly motivated is the most important asset that any world-class organisation can boast of (Alleyne and Alexander, 2018, Benin, 2018). Also, extant literature indicate that any effective Lean framework should be based on the 5 main Lean principles including: specify value, identify value stream, create flow, pull and strive for perfection. In addition to these fundamental principles, information technology is the bedrock of the upstream petroleum sector and is critical and all-encompassing within the sector. Last but not least, shop floor management is the bane of lean implementation failures and especially in developing economies like Ghana, any successful lean implementation program must focus on shop floor activities and shop floor management (Yadav et al., 2020).

The second part of the conceptual framework involves 10 pillars that provide broad-base support to the roof, while at the time being the connection between the foundation and the roof of the framework. These pillars which have been identified within the context of the research and grounded in literature include: Waste Elimination(WE), Continuous Improvement(CI), Value Stream Mapping(VSM), Project Management(PM), Stakeholder Engagement(SE), Petroleum Policy and Strategy (PPS), Leadership and Governance(L&G), Standardisation and Regulation (S&R) and finally Safety, Health, Environment and Sustainability (SHE &S).

The pillars of a structure constitute an important part of the structure and is a reflection of the support the pillars provide for the roof of the structure. Hence, the pillars captured in the

proposed framework represents tools, techniques, and practices (TTPs) relevant to lean implementation and suitable for the upstream petroleum sector.

The third section of the conceptual framework discusses the roof of the structure and consists of 8 elements including: Safety, Cost, Profitability, Quality, Flexibility, Sustainable Production, People and Environment. The business priorities in essence relates to the primary focus or the main objectives of any lean implementation agenda within the upstream petroleum sector. Because Ghana is a developing economy and heavily dependent on petroleum revenue, the business priorities are shared priorities between the petroleum sector and government.

The proposed conceptual framework presented in Figure 6.3, identifies the main pillars between the key principles in the framework development process. These principles, supported by strong lean leadership commitment, and cultural change adequately provides guidance and support lean implementation success. As illustrated in figure 6.3, adapting a holistic lean approach with effective shop floor management activities support the requirements for development of a framework suitable for implementation within developing economies.

The proposed framework will be relevant to stakeholders in the upstream petroleum sector because it provides recommendations to enhance operational excellence whilst ensuring sustainable production within the upstream petroleum sector. The framework provides guidance that enhances the flow of the interconnected segments of a company's functional systems. Due to the susceptibility of the upstream petroleum sector to price volatilities, environmental and other related operational challenges, guidelines/roadmap to enhance holistic operations of the upstream petroleum sector is relevant. It is also envisaged that this research will foster, within the geopolitical context of Ghana, a need for expertise to guide Lean

implementation within the local context. Last but not least, the framework contributes to the body of knowledge of lean implementation within the upstream sector in Ghana.

6.3 .2 The Framework Development Process

The framework development process comprised a 3-tier approach including: the development process (Fig 6.2), the conceptual framework itself (Fig 6.3) and a proposed implementation plan (Fig 6.4). The conceptual framework consists of foundational elements, pillars and competitive business priorities. Fig. 6.1 illustrates the elements that constitute the conceptual framework.

Figure 6. 1: Elements of the Lean Framework

Source: Author's Construct (2021).

Figure 6. 2: Framework Development Process

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

Figure 6. 3: Proposed Conceptual Lean Framework

Source: Author's Construct (2021)

6.4 The Proposed Framework Implementation Plan

A well planned implementation schedule constitutes a critical part of a good Lean framework and provides adequate guidance on how managers and practitioners should undertake implementation programs. Implementation timelines are important in Lean implementation especially in the upstream petroleum sector which is heavily laden with projects. Because Lean implementation ought to assume a systemic approach, the importance of adopting a frontloading approach to framework development cannot be overemphasized.

Thus, well-planned framework with scheduled implementation plan which breaks down work schedules and application will inure to the success of Lean implementation programmes. Nonetheless, this cannot and should not be interpreted as over-simplifying Lean processes which has a tendency to derail Lean success.

The proposed conceptual framework provides thematic guidelines on what to consider and how to proceed with Lean implementation. The proposed plan does not include timelines because of organizational unique requirements. Figure 6.4 illustrates the proposed conceptual framework implementation plan.

Figure 6. 4: Proposed Conceptual Implementation Plan

Source: Author’s Construct (2021)

CHAPTER SEVEN

CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

7.0 Introduction

This final chapter presents a summary of the conclusions, recommendations of the research with specific reference to the research objectives, and the research questions. To align with research requirements, the chapter revisits, the main objectives as well as the research questions in order to arrive at informed conclusions and propose insightful recommendations. The chapter also presents research contributions to theory, policy and practice and makes recommendations for future research.

7.1 Overview of Research

The research which aimed at developing a conceptual Lean Framework for application in the upstream petroleum sector, explored the suitability of lean manufacturing for adoption in the upstream petroleum industry. The concept of lean has been adopted by many organisations across various industrial/economic sectors, and whilst there are mixed reactions about the successes and failures of lean manufacturing, research shows the concept continuous to gain widespread acceptance across academia, industry and consultancy.

The author set out by conducting an extensive review of relevant and related literature on Lean Manufacturing, its application in the petroleum industry as well as its application within aligned industries. The literature review process constitutes a critical part of the research. Though literature abound on lean application in other sectors, same cannot be said about lean application in the upstream petroleum sector in the context of this research. The paucity of literature, especially

within the geographical context of this research presents both a challenge and an opportunity. Informed by a pragmatists worldview, a mixed methods approach was adopted and supported by an exploratory sequential design. The chosen methodological approach helped the researcher gain deeper insights on Lean manufacturing implementation requirements in the context of this research where due to trade secrets and patent rights, participants were unwilling to disclose vital information.

Extant literature within the geographical context of this study were predominantly focused on the construction industry (Ayarkwa, Joshua, Agyekum, Kofi, Adinyira, Emmanuel, Osei-Asibey, 2012), health (Carter, 2012), Financial and real state (Osumanu et al., 2018), University education (Tetteh, 2019). Several studies have been conducted on various aspects of the petroleum sector operations including; Benin (2017) who explored local content and human resource implications for the upstream sector in Ghana, Overa (2016) who investigated the discovery of oil in Ghana, Stephens (2019), Banda (2019), Philip et al., (2016) and Siakwah (2017) all explored aspects of the petroleum industry operations in Ghana. Notwithstanding the extensive research on the petroleum industry in Ghana, very few if any publications/studies have been conducted on lean application in the petroleum industry in Ghana, hence this research contributes to close the gap identified.

The aim of this research was to develop a conceptual framework to improve LM application in the upstream petroleum sector. The framework was developed based on extensive review of existing frameworks, and adjusted based on expert feedback from lean consultants and practitioners. To achieve this, the researcher explored opportunities and threats in LM implementation and

identified critical success and failure factors (CSFs & CFFs) for the upstream sector. Furthermore, a review of existing lean frameworks resulted in the identification of gaps, emerging themes, and an outline of lean principles/dimensions relevant for the development of a sound framework capable of improving lean implementation success in the upstream petroleum sector. Also, the researcher analysed the petroleum exploration and production processes to ascertain opportunities for LM implementation.

The following were the main objectives of the research:

1. Review existing frameworks and identify key dimensions to successful framework development
2. To identify and evaluate critical success factors (CSFs) suitable for lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector.
3. To translate lean waste associated with the upstream petroleum sector
4. To determine the relationship between competitive priorities and lean principles
5. Explore LM tools, techniques, and practices adaptable to the upstream petroleum sector.
6. To develop a conceptual framework to improve lean adoption in the upstream petroleum sector.

The purpose of the research was to explore ways to improve lean implementation success within the upstream petroleum sector in developing economies, and in order to achieve this, the researcher explored appropriate and applicable lean tools, techniques, practices, and associated cultural issues in the petroleum industry. In the literature review phase, the researcher explored the concept of lean, its evolution and how lean its popularity, as well as its suitability for adoption in the upstream petroleum sector. The literature reviews further explored the linkages between lean manufacturing

and the petroleum industry. Evidence suggest that the petroleum industry has, and continuous implement lean methodologies (Taj and Morosan, 2011a, Rachman and Ratnayake, 2016, 2019).

7.2 Evaluation of research contribution

7.2.1 Introduction

The study explored how LM can be successfully implemented in the upstream petroleum sector through development of a conceptual framework to improve lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. In the process, the research contributes to both the existing knowledge on LM practices and proffer ways by which companies in developing economies like Ghana can draw insights from LM methodology to enhance operational efficiency.

7.2.2 Contribution to knowledge

This research is novel and ventures into uncharted territories yet to be explored by many researchers. It is an exploratory research and touched on the core of Lean manufacturing implementation within the context of the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. Also, and perhaps most importantly, the research methodology adopted in this research lays the foundation for further studies in the petroleum industry in Ghana.

Also, this research expands the body of literature on lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana, which is at present underdeveloped. The study also contributes to improvement of local expertise in Lean management within the upstream petroleum sector. Data collection from upstream petroleum operators in Ghana for this research confirmed the lack of research on lean manufacturing and lean thinking in the operations of upstream petroleum sector

in Ghana, and most importantly the lack of local expertise within the upstream petroleum regulatory agency to help shape policies towards a more efficient sector.

A pilot study as part of this research identified critical success factors suitable for lean implementation in the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. Prominent among the success factors identified include: Management Commitment (MC), Active Leadership (AL), Management Support (MS), Communication (C), Organizational Culture (OC), Sustainable Production (SP), Training and Skills Development (TSD), Shared Vision (SV), Financial Capability (FC), Work Environment (WE), Continuous Improvement Organization (CIO), Measurement Framework (MF), Supplier benchmarking (SB) and Lean Readiness (LR). This exploratory awareness contributes to exterminate the paucity of lean literature within the upstream petroleum sector.

7.2.3 Contribution to Practice

Research contribution to practice may assume different dimensions from a strategic level as well as from an operational level. At the strategic level, leadership within the upstream sector may draw insights on the rationale for Lean implementation based on the need not only to improve competitive business priorities, but also to oversee sustainable business transformation. At the operational level, the application of shop floor management activities and visual management tools resulting in quick wins motivates employees to take ownership of the process.

Furthermore, the study recommends the adoption of business process change theory as a model to improve lean implementation success. The findings and recommendations of this study provides guidelines, insights, tools, techniques and practices that will enable Lean managers, practitioners and consultants within the upstream petroleum sector explore innovative approaches to lead in the improvement of operational and business performance.

Last but not least, the outcomes of the study serve as a guide for practitioners in the upstream petroleum sector, and policy makers to enhance awareness of the benefits and importance of lean implementation practices in the upstream petroleum sector, and suitable approaches for effective implementation. The findings, recommendations, tools, techniques, practices and insights generated can be adopted and/or adapted by management to inform strategic decisions and policy initiatives. The conceptual framework developed in this study can provide guidance on adequate selection and application of appropriate elements to improve implementation success. These elements when adopted and implemented effectively in the upstream sector will lead to operational excellence. Finally, practitioners can draw insights, from the proposed conceptual framework, the implementation guide, and the elements identified to educate and create awareness among employees about Lean as an improvement tool.

7.2.4 Contribution to Policy

Policy formulation anchors the direction to achieve sustainable business operations. Insights from research inform and shape policy directives organisations may consider based on requirements of the ever-changing business and/or manufacturing landscape. This research is novel within the geographical context of Ghana for which it is focused. Regulatory agencies including the Petroleum Commission, Lean practitioners and upstream operators as well as service companies may draw insights from the findings and recommendations from this research in order to review and/or formulate policies that will improve efficient operations within the upstream sector.

In the course of this research, feedback from consultants in the upstream petroleum sector point to an informed conclusion that petroleum operations in Ghana need to be lean enough to be sustainable. The application of the upstream petroleum resources based on current policies could

be re-visited to explore better post-oil diversification policies capable of economic transformation to enhance the living standards of the average Ghanaian. In other words, the importance of petroleum resource depletion policy review cannot be overemphasized.

Furthermore, a pragmatic approach to research, education and training policies aligned not only with the petroleum sector, but aligned with the future of post-oil industrial sector requirements is pivotal to the judicious application of revenue accrued from petroleum resource in anticipation of Ghana's future economic benefit.

7.3 Limitations of the Research

The following are limitations drawn from the study:

1. Qualitative sample and data collection for this research delimits any possibility of generalising the findings and recommendations of this research.
2. The proposed framework is conceptual and hence requires validation. The framework attempts to, but does not address all the issues of lean implementation. This is because the framework is used as an improvement model to provide guidance on Lean implementation issues for consideration. However, the framework is no guarantee of Lean implementation success, nonetheless, its absence is regarded as a setback to Lean implementation. Thus, lean implementation strategy has to be developed and implemented within the context of an organization and validated accordingly. This is because organizational culture is important for lean success.
3. To realise the benefits of lean and measure impact would have been positioned in the context of a longitudinal research. However, this research adopted a cross-sectional

approach partly as a consequence of logistical and resource constraints and this scope to be realistic and achievable. This notwithstanding, results of the research will generate insights for further research. Though data collection and analysis from the upstream petroleum sector provides insights from which the proposed conceptual framework has been developed, results seem restricted and cannot be extrapolated.

4. Lean awareness within the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana is very low and hence no structured implementation of lean initiatives that others can benchmark within the sector. However, discussions with both line managers and shop floor employees revealed that pockets of lean tools and practices have been implemented in some organisations.
5. Another limitation relates to challenges encountered at data collection stage due to the highly competitive nature of the industry, as well as trade secrets and patents within the industry.
6. Last but not least, a paucity of relevant Lean literature within the petroleum industry in Ghana has negatively affected Lean awareness in this study. Thus, high expectation of Lean proficiency which could translate into high quality response rate could not be achieved.

7.4 Research recommendation and suggestions for further research

It is admissible to acknowledge limitations and shortcomings in research which is characteristic of any research, and based on limitations emanating from sample size, sampling methods, data collection, research methodology, analysis, results, findings and discussions. Akin to other studies, and having outlined the limitations of this research, it is logical to proffer the following recommendations:

1. To ensure research results and findings are extrapolated, it imperative to ensure a more balanced sample size, sampling technique and analytical techniques explored in order to provide results that can be generalized. In this research, quantitative data collection/survey questionnaire was limited to operators within the upstream petroleum sector with little participation from academic institutions and service companies related to the upstream petroleum sector.
2. This research adopts a pragmatist approach and combined insights from Jasti and Kodali (2016), and Yadav et a., (2020) in the development of a 3-tier conceptual framework. Thus, it would be helpful if this framework is validated in future by interested researchers who can then critique and adjust it accordingly.
3. Leadership is said to be the bane of an organisation's operational progress especially in developing economies. This research found that corruption and lack of lean leadership significantly impact operational progress of the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana. Similarly, unhealthy political interference is a huge risk to Ghana's upstream petroleum sector. Further research in this regard, benchmarking best practices from countries like Scotland and transformational progress of the upstream petroleum operations in Dubai should shed light on the significant role of lean leadership in the judicious application of natural resource revenue for strategic diversification and sustainable planning and national development.
4. Furthermore, due to a paucity of research on Lean manufacturing application in the upstream petroleum in general, and particularly in the Ghanaian context, this research explored 101 frameworks across different economic sectors, some of which may not be suitable for organisations operating within developing economies. However, based on the

assumption though contested, that Lean principals are ubiquitous, this study only identified the elements used in developing the frameworks. Upon further reflection however, the criteria could have been expanded to include: frameworks that have been validated, research method adopted and extent of stakeholder participation in framework development process. Therefore, it is recommended that further research is conducted to expand the criteria in order to generate valuable insights in future studies.

5. Further research on Lean 4.0 is recommended in the context of the upstream petroleum industry in developing economies.
6. Last but not least, a holistic strategic integration of Lean manufacturing principles together with Six Sigma and sustainability strategies (Cherrafi et al., 2016), for implementation within the upstream petroleum sector will serve as a two-pronged approach to tackle sustainable operations while minimising the impact exploratory activities on the environment.

In conclusion, this cross-sectional exploratory sequential research adopted a mixed-method approach to explore the suitability of Lean manufacturing implementation within the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana and subsequently developed a Conceptual framework to improve Lean implementation using a 3-tier approach which consisted of: the framework development process, the proposed conceptual framework and last but not least, a proposed implementation plan. The conceptual framework comprised 6 foundational Lean elements, 10 pillars and 8 competitive business priorities. Though the validity and reliability of the Lean elements have been tested, including the test of the structural relationship of the Lean elements and the

competitive priorities, the proposed framework requires validation to ascertain its applicability in the upstream petroleum sector.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A – Questionnaire

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Respondent,

The questionnaire designed to help collect data in order to develop a framework a Lean Framework for the Upstream Petroleum Sector. The identity of the respondents will be held confidential. Kindly take some time to fill it. Thank you.

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

1. Gender: a. Male b. Female
2. Age Group: a. 18-27 b. 28-37 c. 38-47 d. 48 -57 e. 58+
3. Educational Level: a. Senior High School b. Diploma c. Degree
d. Post-Graduate e. Others
4. Employment Status: a. Casual Worker b. Permanent Staff
5. Designation: a. Factory Worker b. Factory Supervisor c. Factory Manager

SECTION B: Kindly tick the degree or the extent of practice of each item, ranking from the lowest 1 – Strongly Disagree (SD), 2 – Disagree (D), 3 – Neutral (N), 4 – Agree (A), and to the highest 5- Strongly Agree (SA).

QUESTIONS	SD 1	D 2	N 3	A 4	SA 5
DEVELOPMENT OF A LEAN FRAMEWORK IN THE UPSTREAM PERTOLEUM SECTOR					
LEAN PRINCIPLES					
Waste Elimination					
7. Focused Factory Production					
8. Storage Space Reduction					
9. Single Exchange of Die					
10. Flat Organisation Structure					
11. Production Smoothing					
12. Cellular Layout					
Leadership Direction					
13. Lean Vision and Mission					
14. Long-term Business Thinking					
15. Create a Learning Culture Organisation					
16. Horizontal and Vertical Information System					
17. Communicate Organisational Policy					
18. Develop Effective Leadership					
Standardisation					
19. Housekeeping					

20. Jidoka (automation)					
21. Work Standardisation					
Customer Focus					
22. Maintain Spare Capacity					
23. Cellular Manufacturing					
24. Value Stream Mapping					
25. Takt Time or Takt Calculation					
Continuous Improvement					
26. Use of Problem-Solving Tools					
27. Safety Improvement Programmes					
28. Elimination of Buffers					
29. Total Productive Maintenance					
30. Multifunctional Training					
31. New Process or Equipment Technologies					
Respect For Humanity/Human Resource Management					
30. Long-Term Employment					
31. Employee Empowerment					
32. Employee Participation					
33. Rewards and Recognition					
34. Cross-Functional Teams					
35. Suggestion Schemes					
36. Job Enlargement or Nagara System					
37. Communication Between Employees					
38. Job Rotation or Flexible Job Responsibilities					
39. Point of Usage Storage					

SECTION C: Kindly tick the degree or the extent to which you agree or disagree ranking from the lowest **1** – Strongly Disagree (**SD**), **2** – Disagree (**D**), **3** – Neutral (**N**), **4** – Agree (**A**), and to the highest **5**- Strongly Agree (**SA**).

COMPETITIVE PRIORITIES					
Quality					
40. Lean Principles improves the quality of work relationships					
41. Lean Principles improves the quality of raw materials purchased					
42. Lean principles improves the quality of production process					
43. Lean principles improves the quality of petroleum products produced					
Cost Reduction					
44. Lean Principles minimises the cost of equipment					
45. Lean Principles minimises the cost of raw materials					
46. Lean Principles minimises the cost production processes					
47. Lean Principles minimises the cost of petroleum products produced					

Appendix B - Semi-Structured Interview Guide

	<p>Semi-structured interview Guide</p> <p>Target Audience: Managers(Junior and Senior) and Consultants</p>
	<p>Opening:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Start interview by showing appreciation to interviewees for their time and willingness to participate. ▪ Briefly explain ethical issues guiding the conduct of the research including: UWS ethical standards, confidentiality of data obtained, voluntary participation and freedom to discontinue interview at any time without prejudice. ▪ Interview will be recorded and any part interviewee does not want to be captured in tape will be deleted in the presence of the interviewee. ▪ Highlight the purpose of the research and the intent of the interview- to elicit interviewee knowledge and understanding of lean management. ▪ Let interviewees be aware that data obtained will be used to develop a conceptual LM framework for the upstream petroleum sector.
	<p>Interviewer Prompts</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Can you tell me more about yourself: your background, education, work experience and what role you play in your current organisation?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Give an overview of the upstream petroleum sector in Ghana? ▪ What are some competitive priorities of emerging oil producing countries? ▪ What do you think are the strategic issues facing oil producing companies within the sector? ▪ What improvement strategies are suitable for enhancing operational efficiency in the upstream sector?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What is your understanding of Lean Management? ▪ Discuss your view about lean awareness in emerging markets like Ghana and most especially in the upstream petroleum sector? ▪ What are your thoughts about chances of Lean success/failures in the upstream petroleum sector in emerging markets like Ghana? ▪ What are some of the challenges with regards to Lean implementation? ▪ What are the benefits of using a laid down procedure/model to guide lean implementation? ▪ In what way/s can Lean implementation be improved/sustained?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Discuss effective people management strategies to enhance employee engagement, motivation and ownership of improvement processes in the organisation. ▪ To what extent should cultural issues affect lean implementation? How should cultural issues be managed to ensure success?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What cultural/soft issues are critical to lean implementation success?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What important leadership actions are critical to ensure lean implementation success? And how can these actions drive desired work culture for lean success? ▪ What expectations do leadership expect in a lean project? Do these expectations show a good understanding of the real impact of lean? In what way(s) can lean practitioners align leadership expectations to lean success initiatives? ▪ How will you define success of a lean initiative? And what indicators do you look out for as pointers of lean success?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What problems/challenges characterize the petroleum sector? How are these problems impacting the operations of the sector? How should these challenges be tackled? ▪ To what extent will the application of improvement initiatives help ▪ Will the technical aspects or the soft aspects be your topmost priority and why?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What expected results motivate senior managers to embark on Lean implementation initiatives? ▪ In what way/s do these expectations reflect the main objectives of Lean management initiatives? ▪ In what way/s can senior management/ Business leaders differentiate between business performance and Lean success?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ What are the critical governance issues facing upstream petroleum sectors from emerging markets like Ghana? What are the sources of these issues and how best can these be resolved? ▪ Discuss standards and policies in upstream petroleum management. To what extent are these sustainable in emerging markets? How can these standards enhance operational efficiencies and at the same time inure to the benefit of future generations? ▪ What's your view on the impact of petroleum production on the environment, what recommendations will you offer to upstream regulators?
	<p>Closing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Thank you for taking time to participate in this interview. Is there any other issue/s you think I should include which I have not captured? ▪ Is it possible to contact you either via email/phone call if I require any further information? ▪ Is there anything you said which you want deleted right away? If not, then the recording will be transcribed and analysed in line with UWS research policies. ▪ Once again, thank you for your time.

Appendix C – Lean Frameworks

		Supplier Relationship Management	Customer Relationship Management/ Customer	Order-based production	Zero-Defects	Elimination of waste	Human Resource Management/Respect	Communication and feedback	Leadership and Direction	Just in Time/Continuous Flow Production	Culture and change management	Basic and operational stability	Safety improvement programs	Pull System linked to customer	Reengineered production	Equipment work processes	Planning and scheduling strategies	Building Lean Expert	Lean Expert awareness training and education
Abdallah and Al-Ali	2016	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Abdul Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman	2013	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Afonso and Rosario Cabrera	2015	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Ahlstrom	1998	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0
Alam	2015	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Alkhorait and McLaughlin	2018	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2017	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
AlManei et al	2018	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Almutairi et al	2019	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Alsmadi, Almani and Jerisat	2012	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Amin and Karim	2010	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Amin et al	2018	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
Anand and Kodali	2010b	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Andrade	2017	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
Anvari et al	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atilano et al	2019	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0
Bajjou, Chafi and Ennadi	2019	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
Belhadi et al	2016	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Bhamu	2013	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0
Bortolotti and Romano	2012	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Brandl, Kagerer and Reinhart	2018	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Buus	2011	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1		1	0	0	0	0	0
Chang	2001	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chaurasia et al	2015	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
Chavez et al	2019	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Chay et al	2015	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Davies and Merwe	2015	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Supplier Relationship Management	Customer Relationship Management/ Customer	Order-based production	Zero-Defects	Elimination of waste	Human Resource Management/Respect for	Communication and feedback	Leadership and Direction	Just in Time/Continuous Flow Production	Culture and change management	Basic and operational stability	Safety improvement programs	Pull System linked to customer	Reengineered production processes	Equipment work processes	Planning and scheduling strategies	Building Lean Expert Team	Lean awareness training and education
De et al	2020	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Deshkar et al	2018	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Dombrowski and Zahn	2011	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Effah-Kesse	2017	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Farias et al	2019	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Filho and Barco	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Franciosi et al	2020	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1
Gao and Low	2014	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
Garcia and Drogosz	2005	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
Ghosh	2013	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Gibbons et al	2012	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Hines et al	2006	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Idayu, Ali and Kasim	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
Jadhav, Mantha and Rane	2014	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Jagoda et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2016	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2019	1	1		0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2015	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Karim and Arit-Uz-Zaman	2013	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
Kennedy and Widener	2008	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Keyser, Sawhney and Marella	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Kruse et al	2019	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Kumar et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Larteb et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Lermen et al	2018	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malmbrandt and Ahlstrom	2013	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
Maqbool et al	2019	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Merwe et al	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1

Author(s)		Supplier Relationship Management	Customer Relationship Management/ Customer	Order-based production	Zero-Defects	Elimination of waste	Human Resource Management/Respect for	Communication and feedback	Leadership and Direction	Just in Time/Continuous Flow Production	Culture and change management	Basic and operational stability	Safety improvement programs	Pull System linked to customer	Reengineered production processes	Equipment work processes	Planning and scheduling strategies	Building Lean Expert Team	Lean awareness training and education
Ming, Li and Wang	2011	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0
Mogogole and Jokonya	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Mostafa et al	2013	0	0	0	0	1		1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Motwani	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Nashaat et al	2019	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Nordin et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
Ogunbiyi	2014	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Okhovat et al	2012	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Padilla and Pekmezci	2011	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0
Paez	2005	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Paez et al	2005	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
Pan et al	2018	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Panagopoulos et al	2017	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Panwar et al	2015	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Perez	2014	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
Powell et al	2013	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1
Prasad et al	2020	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Primadasa & Alfarisi	2018	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1

Author(s)		Supplier Relationship Management	Customer Relationship Management/ Customer	Order-based production	Zero-Defects	Elimination of waste	Human Resource Management/Respect for	Communication and feedback	Leadership and Direction	Just in Time/Continuous Flow Production	Culture and change management	Basic and operational stability	Safety improvement programs	Pull System linked to customer	Reengineered production processes	Equipment work processes	Planning and scheduling strategies	Building Lean Expert Team	Lean awareness training and education
Rachman and Ratnayake	2018	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Reinhardt et al	2020	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Resta Powell and Cairdelli	2015	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Rishi et al	2018	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Rusev and Salonitis	2016	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
Saad and Khamkham	2018	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Salifu-Asubay and Adjei Mensah	2015	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Salimi et al	2012	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Sangwa and Sangwa	2018	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Saurin et al	2011	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1
Seifullina et al	2018	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Seitz	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Sharh and Ward	2003	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0
Sharma and Kodali	2008	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Soltan and Mostafa	2015	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soni and Kodali	2013	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sopadang et al	2014	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Sternberg et al	2013	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suhartini et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Susilawati et al	2013	1	1		1	1	1	1		0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Syed Ahmad	2013	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wahab et al	2013	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Wang et al	2015	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Wong and Wong	2011	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1		1	1	1	0	0
Wuni and Shen	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yadav et al	2020	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1
Zwet	2017	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Overall		24	27	7	13	37	35	23	36	26	23	6	11	17	11	18	16	27	30

Author(s)		Review potential wastes and lean practices	Continuous improvement	Waste analysis/Identification of	SWOT analysis for lean application	Define lean assessment metrics	Employee involvement and participation	Empowerment	Top Management Commitment	Readiness for change	Process control systems	Lean Project Management	Focus on Value Stream Mapping	Kaizen	Frontloading	One piece flow	Autonomation	Information Technology Systems	Total Quality management/Quality
Abdallah and Al-Ali	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Abdul Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman	2013	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
Afonso and Rosario Cabrita	2015	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ahlstrom	1998	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alam	2015	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alkhorait and McLaughlin	2018	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
AlManei et al	2017	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2018	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Almutairi et al	2019	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alsmadi, Almani and Jerisat	2012	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Amin and Karim	2010	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amin et al	2018	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010b	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Andrade	2017	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Anvari et al	2010	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atilano et al	2019	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Bajjou, Chafi and Ennadi	2019	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
Belhadi et al	2016	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bhamu	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bortolotti and Romano	2012	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Brandl, Kagerer and Reinhart	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Buus	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chang	2001	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Chaurasia et al	2015	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
Chavez et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Chay et al	2015	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Davies and Merwe	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0

Author(s)		Review potential wastes and lean practices	Continuous improvement	Waste analysis/identification of	SWOT analysis for lean application	Define lean assessment metrics	Employee involvement and participation	Empowerment	Top Management Commitment	Readiness for change	Process control systems	Lean Project Management	Focus on Value Stream Mapping	Kaizen	Frontloading	One piece flow	Automation	Information Technology Systems	Total Quality management/Quality
De et al	2020	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Deshkar et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dombrowski and Zahn	2011	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Effah-Kesse	2017	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Farias et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Filho and Barco	2015	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Franciosi et al	2020	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gao and Low	2014	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
Garcia and Drogosz	2005	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
Ghosh	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gibbons et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
Hines et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Idayu, Ali and Kasim	2020	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1
Jadhav, Mantha and Rane	2014		1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1			1
Jagoda et al	2013	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2016	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Jasti and Kodali	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Jasti and Kodali	2015	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Karim and Arit-Uz-Zaman	2013	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Kennedy and Widener	2008	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Keyser, Sawhney and Marella	2016	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kruse et al	2019	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Kumar et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Larteb et al	2015	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
Lermen et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malmbrandt and Ahlstrom	2013	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Maqbool et al	2019	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Merwe et al	2014	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Review potential wastes and lean practices	Continuous improvement	Waste analysis/identification of analysis/identification of	SWOT analysis for lean application	Define lean assessment metrics	Employee involvement and participation	Empowerment	Top Management Commitment	Readiness for change	Process control systems	Lean Project Management	Focus on Value Stream Mapping	Kaizen	Frontloading	One piece flow	Automation	Information Technology Systems	Total Quality management/Quality	
Ming, Li and Wang	2011	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mogogole and Jokonya	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Mostafa et al	2013	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Motwani	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
Nashaat et al	2019	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Nordin et al	2012	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogunbiyi	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Okhovat et al	2012	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1
Padilla and Pekmezci	2011	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Paez	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez et al	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Pan et al	2018	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Panagopoulos et al	2017	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Panwar et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Perez	2014	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Powell et al	2013	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
Prasad et al	2020	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Primadasa & Alfarisi	2018	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1

Author(s)		Review potential wastes and lean practices	Continuous improvement	Waste analysis/Identification of	SWOT analysis for lean application	Define lean assessment metrics	Employee involvement and participation	Empowerment	Top Management Commitment	Readiness for change	Process control systems	Lean Project Management	Focus on Value Stream Mapping	Kaizen	Frontloading	One piece flow	Autonomation	Information Technology Systems	Total Quality management/Quality
Rachman and Ratnayake	2018	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1		0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Reinhardt et al	2020	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Resta Powell and Cairdelli	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Rishi et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Rusev and Saloniitis	2016	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Saad and Khamkham	2018	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salifu-Asubay and Adjei Mensah	2015	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Salimi et al	2012	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Sangwa and Sangwa	2018	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
Saurin et al	2011	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
Seifullina et al	2018	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		0	0	0	0	0
Seitz	2003	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sharh and Ward	2003	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Sharma and Kodali	2008	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Soltan and Mostafa	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soni and Kodali	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Sopadang et al	2014	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sternberg et al	2013	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suhartini et al	2012	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Susilawati et al	2013	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
Syed Ahmad	2013	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wahab et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Wang et al	2015	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
Wong and Wong	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wuni and Shen	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Yadav et al	2020	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Zwet	2017	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Overall		11	40	20	2	11	24	15	29	15	16	18	22	16	3	9	4	15	19

Author(s)		Standardisation	Goals and objectives/Strategic	Network relationships	Process mapping practices	Kanban	Jidoka	Coaching leadership	TPM	Adoption of Lean Paradigm/Lean thinking	Learning organisation	Organisational culture	Lean Culture	5s/Workplace Housekeeping	Quality Circles	DMAIC	Mistake Proofing	Justification	Vision, Mission and Values(VMV)
Abdallah and Al-Ali	2016	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Abdul Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman	2013	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Afonso and Rosario Cabrera	2015	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Ahlstrom	1998	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alam	2015	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alkhorait and McLaughlin	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
AlManei et al	2017	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
AlManei et al	2018	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Almutairi et al	2019	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Alsmadi, Almani and Jerisat	2012	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Amin and Karim	2010	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Amin et al	2018	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010b	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Andrade	2017	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Anvari et al	2010	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atilano et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bajjou, Chafi and Ennadi	2019	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Belhadi et al	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bhamu	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bortolotti and Romano	2012	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Brandl, Kagerer and Reinhart	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Buus	2011	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chang	2001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chaurasia et al	2015	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
Chavez et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chay et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Davies and Merwe	2015	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Standardisation	Goals and objectives/Strategic	Network relationships	Process mapping practices	Kanban	Jidoka	Coaching leadership	TPM	Adoption of Lean Paradigm/Lean thinking	Learning organisation	Organisational culture	Lean Culture	5s/Workplace Housekeeping	Quality Circles	DMAIC	Mistake Proofing	Justification	Vision, Mission and Values (VMV)	
De et al	2020	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Deshkar et al	2018	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dombrowski and Zahn	2011	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Effah-Kesse	2017	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Farias et al	2019	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Filho and Barco	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Franciosi et al	2020	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gao and Low	2014	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Garcia and Drogosz	2005	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ghosh	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gibbons et al	2012	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hines et al	2006	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Idayu, Ali and Kasim	2020	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jadhav, Mantha and Rane	2014	1			1	1	1		1	1		0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Jagoda et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2016	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2019	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2015	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Karim and Arit-Uz-Zaman	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kennedy and Widener	2008	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Keyser, Sawhney and Marella	2016	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Kruse et al	2019	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kumar et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0		0	0	1		0	1	0	0	0
Larteb et al	2015	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lermen et al	2018	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malmbrandt and Ahlstrom	2013	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maqbool et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Merwe et al	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1

Author(s)		Standarisasi	Goals and objectives/Strategic	Network relationships	Process mapping practices	Kanban	Jidoka	Coaching leadership	TPM	Adoption of Lean Paradigm/Lean thinking	Learning organisation	Organisational culture	Lean Culture	5s/Workplace Housekeeping	Quality Circles	DMAIC	Mistake Proofing	Justification	Vision, Mission and Values(VMV)
Ming, Li and Wang	2011	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Mogogole and Jokonya	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mostafa et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Motwani	2003	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nashaat et al	2019	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nordin et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogunbiyi	2014	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0		0	0	0	0
Okhovat et al	2012	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
Padilla and Pekmezci	2011	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Paez	2005	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez et al	2005	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pan et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panagopoulos et al	2017	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Panwar et al	2015	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Perez	2014	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Powell et al	2013	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Prasad et al	2020	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Primadasa & Alfarisi	2018	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Standarisation	Goals and objectives/Strategic	Network relationships	Process mapping practices	Kanban	Jidoka	Coaching leadership	TPM	Adoption of Lean Paradigm/Lean thinking	Learning organisation	Organisational culture	Lean Culture	5s/Workplace Housekeeping	Quality Circles	DMAIC	Mistake Proofing	Justification	Vision, Mission and Values(VMV)	
Rachman and Ratnayake	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Reinhardt et al	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Resta Powell and Cairdelli	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rishi et al	2018	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Rusev and Saloniitis	2016	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Saad and Khamkham	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salifu-Asubay and Adjei Mensah	2015	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salimi et al	2012	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Sangwa and Sangwa	2018	1	1		0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0		0	0	0
Saurin et al	2011	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seifullina et al	2018	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seitz	2003	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sharh and Ward	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sharma and Kodali	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soltan and Mostafa	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soni and Kodali	2013	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Sopadang et al	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sternberg et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suhartini et al	2012	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Susilawati et al	2013	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Syed Ahmad	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wahab et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wang et al	2015	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wong and Wong	2011	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wuni and Shen	2020	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yadav et al	2020	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Zwet	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Overall		31	20	2	23	17	7	4	22	10	7	1	2	18	2	2	2	2	2	11

Author(s)		Focus on Lean Structure and Behaviours	Lean Enterprise transformation	Engagement	Lean Performance Metrics	Consistency	Accountability	Resources, Needs and Requirements	Understanding Lean Concept System	Testing and Validation	Process variability	PDCA	QFD	SPC	FMEA	3Ps	Value Engineering/Value Identification	Lean Accounting	Lean Philosophy
Abdallah and Al-Ali	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Abdul Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Afonso and Rosario Cabrita	2015	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ahlstrom	1998	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alam	2015	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Alkhorait and McLaughlin	2018	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2017	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2018	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Almutairi et al	2019	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alsmadi, Almani and Jerisat	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Amin and Karim	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amin et al	2018	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Andrade	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anvari et al	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atilano et al	2019	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bajjou, Chafi and Ennadi	2019	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Belhadi et al	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bhamu	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bortolotti and Romano	2012	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Brandl, Kagerer and Reinhart	2018	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Buus	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chang	2001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chaurasia et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chavez et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chay et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Davies and Merwe	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Focus on Lean Structure and Behaviours	Lean Enterprise transformation	Engagement	Lean Performance Metrics	Consistency	Accountability	Resources, Needs and Requirements	Understanding Lean Concept System	Testing and Validation	Process variability	PDCA	QFD	SPC	FMEA	3Ps	Value Engineering/Value Identification	Lean Accounting	Lean Philosophy
De et al	2020	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Deshkar et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dombrowski and Zahn	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Effah-Kesse	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Farias et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Filho and Barco	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Franciosi et al	2020	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Gao and Low	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Garcia and Drogosz	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ghosh	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gibbons et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Hines et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Idayu, Ali and Kasim	2020	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jadhav, Mantha and Rane	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jagoda et al	2013	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Karim and Arit-Uz-Zaman	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kennedy and Widener	2008	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Keyser, Sawhney and Marella	2016	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kruse et al	2019	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Kumar et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Larteb et al	2015	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Lermen et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Malmbrandt and Ahlstrom	2013	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maqbool et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Merwe et al	2014	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Focus on Lean Structure and Behaviours	Lean Enterprise transformation	Engagement	Lean Performance Metrics	Consistency	Accountability	Resources, Needs and Requirements	Understanding Lean Concept System	Testing and Validation	Process variability	PDCA	QFD	SPC	FMEA	3Ps	Value Engineering/Value Identification	Lean Accounting	Lean Philosophy
Ming, Li and Wang	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Mogogole and Jokonya	2018	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mostafa et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Motwani	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nashaat et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nordin et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogunbiyi	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Okhovat et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Padilla and Pekmezci	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Paez et al	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Pan et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panagopoulos et al	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panwar et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Perez	2014	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Powell et al	2013	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
Prasad et al	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Primadasa & Alfarisi	2018	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Focus on Lean Structure and Behaviours	Lean Enterprise transformation	Engagement	Lean Performance Metrics	Consistency	Accountability	Resources, Needs and Requirements	Understanding Lean Concept System	Testing and Validation	Process variability	PDCA	QFD	SPC	FMEA	3Ps	Value Engineering/Value Identification	Lean Accounting	Lean Philosophy
Rachman and Ratnayake	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Reinhardt et al	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Resta Powell and Cairdelli	2015	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rishi et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rusev and Salonitis	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saad and Khamkham	2018	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salifu-Asubay and Adjei Mensah	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Salimi et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sangwa and Sangwa	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Saurin et al	2011	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seifullina et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seitz	2003	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sharh and Ward	2003	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Sharma and Kodali	2008	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soltan and Mostafa	2015	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soni and Kodali	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sopadang et al	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Sternberg et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suhartini et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Susilawati et al	2013	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Syed Ahmad	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wahab et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wang et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wong and Wong	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wuni and Shen	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yadav et al	2020	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Zwet	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Overall		13	10	8	15	1	3	12	2	4	4	5	4	9	5	1	5	2	1

Author(s)		Six Sigma	Cellular Manufacturing	Production leveling	Production and Production Logistics	Cost Reduction	Labour Relations/Engage Labour Unions	Poka Yoke	SMED	6Rs	Multifunctional employees	Small lot size	8 wastes	Creative thinking and innovation	Volume flexibility	Fast and reliable delivery	Conformance to Quality	Vendor Development	Inventory Reduction	
Abdallah and Al-Ali	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Abdul Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Afonso and Rosario Cabrita	2015	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Ahlstrom	1998	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alam	2015	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alkhorait and McLaughlin	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Almutairi et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alsmadi, Almani and Jerisat	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amin and Karim	2010	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Amin et al	2018	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Andrade	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anvari et al	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atilano et al	2019	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bajjou, Chafi and Ennadi	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Belhadi et al	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bhamu	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bortolotti and Romano	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Brandl, Kagerer and Reinhart	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Buus	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chang	2001	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chaurasia et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chavez et al	2019	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chay et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Davies and Merwe	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Six Sigma	Cellular Manufacturing	Production leveling	Production and Production Logistics	Cost Reduction	Labour Relations/Engage Labour Unions	Poka Yoke	SMED	6Rs	Multifunctional employees	Small lot size	8 wastes	Creative thinking and innovation	Volume flexibility	Fast and reliable delivery	Conformance to Quality	Vendor Development	Inventory Reduction	
De et al	2020	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Deshkar et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dombrowski and Zahn	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Effah-Kesse	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Farias et al	2019	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Filho and Barco	2015	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Franciosi et al	2020	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gao and Low	2014	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Garcia and Drogosz	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ghosh	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gibbons et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hines et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Idayu, Ali and Kasim	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jadhav, Mantha and Rane	2014	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Jagoda et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Karim and Arit-Uz-Zaman	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kennedy and Widener	2008	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Keyser, Sawhney and Marella	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kruse et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kumar et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Larteb et al	2015	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lermen et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malmbrandt and Ahlstrom	2013	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1
Maqbool et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Merwe et al	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Six Sigma	Cellular Manufacturing	Production leveling	Production and Production Logistics	Cost Reduction	Labour Relations/Engage Labour Unions	Poka Yoke	SMED	6Rs	Multifunctional employees	Small lot size	8 wastes	Creative thinking and innovation	Volume flexibility	Fast and reliable delivery	Conformance to Quality	Vendor Development	Inventory Reduction	
Ming, Li and Wang	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
Mogogole and Jokonya	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mostafa et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Motwani	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nashaat et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nordin et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogunbiyi	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Okhovat et al	2012	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Padilla and Pekmezci	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez	2005	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez et al	2005	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pan et al	2018	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panagopoulos et al	2017	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	
Panwar et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Perez	2014	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Powell et al	2013	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Prasad et al	2020	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Primadasa & Alfarisi	2018	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1

Author(s)		Six Sigma	Cellular Manufacturing	Production leveling	Production and Production Logistics	Cost Reduction	Labour Relations/Engage Labour Unions	Poka Yoke	SMED	6Rs	Multifunctional employees	Small lot size	8 wastes	Creative thinking and innovation	Volume flexibility	Fast and reliable delivery	Conformance to Quality	Vendor Development	Inventory Reduction	
Rachman and Ratnayake	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Reinhardt et al	2020	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Resta Powell and Cairdelli	2015	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rishi et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rusev and Salonitis	2016	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saad and Khamkham	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salifu-Asubay and Adjei Mensah	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salimi et al	2012	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sangwa and Sangwa	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saurin et al	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seifullina et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seitz	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sharh and Ward	2003	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Sharma and Kodali	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Soltan and Mostafa	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soni and Kodali	2013	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sopadang et al	2014	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Sternberg et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suhartini et al	2012	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Susilawati et al	2013	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1
Syed Ahmad	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wahab et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wang et al	2015	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Wong and Wong	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wuni and Shen	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yadav et al	2020	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
Zwet	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Overall		3	8	4	6	10	6	3	9	4	13	3	10	3	1	1	3	3	7	

Author(s)		Focused Factory and Production System	Group Technology	Value Stream	Process simplification	Transparency	Waste elimination guidelines	Business Process Improvement	Strategic Alignment	Drivers for lean success	Policy and strategy deployment	Competitiveness	Lean Tools, Principles and practices	Lean sustainability	Current state evaluation	Cycle time reduction	Agile manufacturing strategies/Agile	Competitive benchmarking	Partnerships
Abdallah and Al-Ali	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Abdul Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman	2013	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Afonso and Rosario Cabrita	2015	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Ahlstrom	1998	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alam	2015	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alkhorait and McLaughlin	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2018	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Almutairi et al	2019	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alsmadi, Almani and Jerisat	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amin and Karim	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amin et al	2018	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Andrade	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anvari et al	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atilano et al	2019	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Bajjou, Chafi and Ennadi	2019	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Belhadi et al	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bhamu	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bortolotti and Romano	2012	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Brandl, Kagerer and Reinhart	2018	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Buus	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chang	2001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chaurasia et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
Chavez et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chay et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Davies and Merwe	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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De et al	2020	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Deshkar et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dombrowski and Zahn	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Effah-Kesse	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Farias et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Filho and Barco	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Franciosi et al	2020	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Gao and Low	2014	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Garcia and Drogosz	2005	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ghosh	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gibbons et al	2012	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hines et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Idayu, Ali and Kasim	2020	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Jadhav, Mantha and Rane	2014	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jagoda et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Karim and Arit-Uz-Zaman	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kennedy and Widener	2008	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Keyser, Sawhney and Marella	2016	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kruse et al	2019	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kumar et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Larteb et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
Lermen et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malmbrandt and Ahlstrom	2013	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
Maqbool et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Merwe et al	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

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Ming, Li and Wang	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mogogole and Jokonya	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mostafa et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Motwani	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		1				
Nashaat et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nordin et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogunbiyi	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		1	1		1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Okhovat et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Padilla and Pekmezci	2011	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1			1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez et al	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pan et al	2018	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panagopoulos et al	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Panwar et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Perez	2014	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Powell et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Prasad et al	2020	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Primadasa & Alfarisi	2018	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Focused Factory and Production System	Group Technology	Value Stream	Process simplification	Transparency	Waste elimination guidelines	Business Process Improvement	Strategic Alignment	Drivers for lean success	Policy and strategy deployment	Competitiveness	Lean Tools, Principles and practices	Lean sustainability	Current state evaluation	Cycle time reduction	Agile manufacturing strategies/Agile	Competitive benchmarking	Partnerships
Rachman and Ratnayake	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Reinhardt et al	2020	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Resta Powell and Cairdelli	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rishi et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rusev and Salonitis	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saad and Khamkham	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salifu-Asubay and Adjei Mensah	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salimi et al	2012	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sangwa and Sangwa	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saurin et al	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seifullina et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seitz	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sharh and Ward	2003	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0
Sharma and Kodali	2008	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soltan and Mostafa	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soni and Kodali	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sopadang et al	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sternberg et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suhartini et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Susilawati et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Syed Ahmad	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wahab et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Wang et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
Wong and Wong	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wuni and Shen	2020	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yadav et al	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Zwet	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Overall		4	5	5	6	5	8	12	9	7	5	0	9	6	2	7	1	0	0

Author(s)		Set up Reduction time	Equipment Utilisation	Reward Schemes	Reduction in Lead time	Sense of urgency	Problem-solving techniques	Visual Control Systems	Market Share	Concurrent Engineering	Stakeholder involvement	Pareto analysis	Cause and effect diagrams	Control Charts	5 Whys	Genchi Genbutsu
Abdallah and Al-Ali	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Abdul Wahab, Mukhtar and Sulaiman	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Afonso and Rosario Cabrera	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ahlstrom	1998					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alam	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alkhorait and McLaughlin	2018					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2017					1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
AlManei et al	2018					1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Almutairi et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Alsmadi, Almani and Jerisat	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amin and Karim	2010	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Amin et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anand and Kodali	2010	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
Anand and Kodali	2010b					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Andrade	2017					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Anvari et al	2010					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Atilano et al	2019					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bajjou, Chafi and Ennadi	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Belhadi et al	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bhamu	2013					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bortolotti and Romano	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Brandl, Kagerer and Reinhart	2018					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Buus	2011					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chang	2001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chaurasia et al	2015					0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chavez et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chay et al	2015					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Davies and Merwe	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Set up Reduction time	Equipment Utilisation	Reward Schemes	Reduction in Lead time	Sense of urgency	Problem-solving techniques	Visual Control Systems	Market Share	Concurrent Engineering	Stakeholder involvement	Pareto analysis	Cause and effect diagrams	Control Charts	5 Whys	Genchi Genbutsu
De et al	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Deshkar et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dombrowski and Zahn	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Effah-Kesse	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Farias et al	2019					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Filho and Barco	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Franciosi et al	2020					0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Gao and Low	2014					0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
Garcia and Drogosz	2005					0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Ghosh	2013	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gibbons et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hines et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Idayu, Ali and Kasim	2020					0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jadhav, Mantha and Rane	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jagoda et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2016					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2019					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Jasti and Kodali	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Karim and Arit-Uz-Zaman	2013					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kennedy and Widener	2008					0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Keyser, Sawhney and Marella	2016	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kruse et al	2019	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kumar et al	2006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Larteb et al	2015					0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lermen et al	2018					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Malmbrandt and Ahlstrom	2013	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Maqbool et al	2019					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Merwe et al	2014					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Set up Reduction time	Equipment Utilisation	Reward Schemes	Reduction in Lead time	Sense of urgency	Problem-solving techniques	Visual Control Systems	Market Share	Concurrent Engineering	Stakeholder involvement	Pareto analysis	Cause and effect diagrams	Control Charts	5 Whys	Genchi Genbutsu
Ming, Li and Wang	2011	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mogogole and Jokonya	2018					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mostafa et al	2013					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Motwani	2003					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nashaat et al	2019					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nordin et al	2012	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ogunbiyi	2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Okhovat et al	2012					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Padilla and Pekmezci	2011					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez	2005					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Paez et al	2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pan et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panagopoulos et al	2017	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Panwar et al	2015					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Perez	2014	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Powell et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Prasad et al	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
Primadasa & Alfarisi	2018	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0

Author(s)		Set up Reduction time	Equipment Utilisation	Reward Schemes	Reduction in Lead time	Sense of urgency	Problem-solving techniques	Visual Control Systems	Market Share	Concurrent Engineering	Stakeholder involvement	Pareto analysis	Cause and effect diagrams	Control Charts	5 Whys	Genchi Genbutsu
Rachman and Ratnayake	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Reinhardt et al	2020					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Resta Powell and Cairdelli	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rishi et al	2018					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rusev and Salonitis	2016					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saad and Khamkham	2018					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salifu-Asubay and Adjei Mensah	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Salimi et al	2012	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sangwa and Sangwa	2018					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Saurin et al	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seifullina et al	2018	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seitz	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sharh and Ward	2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sharma and Kodali	2008	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soltan and Mostafa	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Soni and Kodali	2013					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sopadang et al	2014	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sternberg et al	2013					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Suhartini et al	2012	1			1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Susilawati et al	2013	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Syed Ahmad	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wahab et al	2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wang et al	2015	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wong and Wong	2011	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wuni and Shen	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Yadav et al	2020	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Zwet	2017					0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Overall		1	0	0	2	2	7	6	1	2	8	1	1	1	1	2

Appendix D – Themes and Codes

Name	Files	References
Petroleum Production Process and Engineering Project Management	15	380
Industry Specific Classification	15	275
industry	14	58
gas industry	8	17
upstream petroleum industry	4	9
upstream industry	5	8
oil industry	1	3
extractive industry	2	2
service industry	1	2
food industry	1	2
construction industries	1	1
local industries	1	1
downstream industry	1	1
industry work	1	1
industry standards	1	1
whole industry	1	1
engineering industry	1	1
international industry	1	1
evry industry	1	1
petroleum industry	1	1
upstream oil industry	1	1
industry field	1	1
thus industry	1	1
specific industry	1	1
beverage industry	1	1
sector	14	56
upstream sector	12	32
upstream petroleum sector	6	12
gas sector	4	4
mining sector	2	2
upstream oil sector	1	2

major sectors	1	1
sector emm	1	1
sector emanate	1	1
petroleum sector	1	1
companies	14	53
local companies	6	12
producing companies	3	4
national oil company	2	3
multinational companies	2	3
hear companies	2	2
current company	2	2
upstream company	2	2
international companies	1	2
service company	2	2
indigenous company	2	2
expatriate company	1	2
gas companies	1	2
national company	1	1
legacy companies	1	1
big companies	1	1
oil services companies	1	1
private company	1	1
mining companies	1	1
subsidiary company	1	1
limited liability company	1	1
big exploration companies	1	1
local insurance companies	1	1
global companies	1	1
cost company	1	1
joint venture company form	1	1
indigenous oil company	1	1
exploration companies	1	1
upstream sector	12	32
upstream sector	12	32

oil	11	23
national oil company	2	3
oil industry	1	3
upstream oil sector	1	2
upstream oil	2	2
huge oil leak	1	1
oil country	1	1
oil services companies	1	1
oil production	1	1
oil operators	1	1
much oil	1	1
bulk oil	1	1
oil storage	1	1
young oil	1	1
oil fields	1	1
indigenous oil company	1	1
oil security	1	1
upstream oil industry	1	1
upstream petroleum	11	23
upstream petroleum sector	6	12
upstream petroleum industry	4	9
upstream petroleum	1	1
upstream petroleum business	1	1
gas industry	8	17
gas industry	8	17
petroleum sector	7	13
upstream petroleum sector	6	12
petroleum sector	1	1
gas	9	32
gas industry	8	17
gas sector	4	4
gas management	2	2
gas companies	1	2
gas organizations	1	1

gas division emm	1	1
gas operations	1	1
gas province	1	1
gas project	1	1
gas country	1	1
gas activities	1	1
production	8	16
production processes	2	2
development production	2	2
full production	1	1
floating productions	1	1
petroleum products	1	1
making production	1	1
oil production	1	1
production levels	1	1
production stage	1	1
particular product	1	1
delivering product	1	1
productive work	1	1
production profile	1	1
product life cycle	1	1
upstream petroleum sector	6	12
upstream petroleum industry	4	9
Operational Efficiency	4	5
work experience	4	4
productive work	1	1
petroleum activities	2	3
petroleum engineer	3	3
petroleum activities (2)	2	3
petroleum commission	2	2
petroleum resources	2	2
initial exploration activities	1	2
petroleum products	1	1
petroleum stuff	1	1

upstream petroleum	1	1
petroleum commerce	1	1
petroleum agreement	1	1
upstream petroleum business	1	1
current petroleum	1	1
petroleum sector	1	1
otherwise petroleum	1	1
petroleum industry	1	1
decommissioning activity	1	1
offshore activities	1	1
exploration activity onshore	1	1
exploration activities	1	1
gas activities	1	1
pipeline management services	1	1
Continuous Improvement	13	133
Lean Implementation Strategies	12	93
lean management (3)	7	15
lean management	6	13
lean management concept	1	1
lean management implementation	1	1
implementation	7	14
lean implementation	5	6
lean implementation project	1	2
lean management implementation	1	1
lean implementation strategies	1	1
implementation system	1	1
implementation process	1	1
implementation side	1	1
implementation methodologies	1	1
lean management	6	13
lean management (2)	6	13
lean implementation	5	6
lean programme	3	3
lean system	1	3

lean implementation project	1	2
lean concept	2	2
lean processes	2	2
lean champion	1	2
lean application	1	1
lean perception	1	1
lean management concept	1	1
lean management implementation	1	1
lean deals	1	1
lean objectives	1	1
lean implementation strategies	1	1
lean success	1	1
lean strategy	1	1
lean thinking	1	1
lean adoption	1	1
lean finance	1	1
lean specialists	1	1
lean methodology	1	1
lean elements	1	1
lean management implementation (2)	1	1
lean management concept (2)	1	1
implementation side	1	1
process flow	10	23
whole process	3	3
procurement processes	2	3
production processes	2	2
lean processes	2	2
tender process	2	2
entire process	1	1
continuous process improvement	1	1
decommissioning process	1	1
admissions process	1	1
process mapping	1	1
implementation process	1	1

everyday business process	1	1
registration process	1	1
human resource processes	1	1
improvement management processes	1	1
existing process	1	1
system approach	5	15
lean system	1	3
double deck system	1	2
equal system	1	2
business system	1	1
upstream system	1	1
implementation system	1	1
quota system	1	1
reason systems	1	1
hub system	1	1
safety system	1	1
corporate system	1	1
improvement management processes	1	1
engineering conceptualization and design	1	1
Leadership and Management Commitment	15	94
Business Priorities	13	66
Cost	9	24
Cost	9	19
vessel cost	2	2
cost cutting	2	2
ensuring cost efficiency	1	2
spread cost	1	1
cost factor	1	1
minimizing cost	1	1
cost implications	1	1
finding cost	1	1
cost efficiency ways	1	1
giving cost	1	1
operating cost	1	1

huge cost	1	1
certain cost	1	1
cost company	1	1
safe cost	1	1
operating cost (2)	1	1
finance management	1	2
revenue management law	1	2
audit management	1	1
business	10	22
serious business	2	2
business structure	1	2
sustainable businesses	2	2
good business practice	1	2
business basis	1	1
normal business areas	1	1
technical business functions	1	1
business system	1	1
local businesses	1	1
goal business goal	1	1
business administration	1	1
everyday business process	1	1
upstream petroleum business	1	1
offshore business	1	1
business organisation	1	1
business outcomes	1	1
business requirement	1	1
business results	1	1
Operations	5	12
upstream operations	2	2
operator side	1	1
onshore operations	1	1
aqua operations	1	1
offshore operations	1	1
oil operators	1	1

major operators	1	1
gas operations	1	1
operation office	1	1
various operation	1	1
started operations	1	1
key priorities	4	5
Quality (2)	2	3
service quality	1	1
managing quality	1	1
resource management	1	1
Quality	0	0
Profitability	0	0
leadership	7	12
government leadership	2	3
political leadership	2	2
leadership commitment	1	2
leadership perspective	1	1
leadership right emm	1	1
good leadership	1	1
leadership issues	1	1
organizational leadership	1	1
Management Commitment	5	6
top management commitment	1	2
top management	2	2
management expectation	1	1
senior management buy-in	1	1
government leadership	2	3
business leader	1	1
business head	1	1
political leanings	1	1
strategic management committee	1	1
corrupt activities	1	1
leadership right	1	1
right direction	1	1

HRM, Culture and Change Management	14	58
local content	9	22
local content	5	9
local content policy	2	3
local content participation	2	3
local content law	1	3
local content law changes	1	2
local content perspective	1	1
local content practices	1	1
people	10	19
local people	3	3
experienced people	2	2
right people	1	2
people aspect	2	2
ghanaian people	2	2
trying people	1	1
competent people	1	1
generally people	1	1
people recognition	1	1
people side	1	1
political people	1	1
indigenous people	1	1
african people	1	1
human resource practice	2	2
human resource development	1	2
middle management	1	2
middle level managers	2	2
performance management practices	1	1
human resource processes	1	1
reservoir management team members	1	1
eloquent management staff	1	1
strategic management level	1	1
service supervisor	1	1
industry work	1	1

right person	1	1
Employee Categories	1	1
petroleum engineer	3	3
safety engineers	1	1
subsea engineer	1	1
technical sale engineer	1	1
chemical engineer	1	1
engineer	1	1
mechanical engineer	1	1
mining engineer	1	1
field service manager	1	1
Organisational Culture and Work Environment	0	0
right people	1	2
working years	1	1
work environment	0	0
Corporate Policy and Strategy Formulation	12	31
Theory and Practice	8	12
government side	4	4
operator side	1	1
downstream side	1	1
technical side	1	1
people side	1	1
regulatory side	1	1
commercial side	1	1
revenue side	1	1
theory	1	1
local content policy	2	3
zero discharge policy	1	2
depletion policy	2	2
government policies	1	2
policy directions	1	2
research policy	1	2
government policies (2)	1	2
corporate business policy	1	2

policy change	1	1
policy formulation	1	1
Standardization and Regulatory Agencies	10	27
standards	5	12
tenth edition standards	1	2
environmental standards	1	1
standard regulations	1	1
international standards	1	1
local standards	1	1
discussed standards	1	1
industry standards	1	1
ethical research standard	1	1
minimum standards	1	1
adequate standards	1	1
ethical standards	1	1
Lean Framework	5	5
lean framework	5	5
work plan	1	2
right permits	1	2
applicable regulation systems	1	1
specific works	1	1
define works	1	1
work permit	1	1
work place	1	1
quasi government agency	1	1
government perspective	1	1
Stakeholder Engagement and Supplier Relations	6	7
Natural Resource Ownership	6	7
government side	4	4
government ownership	1	1
government activities	1	1
government run exploratory institution	1	1
Safety, Health and Environment and Sustainability	3	4
sustainable production	2	2

safety management	1	1
fossil production	1	1
Waste Elimination	1	1
sustainable resource	1	1

Appendix E: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	18.690	39.767	39.767	18.690	39.767	39.767
2	2.313	4.921	44.688	2.313	4.921	44.688
3	1.848	3.931	48.619	1.848	3.931	48.619
4	1.557	3.312	51.931	1.557	3.312	51.931
5	1.409	2.999	54.930	1.409	2.999	54.930
6	1.140	2.427	57.356	1.140	2.427	57.356
7	1.105	2.352	59.708	1.105	2.352	59.708
8	.983	2.090	61.799			
9	.948	2.017	63.816			
10	.831	1.767	65.583			
11	.821	1.747	67.331			
12	.812	1.727	69.058			
13	.775	1.649	70.706			
14	.711	1.512	72.218			
15	.699	1.487	73.705			
16	.676	1.439	75.144			
17	.630	1.341	76.485			
18	.607	1.291	77.776			
19	.589	1.253	79.029			
20	.575	1.222	80.252			
21	.562	1.195	81.446			
22	.520	1.107	82.553			
23	.510	1.085	83.638			
24	.489	1.041	84.679			
25	.470	1.001	85.680			
26	.449	.955	86.636			
27	.420	.893	87.529			
28	.406	.865	88.393			
29	.397	.845	89.238			
30	.393	.835	90.073			
31	.378	.804	90.878			
32	.373	.794	91.671			
33	.348	.741	92.412			

34	.334	.710	93.122		
35	.318	.676	93.798		
36	.302	.642	94.440		
37	.299	.635	95.076		
38	.292	.622	95.697		
39	.266	.565	96.263		
40	.253	.539	96.801		
41	.244	.519	97.321		
42	.243	.517	97.838		
43	.224	.477	98.314		
44	.219	.466	98.780		
45	.208	.443	99.223		
46	.191	.406	99.629		
47	.174	.371	100.000		

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Appendix F: Initial Modification Indices

Covariances: (Group number 1 - Default model)

	M.I.	Par Change
e42 <--> human	9.646	.028
e42 <--> cost	18.048	-.055
e41 <--> cost	4.787	-.032
e40 <--> human	7.192	-.033
e40 <--> cost	9.023	.052
e40 <--> leader	6.083	.035
e39 <--> cost	18.052	.061
e39 <--> waste	4.102	.029
e39 <--> e42	8.477	-.055
e38 <--> conti	8.217	.040
e38 <--> waste	4.782	-.035
e37 <--> human	10.631	-.034
e37 <--> e38	83.105	.217
e36 <--> conti	8.859	-.034
e35 <--> human	5.466	.020
e35 <--> cost	5.246	-.028
e35 <--> e38	29.391	-.106
e34 <--> e40	4.312	-.044
e34 <--> e37	19.455	-.079
e34 <--> e35	18.195	.063
e33 <--> quality	23.848	.059
e33 <--> standard	9.743	-.037
e33 <--> human	7.380	-.025
e33 <--> e42	10.438	.055
e33 <--> e41	11.645	.065
e33 <--> e38	5.056	-.047
e32 <--> quality	8.157	.034
e32 <--> standard	8.658	.034
e32 <--> human	13.829	-.033
e32 <--> cost	5.803	-.030
e32 <--> e42	6.997	.044
e31 <--> e37	4.648	-.041
e30 <--> standard	4.369	-.022
e30 <--> human	4.414	.017
e30 <--> conti	6.003	-.025
e30 <--> e41	4.542	.037
e30 <--> e40	5.997	-.051
e30 <--> e38	11.478	-.064

	M.I.	Par Change
e30 <--> e37	4.333	-.037
e30 <--> e31	15.004	.058
e29 <--> conti	4.230	-.020
e29 <--> e31	11.902	.049
e29 <--> e30	8.364	.038
e28 <--> human	7.242	.023
e28 <--> e32	7.084	-.042
e28 <--> e31	4.382	.033
e28 <--> e30	6.202	.036
e27 <--> quality	9.457	-.034
e27 <--> human	9.367	.025
e27 <--> e40	4.689	-.046
e27 <--> e35	5.081	.033
e27 <--> e31	4.854	-.033
e27 <--> e29	11.796	.046
e27 <--> e28	8.710	.044
e26 <--> conti	7.740	.029
e26 <--> waste	6.024	-.029
e26 <--> e41	4.368	-.036
e26 <--> e31	12.573	-.053
e26 <--> e29	9.644	-.041
e26 <--> e27	10.609	.046
e25 <--> standard	12.339	.041
e25 <--> e36	8.943	.050
e25 <--> e34	4.288	.032
e25 <--> e31	7.919	-.046
e25 <--> e30	7.194	-.041
e25 <--> e28	4.229	-.033
e25 <--> e26	27.501	.079
e24 <--> human	21.988	-.048
e24 <--> conti	4.499	.028
e24 <--> e42	4.127	-.040
e24 <--> e38	5.697	.057
e24 <--> e36	5.069	-.043
e24 <--> e30	5.254	-.040
e24 <--> e29	5.691	-.040
e24 <--> e27	5.398	-.041
e24 <--> e26	5.721	.042
e23 <--> human	12.922	.038
e23 <--> cost	9.806	-.046
e23 <--> leader	5.088	-.028

	M.I.	Par Change
e23 <--> e40	4.660	-.058
e23 <--> e37	6.860	-.059
e23 <--> e33	9.879	-.062
e23 <--> e30	9.959	.057
e23 <--> e29	5.154	.039
e23 <--> e26	5.201	.041
e23 <--> e25	5.275	.045
e22 <--> cost	4.121	.034
e22 <--> e42	6.456	-.058
e22 <--> e40	5.280	.070
e22 <--> e35	5.821	-.051
e22 <--> e34	7.755	.059
e22 <--> e23	5.290	-.060
e21 <--> human	7.110	-.026
e21 <--> leader	12.534	.040
e21 <--> waste	4.944	-.031
e21 <--> e33	6.406	.046
e21 <--> e29	4.997	-.035
e20 <--> e42	5.049	-.049
e20 <--> e40	13.204	.107
e20 <--> e23	7.211	-.068
e20 <--> e22	26.628	.149
e19 <--> quality	4.108	-.029
e19 <--> leader	5.803	-.030
e19 <--> waste	5.987	.037
e19 <--> e41	20.724	-.102
e19 <--> e37	8.541	.066
e18 <--> human	7.904	-.027
e18 <--> conti	18.699	-.052
e18 <--> leader	54.927	.083
e18 <--> e42	6.605	-.047
e18 <--> e30	18.971	-.071
e18 <--> e29	5.624	-.037
e18 <--> e24	5.425	.048
e18 <--> e23	4.041	-.042
e18 <--> e20	4.455	.049
e17 <--> leader	15.611	.045
e17 <--> e35	6.036	-.043
e17 <--> e28	8.016	-.050
e17 <--> e18	4.384	.041
e16 <--> human	9.148	-.033

	M.I.	Par Change
e16 <--> leader	9.964	.040
e16 <--> waste	4.976	.035
e16 <--> e36	8.855	-.060
e16 <--> e34	4.688	.042
e16 <--> e25	8.246	-.058
e16 <--> e17	58.982	.171
e15 <--> standard	8.579	-.036
e15 <--> human	4.717	.020
e15 <--> conti	5.329	.027
e15 <--> leader	19.045	-.047
e15 <--> e42	4.565	.038
e15 <--> e40	5.496	-.055
e15 <--> e37	7.670	-.055
e15 <--> e31	7.427	-.046
e15 <--> e27	4.679	.035
e15 <--> e26	23.044	.076
e15 <--> e23	8.281	.059
e15 <--> e20	6.334	-.056
e15 <--> e18	20.598	-.084
e14 <--> conti	6.974	.032
e14 <--> e23	6.955	-.057
e14 <--> e19	7.936	.061
e14 <--> e17	7.530	-.055
e14 <--> e16	16.834	-.092
e14 <--> e15	44.335	.127
e13 <--> human	4.392	.021
e13 <--> leader	7.309	-.031
e13 <--> waste	6.909	-.037
e13 <--> e42	9.522	.057
e13 <--> e41	4.284	-.043
e13 <--> e18	22.337	-.092
e13 <--> e17	10.859	-.066
e13 <--> e16	17.640	-.093
e13 <--> e14	11.600	.068
e12 <--> leader	7.227	-.028
e12 <--> e39	4.509	-.040
e12 <--> e32	4.011	.033
e12 <--> e31	6.716	.042
e12 <--> e28	5.401	.037
e12 <--> e17	9.080	-.055
e12 <--> e16	12.695	-.072

	M.I.	Par Change
e12 <--> e14	6.674	.047
e12 <--> e13	47.388	.124
e11 <--> conti	5.846	.040
e11 <--> leader	12.818	-.055
e11 <--> e22	7.151	.087
e11 <--> e16	5.149	.067
e11 <--> e15	14.293	.095
e10 <--> e38	12.417	.079
e10 <--> e34	10.124	-.054
e10 <--> e27	7.818	-.047
e10 <--> e25	15.109	.069
e10 <--> e23	9.129	.064
e10 <--> e19	4.211	.043
e10 <--> e17	4.381	-.041
e9 <--> human	5.601	-.022
e9 <--> conti	5.665	.028
e9 <--> e41	4.260	-.041
e9 <--> e40	26.929	.122
e9 <--> e37	15.923	.080
e9 <--> e30	10.896	-.052
e9 <--> e23	5.730	-.049
e9 <--> e18	21.437	.086
e9 <--> e17	24.750	.095
e9 <--> e15	22.375	-.085
e9 <--> e11	11.265	-.085
e8 <--> quality	5.156	.026
e8 <--> cost	5.424	-.028
e8 <--> e33	4.965	.036
e8 <--> e31	7.783	-.044
e8 <--> e30	4.439	.031
e8 <--> e20	4.080	-.042
e8 <--> e16	18.978	.085
e8 <--> e12	21.853	-.074
e7 <--> conti	9.534	-.035
e7 <--> leader	6.774	.026
e7 <--> e39	7.257	-.050
e7 <--> e35	5.784	.038
e7 <--> e34	4.414	-.033
e7 <--> e31	4.676	.035
e7 <--> e26	5.007	-.034
e7 <--> e22	4.348	-.046

		M.I.	Par Change
e7	<--> e10	6.229	-.044
e7	<--> e8	26.617	.081
e6	<--> conti	10.808	.037
e6	<--> leader	4.540	-.021
e6	<--> waste	6.627	-.033
e6	<--> e40	5.568	-.054
e6	<--> e30	7.256	.041
e6	<--> e21	4.620	.039
e6	<--> e18	7.210	.048
e6	<--> e16	4.150	-.041
e6	<--> e13	4.252	.038
e5	<--> cost	7.478	.037
e5	<--> leader	9.554	-.034
e5	<--> waste	4.849	.030
e5	<--> e28	6.559	.043
e5	<--> e14	8.240	-.056
e5	<--> e10	6.985	.050
e5	<--> e8	10.909	-.055
e4	<--> waste	4.115	.028
e4	<--> e35	10.762	-.056
e4	<--> e34	8.880	.050
e4	<--> e23	10.343	-.068
e4	<--> e22	16.571	.098
e4	<--> e20	6.683	.060
e4	<--> e19	4.173	-.043
e4	<--> e18	5.242	.044
e4	<--> e15	9.833	-.058
e4	<--> e13	5.891	-.047
e3	<--> leader	8.095	.032
e3	<--> e41	12.794	.074
e3	<--> e36	6.217	.045
e3	<--> e35	4.956	-.038
e3	<--> e33	8.388	-.053
e3	<--> e32	7.362	.049
e3	<--> e23	7.046	.057
e3	<--> e18	5.008	.044
e3	<--> e17	14.448	.076
e3	<--> e16	7.673	.061
e3	<--> e13	30.240	-.109
e3	<--> e4	23.312	.094
e2	<--> human	4.224	.017

	M.I.	Par Change
e2 <--> e39	4.862	.039
e2 <--> e35	7.256	.040
e2 <--> e29	4.003	.027
e2 <--> e26	4.462	-.030
e2 <--> e19	5.720	.044
e2 <--> e17	5.447	-.040
e2 <--> e15	6.045	.040
e2 <--> e14	5.387	.040
e2 <--> e9	5.502	-.038
e2 <--> e6	7.511	-.043
e1 <--> e27	11.630	-.065
e1 <--> e24	8.664	.069
e1 <--> e18	5.840	-.053
e1 <--> e13	24.591	.111
e1 <--> e3	6.356	-.055
e1 <--> e2	8.743	.056

Appendix G – Role of Lean Expert

According to BS ISO 18404: 2015(E), the role of the lean expert in any lean implementation process must be clearly outlined. The specific requirements of the lean expert is therefore stated as follows:

The role of the Lean expert is to support the Lean leaders in the application of Lean principles and the selection and use of techniques required. The Lean expert will undertake the following:

- Lead improvement initiatives required
- Determine if any training activities are appropriate and effective
- Provide training in Lean approaches to Lean leaders as required
- Assist in identification of suitable areas for Lean implementation
- Assist in periodic reviews of the implementation
- Provide “internal” consultancy in Lean
- Provide support so that improvements identified are realised and maintained
- Coach and mentor the Lean Leaders in the implementation of Lean principles and the selection and use of techniques required
- Work regularly with senior management to build Lean awareness, Lean skills and support for implementation
- Perform Lean audits at site level and use the results to identify future Lean events
- Benchmarking
- Instigate/coordinate reward and recognition as appropriate

Source: BS ISO 18404:2015 p.29

Appendix H - Invitation

School of Computing, Engineering & Physical sciences
Paisley Campus, Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland, UK
Tel +44(0)1418483000

Invitation to participate in PhD Student Research

To whom it may concern,

I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences, and I am currently conducting my research on Lean management within the upstream petroleum industry. As part of my research, I wish to extend an invitation to interested participant organisations, regulatory institutions, as well as petroleum and lean experts/consultants to participate in my research.

Under the supervision of Dr. Michele Cano (Lead Supervisor and Director at Quality Centre, University of the West of Scotland), Dr. Thanos Kourouklis (1st Supervisor) and Dr. Iain McLellan (2nd Supervisor) respectively, we are looking for companies interested in participating in this research. The purpose of this research is to develop a LM framework for application in the upstream petroleum sector. To achieve the overarching aim of this research, interviews and questions administered will provide valuable data for analysis and interpretation. However, due to time and resource constraints, the outcome of the research will be the development of a conceptual LM framework; hence no validation will be required.

In appreciation for granting access to your company, copies of the research findings will be made available to participating companies. Also, electronic copies will be able for individuals who may require same.

In strict adherence to the code of Ethics of the UWS, all data collected will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will data will be destroyed upon completion of the research. In addition, participating organisations will be coded.

UWS is one of the most innovative young universities in the world with internationally-excellent and world-leading research focus. The university has recently been recognised to be among 3% of universities worldwide by Times Higher Education World University Ranking 2018.

Should this research be of interest to you, or you have any questions about the research process, kindly contact me at [REDACTED]

Appendix I – Information Sheet

School of Engineering, Computing
& Physical Sciences (CEPS)
Paisley, PA1 2BE

Research Information Sheet

Name of Researcher: John Ayanaba – PhD Student, University of the West of Scotland

Research Topic: Achieving Lean Success in the Petroleum industry: Development of a conceptual Framework for Application in the upstream sector in Ghana.

Purpose of the Study: To develop a conceptual lean management framework for application in the upstream petroleum sector.

Rationale for being selected to participate: Your selection to participate in this interview is based on the assumption that you are either an employee working within upstream petroleum sector, or you are an improvement/lean expert.

Participant Consent: You will be required to give consent for the survey or interview to proceed.

Confidentiality: Data collected will be treated with utmost confidentiality in strict adherence to UWS ethical standards. Data obtained for the purpose of this research will be stored and password protected in line with UWS research policy on data management.

Study Results: This interview and survey is part of my research on adoption of lean management in the upstream petroleum industry. The data obtained will be transcribed, analysed and used for purposes of this research. Journal articles may also be presented at conferences and/or published. An electronic copy of the final report will be available to participating organisations and individuals who may wish to have copies.

Ethical Approval: This research has gone through University Ethical approval process and hence meets the standards required both at the supervisory level and at the ethical committee level.

Withdrawal from interview: A research participant is free to withdraw from continuing with the interview/questionnaire at any time he/s feels there is a breach of trust. The participant is free to ignore answering a particular question or stop interview and completely withdraw his/her participation without any obligation.

Gratitude: I wish to express my sincere appreciation to you for taking time off to participate in this research. I sincerely hope the outcome of this research will deepen knowledge, and add value to theory and practice. I can be contacted via the details below.

Appendix J – Consent Form

Participant interview Consent Form

Introduction:

I am a PhD student at the University of The West of Scotland (UWS), and am currently undertaking my research on the application of lean management (LM) in the upstream petroleum sector. The purpose of my research is to develop a LM framework for implementation in the petroleum sector. The interview/questionnaire will elicit factual information related to lean management in the petroleum industry. Participating in this interview/survey is purely voluntary and you are free not to respond to any question(s) should you not feel comfortable to do so.

The scope of this interview/questionnaire is restricted lean management within the petroleum sector. However, you are free to expand to relevant issues in the course of responding to the questions.

Confidentiality:

This research is conducted in strict adherence to ethical standards of the University of the West of Scotland, hence all data obtain herein will be treated with the utmost confidentiality, and will be used **ONLY** for the purpose of this research. Data obtained will be stored and password protected in line with university policy on data management.

In addition, interviews will be recorded and used accordingly. Suitable responses from participants will be used **verbatim** without attribution to the individual. Indicate your willingness to be recorded or otherwise.

Please check each box as applicable:

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
3. I understand that my data from this study will be securely stored by the researchers, will not be identifiable.
4. I understand that this SURVEY will be analyzed, and the results used only for purposes of this research.
5. I agree to take part in the above study.
6. I agree that this form bears my name and signature.

Name of participant Date Signature

Name of Researcher Date Signature

Appendix K – Ethical Approval 1

16/11/2018

Dear John Ayanaba,

Your application 5241: Achieving Lean Success in Petroleum industry: Development of a Conceptual Framework for Application in the Uptream Sector, submission

4479, has been approved by the Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Hughes

Appendix L – Ethical Approval 2

21/10/2019

Dear Mr John Ayanaba,

Your application 5241: Achieving Lean Success in Petroleum industry: Development of a Conceptual Framework for Application in the Upstream Sector, submission reference 7288, has been approved, with conditions, by the Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Title	Comment
Title of Study	Approval is given on the basis of the previous approval in Novemebr of 2018 and conditional on the same approach and the use of the same information and consent forms for use with participants.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Hughes

Appendix M -- Key terminologies in the petroleum production process

Drilling

When seismic survey and data analysis are completed, the next task consists of drilling which is an important step in the exploratory phase of upstream petroleum activities. Crude oil is produced from wells drilled both vertically and horizontally until the discovery of oil, gas, and bitumen (Coppock and Christian, 2018). In the process of drilling, fluids used as lubricants to cool, lubricate, and support the walls of the wells. Drilling occurs in the onshore and offshore production sources, however, drilling in offshore deep-water exploration sites is more sophisticated and requires huge capital investment compared to onshore drilling. Notwithstanding the pivotal role drilling plays in the petroleum exploration process, challenges continue to impact the operations in diverse ways among which is knowledge in the drilling process which is essential to optimize operational efficiency (Bland et al., 2006). Extant literature asserts that a series of tasks are carried out before the actual drilling process, including geological subsurface maps, geophysicists' map seismic data, and drilling engineers designing the well before drilling commences. Besides, environmental regulations are also explored and addressed before drilling. Also, technology and big data play a crucial role in the cost of drilling and safety optimization (Alleyne and Alexander, 2018, Baaziz and Quoniam, 2019). Whereas some made-to-order FPSOs consist of drilling functionality, specialized drilling rigs on mobile units for onshore drilling, or offshore floating rigs (Alvarado et al., 2002, Devold, 2013, Allahyarzadeh-Bidgoli et al., 2018).

Fracking

Hydraulic fracturing or “fracking” is carried out in which water and sand or water containing chemicals are pumped down the borehole in the process of drilling as a way of propping or reducing the fractured pores within the borehole. The rationale for performing fracking in the

drilling process is to keep the pores open for oil and gas extraction. Fracking is also perceived as the process of stimulating the borehole walls to open the pores by injecting water or chemicals as a way of reducing the fractured closures that will enhance production(Richards et al., 2015, Coppock and Christian, 2018). As indicated earlier, the addition of chemicals in the fracking process is meant to enhance operational efficiency. Increasingly, operators adopt a horizontal drilling technique as a way to get access to relatively inaccessible deposits(Richards et al., 2015).

New Well Evaluation

Upon completion of the drilling process, it is critical to establish the economic viability of the drilled well. This informs the commercial amount of crude oil that can be produced from the well as well as the estimated depletion period. Li and Chan (2009), opine that though decision-making regarding the production capacity of a new oil well cannot be overemphasized, it is at the same time difficult to accurately predict a well's production capacity. However, as part of their research, they developed a model known as a neural-based decision model(NDT) and used five parameters that affect oil production. The parameters included permeability, porosity, first shut-in pressure, residual oil, and saturation. However, in another study, Markle et al. (2020), adopted a different approach known as an electric logs analysis to assess well production capacity and porosity.

Also, cognizant of the high risk and quality-related issues associated with this phase of upstream activities, researchers have explored the application of Lean Six Sigma and ISO standards to enhance not only simulation and production capacity measurement, but also provide overall quality guidelines for upstream operations(Buell and Turnipseed, 2004).

Well Casing

After drilling, and before production, the new oil well must be “completed”, an activity that involves installing the good casing, wellhead as well as lifting equipment in readiness for production. Strict adherence to safety protocols before the commencement of production anchors the casing of the well (Devold, 2006, 2013, Jafarinejad, 2017, Alleyne and Alexander, 2018). Effective planning, project management skills, and adequate skill set are pre-requisites for operational success. Nonetheless, collapsed, dented, partially collapsed wells can be repaired (Prout and Beach, 1945; Skipper, 1964). Figure 2.10 depicts a typical well casing scenario.

Figure 2. 19: Typologies of well casing

Source: Devold,(2013)

Production

The primary activity of the upstream activities is the extraction of hydrocarbons from the oil well. Following the upstream value chain system including prospect generation, development planning, well construction, and production (Devold, 2013, Alleyne and Alexander, 2018). An important factor in upstream activities is the cost of operation. High rents for production are issues of concern to both governments and investors (Mitchell and Mitchell, 2014). With specific reference to deep-water exploration, and mindful of the highly complex nature of the operation, the importance of automation of petroleum production and separation facilities cannot be overemphasized (Chan, 2005). Production is critical in the entire petroleum value chain for countless reasons but primarily because the industry is highly regulated with intermittent volatilities and/or shocks which may require operators to increase production, optimize costs and ensure sustainable operations (Baaziz and Quoniam, 2013).

In the course of production, reservoir fluid composition changes when less valuable products like water enter the production stream (Foss et al., 2017). A significant consideration is the production life of a well consisting of ramping-up, plateau, and decline phases. The well production life-cycle provides ample information for planning, decision-making, forecasting, and depletion action plans including decommissioning activities (Chan, 2005; Fernandes et al., 2010; Foss et al., 2017). Operational efficiency and sustainability are critical for petroleum producing companies. The focus of this research examines the activities within this section of the upstream petroleum value chain and explores approaches for lean application in petroleum-producing organizations. A multiplicity of factors underpins the price volatility of crude oil on the international market sometimes with a disproportionate ripple effect on global economic activities. Regarded as a highly regulated industry (Baaziz and Quoniam, 2013), whose impact is felt within the shortest

possible time, actors within the industry adopt innovative and sustainable, long-term production and management strategies to continuously stay afloat in the industry instead of overly reliant on conventional cost-cutting, short-term ad-hoc measures.

There is no doubt that the upstream petroleum industry is riddled with several challenges. Geopolitical, technological, leadership, civil unrests, corruption, inadequate skills, environmental pollution are among a legion of challenges are not both affect production and management of upstream petroleum companies(Mahroos and Zubari, 2009, Siakwah, 2017, Arove and Bankole, 2018, Alleyne and Alexander, 2018, Rachman and Ratnayake, 2019).

Subsequent sections of the study provide an introduction to Lean management, examines whether lean is a suitable strategy for the upstream sector, and how it can play a role in solving the challenges facing the upstream petroleum sector.

Emerging petroleum Gateways

Crude oil production is a major business activity which enhances economic development. Thus, countries endowed with crude oil deposits and effectively managed are not only guaranteed enhanced socio-economic development, but tend to become business hubs. A key example of a state that has become a business hub is Dubai, which has epitomized petroleum resource management and diversification. Similarly, Cape Town, Mauritius, Durban and Accra have become business hubs and gateways to Africa and Brazil as a consequence of petroleum production(Scholvin, Breul and Diez, 2019, Scholvin, 2020a, 2020b).

Thus, suffice to reiterate the fact that gateways serve as anchors of regional development. Herbert-Burns (2012 p.38) posit that “*gateways are usually small states or significant urban-industrial-trading nodes strategically located so as to link different regions or that link sea-trading access to*

land-locked or continental interiors". Furthermore, because cities are vital to enhance value chain, when serving as "gateways", they interlink hinterland locations(Scholvin, Breul and Diez, 2019). Gateway cities around including Buenos Aires, Cape Town, Singapore, Mauritius, Dubai, Durban, Rio de Janeiro, São Paulo and Accra provide outstanding contributions to regional economic development processes(Scholvin, 2020a).

According to Herbert-Burns (2012), citing Cohen (2003), several petroleum gateways exist in the world, including but not limited to: "New York/New Jersey; the Houston-Texas City-Galveston conurbation; Rotterdam; Singapore; the Ras Tanura-Juaymah-Abqiaq complex, Baku in Azerbaijan, Novorossiysk on Russia's Black Sea coast, Port Harcourt in Nigeria, and the Ceyhan Marine Terminal in south-eastern Turkey. More recently however, new and potential gateways are emerging in Asia, the Indo-Pacific spaces and Africa. These include the UAE; South Korea; Pakistan; Sikka and Jamnagar in India; Yan and Bachok in Malaysia; Ningbo and Qingdao in China; and Russia's far eastern Pacific coast" Cape Town, Maritius and Accra(Herbert-Burns, 2012, Scholvin, Breul and Diez, 2019, Scholvin, 2020a). The establishment of the African Continental Free Trade Area(AfCFTA) with its secretariat in Ghana further projects Ghana not only as oil producing country with stable socio-political geographical location to serve as an anchor for regional trade and global fair trade relations(Obeng-Odoom, 2020).

In conclusion, upstream petroleum sector anchors global economic development and transnational trade. Its exploration, discovery, production and distribution constitutes a complex process and requires specialized mode of operation. This requires highly skilled personnel, advanced technological and engineering project management capabilities and huge capital expenditure.

Safety, sustainability, quality and cost are some of the fundamental priorities of the sector. Also, because crude oil is a non-renewable resource, depletion policies, including economic diversification programs play a vital role in the economic transformation process. In light of this, petroleum getaways provide a platform for transformational and economic diversification initiatives as evidenced in the United Arab Emirates. The production process of petroleum is dictated by factors which call for operational efficiency. Lean manufacturing ensures operational efficiency, eliminates waste, delivers profitability and customer satisfaction. The next section of this research explores extant literature on Lean manufacturing evolution and the extent to which it is suitable strategy for adoption in the upstream petroleum sector.